

CHAPTER ONE
GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background to the Study

Sometime in 2011, I was at the University of Ibadan Security Unit otherwise called *Abefélé* to lodge my complaint about a ‘friend’ whom I suspected was using my credentials for impersonation. The young man had actually requested the original copies of my credentials, having collected some photocopies prior to this time, with a promise that he was going to help me secure a lecturing job in some schools where he claimed he had influence. However, I became suspicious when he later called me to request the original copies of my documents, saying he needed them to get some money from a popular philanthropist in Ibadan; having lied to him he was seeking admission into an M.A in Linguistics programme in the University of Ibadan.

Having informed the security unit beforehand, some men of the unit showed up as soon as I alerted them to the presence of my friend when he came around to collect the said documents. The men came in their security vehicle and took us down to their office for “interrogation/interview”. In the course of the interrogation/interview that lasted close to one hour, my linguistic antenna picked some ‘signals’ which serve as the bedrock and motivation for this work. I noticed the display of power, dominance and force (however subtle), and (im)politeness strategies employed by the security men while interrogating the suspect(my friend). As a matter of fact, my friend owned up to his mischiefs, obviously owing to how he was “fried” with language during the exercise.

It, therefore, became appealing to me to examine the nature of the relationship that exists between the police and suspects in the course of their interaction in a work like this. Sometimes, it can be fascinating seeing how the police use their institutional power to gain confessions from suspects, but oftentimes, it can also be mind-worrying and thought-provoking witnessing a scenario where the police overuse and perhaps abuse their institutional power while interacting with suspects. In such instances, the police officer assumes a position of authority and superiority

over and above suspects. This is what is often observed during the police-suspect discourse (including *interrogation/interview*¹).

1.1. Conceptualising Interview , Interrogation and Questioning in Police Language

The interview conducted with the OC General Investigation² (OCGI) of the station used as the setting for this research work and the observation made during data collection proper have given birth to this work. In the course of the interview that lasted about thirty minutes on my first day in the station, precisely in the OCGI's office, I emphasised my interest in the language used in “interrogating” suspects by the police. The said OCGI was quick to point my attention to the fact that the use of *interrogation* in my research topic was inappropriate. Interrogation, he claimed, is no longer in the parlance of the Nigeria Police, as a group of human rights activists had earlier fought against the use of the word in police-suspects' interaction. He explained the word interrogate or interrogation connotes or carries elements of coercion, force, humiliation and dehumanisation. Hence, instead, police-suspects interaction can best be described as *questioning*.

However, what became obvious in the course of data collection was the constant use of the words “interrogation and interrogate” by IPOs while interacting with suspects. Also, one of the IPOs interacted with in the process of data collection used the word *interview* while describing what transpired between him, his OC and a suspect. The question that came to mind after these observations is that “is there any definitional vagueness surrounding the conceptualisation of these three related but different words, especially as far as the language of the Nigeria Police is concerned?” This is the question this paper attempts to provide an answer to. As important as the issue raised above is, previous works such as Terebo (2012), Sadiq (2011), Adebowale (2010), Oyebade (2007), Ogunsiji (1989), Farinde (1997, 2011), Bamgbose (1971 and 1995), to mention but a few, have glossed over it.

¹ These are used here pending the time we would do adequate justice to the difference(s) between them as would be revealed by our data

² Officer in Charge of General Investigation

1.1.1 Interview

The process of interview is non-accusatory. In other words, during an interview, the investigator adopts a neutral and objective attitude and does not accuse the subject of wrongdoing (Inbau *et al*, 2001 : 2). The primary goal of an interview is to gather information that is relevant to the investigation at hand. This information can include “who, what, when, where, why, and how” of any criminal investigation and can also involve assessing the credibility of the source of the information supplied by the respondent. Interviews are generally flexible and are free-flowing interactions. They are a dialogue between the investigator and the suspect. It is a question and answer session in which both parties may ask questions and give answers. The investigator usually has several key points he is interested in covering, but these are not so fixed, as they are subject to change as the dialogue continues or progresses. According to Inbau *et al* (2001:2-4), an interview can be carried out at any point in time during an investigation to get some facts about the crime committed, to unravel the suspect’s potential culpability. Interviews are carried out in a more friendly or cheerful atmosphere. The interviewee feels relaxed and at ease. It is assumed that when an interviewee feels no anxiety or unthreatened by the interviewer doing the “questioning”, the greater the tendency that he or she would speak more and thus give out more information.

Complementing the position of Inbau *et al* (2001), Meissner *et al* (2012) report that the information-gathering (interview) approach, used in the United Kingdom, New Zealand, Australia, and elsewhere, as more generally in Western Europe, is characterized by rapport-building, truth-seeking, and active listening, and it is more reliable and prevents false confessions, as evident in its effective use in the countries mentioned earlier and Western Europe in general.

1.1.2 Interrogation

Interrogations, on the contrary, are generally more tightly structured. It involves active persecution on the part of the interrogator. In other words, interrogations are accusatory. The interrogator usually begins an interrogation by directly accusing the suspect (accused) of committing the crime that is under investigation, and the entire transaction will revolve around the accusation (Inbau *et al*, 2001 : 2). Meissner *et al* (2012) posit that this accusatory approach, fondly used in America and Canada during police investigation, is characterized by accusation,

confrontation, psychological manipulation, and the disallowing of denials. Consequently, the investigator dominates the interrogation and the exchange will appear to be a persuasive monologue, rather than a question and answer dialogue. This is usually so because the investigator has already developed a mindset to unearth the truth from the person being interrogated, while the interrogated is appealing to the conscience of the interrogator, convincing him or her of his or her innocence. Unlike interview, the goal of an interrogation is not to gather information regarding a crime and a suspect's potential culpability; but it is to learn the truth about the details of the crime from someone who is suspected to have committed the crime. The truth will often but not always involve the confession of the suspect being interrogated (Inbau *et al*, 2001: 2-4). In Inbau et al's submission, an interrogation should only be conducted when the investigator is reasonably certain that the suspect is guilty of the allegation levelled against him or her. From the following, it suffices to conclude the purpose of an interrogation is, therefore, not to discern the truth, determine if the suspect committed the crime, or evaluate his or her denials. Rather, police are trained to interrogate only those suspects whose guilt they presume on the basis of their initial investigation (Inbau *et al* 2001).

Interrogation involves a person being subjected to severe psychological (and sometimes physical) pressure, placing an individual in great discomfort. In interrogation, the investigator uses psychological and linguistic "warfare" to gain control and force a confession out of the person. These scholars thus recommended that an interrogation should not be the primary means for determining the truthfulness of a suspect; rather a non-accusatory interview is a more appropriate forum for assessing truthfulness. In the light of this, Oxford Advanced dictionary defines interrogation as the act or process of asking somebody a lot of questions over a long period of time, especially in an aggressive way.

1.1.3 Questioning

The position maintained by the said OCGI is that questioning is devoid of the coercive features that characterise interrogation. Rather, it is purely a fact-finding activity. Perhaps, the police are operating in line with definition of questioning as : the activity of asking somebody questions (Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary). However, in the words of Farinde (2011), questioning in police-suspect interaction is different from what is obtainable in everyday conversation. It is

assumed that in everyday conversation, all participants or interlocutors are free to ask questions. Contrariwise, in police-suspect interaction, “the typical social relation means that the underlying assumption, subject to certain exception, is that the police (interrogator) asks questions and the suspect replies” (Farinde, 2011: 8). In line with this proposition, Gibbons (2008: 120) asserts that the major characteristics of police questioning are that only one party is normally allowed or permitted to ask questions, and the other party is only allowed to respond and normally must respond; and these responses are legally constrained to be true. In the same vein, Stygall (1994: 120) posits that question(ing) is a powerful tool the police use to control the flow of discourse, requesting particular information in a particular fashion, presenting the story in the order they impose, which does not follow, necessarily, the temporal succession of the actual events.

It is not very surprising the fact that many people (Nigerians) are yet to come to terms with the fact that the concepts of interrogation, questioning and interview are three separate concepts which do not necessarily have the same meaning. Perhaps, this is borne out of their observation of the way and manner security agents and agencies, and police in particular, go about their investigative activities, which oftentimes does not reflect the differences between the three concepts. In view of this therefore, it is necessary to devote this portion of the research work to do justice to the differences between these three concepts. In doing this, the major characteristics of the concepts will be discussed.

1.2 Defining a Suspect (accused) and the Process of Arresting One

A suspect is an individual who has been alleged to have committed a crime or an offence and an individual has been the victim of the offence or crime. The fellow brings the matter to the notice of the police station closest to him or her. The statement of the individual is taken by the desk sergeant who asks him or her questions ranging from when, where and how the crime was committed and who the offender is. After answering these questions, the most senior officer in charge of the police station assigns or directs one or more officers to take up the task of apprehending the “offender” and bringing him or her to the station. The police officer then follows the victim of the crime to the scene of the crime, where the suspect can be arrested. The process of arrest begins.

However, sometimes, the arrest of the suspect may be by warrant. This is usually true of very serious crimes e.g murder, manslaughter and other serious offences in this category. The warrant must be signed by a magistrate, a customary court president, a judge or a justice of peace of the area where the crime has been perpetrated. Such a warrant of arrest must be on oath either by the complainant or by a material witness. On the realisation of the fact that a person is assumed to be innocent until proved otherwise, and that he has an absolute right to move about in any part of the country and to carry on his/her lawful duties without any undue interference from any other person, such other person will think seriously before tampering with this unfettered right unless there is justification for doing so. This implies that it is pertinent that any individual who may wish to arrest another person for an alleged offence must think twice and as such take caution in doing so as not to incur the wrath of the law eventually.

The law requires that the police officer or other person making the arrest shall actually touch or confine the body of the person arrested, unless there is a submission to the custody by word or action. This implies no resistance is expected from the person to be arrested. However, where the person to be arrested uses force in resisting arrest, or execution of the warrant of arrest, it is lawful for a person who is empowered by the law to effect the arrest to use force as may be reasonably necessary to overcome the force put up by the person to be arrested. However, the law does not justify any unnecessary restraint on the person being arrested except by the order of the court, a magistrate or a justice of peace. Put in another way, an arrested person shall not be handcuffed unless the person arresting has reasonable grounds to believe that there is the tendency of violence from the arrested person or of an attempt to escape arrest or the restraint is in the interest of the person arrested. The Law demands that the police officer making an arrest inform the person to be arrested of the cause of the arrest except when the person is in the actual commission of the crime or escape from lawful custody (Adesiyan 2005:1-2).

1.3 Statement by a Suspect or an Accused Person

Practically, the issue of making a statement by a suspect or an accused person who has been alleged to have committed a criminal offence arises when a complainant has made his allegation, whether or not on oath that the suspect has, in actual fact, committed a crime which eventually leads to the arrest of the suspect. The suspect's statement will guide the police, taking all things

into consideration, whether or not he/she should be prosecuted in an appropriate court of law. Although the law makes provision for the police to interrogate/interview the suspect or accused person accordingly, any use of force, psychological coercion, promise or favour, etc to make him/her answer a question or write down anything against him/herself, which in the absence of any of these things, he/she will not do it, is illegal. In fact, answers made to such a question or the writing made under such circumstances will be inadmissible in a trial of the person before any court of law. Also, neither the suspect nor the witness is obliged to give statements which will implicate himself or herself in a criminal investigation unless he or she has been assured that such a statement will not be used against him/her subsequently.

In the light of the above, Adesiyon (2005: 27) submits the issue of an accused or a suspected person's statement dates back to 1912 and 1918 when the Judges' Rules were formulated. "These rules have been adopted in Nigeria although one cannot trace any enabling authority for their adoption". The Judges' rules are as follows:

1. When a police officer is endeavouring to discover the author of a crime, there is no objection to his putting questions in respect thereof to any person or persons, whether suspected or not, from whom he thinks that useful information can be obtained.
2. Whenever a police officer has made up his mind to charge a person with a crime, he should first caution such person before asking him any questions, or any further questions as the case may be.
3. Persons in custody should not be questioned without the usual caution being first administered.
4. If the prisoner wishes to volunteer any statement, the usual caution should be administered. It is desirable that the last two words of such caution should be omitted, and that the caution should end with the words "be given in evidence".
5. The caution to be administered to a prisoner, when he is formally charged, should therefore, be in the following words: "Do you wish to say anything in answer to the charge? You are not obliged to say anything unless you wish to do so, but whatever you say will be taken down in writing and may be given in evidence."

6. A statement made by a prisoner before there is time to caution him is not rendered inadmissible in evidence merely because no caution has been given, but in such a case he should be cautioned as soon as possible.
7. A prisoner making a voluntary statement must not be cross-examined, and no questions should be put to him about it except for the purpose of removing ambiguity in what he has actually said. For instance, if he has mentioned an hour without saying whether it was morning or evening, or has given a day of the week or a day of the month which does not agree, or has not made it clear as to what place he intended to refer in some part of his statement, he may be questioned sufficiently to clear up the point.
8. When two or more persons are charged with the same offence and their statements are taken separately, the police should not read these statements to the other persons charged, but each of such persons should be given a copy of such statements by the police and nothing should be said or done by the police to invite a reply. If the person charged desires to make a statement in reply, the usual caution should be administered.
9. Any statement made in accordance with the above rules should, whenever possible, be taken down in writing and signed by the person making it after it has been read to him and he has been invited to make corrections he may wish. (*Source: Adesiyan 2005*)

1.4 Confessional Statement

According to the Oxford Advanced Learner's dictionary (7th edition), a confession is a statement that a person makes, admitting that they are guilty of a crime. It shows that one agrees one has done something wrong, illegal, or embarrassing, especially a formal statement. Confession shows remorse and regret for having done something illegally acceptable. In practically all cases, an accused person or a suspect would under normal circumstances not make a statement confessing to the commission of a crime, however serious or grave the crime might appear. The aforesaid is not then to say that confessional statements are not made, but more often than not, the accused person believes even when he has committed a crime, confessing to the commission of the crime implies quick punishment; which can sometimes be a heavy one. Therefore, an accused person or a suspect tries as much as possible to cover his tracks, hoping to evade justice. A confessional statement, according to Adesiyan (2005), is one made at any time by a person charged with a crime, stating or suggesting the inferences that he committed that

crime. Thus, such a statement can only be used against the suspect or accused person who made it. Where the suspect or accused person is charged jointly with other persons and the confession is made in their presence incriminating any of or all the other accused persons, the statement cannot be used against any of them except such persons adopt the contents of the confessional statement by word or conduct. Where a statement has been given by an accused or a suspect, it must not have been given under duress, inducement, threat or promise (Adesiyani 2005: 30-31).

A confession made or given by an accused or a suspect under such conditions as mentioned above will be considered irrelevant when presented in the court of law. Such confessions are regarded as false confessions. There have been reported cases of false confessions all over the world. For instance, Leo (2008:195) reports thus: In 1998, two young boys -aged seven and eight in Chicago were charged with murdering an eleven-year-old girl named Ryan Harris who had been badly beaten around the head. Her underpants had been stuffed into her mouth and she appeared to have been sexually assaulted. After an unrecorded interrogation, the two boys had “confessed” to hitting Harris in the head with a brick (and then stuffing leaves and grass in her nose) in order to steal her bicycle. Principally because of the boys’ ages, the case attracted national media attention: the country was surprised that two prepubescent boys were capable of committing so grave a crime. Although the evidence pointed to an adult sex crime, the police insisted that the two boys were not too young to have committed the act and that they knew details that could be known only to the detectives or the perpetrators.

Months later, the Illinois State Crime laboratory discovered semen on Ryan Harris’ underpants- the evidence that the crime could not have been committed by suspects that are young, and prosecutors dismissed the charges. The collected DNA was later linked with Floyd Durr, an adult already charged with sexually assaulting three other young girls in the same neighbourhood. Durr later owned up to having committed the crime- committing a sex act over Harris’ body (Drizin and Leo 2004 cf. Leo 2008).

1.4.1 Types of False Confession

With reference to the pages of legal history, Kassin and Wrightsman (1985 cf. Kassin *et al* 2010:34) propose a taxonomy that distinguished among three types of false confession:

voluntary, coerced-compliant, and coerced-internalized (see also Kassin, 1997; Wrightsman & Kassin, 1993 cf. Kassin *et al* 2009: 15). This is a useful framework for the study of false confessions and has since been used, and criticised and modified by other scholars (Gudjonsson, 2003; Inbau et al., 2001; McCann, 1998; Ofshe & Leo, 1997a, 1997b).

1.4.1.1 Voluntary False Confessions

Observation, or better put, experience has shown that sometimes innocent people do accept responsibility for crimes which they have not committed. This has occurred in several high-profile cases. For instance, as observed by (Kassin *et al*, 2003), after Charles Lindbergh's infant son was kidnapped in 1932, 200 people volunteered confessions. When “Black Dahlia” actress Elizabeth Short was murdered and her body mutilated in 1947, more than 50 men and women confessed. In the 1980s, Henry Lee Lucas in Texas falsely confessed to hundreds of unsolved murders, making him the most prolific serial confessor in history. In 2006, John Mark Karr volunteered a confession, replete with details, to the unsolved murder of young Jon Benet Ramsey.

There are a host of reasons why people have volunteered false confessions—such as a pathological desire for notoriety, especially in high-profile cases reported in the news media; a conscious or unconscious need for self-punishment to show or demonstrate feelings of guilt over prior transgressions; an inability to distinguish fact from fantasy due to a breakdown in reality monitoring, a common feature of major mental illness; and a desire to protect the actual perpetrator—the most prevalent reason for false admissions (Gudjonsson, Sigurdsson,& Einarsson, 2004; Sigurdsson & Gudjonsson,1996, 1997; 2001). Gudjonsson (2003) also makes mention of another case where a man confessed to murder as a revenge strategy to mislead the police, having been “unjustly” arrested before. Radelet *et al.* (1992) describe one case in which an innocent man confessed to a murder in order to impress his girlfriend.

1.4.1.2 Compliant False Confessions

Compliant false confessions are somewhat different from the voluntary false confessions. Contrary to voluntary false confessions, in this case, suspects are induced through police interrogation to confess to a crime they have not committed. In these cases, the suspect agrees to

the demand for a confession so as to escape untoward treatment in the hand of the police as quickly as possible. Demonstrating the form of influence observed in classic studies of social influence (e.g., Asch, 1956; Milgram, 1974), this type of confession is an act of mere public compliance by a suspect who knows that he or she is innocent but comes to believe that the short-term benefits of confession relative to denial outweigh the long-term costs. Based on a review of a number of cases, Gudjonsson (2003) identifies some very specific incentives or benefits accruable from this kind of compliance, e.g being allowed to sleep, eat, make a phone call, go home, or, in the case of drug addicts, feed a drug habit. Another reason people could give this kind of confession could be the desire to bring the interview/interrogation to an end and avoid further confinement.

1.4.1.3 Internalised False Confessions

In this type of false confession, an innocent but weak suspect is told that there is glaring and obvious evidence to consolidate the allegation against him or her. The police paint a picture that subtly links the suspect with the crime. They make them believe they may have committed the crime in question, sometimes fabricating false memories in the process. Gudjonsson and MacKeith (1982) opine that this kind of false confession occurs when people develop such a profound distrust of their own memory that they become vulnerable to influence from external sources. Looking critically at the nature and the characteristic features of this kind of false confession, Ofshe and Leo (1997a) conclude that the term “persuaded false confession” is a more accurate description of the phenomenon. The case of a 14-year-old Michael Crowe, whose sister Stephanie was stabbed to death in her bedroom, illustrates this type of persuasion. After a series of interrogation sessions, during which time police presented Crowe with compelling false physical evidence of his guilt, he concluded that he was a killer, saying: "I'm not sure how I did it. All I know is I did it." Consequently, he admitted that he had a split personality—that “bad Michael” acted out of a jealous rage while "good Michael" blocked the incident from memory.

The charges against Crowe were later dropped when a drifter in the neighborhood that night was found with Stephanie's blood on his clothing (Drizin and Colgan, 2004). However, it is worthy of note that an accused or a suspect’s statement or confession is only an evidence against

him/herself. It cannot under any circumstances be used against co-accused persons or accomplices except such other persons adopt same by their words or conduct.

1.5 The Process of Obtaining Statement from Suspects or Accused Persons

Okonkwo and Naish (2012) categorise crimes or offences in Nigeria into preliminary and specific offences for which “cluprits” could be brought to the custody of the police before proceeding to the court. Among the preliminary crimes according to these scholars are attempts, attempt to procure, and conspiracy, while crimes like homicide, assaults, defamation, bigamy, stealing, robbery and burglary, false pretences, cheating, forgery, unlawful assembly, seditious meeting, e.t.c. Whenever any of the aforementioned crimes is committed, such an individual is brought to the police for interview or interrogation. In such a situation, the accused is permitted to write or make his or her statement(s). Usually, after such statements are made, he or she is allowed to read it before it is signed. In the event that the accused or suspect is not literate, the statement is read to him or her before he/she appends his/her signature. The accused person or suspect equally has the right to have the service of an interpreter in such an instance, as it is stated in the Police Training Manual that the detainee (accused/suspect) is allowed to use an interpreter, if necessary.

The process of making statement by accused/suspects is usually anchored by Investigating Police Officers (IPOs). However, it appears every police officer functions in this capacity, as our observation has revealed. Every police officer assigned by the Head of a unit to investigate a case and collect statements from accused or suspects is under obligation to do so in accordance with section 118 of police code of conduct. In the process of statement collection, the police officer first gives words of caution to the suspect or the accused person that he or she is not coerced into giving the statement he or she is about to give, and as such, whatever is written or said would will be used as evidence in the court of law (if the matter eventually gets to court).

The format for interrogation or interview is as follows:

- The IPO must be alone with the suspect/accused
- The IPO does not frighten or threaten the accused

One can begin to ask questions as to the level of professionalism involved in the conduct of the Nigerian Police, especially the IPOs, during the process of obtaining statement from suspects or accused; as their conducts violate the conditions stated above. This will be brought to bare in chapter four of this work.

1.6 The Rights of a Suspect/Accused under the Nigerian Criminal Law

Salman (2009) observes there are certain rights that are accorded every suspect or accused person as eshrined in the country's laws. These rights are divided into three viz pre-trial rights, trial rights and post-trial rights. The one related to this study however is pre-trial rights and shall be reviewed as appropriate. Under the pre-trial rights are right to life, right to dignity, right to remain silent, right to bail, right to be informed of the nature of the offence, and right to time and facilities for defence.

1.6.1 Rights to Life

A suspect (or an accused), just like every other Nigerian, has a right to life under the constitution, subject to certain exceptional cases or situations. According to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, no person shall be deprived intentionally of his life except in execution of the sentence of a court in relation to a criminal offence of which an individual has been found guilty.

1.6.2 Rights to Dignity

In this regard, the 1999 Constitution section (34), sub-section 1 provides thus: Every individual is entitled to respect for the dignity of his/her person, and accordingly (therefore) "*No person shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment*". From the foregoing, it is obvious that a suspect is entitled to being treated with respect and sense of humanness. The police has the statutory power to effect an arrest, especially on commission of an offence or upon reasonable belief that an offence is about to be committed. However, such arrest must be in compliance with the provision of the constitution. When a suspect is arrested, he or she must be treated with utmost respect and dignity. Such a suspect must not be subjected to handcuffing or leg-chaining, except in a case or situation the suspect has been perceived to want to attempt to escape or where the suspect is violent, resisting arrest. The officer effecting the arrest is expected

to take the suspect to the police station. As observed by Salman (2009), “it is sad to note that these provisions are observed more in breach than compliance by the Nigerian Police.

1.6.3 Rights to Remain Silent

This is another pre-trial right of the suspect as provided in the country’s constitution. A suspect (undergoing interviewing, questioning or interrogation) has the right to remain silent during the questioning or interrogation exercise, before he consults with a legal practitioner. With respect to this, the constitution provides thus: *“Any person who is arrested or detained shall have the right to remain silent or avoid answering any questions until after consultation with a legal practitioner or any others of his choice in Nigeria”*.

1.6.4 Rights to Bail

Bail is a basic constitutional right guaranteed by the 1999 Constitution (Salman, 2009). Bail here refers to the temporary release or freedom that is granted to a suspect before he or she is charged to court. It is a temporary release or freedom from custody, pending the conclusion of investigation or determination of the case against the suspect. Constitutionally, the police has the power to grant bail at the pre-trial stage and this power is exercisable before the suspect is charged to court. When a police officer arrests a suspect without a warrant, such a suspect is expected to be released on bail on his or her surety’s cognisance if it will not be possible to present such before the court within twenty-four hours. However, this provision might not be applicable if the officers perceive the committed offence to be a serious one. Salman concluded on this that it is apparently obvious (perhaps from the practice of the police) that the police use bail as punitive rather than a facilitative tool of administering justice.

1.6.5 Rights to be informed of the Nature of the (Committed) Offence

This is another fundamental (human) right a suspect or an accused person is accorded before trial. A suspect has the prerogative of being informed of the nature of the offence he/she has been alleged to have committed. In other words, he/she needs to be appropriately and adequately informed of the reasons for his/her arrest. In line with this, the constitution stipulates thus: *“Any person who is arrested or detained shall be informed in writing within twenty-four hours of the fact and grounds for his arrest or detention (in a language he understands)”*.

1.6.6 Rights to Time and Facilities for Defence

A suspect has the right to adequate time and facilities in preparing for the defence. Due to the intervals between arrsets, arraignments and eventual prosecution of a suspect, provisions exist for time and facilities towards his defence, pending the conclusion of police investigation. However, as pointed out by Salman (2009), reported cases of corrupt practices by the police officers in this regard, have shown that suspects and accused persons always experience difficulties in having access to their counsel.

1.7 Pragmatics: An Overview

It will not be out of place to state that the task of defining the concept of pragmatics is a Herculean one, as scholars vary in their conception of the concepts, a fact which reflects in their definitions and explanations of the concept. However, it is worthy of note that the modern usage of the term pragmatics is credited to Charles Morris (1938). As far as linguistics is concerned, Morris (1938: 6) distinguishes three branches namely syntactics (or syntax) being the study of the formal relation of signs to one another (usually within semiotics), Semantics, which studies the relations of signs to the objects to which they are applicable, and Pragmatics, which studies the biotic aspects of semiosis, that is, with all the psychological, biological and sociological phenomena which occur in the functioning of signs (Morris 1938:108). This implies that pragmatics encompasses fields as psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics and neurolinguistics. According to him, pragmatics is the study of language usage. It is a field of study that focuses on those principles that will account for why a certain set of sentences are anomalous or not possible. In the opinion of Bar-Hillel (1954), pragmatics is the study of languages, both natural and artificial that contain indexical or deictic terms. It is a field of study that attempts to explain facets of linguistics and structured by reference to non linguistic pressures and causes.

In defining pragmatics, Katz (1977:19) observes thus:

Grammars are theories about structure of sentence types...,
Pragmatic theories, in contrast, do nothing to explicate the structure
of linguistic constructions or grammatical properties and relations.

They explicate the reasoning of speakers and hearers in working out the correlation in a context of a sentence taken with a presupposition. In this respect therefore, a pragmatic theory is part of performance.

Scholars like (Bach and Harnish (1979), Welber and Sperber (1981), Leech(1983) among others subscribe to the view that pragmatics as opposed to semantics, focuses on utterance meaning. Advancing the cause of this view, Leech and Short (1981: 290) say:

The pragmatic analysis of language can be broadly understood to be the investigation into that aspect of meaning which is derived not from the formal properties of words and constructions, but from the way in which utterances are used and how they relate to the context in which they are uttered.

Deduceable from these definitions is the fact that pragmatics deals basically with the functional use of language. Central to the field of pragmatics are Politeness and Impoliteness theories.

1.8 Problem Description

Forensic discourse analysis is a field of study that has enjoyed fairly little attention from scholars in Nigeria. The few works in existence in this area of study: Ogunsiji (1989), Farinde (1997), Oyebade (2007), Fayemi (2009), Adebowale (2010), Farinde (2011), Oyebade (2011), Sadiq (2011) and Terebo (2012) have concerned themselves with the application of some form of Discourse Acts as proposed by Sinclair and Coulthard (1975) and Speech Acts in the analysis of language use in police-suspect discourse and courtroom conversation. They have however, either covertly or overtly, left unexamined the various politeness and impoliteness strategies observed in police-suspect interaction, and how the use of these strategies signal asymmetrical distribution of power between police and suspects in police-suspect interaction.

Also, it has been observed of the existing literature the non-examination of the ideological motivation behind the use of politeness and impoliteness strategies by IPOs and suspects during police-suspect interaction. Similarly, none of the existing works has addressed, from linguistic

point of view, how the constitutional rights of suspects (as provided for in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria) are violated during police-suspect interaction.

In view of the issues raised above, this work, therefore, adopts a new approach to the study of police-suspect discourse in Nigeria, with the application of Politeness Theory proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987), and Culpeper's (1996) Impoliteness theory; within the Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis proposed by Fairclough and Wodak (1997).

1.9 Scope and Limitations of Study

It might be misleading for any singular work to claim to cover or to have covered all issues that need to be covered on a subject matter, hence its scope and limitations need to be defined. This work sees the existing literature as a springboard to achieve its aims and objectives. As such, the work applies the Brown and Levinson's (1987) Politeness theory and Culpeper's (1996) Impoliteness theory to police-suspect discourse in the State Criminal Investigation Department, Iyaganku Division, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, with the view to gaining insights into how politeness and impoliteness strategies mark asymmetrical distribution of power during police-suspect interaction. It is important to state categorically that suspects whose cases are examined in this work are those interrogated in the Investigation hall of the State Criminal Investigation Department, Nigeria Police, Iyaganku Division, Ibadan, Oyo State. This is because the letters of approval got from the Commissioner of Police on the two occasions we applied for approval restricted us to this section of the station. We, however, later understood the rationale behind this. This section of the station, as we got to know, is the only unit in the state saddled with the responsibility of conducting investigations into all manners of crime within the state. All other stations in Oyo State do refer criminal cases to the section for proper and thorough investigations.

The suspects whose cases are considered in this work are those we refer to as 'commoners' or uninformed (low-profile) suspects and informed (high-profile) suspects. By commoners we mean individuals who belong to the lower class of the society, either by virtue of their status, qualifications, jobs, areas of residence, and standard of living in general, and high-profile suspects refer to those in the middle or upper class, given the variables stated above. However, it

needs to be pointed out that the high frequency of the cases involving low-profile suspects in the Interrogation/Investigation hall of the station made it impossible for us to have access to the same number of cases involving these two categories of individuals. And in fact in many situations, cases involving high-profile suspects took place in offices we could not access. These limitations, we believe, would not detract from the value of this study considering the fact that the data we were able to gather were robust enough to justify the deductions made therefrom.

1.10 Research Objectives

Doing a work of this nature without any objective will be like travelling with no destination in view. To avoid the aforepainted scenario therefore, this work aims at examining the various impoliteness and politeness strategies employed by the police and suspects in police-suspect discourse. In doing this, the work hopes to achieve the following:

- i. To examine the impoliteness strategies by IPOs and Suspects in police-suspect interaction
- ii. To examine the politeness strategies employed by IPOs and Suspects in police-suspect interactions
- iii. To examine how the deployment of impoliteness and politeness strategies demonstrates asymmetrical distribution of power between IPOs and suspects in police-suspect interaction
- iv. To identify and explain the ideologies and motivation behind the use of politeness and impoliteness strategies by IPOs and Suspects during police-suspect interaction
- v. To examine if class or social status influences the way and manner police officers interact with suspects
- vi. To vividly demonstrate how power is distributed between police officers and suspects in police-suspect interaction, with emphasis on how the constitutional rights of low-profile suspects are violated from linguistic point of view.
- vii. To attempt a classification of police-suspect interaction, considering their characteristic features

1.11 Expected Contributions to Knowledge

This work is expected to contribute to knowledge in the following ways:

- Existing works on police-suspect interaction in Nigeria have focused on Discourse Acts in general, with particular reference to Sinclair and Coulthard's classification of discourse acts. This work, therefore, takes a different dimension to the study of interaction between police and suspects, looking at it from the angle of politeness and impoliteness theories proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) and Culpeper (1996) respectively.
- Although the various existing works such as Sadiq (2011) and Farinde (1997) have talked about the concept of power in police-suspect interaction, they have failed to demonstrate to us how IPOs employ non-physical (linguistic) force to exert their institutional power over suspects, and ultimately violate their fundamental human rights. At best, Farinde (2011) merely mentions questioning as a linguistic device employed by the IPOs to dominate police-suspect interaction. This work, therefore demonstrates, in concrete terms, how linguistic devices (other than questions) and paralinguistic devices are used in this wise.
- Similarly, no known work has attempted a conceptualisation of the three related but different terms of Interrogation, Questioning and Interview, with the view to defining their places and use in police language. This work addresses this phenomenon.

1.12 Significance of the Study

There is a popular belief by many Nigerians that the police often trample upon the fundamental human rights of the common man in the country, especially when such happens to be a suspect. However, from keen observations, no known work has addressed this untoward phenomenon from a linguistic perspective. This work, therefore, becomes imperative as it addresses this unsavoury situation.

The work is a veritable reference material for scholars and researchers interested in examining how status and social class play a fundamental role in the way the police deploy politeness and impoliteness strategies in police-suspect interaction.

Similarly, the work is significant in that it is a clarion call on the Nigeria Police on the need to review its practice in view of the current global call for respect for human rights by law enforcement agencies and agents, even during crime investigations.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0 Literature Review

Since this work does not claim to be the first on its subject matter, it is then very expedient to delve into preceding works that are related to it as a foundation upon which the study will be built. In view of this therefore, works on crime and politeness and impoliteness theories will be reviewed here.

2.1 Crime: Definitions and Causes

It is no gainsaying the fact that defining the concept of crime is a Herculean task. This statement is true in view of the complex nature of the term. Its complexity can be said to be inherent in its relativity and subjectivity. For instance, referring to the subjective nature of crime, Henry and Lanier (2001: 7) suggests that “what counts as a crime at one place and time, culture, or location may not be considered criminal at another time, in another culture, or even across the street”. This observation of Henry and Lanier suggests that the concept of crime is embedded in the culture of a people. That is why, for instance, polygamy will be a crime in the U.S and not in a country like Nigeria, especially in marriages instituted under the customary law. From the various definitions of the concept by different scholars, two schools of thought could be said to have emerged : the factual school and the normative school. The factual school gives the factual definition of the concept while the normative school gives a normative definition of the concept. These two will be examined here.

2.1.1 The Factual Definition

Most of the scholars who have this view simply opine that crime is a violation of the law. Tappan (1960: 10) provides an example for this kind of definition. Tappan defined crime as “an intentional act or omission in violation of criminal law (statutory or case law), committed without defence or justification, and sanctioned by the state as a felony or misdemeanour.” From this definition, it becomes obvious that the concept is being approached from a legal perspective. Thus, we can say crimes are acts or omissions that are forbidden by the law and as such

punishable by imprisonment or fine. Therefore, according to the law, certain (anti)social acts like murder, burglary, stealing, rape, drunken driving, child trafficking, homicide etc., are crimes that are punishable under the law. This definition sees the (anti)social behaviours as crimes.

2.1.2 The Normative Definition

Normative approaches go beyond the social reaction, and try to find, in the features of the behaviour, reasons that might justify *a crime*. When the concept of crime was not yet a problem (Garofalo 1968:46), this kind of definition, based on the concept of harm or damage caused to others, was common. Though this conception of crime was at the very heart of early criminology, fewer and fewer authors now feel that the question of the nature of crime can be resolved by providing a definition of it that is limited to a single phrase (one exception is Gassin 1994, 17, who, following a straight line from Garofalo, defines crime in terms of the violence and/or duplicity involved (cf. Law Commission of Canada, 2004). However, the view adopted in this work is the factual definition.

2.2 Factors that Engender Criminal Behaviour

Criminal behaviour is the product of a systematic process that involves complex interactions between individual, societal, and ecological factors over the course of our lives (Schiller, Black, & Murphy, www.des.ucdavis.edu/faculty/Richerdson/Bookonline). In other words, before a crime or crimes can be committed, all the aforementioned factors must be involved. Man is a product of his intellectual, emotional and physical attributes on the one hand, and his interaction with his physical environment and people, on the other. Hence, most times, the particular way of life adopted by man could be a product of his intellectual, emotional and physical being and his environment. These systematic interactions affect the transmission from generation to generation of traits associated with increased involvement in crime.

2.2.1 Ecological Factors

Ecological factors have to do with interactions between people and their activities in a physical environment. This category includes things associated with the physical environment such as geography and topography, crowding, pollution, and recreational opportunities. These ecological factors most times affect the physical and emotional development of people, in terms of the way

they feel over their lives, hostility, fear, or well-being from time to time. Ecological factors also determine what opportunities for crime exist because they include interactions between people and the ways physical environments channel those interactions. The routine activities of people in a physical setting can have important effects on when and where opportunities for crime occur. A crime is not possible unless a motivated and able offender converges with a victim, property, illicit substance or behaviour in the absence of capable guardianship (people or physical barriers to prevent the crime). A child brought up in an environment that is prone to acts of criminality is prone to being influenced by such and hence adopt that as way of life, without necessarily seeing it as negative way of life. Even the one that later realises it as a negative way of life might be somewhat helpless in correcting the criminal tendencies in him, because he has become accustomed to that way of life. Such a child might need the attention of juvenile rehabilitation outfits to abandon his criminal tendencies.

2.2.2 Societal or Macro-level Factors

These factors deal with systematic interactions between social groups. Societal factors determine the structure of the society. These societal factors include such things as the population distribution of people in the society in relation to the distribution of information, resources. Societal factors encompass the variety and heterogeneity of racial, ethnic, cultural or productive groups, their behaviors and beliefs, and economic relations.

2.2.3 Motivation and Opportunity

Motivation is the outcome of a process in which a goal is formulated, costs and benefits are assessed, and internal constraints on behaviour are applied. The relative importance of the components of this process may vary from one individual to individual, time to time, and situation to situation. Although ecological and societal factors must be included in any full explanation of crime, individual factors always intervene between them and a criminal act. For this reason, individual factors need to be the centre of any description of the causes of crime. Although ecological and societal factors must be included in any full explanation of crime, individual factors cannot be overemphasized. This explains why the individual factor is central in the description of the causes of crime. For this reason, individual factors need to be the centre of any description of the causes of crime. Individual or microlevel factors describe how a person

becomes motivated to commit a crime. However, being motivated to commit a crime alone cannot be the cause of a crime. There must be an opportunity to commit a crime before it can actually be committed. In fact, Katz (1988) observes that opportunity itself may birth motivation. This is what is commonly referred to as “temptation”. Therefore, a person’s tendency to commit a criminal act at a given point in time is a function of both motivation and opportunity. Some may be motivated to seek out and exploit criminal opportunities that offer extremely small rewards; others will commit crimes only when presented with relatively enormous opportunities; and a very few will not commit crimes regardless of rewards. Another factor that could motivate a crime, is what the intending criminal stands to gain or what he stands to lose (advantage and disadvantage). For instance, one might want to opine politicians who offer and take bribe do not manifest criminal tendencies as hardened criminals who go about with guns or other harmful objects, but still have more tendency to commit crimes than their colleagues who do not indulge in this act.

Also, comparing the level of crime in politics and sciences, it might not be shocking that that of politics would be higher relative to what is found in sciences. This is because in politics, the opportunities are enormously tempting. Scientific crimes are relatively rare. In this wise, it is not motivation but opportunity that is lacking. Criminologists have suggested that a number of individual factors determine a person’s motivation to perpetrate a criminal act. To them, motivation at a particular point in time is the outcome of interactions over a person’s life course between biological, socio-cultural, and developmental factors—as well as contemporaneous opportunity. Psychological factors are the outcomes of interactions between biological and socio-cultural factors. As observed by Fishbein (1990), and Wilson and Herrnstein (1985), biological factors include such things as physical size, strength, or swiftness, and the excitability or reactivity of nervous and organ systems in the body. It is easy to assume that big, athletic young males are likely to be statistically over-represented among strong armed robbers compared to small, skinny, awkward fellows.

Although these factors set the physical boundaries of peoples’ behaviour and influence their affective state, they do not necessarily determine which of the many possible behaviours people exhibit. These sociocultural factors include the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and other cultural

information we learn through interactions with other people and groups, as well as from cultural artifacts such as books and movies. For example, the value we place on the good will and opinion of others is a socio-cultural factor, as are many of the beliefs that affect the value we assign to material or symbolic goods. Socio-cultural factors influence the strength of self-control that helps individuals resist temptation. They also can produce “strain” that magnifies temptation when there are disjunctions between what we have learned to desire and the opportunities we perceive. The relationship that exists among the various factors explained above is illustrated with the diagram below:

Fig. 1: The Nature and Distribution of Crime

Source: (Schiller, Black, & Murphy, www.des.ucdavis.edu/faculty/Richerdson/Bookonline)

2.3 Criminal Law in Nigeria: Some Preliminary Issues

In the opinion of Okonkwo and Naish (2012), a large number of systems of criminal law had been in existence in Nigeria prior to the coming of the British to the country. Every region of the country had specific ways of handling crimes and criminal matters. For instance, in the South,

there were myriads of relatively simple systems of social norms based on the unit of the family, village, or the group of villages (pp. 4). In the Northern part of an area known as Nigeria today, there was the highly systematised and well-executed Moslem law of crime (Sharia law); so well-organised that there were in existence many schools of jurists (functioning as custodians of the Northern region's law). A typical example of these schools was the Maliki school. Also in the North, there were 'pagan' communities which maintained their own criminal laws and the dominant Moslem law. Apart from these Moslem law, there was the customary criminal law which, as at that time, had not been committed into writing.

This organised system of handling criminal matters in the area then prepared a peaceful and organised society for the coming of the British. Everybody knew what was wrong from what was right, and the possible consequences of any aberrant behaviours. With the coming of the British to Nigeria, the English common law which included the common law of crime was first introduced in the Lagos colony, while the customary criminal law was in operation in every other colony. However, with the desire for the development of a centralised system of government, it was felt by the British administration to introduce a clearly stated unified set of criminal principles, which would be applicable in British courts. Following this was a proclamation in 1904 by the Lord Lugard administration of a Criminal Code in the North, whose purpose was to amend the existing customary criminal law already in existence. This was later extended to the whole country in 1916, after the unification of the northern and southern protectorates in 1914. This code was patterned in line with the Code introduced into the State of Queensland, Australia, in 1899.

The application of the Northern criminal code was initially strictly limited, as its section clearly exempted "native tribunals", and this was on till 1916. Even much after 1916, most criminal cases in Nigeria were still not governed by the Code, but by the native law and customary law. Obviously, the British administration was not at home with this development (the situation in which there were two or more systems of criminal law in operation in a geographical area). In particular, the British administration was disenchanted with the Moslem law (as interpreted by the Maliki school) in the North. The Maliki law had in it many rules which did not go down well with those in English law. For instance, the offence of homicide, punishable with death, included

any hostile, unjustified assault ending in death, even though this might not be intentional. Political offences were ambiguous and vague of definition. At the height of the friction between the English law and the customary law was the concept of provocation which was recognised by the Criminal code capable of reducing murder to manslaughter, but which was not admitted in the Maliki law. The Maliki law was considered too attached to the Northern Muslims' way of life. In 1933, the legal system of the country was overhauled; and many people were of the opinion that the customary criminal law should be abrogated. This then led to the amendment of the section 4 of the criminal code ordinance, which provided that:

No person shall be liable to be tried or punished in any court in Nigeria, other than a native tribunal, for an offence except under the express provisions of the Code or some other Ordinance, or some law, or some Order in Council made by His Majesty for Nigeria or under the express provisions of some statute of the Imperial Parliament which is in force in, or forms part of the law in Nigeria.

2.4 A Global Picture of the Mandate of the Police

However 'crime-free' a society, a nation or country appears to be or claims to be, such a society, nation or country cannot completely do away with the services of the police, equipped with certain institutional powers by the law in operation in such a country. The mandate of the police is made up of a number of accretions and avulsions to and from the basic requirements of keeping peace and stopping crime (Buckner, 1967: 33). The police are saddled with such responsibilities and assignments which they carry out without being "successfully challenged". It is via these institutional routine performance that the police establishes and exercises its institutional authority in society. However, the complex nature of the mandate of the police has left us with the question of "in what regard or instance do we say they are doing a nice job?" In view of this, Banton (1964: 28) writes thus:

In the case of certain organisations, it is fairly easy to agree on criteria of organisational efficiency. Armies are efficient insofar as they can defend national interests by military action; the fishing

industry is organised to catch large quantities of fish at economic cost; motor manufacturers are efficient if they produce reliable and inexpensive vehicles, and so on. But the police have to meet many criteria and it is difficult to compare the value of success in one direction at the expense of shortcomings in another. For example, a police force which solved more crimes but which treated suspects with undue severity would be in one sense more efficient, but its activities would excite public protest. The police are given a variety of objectives but they are simultaneously subjected to a host of restrictions concerning the ways in which they may attain them, and the interplay between the ends and means is much more complex than in most organisations. The efficiency of the police may therefore be less important than their responsiveness to the community they are required to serve.

The police, in order to carry out their responsibilities, exercise certain powers which are “legally granted” to them; sometimes wield certain powers on which the law is seemingly ‘silent’. These powers exercised by the police are weapons with which they conquer the minds of any individual(s) caught in their web. They have the right and prerogative to effect an arrest for social misconduct or misdemeanours when they are witnesses to the social misdemeanours. When it is not done in their presence, however, a complainant making or instituting an arrest must be certain or sure that the offence has taken place, or else, he or she could be liable for false arrest. For instance, the police have the institutional right or power to arrest a person for felony when there is a reasonable cause to believe that the individual has actually committed the crime, irrespective of whether or not the act was perpetrated. In the same vein, a citizen may make an arrest when he has the reasonable cause to believe that felony has been committed by the offender, but he must be very certain that felony must have been committed; if not, he might be liable himself.

The law equally equips the police with the power to persist in their attempts to effect an arrest in the face of resistance, and in fact make such resistance itself an offence. In both cases, the citizen

has “almost” the same rights but the police have more latitude. This is probably due to the conception by the law of the police officer as being ‘a little above the average’ citizen of a country. In fact, the right to arrest resides more with the police than the citizen(s). The police equally have access to equipment like gun, handcuff, teargas to facilitate the process of arrest of a suspect or an accused person. The police personalise the prerogative to use discretion to enforce the laws they have to enforce. They might decide for some reason to enforce a law in one area but not in another. They may equally decide not to enforce a law in a particular situation in order to give them bargaining powers. All these are what make the police an institution that has established itself as an agent of social control.

2.5 The Nigeria Police (Force): Its Origin and Development

The word “Police”, according to Afonja (2008), came from France in the 10th century. It referred to the body of men and their system of cleaning, lighting and repairing the cities and urban areas. However, in today’s world, the term refers to a country’s arrangement for the maintenance of law and order as well as the protection of life and property. The Nigeria Police started in Lagos in the middle of the 19th century, with its creation birthed by the political and socio-economic difficulties faced by the British administration between 1840 and 1860. Prior to this time, the Native Authority system had been in practice, with messengers and royal guards in every locality to ensure the security of traditional rulers and their properties and maintenance of law and order.

In 1861, the Lagos Consular Guard was founded to maintain law and order; what formed the nucleus of the modern Nigeria Police. As a follow up to this, in 1863, the Armed Hausa Police was formed. This outfit, though military in nature, equally performed civil police duties within the Colony and its environs. Apparently and arguably, this force was established to enforce obedience to the Colonial rule and masters. Also in 1879, the Hausa Constabulary was created as a more organised and regularised body of the Armed Hausa Police. This was constituted by 1200 officers and men, equally saddled with the responsibility of inspecting weights and measures and prisons.

In 1886, the Lagos Constabulary was established. It came as an enlargement of the Hausa Constabulary with a more refined and pragmatic system of administration. In the same vein in

1888, the Royal Niger Constabulary was founded as a sister-outfit to the Hausa Constabulary of the Colony with its Headquarters in Lokoja, meant to serve the Northern Protectorate of Nigeria, especially the properties and operations of the Royal Niger Company along the River Niger.

In 1891, the Marine Police was established to be in charge of the coastal area of the Colony, and this was immediately followed in 1894 by the establishment of the Niger Coast Constabulary whose headquarters was in Calabar, with the responsibility of policing the Oil River Protectorate. The Lagos Police (Force) was established in 1896 as a modified body of the Hausa and Lagos Constabulary and in 1897, the Detective Corps of the Lagos Police Force was established and specially and specifically trained for crime investigation, particularly in the Colony area. In 1899, the Railway Police was created to maintain security of the Railway Transport system. Shortly after the establishment of the Railway Police, the Southern Nigeria Police was established (precisely in 1906) and absorbed the Lagos Police Force and the Niger Coast Constabulary. This force was under the control of the Inspector-General of Police and was saddled with the responsibility of preventing and detecting crime, repressing internal disturbances and ensuring the defence of the colony and the Southern Protectorate against any external aggression and forces. The force was equally responsible for the prison system and the Fire Brigade.

In 1908, the Northern Nigeria Police was established having some of the men of the Royal Niger Company disbanded in 1900 when the Protectorate of Northern Nigeria was proclaimed. In 1930, there was the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Police, which saw the bringing together of both regiments to form the base of the Nigeria Police Force for the country (as we have today).

The year 1960 saw the establishment of the Nigeria Police Force under the Independence Constitution of 1960 and the Republican Constitution of 1963, as a Federal Force under the command of the Inspector-General of Police, saddled with the task of maintaining law and order throughout the country. The Nigeria Police Force was re-established by section 194 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1979, the Police Act Cap. 359 Laws of the Federation 1990 and later by section 214 (1) of the 1999 Constitution.

2.5.1 Functions and Basic Duties of the Nigeria Police Force

The Nigeria Police is an outfit that is saddled with myriads of (difficult) tasks which range from ensuring maintenance of law and order, safety of life and property and ensuring the security of the nation. However, specifically, the organisation is saddled with the following responsibilities, as contained in section 4 of the Police Act of the Federal Republic of Nigeria:

2.5.1.1 Prevention and Detection of Crime

This, is perhaps, the greatest and the most herculean task the organisation is saddled with. The Police Force protect the citizenry, and in a bid to perform this task maximally, members of the force have to risk their lives in order to save others' lives. Prevention strategy is based on physical presence of the police officer.

2.5.1.2 Protection of Life and Property

Protecting life and property is another tasking job of the police; what Afonja (2008) calls the "sacred duty" of the police. The life of a man forms the basis of every human society, therefore, its protection is pertinent, and this is the business of the police. Just as the life of a man is protected, his properties that make life worth living for him must be protected. This explains (perhaps) why the police conduct patrols on the streets, keeping their eyes on the belongings of the people.

2.5.1.3 Preservation of Law and Order and Apprehension of Offenders

This is equally very important among the many roles of the police. "Preservation of law and order is the basis of human existence, as without law and order, there would be no society" (Afonja 2008: 59). This duty involves the activities of the police, such as the enforcement of traffic laws and regulations, regulation of public meetings and processions, under the Public Order Act of 2002 and other related statutes, ensuring peace and orderliness by apprehending and prosecuting of offenders, and due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are directly charged.

2.5.1.4 Performance of Military Duties

The police may equally sometimes be asked to perform military duties within or outside Nigeria, especially during insurrection, communal strife or crisis and external aggression for the preservation of life and property. For instance in 1960, members of the Nigeria Police were deployed to Congo to help restore peace in the country. Also in 1992, the Nigeria Police was deployed to Namibia to salvage the chaotic situation of the country; and in 1994, the organisation was equally deployed to Angola for peace and order restoration during the multi-party elections held in the country at that period. The organisation was equally involved in restoring peace and order in the Bakkasi imbroglio that ensued between Nigeria and Cameroon.

In addition to the tasks above, the police equally perform the following:

- Decide whether or not to prosecute suspected offenders
- Conduct minor prosecutions
- Conduct road traffic
- Carry out duties in connection with applications for Nigerian Nationality
- Control possession and use of certain categories of arms and ammunitions
- To assist anyone in need of help in minor or major disasters.

2.6 Forensic Linguistics: An Overview

Coulthard and Johnson (2007:5) observe that the term forensic linguistics was first used in 1949 by Philbrick in his work titled *Language and the Law: the Semantics of Forensic English*. Predicating on the work of Philbrick, Jan Svartvik, in 1968, did the analysis of the statements given by Timothy Evans, who had been accused of killing his wife and child. It was in this work that the concept of forensic linguistics first featured. Svartvik opined that Evans did not give all the statements as depicted in the record written by the police; many of the statements were observed distinctive owing to their formal style.

Also prominent in the development of the field of forensic linguistics is Roger Shuy, whose contribution to the science is related to Miranda rights (Kalajdzalihovic, 2011: 994). Shuy made it explicit that an individual cannot be talked into testifying non voluntarily, particularly if he or

she does not understand his or her rights. Thus, one of the prominent contributions of forensic linguistics to police interrogations is ensuring that an individual's words are recorded properly and not paraphrased or embellished such that it could have implicating effects on a suspected individual, who has been interrogated by the police. Forensic linguistics is (equally) a field of study that is interested in police interrogation and court-related matters. It is a field that is well interested in as sensitive but seemingly "unattended" issues like detecting plagiarism and attributing authorship to different types of written documents, discourse or conversation, e.g. electronic mail, SMSs, legal documents, etc. Forensic linguistics is the study of language as applied to forensic purposes and contexts (McMenamin, 2002).

2.7 Some Notable Works on Forensic Discourse Analysis

Fox (1993) attempts to compare *policespeak* and *normalspeak*. He observed that the most conspicuous grammatical feature of police officers' statements is the use of "then" immediately after a subject rather than have it at the beginning of the clause. As observed by Farinde (1997), "then" is not the only adjunct used after subject(s) in police statements. Time and frequency adjuncts like 'again', 'at first', and continually are also untypically frequent in that position.

Also, Fox (1993) notes that police officers are very particular about time in their statements. In their statements, actual times are usually stated: 'at 5:12 p.m., 'at 9:23 p.m., e.t.c. These are used mainly to indicate when questioning begins and ends. They are also used to indicate times of events, either as reported by the suspect (accused) or as observed by the police. There is also the use of many approximate times in police statements, such as 'at approximately 3: 10 am, at about 1:12 p.m. This feature is usually reflected in witnesses' statement, probably because of the obsession of the police for time is felt by the witnesses, who meticulously try to fix all events into appropriate time and sequence.

In addition, Fox observed that even more common in police statements than actual times are adverbials of time, often used at the beginning of a clause. Some of these adverbials of time are 'later, later on, later the same day, at this time, after this, a short time after this, the next day, in the morning of that day, etc. This is in line with Coulthard's (1992) position on the use of adverbs in forensic discourse. Some of the adverbs of time noted in forensic discourse by

Coulthard are ‘ after this, the next day, later on, etc. Police statements are usually very exact in the way they describe events. This is usually done via the expression of an already described time, and also by clauses signalled by as, when, whilst, while, just as we were walking out ..., when he had finished raping her, he then threw her out of the room, while patrolling the area looking for the pond, while he was doing it, after examining the item, on entering the kitchen I saw .., at this point she asked.... (Farinde 1997:11).

Fox (1993) equally points out that the police statements are usually characterised by certainty or precision in the setting of the scene, where the interview or interrogation is taking place, where an arrest is effected, etc. Another feature inherent in police statement (as observed by Fox 1993) is the use of passive voice. This usually gives the feeling that an event has occurred without human intervention. Farinde (1997) gives some examples of this, presumably from his data. Some of these are “the car was removed to Yaba Police station, where it was technically examined”, Mr Frederick Moses was served a meal in his cell”, etc. There are also the use of prepositional phrases starting with “by” in police statements. This must have resulted from the preponderant use of passive sentences by police officers both in their spoken and written statements. Consider the following examples as cited from Farinde (1997: 12): “the licensed premises was robbed *by* two armed and masked men”; “Tunde was ordered across to the traffic island in the middle of the road *by* the gunman with the shotgun”; “Reuben was taken to an interview room at 10:28 *by* Detective Constable Okoro”; “ Prior to that, he was supplied with a meal *by* Detective Constable Okoro”, etc.

Policespeak and normalspeak have equally been identified to be different in their vocabulary. There are words referring to different offences, all of which have their precise and exact meanings in law, which might not easily and readily be found in the vocabulary of “innocent layman”. Some of these words or phrases are burglary, stealing, malicious damage, unlawful sex, homicide, conspiracy, burden of proof, murder, etc. There are some jargon peculiar to the police system and, as such, important not only to people who use them, but also to the people they are used for. Understandably, some of these words or phrases are not explained in conventional dictionaries. In the same vein, Fox (1993) posits the word “alleged” is an attributive adjective common in police statements in particular, and data in general. Hence, we have expressions as

“alleged perpetrator, “alleged trespasser”, “alleged rape”, etc. When the word “alleged” is used in this wise, it implies “said to have taken place, but has not been proved or investigated to its logical conclusion”.

Also, in the vocabulary of the police, shots are not “fired” but “discharged”, jewellery or stolen items are not found but “recovered”, people “undergo” an examination and not “have” one, the police “retain” possession of property” and do not keep it; prisoners are “conveyed back” to the prison and not “taken back”, journeys are “commenced” and not “begun” or “started”. Fox equally observed that a particular verb is recurrent or frequently used in police statements. The verb is the verb “continue”:” the police continue with enquiries, continue to question”; they continue questioning. Equally, police officers do not list dates but enumerate dates and time.

The verb enumerate is a legal jargon, and as such is often used in this context than in normal or casual conversations; so also is the verb “patrol”. Policemen or security officials “patrol” an area or areas. Fox (1993) submits that the prevailing tone of many police statements is that of pomposity, perhaps caused by too high level of formality and their institutional authority. This is very prevalent in our data, where the IPOs relate to suspects as superior interlocutors and suspects, the inferior or less-superior position in police-suspect discourse. However, Farinde (1997) is quick to point out that this is not true of all statements, or indeed of the whole of a statement. This might be true to some extent, but it must be pointed out that, preponderantly, police officers exercise some form of power and authority over suspects in their discourse.

Coulthard’s (1992) work is one of the earliest contributions to the field of forensic linguistics/discourse analysis. As observed by Davis (1986), prior to 1992 when Coulthard’s forensic analysis came on board, most of the forensic works in existence had been in the area of samples of handwriting and of tape-recorded voices (Nolan 1983, Baldwin and French 1990). Coulthard (1992) opines forensic discourse analysis is concerned with two kinds of text-handwritten contemporaneous records as made by police officers of interviews with witnesses and suspects, and statements which are dictated to police officers by witnesses and suspects. In his view, an interview is conventionally and normally conducted by one, usually the more senior police officer, and transcribed by a second (a junior officer to the one that conducted the interview).

Usually, an interview proceeds very slowly and gradually; and usually at 20 to 25 words a minute. The text is taken as a complete record of what was said during the interview, which would include the caveat or caution: *You are not obliged to say anything unless you wish to do so, but what you say will be put into writing and given in evidence. Do you understand?*

We actually observed something similar to this during our data collection exercise. Whenever a statement had been taken, the IPO would read what the suspect might have written down or been helped to write down as he talked (in cases involving suspects that could not write). Coulthard (1992) is of the opinion that the responsibility of the forensic discourse analyst is to take one or more interview records or statements and analytically comment on their possible authenticity. Put in another way, whenever there is a bone of contention between an accused person or a suspect and the police as to the originality of the statement credited to him or her (in case of fabrication for instance), the forensic linguist or discourse analyst is contracted to clear the air over the controversy. In essence, the forensic discourse analyst would be able to show that some or all the contents of the interview are not true. In doing this, therefore, the analyst points out that it might be impossible to say anything about the veracity of what is written in the disputed text; but surely, he can comment meaningfully and usefully on the veracity of the divergent claims made by the opposing sides about the text.

According to Coulthard (1992), a police or investigating officer, who fabricates lies in his statements can be detected in three ways, viz through psycholinguistic consideration, quantity of information, and discourse structure. Under the psycholinguistic consideration, Coulthard opined the responsibility of the investigating officer is to prevent an ambiguous or vague statement being presented to the court. However, whenever he is bent on implicating the accused person, he deliberately paints up some fabrications. The experienced discourse analyst should easily detect this via the identification of embedded contradictions. With respect to quantity of information, reference is made to Grice's (1975) maxims. Grice maintained that one of the controls on speaker's contributions is the quantity maxim, which he summarised thus:

- make your contributions as informative as is required
- do not make your contribution more informative than required. Grice (1973) submits that fabricators often break this maxim easily because they want to satisfy or convince the

court. They try to be unambiguous, but at the same time, they say more than required because of their intention to manipulate facts.

As observed by Coulthard (1992), the difficulty with evidence based on discourse structure comes in two ways; first, we have the acknowledged fact that nothing can be regarded as undiscoursal, that is, anything can occur and so the analyst is forced to argue at best by appealing to probabilities; secondly, we currently lack a database, that is, substantial collection of texts with which we can compare a suspect's text (Farinde 1997: 16). Studying the discourse structure in a normal sequence, the forensic discourse analyst can have a clue on areas of fabrication, as statements fraught with fabrications might be characterised by sequential inconsistency. No doubt, Coulthard's (1992) *Forensic Discourse Analysis* is a colossal insight into the field of forensic linguistics in general.

2.8. Review of Specific Works on Police-Suspect Discourse in Nigeria

Bamgbose (1971) observes that (Nigerian) Pidgin English is a language preponderant in police discourse in Nigeria. In fact, the language could be described as the semi-lingua franca of the organisation. This assertion by Bamgbose is obviously birthed by the fact that the language features prominently in police communication in Nigeria. However, this variety of English in Nigeria was later referred to by Bamgbose (1995) as Broken English. The use of Broken English by the Nigeria Police Force can be said to have evolved from the fact that English, being the official language in the country, is used as the official language in the force and not “many police officers can converse fluently in Standard English”; and as a way of finding their way out of this dilemma, officers who are not very competent in the use of the language find respite in the use of Broken English. This conclusion was further reinforced in Terebo (2012) .

Ogunsiji (1989) examines the language of the police in Ila Local Government area in Osun State. He adopts a discourse analytical approach to police communication in Nigeria, and argues that language is a functional and social phenomenon. He differs in his opinion as far as the place of Nigeria Pidgin is concerned in the Nigerian policing system. In his view, police English is an occupational variety of the Nigerian English. Justifying his position, Ogunsiji cites examples of Nigerian English, its characteristics and those factors that contribute to its growth and

development. His application of the principles of Speech Acts, Pragmatics, Semiotics and Sociolinguistics to police communication in Nigeria has helped in painting a graphic picture which portrays the variety of English used in the police force as, first, an occupational variety of Nigerian English, and, second, that it helps the organization in realising her linguistic and communicative goals.

He further argues that, by using the concepts of coherence and cohesion, police language is a complete genre of communication and the police know those discourse principles they are to employ in using the language they use to negotiate meaning. However, as salient as the concept of power (relations) is in police discourse, this is not really handled in Ogunsiiji's (1989) work. Also, as pointed out by Sadiq (2011), the concept of context is not well considered in Ogunsiiji's work.

Farinde's (1997) work titled "A Linguistic Study of Police/Accused Discourse" is a comprehensive work that examines the nature of police interrogation, using the Discourse Analysis approach. The work describes the structure and organisation of police/accused interrogation, observing the communication strategies and their motivation. The work adopts the framework of analysis proposed by Sinclair and Coulthard (1975) which comprises Transaction, Exchange, Move and Act. However, among these, "ACT" is considered to be the most relevant to the work, hence its adoption. Farinde (1997) concludes that Act forms such as Elicitation, Directive, Prompt, Evaluation, Accuse, Excuse and Reply/Informative are attested to in police/accused discourse. According to him, the Elicitation Act form is used by the police to get information from the accused person. In other words, the IPOs always use this Act form to get or elicit information from accused persons. The directive Act form is used in police/accused discourse by the police to instill fear in the accused person, as fear is considered to be a very strong weapon that the police make use of to take advantage of the accused person. Also, the Prompt Act form entails the use of persuasion, threat and torture to force the accused person to confess having committed the crime he is alleged to have committed. The Accusation Act form is used by the police to catch the accused person off-guard, thereby making him to confess his crime unwittingly. The excuse Act form is used by the accused person to exonerate himself of a crime. The Evaluation Act form is used by the police to decide whether the accused person is

speaking the truth or not. And finally, Reply/Informative is the major Act form used by the accused person. The accused person is always replying to the elicitation and prompt Act forms of the police.

As mentioned earlier, Farinde (1997) is a somewhat comprehensive work that could be described to have done some justice to the subject-matter. However, the work, just like many other acclaimed scholarly works on this subject matter, has its deficiencies. To start with, the title of the work could be described as a misnomer. The use of the word “accused” in the title is not appropriate. Rather, the word “suspect” should have been more appropriate. This discovery was made in the course of a personal interview with a Deputy Superintendent of the Police (DSP) in the course of this research work at Eleyele Police Station, the State Headquarters of the Nigeria Police, Oyo State. The interview, coupled with library consultations, revealed the disparity between these closely related but separate terms. An accused is an individual that has been charged to court over an alleged crime while a suspect is an individual who is still within the custody of the police for having allegedly committed a crime. From this explanation therefore, it becomes obvious that the term “accused” is used within the court setting while “suspect” is within the jurisdiction of the police station. These two terms have however, ignorantly perhaps, used interchangeably by many individuals including scholars, Farinde (1997) inclusive.

Also, Farinde (1997) fails to tell us the preponderant Act employed by the police in police/ “accused” discourse among the many Act forms identified in his work. As typical of the various works read on this subject-matter, Farinde (1997) fails to lead us into the pragmatics of the various Acts he has identified in his work. For instance, he claims Elicitation Act which comprises basically questions is used to get information from the accused person; however, bringing this claim to the context of pragmatics (as done in this present study), we observe that the police make use of this act other than just asking fact or information-seeking questions. Also, as central as the concept of power is to interactions between the police and “accused” persons, it is not mentioned in Farinde’s work. In spite of these deficiencies however, Farinde’s effort is commendable at least for one thing, showing us the structure of police/ “accused” discourse.

Moradeyo's (2004) work titled "Sociolinguistic Using Linguistic Means to Detect Crime during Police Interrogation: A Case Study of a Nigerian Police Station, Bodija, Ibadan, Oyo State" is an attempt to examine how linguistics can be applied in crime detection in police-suspect interaction. However, a critical and painstaking examination of this work reveals elements of deviation from the main focus (as suggested in the title). One would have thought that the researcher would witness series of interrogation or questioning exercise in order to collect his data and then subject the data, especially the responses of the suspects and accused identified, to rigorous linguistic analysis to detect instances of falsehood or otherwise. The researcher restricted himself to file cases presented to him by the officers in charge of the visited police station. This he did, not bearing in mind the fact that such reports could have been doctored in one way or the other, as our investigation has shown that many suspects who are either illiterate or semi-literate do rely on Investigating Police Officers in committing their statements into writing. Even when such statements are usually read to the hearing of the concerned, one can never rule out the possibility of instances of misrepresentation or mispresentation of facts in the process. Therefore, any data got through this process might not be very reliable.

Also, going through the work, one cannot see anywhere in the work where linguistics is employed to detect crimes as the title suggests. As a matter of fact, his analysis could be said not to be within the terrain of linguistics but perhaps within the field of law. In spite of these shortcomings however, the work has led us into the fact that many IPOs are biased in the manner in which they handle cases reported to the police. As pointed out by him, they are often fond of relying heavily on the statements of complainants and use such to the disadvantage of suspects. He also recommends the recruitment of forensic linguists to handle language technicalities in police-suspect interaction; a position which is shared by the current researcher.

Adebowale (2010) attempts a sociolinguistic analysis of the language of police interrogation in Nigeria, using Sango Police station in Ibadan as a case study. At best, the work illustrates the stylistic features of police interrogation. She concludes that the language of police interrogation is characterised by threats, warnings, accusations, requests and probes. According to her, the structure of police investigation is dominantly interrogative, although can also be imperative and declarative in nature. Some of the sociolinguistic features she claims characterise the language of

police interrogation in Nigeria include the use of loan words, code mixing, code switching and certain discourse markers. She also submits that the tone of interrogation depends on the nature of the crime, the level of cooperation from the suspect and the temperament of the investigator. Kudos must be given to Adebowale for her indepth analysis of the subject-matter of her work. However, it must be pointed out that the work has its deficiencies, however little they might have been.

First, the researcher identifies features as threats, warnings, accusation, requests and probes as characteristic of police language during interrogation. However, she fails to let us into the pragmatic implications of the use of these elements on suspects and accused persons by the police, in terms of how they are used to relegate suspects to the background in police-suspect discourse. Perhaps, this is because her work takes a sociolinguistic look at the subject-matter as against the pragmatic (within the purview of Critical Discourse Analysis) view of this present work. Also, beyond these elements mentioned above, our observation during data collection has equally shown that abuse, interruptions, and paralinguistics are some other linguistic and paralinguistic elements preponderant in police language during interrogation or questioning activities. In actual fact, all these are weapons the police employ to exert their institutional authority and power over suspects and accused persons in the interrogation or question room. It must also be pointed out that Adebowale (2010) mentions the use of discourse markers that are peculiar to police speech in their interaction with suspects; however, none of these is brought to bear in her analysis.

Oyebade (2007) examines the pragmatic features of English in police communication in Ibadan metropolis. Precisely, the work looked at the graphonological, syntactic, and lexico-semantic features of police English. The cooperative and conversational maxims, pragmatic presuppositions and the sociolinguistic phenomena in police communication were also examined in this work; all within the principles of speech acts. The work identified the following as evident in police communication: contextual beliefs of police officers, contextual beliefs of non police officers, and shared beliefs of police and non police officers, illocutionary acts, and perlocutionary acts. The illocutionary acts include representatives, directives, commissives and declaratives. A critical assessment of Oyebade's (2007) work reveals she alligns her position

with that of Ogunsiyi (1989) in classifying the Nigerian police English as an occupational variety of the Nigerian English. No doubt, Oyebade's work is a great and insightful addition to the existing literature on police language in the country. However, it must be pointed out that the work, just like the already existing ones, fails to examine how the concepts of politeness and impoliteness operate in police-suspect interaction, especially in terms of how these phenomena portray asymmetrical distribution of power during police-suspect interaction. Also, as important as this is, she fails to let us into how the police use language to promote their ideologies, thereby relegating suspects to the background in the course of interrogations.

Sadiq's (2011) work is a discourse analysis of the language of interrogation in "police/criminal" investigations in Kano metropolis. Obviously taking a cue from Farinde (1997), Sadiq (2011) attempts a description of the structure and organisation of the content of police/accused discourse; with the view to gaining insights into the communication strategies and motivation in negotiating the interaction. In his data analysis, Sadiq employs the eclectic model of Grice's Cooperative Principle, Sinclair and Coulthard's (1975) discourse analytic framework and Burton's (1981) work. The data analysis therefore focuses on the examination of the structure of interaction between the Investigating Police Officer and the "accused person" during interrogations, depicting the multidimensional functions of the language used in police/accused discourse; whether it is a question, command, or statement based on their grammatical structure in order to locate them in discourse.

Perhaps as an improvement on Farinde's (1997) work, Sadiq (2011) establishes the fact that "the prototypical patterns of discourse in police/criminal investigation are question/answer sequences, and that questioning forms are used to control the flow of discourse in police/accused interrogation". He also opines that one main factor that makes police officers "successful" in their crime investigation is the asymmetrical relationship of power that exists between Investigating Police Officers and the suspects. However, he does not tell us how this power manifests. Much like the submission of Farinde (1997), Sadiq (2011) establishes the fact that police/accused discourse is highly organised with predictable structures, and the structural harmony observed in police/accused discourse is predicated on the linguistic "acts" employed by the IPOs in the course of interrogating suspects.

As stated earlier, Sadiq (2011) has toed the same path with Farinde (1997) in that both works employ Sinclair and Coulthard's (1975) discourse analysis approach, with Sadiq going a step further to include Grice's (1975) Cooperative Principles and Burton's (1981) analytic framework. Therefore, it is no gainsaying that Sadiq (2011) surfaces to make up for the deficiencies spotted in Farinde (1997). However, this does not preclude Sadiq (2011) from attracting its own criticisms. Sadiq also makes the same *terminological* mistake previous scholars have been observed to have made in their reference to the "accused" and "suspect" as though they were synonyms. In fact, making the matter worse, Sadiq uses the term "criminal" in place of these two as evident in his title. This would paint the "suspect" as being pronounced "criminal" by the court, as only the court has the institutional power to pronounce an "offender" a criminal. Also, Sadiq (2011) concludes that questioning forms are the (only) Act forms employed by the police to control the flow of discourse in their interaction with suspects and accused persons. This is a sweeping conclusion that assumes the preclusion of other means or devices by which the police control the flow of discourse during their interaction with suspects and accused persons. This present work actually takes care of this shortcoming.

Terebo (2012) is a work worthy of mention on police activities and language. Precisely, the work examines the place and role of interpreters in police/suspect discourse. In other words, the work focuses on how apt and accurate (police) interpreters are while serving as intermediaries between the IPOs and suspects or accused persons. The theoretical frame work employed in this work is the interlanguage theory. Among the significant findings of this work is the fact that the observed interpreters are not very proficient in the use of the English language; a development that has made it difficult for them to function effectively well in this regard. Lots of grammatical and semantic errors are spotted in the speech of the interpreters who obviously are police officers. This raises a big question as to the educational requirement of the Nigeria Police in her recruitment exercise, or should one say what is witnessed here is the aftermath of the fallen standard of education in Nigeria?

The researcher concludes there is a need for interpreters in this domain to be proficient in the use of the English language, being the country's official language, in order to be able to be more

effective in their role as interpreters during police-suspect discourse or interaction. She then recommends refresher courses, workshops, seminars and symposiums for the IPOs for them to step up their proficiency in the English language. Terebo's work, no doubt, is a beautiful and comprehensive masterpiece on the subject-matter. However, one must not close one's eyes to some of the deficiencies of the work. For instance, the researcher fails to mention the educational qualifications of the interpreters (IPOs) used in her work. This would have at least given us a clear picture of the educational background of the interpreters with the view to ascertaining their qualification or otherwise to function in this capacity. Also, the researcher fails to let us into the number of cases examined, the number of the interpreters involved, and tell us precisely if all the interpreters whose language was observed in this work are found to be below standard in their interpretation assignment.

In conclusion, as a language specialist, one would have thought the researcher would include, as part of her recommendations, the need to have more language experts such as linguists to handle this aspect of the interaction between police and suspects. This would go a long way in reducing the tension that usually emanates from misinterpretation of language in police-suspect discourse. It also needs to be pointed out that the work is fraught with some typographical and grammatical errors considered to be an oversight on the part of the researcher.

2. 9 Theoretical Framework

This work adopts the Politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1987) and Impoliteness theory of Culpeper (1996, 2008) within the purview of the Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis proposed by Fairclough and Wodak (1997).

2.9.1 The Concept of Politeness

Important in the study of pragmatics are the concepts of politeness and face. The definitions and description of these concepts, like many other concepts in language studies, have generated polarity among scholars. As observed by Meier (1995: 345), "there is a disconcerting amount of divergence and lack of clarity concerning the meaning of politeness" among scholars. Held (1992:131) describes the concept as a linguistic phenomenon which is definitionally fuzzy and empirically difficult. In view of this, therefore, the concept of politeness has been variously

expressed and explained in the literature as formality, deference, indirectness, appropriateness, etiquette, and as tact (Fraser, 1990; Kasper, 1994, Meir, 1995 and Thomas, 1995). Lakoff (1995) views politeness as a means of saying the socially correct thing. Adegbija (1989) links politeness with a situation that enables one to speak or behave in a way that is socially and culturally acceptable and pleasant to the hearer. Ide (1993) sees politeness as behaviour without friction. Brown (1980) adds that politeness is a way of saying and doing things in a manner that takes into consideration the feelings of other people. However, Fraser and Nolen (1981:1) opine “to be polite is to abide by rules of the relationship”. From these, therefore, we can define politeness as being situationally and culturally nice, accommodating and considerate, either verbally or behaviourally.

2.9.1.1 Types of Politeness

Some scholars have attempted taking the definition of politeness beyond the notion of appropriateness. In pursuit of this, these scholars distinguish between First-order and Second-order politeness. This distinction has hitherto been the anchor upon which several other categorisations proposed in the literature hang. For example, Kasper (1994: 3206) views politeness as “proper social conduct and tactful consideration of others and ways in which relational function in linguistics is expressed”. These two views (first-order and second-order) are a reflection of Kasper’s classification of politeness to commonsense notion and pragmatic concept respectively. Following the same categorisation by Fraser, Janney and Arndt (1992: 24) differentiate between social politeness and interpersonal politeness, referred to as tact. To these scholars, social politeness provides conventional strategies in social situations to “coordinate social interaction, while personal politeness focuses on politeness at the pragmatic level, aiming at preserving face and regulating interpersonal relationships”. Interpersonal politeness could be described as precedent to social politeness.

Similarly, Watts (1989, 1992) introduces the term politic behaviour, that is, second-order politeness, which contrasts with polite behaviour, first-order politeness. The author defines politic behaviour as “socio-culturally determined behaviour aimed at establishing and/or maintaining, in a state of equilibrium, the personal relationships between the individuals of a social group” (Watts, 1992 :50). He then proposes two marked forms of behaviour: non-politic,

that is, behaviour leading to communicative breakdowns, and polite behaviour whose function is to save or take care of an individual's image (face) in the eyes of the others.

From the following, one can conclude that although scholars vary in their conceptualisation of the types of politeness, what becomes obvious is the fact that politeness phenomenon is very central to interpersonal and social interaction in every human society.

2.10 Approaches to Politeness

Fraser (1990) argues that there are four approaches to politeness – the social norm view, the conversational maxim view, the conversational contract view and the face-saving view.

2.10.1 The Social Norm View

This view has to do with the normative view of politeness seen as the social standards of behaviour in any human society. There appears to be controversies in the literature with respect to the status of this approach within approaches to politeness. While it is seen as the extreme view which avows that the interpretation of politeness as the desire to be pleasant to others cannot be conceptualised within pragmatics, Fraser (1990) opines that this approach has few adherents in the current research on politeness. However, it seems that this conceptualisation of politeness can be seen as corresponding to another view called “discernment politeness”, which has been proposed as the underlying basis of politeness systems in non-Western cultures (Hill et al, 1986; Ide 1989). This view presumes social standards are akin to discernment politeness in that it refers to the use of the standard in a social setting (Watts et al, 1992). In this respect therefore, this approach to politeness could be said to have its place in pragmatic research.

2.10.2 The Conversational Maxim View

Prominent among the proponents and adherents of this view are Lakoff (1973) and Leech (1983). As maintained by Lakoff, the essence of politeness is avoidance of conflicts; and he went ahead to specify three principles to establish this. These are (1) don't impose (2) give options, and (3) make A feel good. Apparently, these scholars have based their theoretical frameworks on Grice's Cooperative Principle (1967, and published in 1975). The Cooperative Principle is believed to be of key importance in regulating conversation and it is predicated on the assumption of

cooperation in a conversation between and among discourse interlocutors. Lakoff (1973) in particular expands Grice's work and argues for the necessity of both a politeness principle and a cooperative principle. While the Cooperative Principle primarily has a referential orientation, the Politeness Principle addresses relational goals (Kasper, 1994), and serves mainly to reduce friction in personal interaction (Lakoff, 1989: 64).

However, in spite of its impact on politeness-related research subjects, this view has been heavily critiqued and criticised, with the main bone of contention being that the Cooperative Principle is too ambiguous (vague) to be operative and that it does not address the question of what politeness really is (Van De Walle, 1993; Watts et al 1992). This model does not clearly give any insight into how the three proposed levels of politeness, that is, don't impose; give options; and make the hearer feel good operate (Lakoff, 1973). In reaction to the weaknesses of Lakoff's (1973) argument on politeness principle, Leech (1983) proposes a more all-encompassing framework on the subject matter. Here again, the explicit definition of politeness becomes elusive, but it is situated within the domain of Interpersonal Rhetoric, that is, the focus is on the speaker's social aims and goals, rather than his or her illocutionary goals.

Leech (1983:81) then reformulates the politeness principle in a general way to "minimise" the expression of impolite beliefs, and divides it into six interpersonal maxims, namely Tact, Generosity, Approbation, Modesty, Agreement, and Sympathy.

Tact : maximise hearer's cost, maximise hearer's benefit

Generosity: minimise self benefit, maximise your hearer's benefit

Approbation: minimise hearer's dispraise; maximise the hearer's praise

Modesty: minimising praise for oneself; maximising praise for others

Agreement: minimising disagreement between self and others; maximise agreement

Sympathy: minimising antipathy between self and others; maximising sympathy between self and others.

These maxims serve to improve on Lakoff's earlier politeness maxims and extend to all cases of politeness.

2.10.3 The Conversational Contract View

This approach to politeness was proposed by Fraser and Nolan (1981) and subsequently elaborated by Fraser (1990). This is the most general view of politeness, one that places this sociolinguistic phenomenon in the realm of terms and conditions of a conversational contract (CC) existing between participants (Dimitrova-Galaczi, 2005: 5). Fraser (1990) then opines that politeness is virtually the same as using language appropriately. In this sense, Fraser's conceptualisation of the concept of politeness is very much akin to that of Watts (1992:216) which centres on the notion of politic behaviour; which involves maintaining the equilibrium in a relationship. This approach to politeness can be said to be in consonance with the view that politeness is the same as using language appropriately.

2.10.4 The Face-Saving View: Politeness Theory by Brown and Levinson

The notion of face came from Goffman's (1967) work on face and from the English "folk" notion of face, which ties up with notions of being embarrassed, humiliated or losing face (Brown and Levinson 1987). However, the term face-saving view to politeness was proposed by Brown and Levinson (1978,1987). Here, Brown and Levinson connect the three basic notions of (a) communication as a rational activity (b) cooperative principle and maxims of conversation (as proposed by Grice 1975) and (c) face – the public self-image that every member of society wants to claim for themselves.

The notion of face is a term for two separate sets of human wants: positive face and negative face. The positive face is the desire to be approved of by others. It is the self-image which an individual desires others to appreciate and approve during interaction (Brown and Levinson 1987). The negative face refers to the want of an individual to be unimpeded by others. It is an individual's desire to be free of imposition by others and that others do not impede one's action (Sunday, 2010). The basic assumption behind Brown and Levinson's theory is that face is constantly at risk, since any kind of linguistic action called a Face Threatening Act (FTA), which has a relational dimension, is seen as posing a threat to the interlocutor's face. Therefore, such face threatening acts need to be counterbalanced by appropriate doses of politeness (Kasper, 1994). According to Brown and Levinson (1987), there are four strategies that speakers can use in threatening the face of their interlocutors. These strategies are hierarchical, in that they are

presented on the basis of the extent to which they threaten the interlocutor's face. Since each individual is endowed with rationality, the crucial assumption is projected that the speaker will choose the best possible strategy before performing a Face Threatening Act. Brown and Levinson (1978) schematically present this thus:

Source: Brown and Levinson (1978)

First, a speaker can decide not to do the FTA by opting out (1). If he/she decides to do the FTA, he/she can do this in many ways. He/She can decide to be on record (2) or off record (3). If he/she chooses to be on record, he/she chooses to make his/her communicative intentions known to the hearer. He/She can do so baldly (clearly), without redressive action (4) or with redressive action (5). If he/she does not choose redressive action, he/she is not concerned about the face of the hearer. This could be due to an imbalance of power or other reason. If he/she chooses to be on record with redressive action, then it may be either positive (6) or negative politeness (7). The redressive action taken attempts to “counteract or avoid potential face damage.” Examples of the different strategies are given below (cited from Brown and Levinson 1978):

Strategy 1). Speaker chooses not to respond (don't do the FTA). Speaker probably feels that by speaking loss of face would occur to self or others.

Strategy 2, 4). Speaker goes on record, baldly, without redressive action. He might say “Do it now!”. Here the speaker does not feel a risk to face of self or others.

Strategy 3). Speaker does the FTA, but off record. This contrasts with on record. Here the speaker communicates meaning but in a hinting or ambiguous way. For example, knowing that Joe wants to borrow money, Tom says “Damn, I forgot to go to the bank this morning.” Here, Tom is indirectly communicating “Don’t ask for money, because I won’t lend you any.”

Strategy 2,5,6).

Speaker is doing the FTA on record, with redressive action and positive face. The speaker is communicating, but protecting the hearer’s face, i.e. “Since we both want to hear the announcement, let’s stop talking.” **Strategy 2,5,7)** Speaker is doing the FTA on record, with redressive action and negative face. In this strategy, the speaker expresses intentions, but avoids directly damaging or attacking the face of the hearer. Consider this example: “If everyone would stop talking now” (rather than calling down Joe (who was making a noise)). This strategy is also used when evading questions. In line with the above, Bonvillain (1993 cf. Huang 2008) submits that Face-threatening acts (FTAs) vary in terms of the kind of threat involved. Some threaten the hearer’s negative face by imposing on the hearer, for example, requests, orders, offers, and expression of anger.

Other FTAs threaten the hearer’s positive face, the desire to be respected, by indicating the speaker’s lack of concern for the hearer’s self-image, for example, disagreeing, criticism, accusations, insults, contradiction, boasts. And more interestingly, some FTAs could be said to be threatening the speaker himself rather than the hearer because they either offend the speaker’s need not to be imposed upon (thanking, accepting offers, making unwilling promises) or they offend the speaker’s need for positive self-image (apologies, confessions, admissions of responsibility) (ibid).

Malmkjær (2002:427 [Sunday, 2010: 5]) simplifies the figures as follows: 5 represents no imposition at all on the addressee. 4 obscures the function of the FTA, making the speaker appear unintrusive and uncoercive. 3 and 2 are FTAs which cater for the face wants of the addressee: 3 redresses the negative face, realising negative politeness; 2 redresses the positive face, realising positive politeness. 1 is direct, shows no politeness, and has unpleasant

sociological implications (Sunday, 2010: 5-6). The politeness strategies of Brown and Levinson are arranged hierarchically below:

- don't do the FTA
- do the FTA
- do the FTA on record with negative politeness
- do the FTA on record with positive politeness
- do the FTA baldly on record

Malmkjær (2002:427 cf. Sunday, 2010: 5) schematically simplifies these strategies below:

Estimation of Risk of Face Loss

Two things are obvious in the schema- positive and negative politeness. These are discussed below.

2.10.4.1 Positive Politeness

Positive politeness is geared towards the hearer's positive face. This implies the speaker makes sure he treats or addresses the hearer as a member of an in-group, such that the face-threatening acts (FTA) are not seen as a negative evaluation of the hearer's face. Positive politeness involves utterances that are used as a kind of metaphorical extension of intimacy to imply common ground or of sharing of wants to a limited extent, even between strangers who revere themselves for the purpose of conversation. While discussing the concept of positive politeness (face management) as propounded by Brown and Levinson, Thomas (1995) opines as follows:

[Sometimes] when you speak to someone you may orient yourself towards that individual's positive face, and employ positive face, and employ positive politeness (which appeals to H's desire to be liked or approved of) (Thomas: 1995:171) cf. Odebunmi (2009)

Brown and Levinson (1987) classify positive politeness sub-strategies into fifteen as follows:

Strategy 1: Notice. Attend to H (his interests, wants, needs, goods)

Strategy 2: Exaggerate (interest, approval, sympathy to H)

Strategy 3: Use in group identity markers

Strategy 4: Intensify interest to H

Strategy 5: Seek agreement

Strategy 6: Avoid disagreement

Strategy 7: Presuppose/ raise / assert common ground

Strategy 8: Joke

Strategy 9: Assert or presuppose S's knowledge of and concern for H's wants

Strategy 10: Offer promise

Strategy 11: Be optimistic

Strategy 12: Include both S and H in the activity

Strategy 13: Give (or ask for) reasons

Strategy 14: Assume or assert reciprocity

Strategy 15: Give gifts to H (goods, sympathy, understanding, cooperation).

As pointed out earlier, these strategies are used together or separately to redress threat to face.

2.10.4.2. Negative Politeness

Negative politeness is oriented towards the negative face of the hearer. This is usually attained via the use of conventional politeness markers, deference markers, minimising imposition, etc. This can equally be achieved via the employment of non-linguistic actions. It is usually addressed as a redressive action towards the hearer's negative face; that is, his wants to have

freedom of action uninhibited or unhindered and his intention unimpeded. Brown and Levinson (1987) mentions ten strategies for negative politeness as follows:

Strategy 1: Be conventionally indirect

Strategy 2: Question, hedge

Strategy 3: Be pessimistic

Strategy 4: Minimise the imposition

Strategy 5: Give deference

Strategy 6: Apologise

Strategy 7: Impersonalise S and H

Strategy 8: State the FTA as a general rule

Strategy 9: Nominalise

Strategy 10: Go on record as incurring a debt, or as not indebting H

Brown and Levinson developed their model of politeness theory around three ideas, namely

- i. The rationality of a model speaker
- ii. Conversational principles
- iii. The notion of face wants of interlocutors

To Brown and Levinson, the idea of a rational model speaker implies an adult with a complete knowledge of the conversational and communicative conventions of his culture. Such an adult(model) speaker communicates with perfect awareness of cultural needs and requirements. He, therefore, does not make mistakes in this regard. The idea of face is predicated on the belief or assumption that people present themselves in a manner to others and that there are certain means by which such manner may be maintained or threatened. They defined face as “ the public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself” (Brown and Levinson,1978: 66). Obviously, this position of Brown and Levinson on face is in reference to the position of Goffman (1967) on the concept, with some bit of modification.

Expounding the view and position of Brown and Levinson on politeness, Scollon and Scollon (2008) observes there are three main types of politeness in different contexts; which are primarily based on whether there is a power difference (+P,-P), and on the distance between

participants (+D,-D). These are deference politeness, the solidarity politeness and hierarchical politeness systems. These are discussed below:

2.10.5 Deference Politeness System (+D , -D,)

This type of politeness system manifests in interactions between or among people who are of equal status but who for one reason or the other are distant from each other or one another. For instance, in an example given by Scollon and Scollon (2008), if two university professors from two different universities or countries meet, they are likely to refer to each other as Professor X and Professor Y. In such a situation, they would treat each other as equals and employ mainly independence politeness strategies, showing respect for each other as well as their academic statuses. This type of mutual but distant independence is referred to as a deference politeness system. Deference politeness system is characterised by the following:

1. Symmetrical (-P), that is, the participants see themselves as individuals who are on the same social pedestal or status.
2. Distant (+D), that is, each uses independence strategies speaking to the other.

Hence, the face system portrayed here can be sketched as follows:

Fig. 2. Deference Politeness System Structure

These scholars concluded this type of politeness system can be attested to in egalitarian systems but where the participants maintain deferential distance from each other; not forming unnecessarily close ties.

2.10.6 Solidarity Politeness System (-P, -D)

This type of politeness system operates between close friends, demonstrating a solidarity face system. Here, there is a high level of involvement politeness strategies (positive politeness). There is no feeling of a power difference (-P) or distance (-D) between them. This type of politeness system is characterised by the following:

1. Symmetrical (-P), that is, the participants see themselves as being in equal social position.

2. Close (-D), that is, the participants both use politeness strategies of involvement. This is relationship is schematised thus:

Fig.3: Solidarity Politeness System Structure

Scollon and Scollon (2008) opine this type of politeness system could be found anywhere the system is egalitarian and participants feel or express closeness to each other : “Friendships among close colleagues are often solidarity systems” (Scollon and Scollon, 2008: 55).

2.10.7 Hierarchical Politeness System

This type of politeness system is hierarchical. Here, the participants acknowledge, recognise and respect the social differences between them, which place one in a superordinate position and the other in a subordinate position. The superior participant speaks “down” while the subordinate participant speaks “up”. As pointed out by Scollon and Scollon (2008), the main characteristic of this system is the recognised difference in status, for which the designation [+P] is used, irrespective of whether or not there is distance between the participants. The relationships in this type of face system are asymmetrical; such that the participants do not use the same face politeness strategies in speaking to each other. The characteristics of this hierarchical face system are:

1. Asymmetrical (+P), that is, the participants see themselves as being in unequal social position
2. Asymmetrical in face strategies, that is, the “higher” uses involvement face strategies and the lower uses independence face strategies. This is schematised below:

Fig.4 Hierarchical Politeness System Structure

As observed by Scollon and Scollon (2008), this sort of hierarchical face system is quite common in business, governmental, and educational organizations. In fact, it could be said to be the most common sort of organizational relationship, as indicated in tables of organization. A sociolinguistic examination of many different communicative systems depicts that the factors of power (or hierarchy) and distance may arise and manifest differently. In some societies, power differences (+P) are a function of differences in age, gender, wealth, hunting prowess, ability to entertain, education, physical strength or beauty, membership in particular families, or colour of hair or skin. This type of politeness system is found in the interaction between IPOs and suspects, where the IPOs, by virtue of their institutional power, assume a +P position and suspects, especially the low-profile ones, a -P position (see Chapter Five for details).

According to Huang (2008), there are some considerable items or concepts related to politeness. These are highlighted below:

2.11.1. The social background of the communicator

Huang is of the opinion that the social background of a communicator has a great influence on his view about politeness. Generally, the more educated a man is, the more he tends to show his politeness to other people. The more he is exposed to suitable ways to show politeness, the better he becomes, using them to show politeness to others. Also, the personality of the communicator is very important. A good-tempered person prefers to use “face-saving acts” while a bad-tempered person prefers “face-threatening acts” when they come across the “face-losing condition” (Huang, 2008).

2.11.2. The communicative circumstances

Scholars have agreed that communication is a very complicated process. As such, people tend to use formal expressions to show politeness in formal situations, especially people who are just meeting themselves for the first time; whereas in informal situations, people tend to be casual to show intimacy even if it is in the very moment they meet, and that does not mean impoliteness. Let us consider the following example, as given by Huang (2008): A man came into a bar and said to the waiter: “Hi! Buddy! Gimme some Whisky, would ya?” Although they have never met before, the man used very casual phrases to enclose their relationship. This is a usual way to

show friendliness to strangers in similar entertaining places (Huang 2008: 98). Beside the factors listed above, Huang (2008) equally lists some other factors that cause different views of value which affect the concept of politeness. Prominent among them is cultural differences. Differences in culture bring about varying views of values, which affect the criteria of politeness and lead to differences in various aspects. Cultural differences manifest in some ways as follows:

2.11.3. Ways to greet each other farewell

The westerners often greet others with a cheerful “Hello!” or something like “How are you?”. If they are talking with a stranger, they tend to talk about the weather as a way of greeting. The same thing applies in the Yoruba language, but with slight differences. For instance, the Yoruba have different ways of greeting one another in relation to the situation or condition at hand. Also, when two people who are averagely of the same age are meeting for the first time, they often show politeness with the use of the honorific pronoun “ẹ” in addressing each other, but after much familiarity; they can switch over to the use of “o” to relate to each other, without necessarily sounding impolite. Also, in the Yoruba greetings, certain questions like “How are your children”, “Where are you going” Have you eaten?”, “What brings you here? “What are you doing here?”, etc are commonplace. All these would be considered as interferences to privacy for westerners.

As pointed out by Huang, in the Chinese culture, when parting, people rarely seldom say “goodbye” as farewells, as that would be too formal or somewhat distant. Before they leave, Chinese guests like to say “I have to go now.”, “I am going” or “Stay where you are”, and the hosts are used to saying “Go slowly”, “Come again.” to see them off. While two friends are departing after they meet on the road, one of them may say “ I’ve got to leave.”, and the other may say “ Let” s chat next time”, “ Come to see me when you are free.” Or “I would visit you if I can.” As for westerners, they often say “Goodbye!”,”See you!” when they part (Deng Yanchang and Liu Runqing 1989:170).

2.11.4. Addressing terms

In relation to addressing terms, Huang (2008) claims Chinese often use one’s occupation to address him to show respect, either in formal or informal occasions when their social status is

considered to be high or respectful. E.g. Professor Li ,Teacher Zhang , Dean Sun, etc. If their social statuses are considered to be low, such as barber, cleaner, technical worker, cook, plumber and most people in service profession, people will often call them “shifu” instead of their occupations, to show politeness . To westerners, this is not the same. In formal situations, they often address people who hold high social status with their professions as: Professor Green, Chairman Johnson, etc, but they never address people with “teacher or manager”. In informal occasions, even a professor or a chairman prefers himself to be called with his given name to show intimacy to others. And they tend to call others like this while a Chinese may feel unpleasant to be called in such a term by an unfamiliar person. For example, if a girl named “Yang Liyuan” is called as “ Liyuan” or “ Yuan” by an ordinary friend, she will look at it as an insult (Deng, Yanchang & Liu, Runqing, 1989: 171 cf. Huang, 2008). In the Yoruba context however, the major factor that influences the addressing system is “age” and in some few instances the position of individuals.

2.11.5. Ways to praise others

We equally differ in the way we praise people in order to show politeness. For instance, as observed by Huang (2008), westerners like to praise the hostess or the host on their first visit; they consider that to be polite and natural, but this particular act could offend a Chinese host. As a matter of fact, she could become suspicious that the visitor, if it is a man, is interested in her. Usually, the westerners prefer to be praised over their house, garden, car, wife, decorations and room arrangements etc., especially something made with their own hands, but often not their children’s beauty or intelligence which is considered as leading the kids to being vain.

2.11.6. Ways to express thanks

Just as there are different peoples and cultures, so are different ways of expressing thanks across cultures. For instance, the ways thanks are expressed in China are different from the way they are expressed in western countries. Westerners prefer to express their thanks directly while Chinese like to minimize themselves to achieve the same goal. When you praise a westerner on his dress: “How beautiful your dress is! The most likely response would be: “Thanks a lot!”. However, a Chinese person would respond: “Really? It’s just an ordinary dress.” When they appreciate your help, westerners: “ You” re really a great help to me.”“I can’t imagine how I can manage it

without you!” “Thank you for enduring so much trouble I brought to you!” “I really appreciate your help!” ...Chinese: “Sorry to have wasted your time.” “Sorry for having taken up your precious time.” “I’m not at ease for bringing you so much trouble.” Westerner’s appreciations: “thank you. You have helped me a lot today. You must have been very tired.” (Huang 2008).

2.11.7. Considerations of taboos

The concept of taboo has been variously defined by scholars. Hornsby (19974:878) defines taboo as “something which religion or custom regards as forbidden, not to be touched or spoken of”. In the opinion of Wardhaugh (1986:230 cf. Okunola, 2005: 5):

Taboo is the way in which a society expresses its approval of certain kinds of behaviour believed to be harmful to its members, either for supernatural reasons or because such behaviour violates a moral code. Consequently, so far as a language is concerned, certain objects can be referred to only in certain circumstances, for example, only by certain people or through deliberate circumlocutions, i.e. euphemistically.

In the opinion of Oyetade (1994), certain utterances are considered forbidden in language use and are therefore avoided in embrace of their pleasant alternatives. Such utterances or expressions are called taboo expressions.

From these definitions, it becomes obvious that the concept of taboo is such that cuts across cultures; they are expressions that are closely bounded to cultures. However, what constitutes a taboo in a culture might not constitute a taboo in another culture. Let us consider the concept of age for instance. In Western countries, woman’s age is taboo in daily conversations; never will you hear a woman ask you questions like “How old are you?” during conversations. And in Western countries, the aged people will not usually like the young people to call or refer to them as “old man”, they prefer “senior man” or “senior citizen”. Also, they do not like others’ help at all, as this will mean they are old and as such need others’ help and sympathy. Similarly, there are many taboos that are linked with Westerners, such as the questions about religions, salary,

children, marriages, sex, etc. These scholars finally submitted that when we are communicating with people from different cultures, it is best to familiarise ourselves with what is appropriate in their culture and act with regard to that, so as to avoid misunderstandings caused by cultural differences.

2.12. Criticisms of Politeness Theory of Brown and Levinson

Brown and Levinson's work on politeness theory has been heavily critiqued and criticised by scholars (e.g. Watts (2003), Arundale (2009)) who apparently maintain a different view on the concept of politeness. For instance, the fact that Brown and Levinson based their theoretical assumptions on data gathered from just three languages, English, Tzeltal and Tamil, has made their work attract serious criticism, especially in respect of their claim on the universality of the concept of politeness. To these scholars, it would be inappropriate to conclude that what obtains in three languages automatically obtains in every language. Central to the argument of these post-Brown and Levinson scholars is the issue of universality versus cultural relativity of the notion of politeness, which, according to Brown and Levinson, centres on the concept of face.

The concept of face is a metaphorical term which cuts across the different cultures of the world. It refers to individual qualities or abstract entities such as honour, respect, esteem and the self. Some of the notable works on the concept of face are Hu (1944), Goffman (1967), Watts (2003) and Odeunmi (2009), to mention but a few. As observed by Lim (1994) and Ho (1994), some Chinese scholars, in their conception of the notion of face, have interpreted the Chinese notion of face as an essentially public and positive concept, consisting of three positive face-types, and as a situational interpersonal construct, as embedded in situational interpersonal relations. These Chinese scholars claimed Brown and Levinson's argument on face views the concept as an individualistic concept. To them, the concept of face should focus more on ingroup interests rather than individual wants. In the same vein, these Chinese scholars questioned the validity of Brown and Levinson's notion of negative face in cultures where the individual's freedom of thought and action are determined by the social status that the individual has in the group.

Similarly, many scholars from other Asian and African cultures have criticised the individualistic conception of the concept of face and the validity of the notion of negative face in Brown and

Levinson's theory (e.g. Matsumoto 1988, Nwoye 1992 and Ide 1993). Also, Brown and Levinson's view on politeness strategies have been criticised for its "pessimistic view on social interaction". For instance, in the opinion of Nwoye (1992:311), "social interaction becomes an activity of continuous mutual monitoring of potential threats to the faces of the interactants, and if this view were always true, it could rob social interaction of all elements of pleasure". In line with Nwoye's view, Werkhofner (1992: 156) opines that the account of Brown and Levinson on politeness is individualistic; it presents the speaker as a rational agent who at least during the generation of utterances is unconstrained by social considerations and is therefore free to select egocentric, asocial and aggressive intentions.

Watts (2003) is another scholar who has done a comprehensive criticism of the politeness theory proposed by Brown and Levinson. In his book titled *Politeness*, Watts vehemently argued for a more pragmatic way of considering the concept of linguistic politeness. With this, he aimed to show the distinction between the commonsense or lay notion of (im)politeness and the theoretical notion of (im)politeness. The commonsense notion is referred to as first-order politeness while the theoretical notion is referred to as second-order politeness. According to Watts, the first-order politeness is a socio-psychological notion that is used for the various ways in which members of socio-cultural groups talk about polite language usage. Contrariwise, the second-order notion is a theoretical, linguistic notion in a sociolinguistic theory of politeness. Predicating his argument on the first-order notion of politeness theory, Watts argued that whether or not a person's (linguistic) behaviour is evaluated as polite or impolite is not merely a matter of the linguistic expressions that the individual uses, but it depends, rather, on the interpretation of that behaviour in the overall social interaction. In other words, what is considered (im)polite in a situation may not necessarily be (im)polite in another context.

The conversation between a husband and a wife below explains the aforesaid:

Husband : Honey, I am hungry; kindly bring my food

Wife (smiling): *Don't even tell me that rubbish.* You know I am very tired, having just come back from work

Husband: *You are not serious* (both husband and wife burst into laughter)

In the excerpt above, the husband and the wife could not be said to be impolite in the way they addressed each other, given the context or mood in which the conversation took place. “Therefore, it should be obvious that all utterances have to be appropriate to the political verbal behaviour of the ongoing discourse activity and also the knowledge of the social situation that the speaker has and can assume her/his addressee to have” (Watts 2003: 95); a fact which Brown and Levinson have not apparently accounted for. As further pointed out by Watts (2003), Brown and Levinson suggested the following equation to compute the seriousness (weightiness) of the FTA since that will determine the appropriate type of strategy to be employed:

$$W_x = D(S, H) + P(H, S) + R_x$$

Where x is the FTA

The seriousness of the intended FTA is a composite of the social distance (D) between the (S)peaker and the (H)earer, the (P)ower (even though they have not really defined what the concept of power means) that H wields over S and R, the degree to which x constitutes an imposition. The greater the value of (W)eightiness, the closer should be the utterance to strategy 5 (in their schema); and the smaller the value of W, the closer it should be to the strategy type 1. The equation above is vehemently criticised by Watts as it ‘fails’ to indicate the quantitative parameters with which W can be computed. Brown and Levinson’s intention for suggesting the formula was to indicate the reasons for choosing one strategy rather than another, and not to suggest that politeness strategies could be measured in relation to a computed value for the variables P, D and R_x . Watts finally concluded that what Brown and Levinson proposed is a theory of facework rather than a theory of politeness.

Therefore, Watts (2003) and Locher and Watts (2005) propose the Theory of Relational Work. In fact, Locher and Watts (2005) view politeness as a small part of relational work, which needs being considered alongside other realisations of interpersonal meaning. The excerpt below captures their argument:

Relational work refers to “Work” individuals invest in negotiating relationships with others. Human beings rely on others to be able to realize their goals and aspirations and as social beings they will

naturally orient themselves towards others in pursuing these goals. Indulging in social practice, they need not be aware of, and indeed are frequently oblivious of, their reliance on others.

(cf. Odebunmi, 2009: 6-7)

It then means that the interactants or interlocutors are accustomed to a particular mode of relation, and that what transpires between interlocutors in form of conversations is expected in view of the context of interaction. The theory of relational work is argued to be context-based, and not on the notion or assumption that politeness is inherent in the expression. The theory is seen as being broad, hence its capability to handle concepts as directness, impoliteness, rudeness/aggressiveness and polite interaction, as well as verbal behaviours that are either appropriate or inappropriate. The basic concept of relational work with reference to politeness is captured below as presented in Odebunmi (2009):

Fig.5 : Relational Work and Politeness Theory

From figure 7, it is obvious that the theory of relational work subsumes politeness theory, as it covers all forms of human interactions as well as their accompanying gestures. The overall argument of the proponents of the Relational Theorists is that what is considered to be polite in the existing literature can simply be referred to what is contextually appropriate (see Locher and

Watts 2005). Odebunmi (2009), however, argues that the cross-cultural consistency of the position of the Relational theory may be difficult to justify. For instance, he argued that it is not appropriate in any context for a child or a wife to use an expression as “That’s crazy” referring to the father among the Yoruba people of Nigeria. But in some other form of discourse like political discourse, this might not be seen as being rude or impolite. He therefore concluded that, the theory needed “to work into its frame cross-cultural and discourse peculiarities and demonstrate how to apply them”. Consequently, for the purpose of his work, he modified the model of relational work as shown below:

Fig.6 Odebunmi’s Modified Schema for the Relational Work Theory

Source: Odebunmi (2009: 10)

Arundale’s (2010) work is another work that questions the argument of Brown and Levinson on Politeness theory. The work is a radical shift from politeness works of scholars like Goffman (1967) and Brown and Levinson (1978 and 1987). Arundale developed a theory called Face-Constituting Theory which he claimed addresses the question “How do participants achieve face in everyday talk?” And outlining this theory involves first sketching the Coinjoint Co-constituting Model of communication as a conceptualisation of achieving of meaning and action

in interaction. Also, the theory conceptualises the concept of face as a relational phenomenon at both culture-general and culture-specific levels. Following these conceptualisations, face-constituting theory sees face as the interpretation participants are able to make out of the relational connectedness and separateness, conjointly co-constituted in talk or conduct-in-interaction.

Another important concept in the argument of Arundale (2010) is the concept of *stasis*, which he claimed caters for a situation where the face of participants in a conversation is neither saved nor threatened. However, one must be quick to point out that Arundale's Face-Constituting theory is a complex theory for which he lacks adequate explanation in his work; and he has even failed to provide adequate data to explain or simplify the theory. It is a theory that leaves out a researcher in what transpires between interlocutors in speech situations, as he argued that the theory is framed from the participant's perspective (and perhaps not from the researcher's perspective).

In spite of all these, Brown and Levinson's (1987) Politeness theory (face-saving view) is adopted in this work because our emphasis is on face in police-suspect interaction.

2.13 Related Works on Politeness in African Languages

Several works have been done on the concept of politeness in African languages by several scholars. Some of these are Obilade (1984), Adegbija (1989), Adejumo (2010), Odebunmi (2010), Ambuyo et al (2011).

Obilade (1994) examines the concept of politeness from the perspective of how the knowledge of the Yoruba language influences the Yoruba speakers' use of the politeness phenomenon in English. In his work, Obilade presented some structures of the English language (apparently the subjects' L2) to ten native speakers of the Yoruba language, and requested these structures be rated by them in terms of politeness. At the end of this 'experiment', Obilade concluded the subjects' mother tongue (Yoruba) has little or no influence on the use of politeness in English (their L2).

One of the major issues with Obilade's position lies in the fact that he drew his conclusion, expressed in strong terms, from data got from just ten subjects, whose level of competence in the said languages could not be ascertained. Also, saying the knowledge of the Yoruba language does not have influence on the use of politeness in English might not be all that acceptable, as observation has shown little Yoruba-English bilingual children often use the pronoun '*they*' which is equivalent to '*àwọn*' in Yoruba to refer to elderly people as a way of showing politeness.

Adegbija (1989) is a comparative analysis of the operation of the phenomenon of politeness in Yoruba, Ogori and the Nigerian English. In this work, Adegbija pointed out four strategies of positive politeness and three strategies of negative politeness in the languages. He pointed out that the use of greetings and honorific pronouns is a means by which participants redress threats to positive face in these languages. He equally identified negative politeness strategies often used in the languages. These include tone and voice modulation, avoidance of interruption, the use of professional, religious, cultural, and social titles. His work reveals that the interpretation of utterances as being polite or impolite is a function of specific pragmatic context or situation. Adegbija, in this work, demonstrated the place of factors as age, cultural and social status in determining the level of politeness in speech situations. He also went further to comment on the discrepancy between the universal concept of politeness and the culture-specific markers. Adegbija opined, for effective communication to take place in language, participants have to be aware and conscious of the peculiarities permissible within individual cultures. He succeeded in establishing the fact that speakers of Nigerian English share some politeness strategies found in the Yoruba and Ogori languages. In spite of all these, it must be pointed out that Adegbija's work failed to address the issue of non-verbal politeness strategies in the three languages- Yoruba, Ogori and the Nigerian English, the languages he employed for his analysis.

Adejumo (2010) opines that politeness is an aspect of the culture of the Yoruba people and language. As a matter of fact, the Yoruba language is synonymous with politeness in the opinion of many non-native speakers of the language. This is in line with the view of Adejumo who argued that an average Yoruba has the attribute of politeness. Adejumo furnished her work with data on the greetings and address tags used by an ideal speaker of the language. Her work, no

doubt, provides a socio-cultural perspective to what has been viewed solely from a linguistic point of view.

Odebunmi (2013) looks at politeness and face management in the conversational interaction between doctors and patients in Southwestern Nigeria. In this work, Odebunmi made use of data gathered from patients and doctors in selected teaching, state and private hospitals in the southwestern part of Nigeria. He observed that the conversational interactions between doctors and patients are replete with tact maxim, the generosity maxim, the sympathy maxim, the pollyanna principle and face threatening acts without redress and face threatening acts with redress. Odebunmi's work is an in-depth study of what obtains in the hospital setting as far as the use of language by medical practitioners and patients is concerned. However, the work failed to tell us which of the maxims observed in the hospital setting is preponderant in the observed domain. Also, he did not tell us why doctors have to use face threatening acts (bald on record) sometimes since that is to be avoided as much as possible in accordance with the ethics of the medical profession.

Adebite and Odebunmi (2010) examine face-threatening acts in conversational interactions between medical practitioners and patients in orthodox and traditional medical practice among the Yoruba in Southwestern Nigeria. The work employs data gathered during interactions among doctors and patients in different hospitals; and traditional medical practitioners (herbalists and divination priests) and patients in their places of consultation. The work concludes that such interactions feature the use of FTA with redress (positive politeness) and FTA without redress (bald-on-record). However, the former features more prominently than the latter. There are also the use of 'off record strategies in such interactions. It must be pointed out that the work is a commendable effort on the part of these scholars. They have been able to demonstrate to us how face is managed in interactions among medical practitioners (orthodox and unorthodox) and patients during consultations.

Ambuyoa et al. (2011) examine politeness in the context of politics during question time discussions of the Kenyan Parliament. As demonstrated by these scholars in this work, politeness is an attempt by the speaker to linguistically show he cares about the others' feelings in the

Kenyan Parliament. Question time is a highly aggressive session full of FTAs but the parliamentarians are constrained to produce parliamentary language required by the standing orders of 2008 (as enshrined in the codes of conduct of the Parliament), therefore, politeness strategies become the only linguistic device to the realization of fruitful political discussions. The live televised question time sessions within a period of two weeks in the months of April and May 2009 were recorded, transcribed and sampled for analysis in this work. This was done using a theoretical framework encompassing positive, negative, and image repair politeness strategies. The findings show that certain strategies are used to mitigate FTAs, thus enhancing effective communication; others are a ritual requirement by the standing orders, whereas others are as a result of mere politics between the different political factions.

According to these scholars, the whole genres of Question Time in Kenyan Parliament is full of FTAs such as criticisms, requests, accusations, blames, complains, reproaches, rebukes, objections, embarrassments amongst others, just as a way of manifestation of the power relations evident among the members of the parliament. Thus, politeness strategies are employed to ensure and enhance continuous flow and fruitful communication in the Kenyan Parliament.

2.14. The Impoliteness Theory

Culpeper's impoliteness theory is adopted to analyse elements of impoliteness in our data. Culpeper (1996, 2008) opines that impoliteness can be divided into two different categories. These are inherent impoliteness and mock politeness or banter. Culpeper (1996: 2) states that there are acts that innately threaten one's face regardless of the context of the act; this is called inherent impoliteness. Contrariwise, impoliteness that stays on the surface and is not intended to insult anyone is called mock impoliteness (Culpeper 1996: 4). He outlines five impoliteness super-strategies which are apparently opposites of Brown and Levinson's politeness super-strategies. Culpeper (1996: 8) says: "Instead of enhancing or supporting face, impoliteness super-strategies are a means of attacking face." Culpeper describes the five super-strategies as follows:

- *Bald on record impoliteness* - the FTA is performed in a direct, clear, unambiguous and concise way in circumstances where face is relevant. This strategy is different from Brown and Levinson's Bald on record in that, for Brown and Levinson, Bald on record is a *politeness* strategy in fairly specific circumstances. For example, when face concerns

are suspended in an emergency, when the threat to the hearer's face is very small (e.g. "Come in" or "Do sit down"), or when the speaker is much more powerful than the hearer (e.g. "Stop complaining" said by a parent to a child). In all these cases little face is at stake, and, more importantly, it is not the intention of the speaker to attack the face of the hearer.

- *Positive impoliteness* - the use of strategies designed to damage the addressee's positive face wants.
- *Negative impoliteness* - the use of strategies designed to damage the addressee's negative face wants.
- *Sarcasm or mock politeness* - the FTA is performed with the use of politeness strategies that are obviously insincere, and thus remain surface realisations.
- *Withhold politeness* - the absence of politeness work where it would be expected. For example, failing to thank somebody for a present may be taken as deliberate impoliteness (Culpeper 1996: 8-9).

Culpeper (1996) goes ahead to spell out strategies for negative and positive impoliteness. These strategies are as follows :

2.14.1 Positive impoliteness output strategies:

- *Ignore, snub the other* - fail to acknowledge the other's presence.
- *Exclude the other from an activity*
- *Disassociate from the other* - for example, deny association or common ground with the other; avoid sitting together.
- *Be disinterested, unconcerned, unsympathetic*
- *Use inappropriate identity markers* - for example, use title and surname when a close relationship pertains, or a nickname when a distant relationship pertains.
- *Use obscure or secretive language* - for example, mystify the other with jargon, or use a code known to others in the group, but not the target.
- *Seek disagreement* - select a sensitive topic. Make the other feel uncomfortable - for example, do not avoid silence, joke, or use small talk.
- *Use taboo words* - swear, or use abusive or profane language.

- *Call the other names* - use derogatory nominations.

2.14.2 Negative impoliteness output strategies:

- *Frighten* - instill a belief that action detrimental to the other will occur.
- *Condescend, scorn or ridicule* - emphasize your relative power. Be contemptuous. Do not treat the other seriously. Belittle the other (e.g. use diminutives).
- *Invade the other's space* - literally (e.g. position yourself closer to the other than the relationship permits) or metaphorically (e.g. ask for or speak about information which is too intimate given the relationship).
- *Explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect* - personalize, use the pronouns 'I' and 'you'.
- *Put the other's indebtedness on record.*

Mills (2003: 121) points out that a lot of research has been carried out on politeness but not many could be said to have been done on impoliteness. In her opinion, the aforesaid might be as a result of the fact that in most studies, conversation is viewed as a phenomenon that follows the contracts of communication and is harmonious and balanced between the speakers. However, there are occasions that speakers attack rather than save each other's faces in conversations, hence the concept of impoliteness. In the opinion of Locher and Bousfield (2008: 3), "Impoliteness is behaviour that is face-aggravating in a particular context . This definition does not differentiate between impoliteness and rudeness. In reaction to this definition therefore , Culpeper (2008) makes a distinction between impoliteness and rudeness. According to Culpeper, both impoliteness and rudeness are "inappropriate and negatively marked" behaviour. However, the difference between them is that, while impoliteness is intentional, rudeness is unintentional negative behaviour. Impoliteness, is therefore, something that is caused intentionally. This position of Culpeper is a sharp contrast to the one maintained by Terkourafi (2008: 61-62) who argues that while impoliteness is unintentional, rudeness is intentional. Terkourafi's argument is hearer-centred rather than speaker-centred.

However, we opt for the view of Culpepper in this work as our observation during data collection shows that police officers intentionally attack the face of suspects with linguistic and paralinguistic devices during police-suspect interactions, what we term impolite, considering what the IPOs aim to achieve with these linguistic and paralinguistic devices. Culpepper (2011) sees impoliteness as a multi-disciplinary field of study that has a link with scientific fields such as psychology, sociology, conflict studies, media . It is thus, a complex and multi-dimensional subject to study (Kuntsi 2012).

2.15 Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)

The norms and values which underlie texts are often “out of sight” rather than overtly stated (Paltridge, 2006), and as Hyland (2005:4) opines, “acts of meaning making are always engaged in that they realise the interests, the positions, the perspectives and the values of those who enact them”. Critical discourse analysis approach to language analysis is thus a means to help reveal some of these hidden and often elusive (out of sight) values, positions and perspectives. According to Rogers (2004:6), discourses are always socially, politically, racially and economically loaded. Critical discourse analysts X-ray the use of discourse in relation to social and cultural issues such as gender, politics, race, status, and seeks to fathom why the discourse is used in a particular way and what the implications are of this kind of use. Traditionally, critical discourse analysis assumes that ‘language use is always social and that discourse both reflects and constructs social world’(Rogers 2004:5). A critical analysis might explore issues like gender, ideology and identity; and how these are reflected in a particular text. This, sometimes, might begin with an analysis of the use of discourse and move to an exploration, explanation and interpretation of the discourse. The analysis might then criticise and eventually deconstruct or challenge the texts, tracing ideologies and assumptions underlying the use of discourse and relating these to different views of the world, experiences and beliefs (Clark, 1995).

van Dijk (1998) asserts that Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a field that is interested in studying and analyzing written and spoken texts to show or depict the discursive sources of power, dominance, inequality and bias. This field of study equally examines how the said discursive sources are maintained and reproduced within specific social, political and historical contexts. Similarly, Fairclough (1992) defines CDA as discourse analysis which is primarily concerned about how to systematically explore often covert relationships of causality and

determination between discursive practices, events and texts, on the one hand and wider social and cultural structures, relations and processes on the other, with a bid to examining how such practices, events and texts arise out of and are ideologically shaped by relations of power and struggles over power. From the above, it then suffices to submit that it is the goal of CDA to make transparent the connections or relationships between discourse practices, social practices, and social structures.

In the same vein, Wodak (2001: 2-3) posits that 'CDA is fundamentally concerned with the analysis of opaque as well as overt structural relationships of dominance, discrimination, power and control that manifest in language use'. It is a field of study that explores and exposes the cultural and ideological meanings hidden in discourse (Fairclough 1989, 1995, Wodak, 2001). What cuts across the various positions of these scholars is the fact that there is a strong link between language and exercise of power and ideology. Critical Discourse Analysis operates with certain principles. These are highlighted below:

2.15.1 Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis

Fairclough and Wodak (1997) is a comprehensive work on the principles with which critical discourse analysis operates; which make it clearly different from other levels of linguistic analysis. These principles include:

- Social and political issues are constructed and reflected in discourse;
- Power relations are negotiated and are performed through discourse;
- Discourse both reflects and reproduces social relations;
- Ideologies are produced and reflected in the use of discourse.

2.15.1.1 Social and Political Issues are Constructed and Reflected in Discourse

This principle, in the view of Fairclough and Wodak (1997 cf. Paltridge 2006: 180), addresses social and political issues and examines ways in which these are constructed and reflected in the use of discourse. Reference to Teo's (2005) study of slogans for Singapore's Speak Mandarin Campaign becomes apt here. In the campaign, it is apparently clear the Singaporeans of Chinese descent should speak Chinese, despite the fact that, at the time of the launch of the campaign, only a small percentage of them actually spoke Mandarin as their first language. The aim of the

campaign was however to connect Chinese Singaporeans with Chinese cultural traditions as well as help counter ‘negative effects of westernisation’ (Teo 2005:123). The fire of the campaign was also remotely ignited by an economic policy which aimed at attracting foreign investment, especially from China. “Mandarin: window to Chinese culture, Speak Mandarin, it’s an asset and speak Mandarin: your children’s future depends on your effort” are slogans that capture the views of the proponents of this idea. The language Mandarin was, via these captivating slogans, presented as cool and of contemporary relevance, and also as a stepping stone to greater business opportunities. This was evident in the speech of the Chairman of the Promote Mandarin Council, who described Mandarin as cool in more ways than one.

2.15.1.2 Power Relations are Negotiated and Performed through Discourse

One way this can be looked at is via an analysis of who controls conversational interactions, who allows a person to speak, and how they do this. Hutchby (1996) observes this in his study of arguments in British radio talk shows. As opined by Hutchby and Wooffit (1998), the first speaker in an argument is oftentimes in a disadvantaged and weaker position than the second speaker. This is predicated on the argument that the first person has to set their opinion on the line while the second speaker merely has to challenge their opponent to expand on, or substantiate their claims. For instance, in a radio call-in programme, it is usually the host that comes in the second position and has the power to challenge or query the caller’s claim, or to ask them to substantiate and justify their points. This principle aptly describes the rationale behind this work. Usually, in the course of police-suspect interaction in Nigeria, power relations are negotiated and performed. Oftentimes, the police use their institutional power to “intimidate”, manipulate and subjugate the mind of the suspects, with the bid to securing confessions from them.

The policeman gives room for an accused or a suspect to hold the floor of a conversation first, trying to prove his or innocence, and, thereafter, he or she uses part or the whole of the statement of the suspect to weave the web or the crime round him/her the more. This is usually achieved via leading questions, accusative expressions and bald-on-record without redress politeness strategy. The following example (a conversation between a doctor and his medical student) from Fairclough (1989 :37-38) is apt here.

(1) Doctor: and let's gather round. the first of the infants – now what I want you to do is to make a basic . neo-natal examination just as Dr Mathews has to do as soon as a baby arrives in the ward . all right so you are actually going to get your hands on the infant. and look at the key points and demonstrate them to the group as you're doing it will you do that for me please . off you go

(2) Student: well first of all I'm going to ()

(3) Doctor: first . before you do

that is do you wash your hands isn't it I . cos you've been examining another baby
(long silence) are you still in a... are you in a position to start examining yet ()

(4) Student: just going to remove this .

(5) Doctor : very good. it's putting it back that's the problem isn't it eh –

(6) Student: come back Mum –

(7) Doctor: that's right. OK now just get a little more room by shifting baby . er up the . thing a bit more that's very good . well now . off you go and describe what's going on

(8) Student : well here's a young baby boy . who we've decided is . thirty . thirty seven weeks old now . was born . two weeks ago . um is fairly active . his er eyes are open . he's got hair on . his head

(9) Doctor: . his eyes are open
yes yes you've
told me that

(10) Student: um he's crying or making

(11) Doctor: yeah we we we've heard

that now what other examinations are going to make I mean –

(12) Student: erm we'll see if he'll respond to

(13) Doctor : now look . did we not
look at a baby with a head problem yesterday?

(14) Student : right

(15) Doctor : and might you not make one examination of the head almost at square one . before you begin .

(16) Student: feel for the ()

(17) Doctor: now what { the next most important thing .

(18) Student: { er gross mogross

(19) Doctor: { motor function well now you come down to the mouth don't we.

(20) Student: { yes

(21) Doctor: now what about the mouth

Source: *'The Boy from Horseferry Road'* Granada Television 1990 cf. Fairclough (1989:37)

Fairclough explained the excerpt above thus. The doctor in the discourse exercised control over the student in so many ways. Firstly, the doctor determined the nature of the discourse in that he went on to announce what was going on in the interaction to the student, including his contributions. Also, the student was continually and expressly told when to start talking, at the end of turns (1) and (7) by signalling (off you go) to the student. The doctor gave explicit instructions to the student as to how he should arrange (sequence) his actions in (3). The doctor went on to evaluate the contributions of the student in (5) (very good) and (7) (that's right). Although they were positive comments, they are techniques of control which would be regarded as presumptuous or arrogant if they are addressed to an equal or someone more powerful (Fairclough, 1989: 38).

The student is put on the spot in the series of questions of turns (13), (15), (17) and (19). These questions constitute a strategically ordered sequence which leads the student through the routine he has failed to master. Also, the student is obliged to answer as there are pauses following the questions from the doctor, which are indications that his answer is needed at that point in time. Also, the doctor used negative questions (as depicted by his intonation) like "did we not, might we not" to abjure the student's approach to the task before him. Asking the student such questions as these is to make him look silly and less powerful before the *all-knowing* doctor. The power relationship is more badly expressed in (17) where the reduced forms of the question

sound curt and abrupt. Finally, the doctor uses a declarative sentence instead of an interrogative sentence with a question tag “don’t we”. Tantamountly, this is like a negative question.

2.15.1.3 Discourse Both Reflects and Reproduces Social Relations

Another principle of critical discourse analysis reinforces the fact that discourse does not only depict social relations but it is also part of, and reproduces social relations. Page’s (2003) study of representations in the media of Cherie Blair, Tony Blair’s wife, explains this principle. Page demonstrates how Cherie Blair is presented in the media as a lawyer, a wife, and a working mother aimed to establish a certain relationship between her and the public and other working mothers. While she is preponderantly depicted by the media as a role model for managing her role as a working mother, working mothers are more typically presented in negative terms in every day discourse, in a way that produces quite different readings of the term, and in turn, different views of women who combine child rearing with work (Page 2003 cf. Paltridge 2006:182). This view is further elucidated by Stokoe (2003). In a study of neighbourhood disputes, Stokoe showed how terms such as mother and single woman can be used to make moral assessments about women as well as perpetuate “taken-for-granted” facts about women’s appropriate behaviour and social relations with other people. In line with Page (2003), the use of language in this way both reflects and reproduces certain social views and relations. It further demonstrates social and gendered stereotypes and inequalities.

2.15.1.4 Ideologies are Produced and Reflected in the Use of Discourse

Another key principle of critical discourse analysis, according to Paltridge (2006:182), is that ideologies are produced and reflected in the use of discourse. This includes ways of presenting and constructing society in terms of relations of power, relations based on gender, class and ethnicity. Mallison and Brewster (2005), in their study of how stereotypes are formed in every day (spoken) discourse, point out that negative attitudes towards non standard social dialects of English are oftentimes transferred to negative views of the people who speak these dialects. For example, a job applicant who speaks a non standard dialect may not be employed when an employer uses this discourse as a way of predicting the applicant’s future occupational performance; the view that good workers speak standard English and bad workers do not. Mallison and Brewster equally observed in their study of U.S restaurant workers’ views of their

black customers that they had negative opinions about them. This reflected in their negative terms and stereotypes to form their expectations about future interactions with black customers, and the broader social group of African Americans. This was further made clear in the “discourse of difference” (Wodak 1997) that they used as they spoke about their black customers and distanced themselves from them. The workers’ views of rural Southerner customers were similarly stereotyped, even though they talked about this group in somewhat different ways, referring to where they lived, the ways they dressed and their food and drink preferences as a way of justifying their claims about them.

From the foregoing, it then becomes obvious that critical discourse analysis aims at making connections between social and cultural practices and the values and assumptions that underlie the discourse. Critical discourse analysis takes the view that the relationship between language and meaning is never arbitrary in that the choice of a particular genre or rhetorical strategy brings without particular presuppositions, meanings, ideologies and intentions (Kress 1991).

Egins (1994:10) puts it this way:

Whatever genre we are involved in, and whatever the register of the situation, our use of language will also be influenced by our ideological positions: the values we hold consciously or unconsciously – the biases and perspectives we adopt.

The quote above aptly describes the relationship between Investigating Police Officers and suspects or an accused persons during interrogations or questioning as they might want to claim. The former are observed to employ language to exercise power and dominion on the latter. More often than not, the police see a suspect or an accused as already guilty of the allegation levelled against him or her, and as such use every “means” to justify their position and ideological belief. Following the position of Fairclough and Wodak (1997), van Dijk (2000) tries to give insights into how central the concepts of power, access (to discourse) and ideology are to Critical Discourse Analysis. His position is discussed below.

2.15.2 Discourse and Power

van Dijk (2000) posits that Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) has been mainly preoccupied with issues relating to the relationship between discourse and power. In other words, it is interested in such issues as how power (abuse) is enacted, legalised or legitimatised by the text and talk of dominant groups or institutions. The concept of power, as mentioned above, is like many abstract notions in the humanities and the social sciences that have defied consensus definition. Thus, we often speak of social power, that is, the power of a people X over another group of people Y. This kind of power is often defined in terms of control (van Dijk 2000:36). X controls the action of Y, and since discourse is a form of action, such control manifests in form of control over discourse as well as its properties – context, topic, turntaking, style, and much besides. It is worthy of note that the concept of power is not such that occurs in a vacuum as it has its base in scarce social resources as money, force, knowledge, information, status or profession.

In line with this position, Dijk, making reference to Clegg (1989); Lukes (1974; 1986), and Wrong (1979) pointed out the following:

- Power is a property of relations between social groups, institutions or organisations, hence the phrase “social power” as against individual power.
- Social power is conceptualised in terms of control exercised by one group or organisation (or its members) over the *actions* or the minds of another group, therefore limiting the freedom of action of the others, or influencing their knowledge, (behavioural) attitudes or ideologies.
- Power of a specific group or institution may be distributed, and may be restricted to specific *domains* or scope, such as that of politics, the media, law and order, education or corporate business, thereby resulting in different centres of power and elite groups that control such centres.
- Dominance is a form of power abuse, a legally or morally illegitimate exercise control over others in one’s own interest, which usually results in social inequality.
- 5. Power is based on privileged access to valued social resources , such as wealth, jobs, status, or a preferential access to public discourse and communication.
- 6. Social power and dominance are often organised and institutionalised so as to allow more effective control, and enable routine forms of power reproduction.

- 7. Dominance is seldom absolute. In other words, it is often gradual and may be met by more or less resistance or counter power by dominated groups.

From the following, it suffices to say that oftentimes, exercise of social power or institutional power results in abuse of power. This power abuse could result in limiting the freedom of action of a particular group and may equally affect their minds. That is, via special access to and control over a discourse in particular contexts, the dominant groups or institutions have the tendency of influencing the minds of the dominated group. Dijk further pointed out that the concept of power in democratic societies is devoid of such concepts as explicit commands, orders, threats or economic sanction. Rather, it involves manipulation and persuasion.

2.15.3 Discourse and Access

Another salient concept worthy of attention, as pointed out in Dijk's work is *access* to discourse. Access in this regard is likened to other valued social resources that form the basis of power in discourse. For example, not everyone has equal access to discourse in whatever field of human endeavour one can ever imagine – medicine, education, judiciary, politics, etc. Therefore, it is important to explore the implications of some salient questions such as “ who may speak or write to whom, about what, when, and in what context. As a matter of fact, how much access a speaker or individual has to discourse may be an indication of the power of the individual or the social group he or she represents. For instance, in the political settings, only politicians have active access to political meetings, and only parliamentarians to parliamentary debates. In such meetings, secretaries or clerks may have passive access only in their roles as people who carry out orders and speak only when they are asked to.

Also in education, it has been observed that teachers do usually have more access to communicative events than students. In other words, teachers control communicative events, distribute turns, have special access to, and therefore exercise control over educational discourse. On the contrary, students have access to classroom discourse only when they are invited or permitted, after having sought the approval or permission of the teacher. In the same vein, in a medical discourse, the doctor may be in control of many parts of the conversation with a patient in terms of influencing or dictating the setting, time, and style. In conclusion, there are elements

of culturally different patterns of access to conversations or discourse as determined by age, class, gender, profession, education and status. This explains why in some cultures, women are dominated in certain discourse contexts by men and young people by adults.

2.15.4 Discourse and Ideology

The concept of ideology is a term that is commonly used in the humanities and the social sciences. However, the term remains one of the vaguest and most “contested” concepts of the social sciences (Dijk, 2006). Different schools of thoughts differ in their opinions on their conception of the concept. Hence, the description of the term as ‘a system of beliefs, false consciousness or misguided beliefs, as a general notion, as the basis of social practices.

2.15.4.1 Ideology as a System of Beliefs

In this regard, ideology is seen as something that has to do with systems of ideas, especially with the social, political or religious ideas shared by a social group or movement. Therefore, we speak of communism, anti-communism, socialism and liberalism, feminism and sexism, racism and anti-racism, pacifism and militarism as examples of ideologies. Members of a group who share the same ideology(ies) stand for the same number of ideas that form the basis of their beliefs about the world. From the foregoing, it is established that ideologies are the fundamental or basic beliefs of a group and its members.

2.15.4.2 Ideology as False Consciousness or Misguided Beliefs

Within the Marxist school of thought, ideologies are seen as forms of false consciousness, that is, popular but misguided beliefs formed by the ruling class so as to concretise their class authority and conceal the real socio-economic situations of the workers. This view of ideology is a central element in the commonsense and political uses of the term, viz as a system of false, misguided or misleading beliefs (Dijk, 2006). For example, in the ideology of anti-communism which dominated the politics and scholarship of the Western world, ideology was associated with communism.

2.15.4.3 Ideology as a General Notion

Looking at ideology from this perspective allows for the recognition of ‘positive’ ideologies like those of feminism and the oppositional ideology as racism as being functionally the same . This is because these anti-ideologies (as anti-racism, anti-sexism) are not just opposing racism or sexism, but have their own ideology. In other words, they are ideologies that sustain and legitimatise opposition and resistance against domination and social inequality. Therefore, they equally have their own ideologies.

2.15.4.4 Ideologies as the Basis of Social Practices

Here, ideology is seen as what social groups or movements have come to believe and uphold, which form the basis of the social practices of the members of the group. Therefore, feminism as an ideology may be at the basis of gender discrimination, and pacifist ideologies may be at the basis of protest against nuclear weapons. From the foregoing, therefore, it suffices to conclude that ideologies constitute the bedrock upon which the social beliefs and characteristics of a group in terms of their identity, position in the society, interests and relations to other groups are built.

2.16 Discourse in Critical Discourse Analysis

As observed by Fairclough and Wodak (1997), critical discourse analysis views discourse as social practice to which the concept of context is crucial. The position of these scholars is evident in the excerpt below:

CDA sees discourse – language as a form of “social practice”. Describing discourse as social practice implies dialectical relationship between a particular discursive event and the situation(s), institution(s) and social structure(s) which frame it. The discursive event is shaped by them, but it also shapes them. That is, discourse is socially constitutive as well as socially conditioned – it constitutes situations, objects of knowledge and the social identities of and relationships between people and groups of people. It is constitutive both in the sense that it helps to sustain and reproduce

the social status quo, and in the sense that it contributes to transforming it. Since discourse is so socially consequential, it gives rise to important issues of power. Discursive practices may have major ideological effects – that is, they can help produce unequal power relations between (for instance) social classes, woman and man, and ethnic/cultural majorities and minorities through the ways in which they represent things and position people (Fairclough and Wodak 1997: 258).

Apparently obvious in the excerpt above is the notion of discourse being the use of language in organising and structuring social life. To this end, discourse (language) marks social identity, ideology(ies), world views, and much besides. The schema below is a graphic representation of the relationship between ideology and discourse.

Fig. 7: Mapping Theories of Ideology and Discourse

Source: Stoddart (2007)

The focus of critical discourse studies is to unite texts with the discourse and sociocultural practices that the text reflects, reinforces and produces (Fairclough, 1995). This position is captured in the chart below:

Fig.8: The relationship between texts, discourse practices and sociocultural practices in a critical perspective

Source: Paltridge (2006)

2.17 Justification for the Choice of the Adopted Theoretical Frameworks

This work adopts the Politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1987) and Impoliteness theory of Culpeper (1996) for data analysis within the purview of the Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) proposed by Fairclough and Wodak (1997). The Politeness theory proposed by Brown and Levinson is adopted in this work because first, a close observation of the data collected reveals the appropriateness of the application of the theory to it in the work, since one of the foci of the work is to examine the face-threatening and face-saving acts in police-suspect interaction; and second because the subsequent theories of politeness such as Face-Constituting theories and Theory of Relational work are apparently offshoots of Brown and Levinson's version of the theory, but by virtue of nomenclature, they have presented themselves as being somewhat independent of the theory when in actual fact their tenets reveal their origin in the theory. The Impoliteness theory proposed by Culpeper (1996) provides analytical tools for addressing the concept of impoliteness and power abuse as witnessed in police-suspect interaction. Fairclough and Wodak's (1997) Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis become

useful in addressing the issue of power relations and ideologies embedded in police's and suspects' use of politeness and impoliteness strategies in police-suspect discourse.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Research Design and Methodology

This work aims at examining the various (im)politeness strategies employed by the police in police-suspect discourse. In doing this, the work hopes to achieve the following:

- i. To examine the impoliteness strategies by IPOs and Suspects in police-suspect interaction
- ii. To examine the politeness strategies employed by IPOs and Suspects in police-suspect interactions
- iii. To examine how the deployment of impoliteness and politeness strategies demonstrates asymmetrical distribution of power between IPOs and suspects in police-suspect interactions
- iv. To identify and explain the ideologies and motivation behind the use of politeness and impoliteness strategies by IPOs and Suspects during police-suspect interaction
- v. To paint a graphic picture of how power is (unevenly) distributed between police officers and suspects in police-suspect interaction, with emphasis on how the constitutional rights of suspects are violated from a linguistic point of view.
- vi. To attempt a classification of police-suspect interactions considering their characteristic features

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives, an ethnographic approach (method) of data elicitation is adopted in this work.

3.1 The Ethnographic Method of Data Collection

The ethnographic method is one which is applicable to the study of a group of people who share similar interests, identity and/or culture. This approach involves the researcher being integrated in the culture or social field of interest ('in the field') and spending a sustained period of time with the subjects or participants of their research in order to observe and document their (language) behaviour as objectively as possible.

3.2 Precedure for Data Collection

The researcher, having collected an approval letter from the Acting Head of the Department, proceeded to the state headquarters of the Nigeria Police in Oyo State to seek the approval of the State Commissioner of Police, Oyo State Command. With the approval got, the researcher was attached to the State Criminal Investigation Department (S C I D) of the Nigeria Police, situated at Iyaganku area, Ibadan, Oyo State. The Department, we would later discover, from our observation and interactions with her men, is the centre of all investigation activities in the state. As we discovered, all cases involving serious and thorough investigation are usually referred to the place from other police stations and divisions in Oyo State. Some preliminary interviews were conducted with some men of the force to gain insights into how the outfit operates. A digital tape recorder and a higher education notebook were used for data collection. The digital recorder was usually placed on the table of the IPOs to record everything that transpired between them and the suspects; after the permission letter must have been shown to them, and the researcher stayed some few distance away from the actual scene of the interrogation scene to take note of all that transpired. The data gathered were transcribed into texts, and for those conversations that took place in Yoruba, efforts were made to transcribe them into the English language.

3.3 The Setting

As mentioned earlier, the recordings and observation took place at the State Criminal Investigation Department, Iyaganku Divisional Police Area, in Ibadan. However, the recordings did not take place just anywhere within the premises but precisely in the interrogation hall-room. It was a hall-like room that is shared by not less than ten police officers. The room has broken benches, rusty metallic filing cabinets and unarranged avalanche of paper documents. The floor of the room is coarse, having lost its smoothness from the obviously worn-out tiles with which it was adorned; an omen to suspects, especially the “unlucky” ones interrogated bare-footed. Being an open room, it usually witnesses the goings-in and out of other non-occupant police officers, who oftentimes interfere in the interrogation exercise or whatever transpires between the IPOs and suspects. Sometimes, as the researcher’s observation reveals, there could be more than one or two interrogation or interactions going on simultaneously in the same room. This raises a big

question as to the level of professionalism that is maintained by the IPOs during police-suspect interaction, especially during interrogation.

3.4 The Data and Method of Analysis

Constant visits were made to the station for a period of six months for data collection, using a digital tape recorder and an observatory note. The data collected on each visit were usually transcribed the very day they were gathered in order not to forget the details. The bulk of the recorded cases were in the Yoruba language and some featured code-mixing and code-switching of the Yoruba and the English languages. For the instances of the use of Yoruba, appropriate translation was done in the English language. In all, a thirty-five hour long recording and note-taking of fifty-five interactive sessions involving sixty-six (66) police officers and fifty-eight (58) suspects constitute our primary data. Two interactions culled from Farinde (1997) and Oyebade (2011) constitute our secondary data. The data are subjected to critical discourse analysis and descriptive statistical analysis. For ethical reasons, in our data presentation and analysis, we have decided not to make direct mention of the names of the participants, that is, the IPOs and the suspects, nor give any information that could reveal their identities. Rather, we have resorted to the use of letters of the English alphabet to refer to them.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS I

4.0 Impoliteness, Politeness Strategies and Power Abuse in Police-Suspect Interaction

Our analysis here will focus on the examination and description of the impoliteness and politeness strategies observed in police-suspect interaction. Precisely, the chapter looks at the impoliteness strategies employed by the police in police-suspect interaction, bringing to bare how these strategies are employed by the police to exert their institutional power and authority on suspects, and more often than not violate their fundamental human rights (*what is termed or referred to as power abuse in this work, considering the position of Section 34 sub-section 1 and Section 36 of Nigeria's 1999 Constitution respectively*); and how certain face-saving acts are employed occasionally by the police to mitigate such face threatening acts. It also gives insights into how suspects, especially low-profile ones, perpetually employ face-saving acts (politeness strategies) to acknowledge the institutional power of the police over them and, as such, appeal to their positive and negative faces. The preponderance of impoliteness strategies in police language as revealed in our data necessitates the reason we are starting with the analysis of impoliteness strategies in this chapter.

4.1 Impoliteness Strategies and Power (Abuse) in Police-Suspect Interactions

Impoliteness and power are two different but highly interrelated concepts. In fact, some scholars have argued that the two always go hand-in-hand. For instance, Bousfield and Locher (2008: 8) opines that power is an essentially crucial aspect in the study of impoliteness. As further argued by these scholars, power is an important part of interactions and “impoliteness is a demonstration of power”. Also, impoliteness brings about restrictions in the ways one can respond to the impoliteness or to the face-attack, and the restriction of one's options to act is of course the use of power (Kuntsi, 2012).

Culpeper (1996: 354) also links power with the use of impoliteness. He posits that impoliteness is more likely to occur in a situation where the speaker is more powerful than the addressee. In other words, when an individual is in a higher position, he or she can employ impoliteness more freely since the fellow might have the means to reduce the ability of the less powerful

participant to retaliate with impoliteness, and threaten more severe retaliation if the less powerful speaker attempts to be impolite.

4.1.1 Bald On Record Impoliteness Strategy

Here, the face-threatening act is performed in a direct, clear, unambiguous and concise way in circumstances where face is relevant. This is quite different from Brown and Levinson's Bald on record politeness strategy. For Brown and Levinson, Bald on record is a *politeness* strategy in fairly specific circumstances. That is, in cases when face concerns are suspended in an emergency, when the threat to the hearer's face is very small (e.g. "Come in" or "Do sit down"), or when the speaker is much more powerful than the hearer (e.g. "Stop complaining" said by a teacher to a student). "In all these cases little face is at stake, and, more importantly, it is not the intention of the speaker to attack the face of the hearer" (Kuntsi, 2012: 22). Instances of this are highlighted below:

CASE 2 : Defraudation (Land Issue)

Fraud: selling a parcel of land to two persons. This involved an 86-year old man who was accused of selling a parcel of land to two different individuals. The interrogation lasted for about thirty minutes in Yoruba, because the old man could not communicate effectively in the English language. However, there were few instances of code switching and code mixing as the interrogation continued.

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Owó tí ẹ gbà, báwo ẹ ẹ pín-in?*

The money you collected, how did you share it?

SUS: Láarín wa la gbé pin int.
We shared it among ourselves

IPO: Èlọ ló bọ sí i yín lówọ nínú seven hundred thousand naira?

How much got to your hand from the seven hundred thousand naira ?

SUS: Mi ò lè sọ bí a ẹ pín-in

I can't say how shared it

IPO: Okay,láti ìgbà wo ni ẹjọ ti bèrẹ lóri ilẹ yí?

Okay, since when did a dispute begin over this land?

SUS: Kò ì tî ju ọdún méjì lọ

Just two years

IPO: Kí ló dé tí ẹ talẹ fọdún méjì tẹjọ dẹ wà lórí ẹ tẹ ẹ rí ǹkankan láti ẹ si?

Why did you sell a land for two years, with controversies on it and you did nothing do it.

In a typical Yoruba society, a younger person would not ask an elderly person the questions the IPO asked the old man in the early part of the excerpt above without showing any sign of courtesy. For instance, the IPO asked: *Owo tí ẹ gbà báwo lẹ ẹ pín-in?* This was a direct face-damaging question that bothered on the integrity of the old man. Perhaps what birthed this question was the knowledge the IPO must have had of the Yoruba world where polygamy is allowed and as such preponderant, especially among the semi-educated and uneducated ones. In such families where a man has many wives and children among whom he shares his property in his “oral” will, oftentimes, there are cases of aggrieved parties going behind to circumvent the position of such oral wills. The IPO asked this question to know whether the old man cheated or outsmarted any other member of the family in the way the proceeds were shared. This is also evident in the follow-up question posed to the suspect as follows: IPO: *Èlọ ló bọ sí i yín lówọ nínú seven hundred and fifty thousand?*

The IPO did not redress the question in any way. The last question of the IPO in the excerpt indicted the old man and depicted him as an irresponsible old man. A popular Yoruba proverb which goes thus will be apt here : *àgbà ò kì í wà lójà kórí ọmọ tuntun wọ* “*an elderly man does not watch a situation go worse in his presence*”. The IPO was using this question to challenge and question the maturity and wisdom of the old man, because, according to the Yoruba, an elderly person, by virtue of his experience in the world, is endowed with wisdom with which a home, a family and the society at large is run without hiccups. To the IPO, the suspect had failed in this regard. The IPO chose to go this way because, in his estimation, the suspect had contravened the law and as such guilty of the allegation against him. With these questions that challenged the integrity of the suspect, the IPO demonstrated his institutional power over him, not minding the age of the suspect that naturally, in the Yoruba world-view, is associated with some kind of social power associated with (old) age . The old man-suspect did not struggle to

claim this power he ordinarily should demonstrate over the IPO, being an old man who should be treated with respect and honour normally, outside this very context he had found himself.

Excerpt 2

IPO: *È mò pé wàhàlà wà lóri ilẹ yẹn kí ẹ tó talẹ fún wọn..... wí pé ẹ sọ pé owó wọn lẹ fẹ dá*
You knew there were issues over the land before selling it
padà tùmò sí pé ẹ gbowó yẹn lònà jìbìtì ni
Saying you will return their money implies you collected their money in a
dubious manner.

SUS: Ohun tó jẹ kí n sọ bẹ ẹ ni pé..... int
The reason I said that was that
 IPO: *È máá sọrò; ó dígbá tí n bá sọrò tán!*
Do not talk; until I finish talking

SUS: È máá gbọ int
Hear me out
 IPO: *È gbọ tẹmi (↗)*
 SUS: Yes sir Hear mine

Making an incision on an already decaying wound, the IPO asserted “È mò pé wàhàlà wà lóri ilẹ yẹn kí ẹ tó talẹ fún wọn” *You knew there was a dispute over the land before you sold it* This is a direct accusation that maligned the integrity of the suspect. The IPO told the suspect to his face, not minding his age, that he had sold the land in a dubious manner. What else could he say to exonerate himself when he had been directly accused by the IPO who had already concluded on his case and declared him guilty. And when the suspect tried to defend himself with an explanation, the IPO shut him up, raising his voice at him and asking him to keep quiet until he (the IPO) had finished talking. This is a typical manifestation of bald on record impoliteness strategy employed by the IPO to show asymmetrical distribution of power between him (the IPO) and suspect in the course of the interaction. The IPO demonstrated his power over the suspect in the way he controlled his speech, determining when he should and when he should not talk. This alludes to one of the principles of CDA as proposed by Fairclough and Wodak (1997) that “power relations are negotiated and are performed through discourse”, and the submission of

Culpeper (1996, 2008) that impoliteness is a clear indication and demonstration of unequal distribution of power between participants in an exchange.

4.1.2 Positive Impoliteness Strategy

As suggested by Culpeper (1996), the sub-strategies of positive impoliteness strategies are as follows:

- *Ignore, snub the other* - fail to acknowledge the other's presence.
- *Exclude the other from an activity*
- *Disassociate from the other* - for example, deny association or common ground with the other; avoid sitting together.
- *Be disinterested, unconcerned, unsympathetic*
- *Use inappropriate identity markers* - for example, use title and surname when a close relationship pertains, or a nickname when a distant relationship pertains.
- *Use obscure or secretive language* - for example, mystify the other with jargon, or use a code known to others in the group, but not the target.
- *Seek disagreement-*
- *Make the other feel uncomfortable* - for example, do not avoid silence, joke, or use small talk.
- *Use taboo words* - swear, or use abusive or profane language.
- *Call the other names* - use derogatory nominations.

Following the proposition of Culpeper (1996) and Culpeper et al (2003) that impoliteness communicative strategies are“ communicative strategies designed to attack face, and thereby cause social conflict and disharmony”, a definition which is further expanded by Culpeper (2005) as follows:

Impoliteness comes about when : (1) the speaker communicates face attack intentionally, or (2) the hearer perceives and/or constructs behaviour as intentionally face-attacking, or a combination of (1) and (2);

examples of face threatening acts (bald on record without redress) include insults, criticisms, or requests, and abuse (Erbert & Floyd, 2004 and Ajayi, 2012). Criticisms, insults, abuse can threaten positive face by displaying a lack of respect and approval and destroying the balance in the relationship, while compliance gaining can threaten negative face by forcing someone to do something and limiting the number of potential behaviours.

We identify instances of Positive Impoliteness strategies at work during police-suspect interaction as follows:

CASE 1:

Background Information: The suspect had been in detention for some days before he was brought out for interrogation. In the course of the interrogation, the researcher observed the suspect had been alleged to have defrauded a popular commercial bank in Ibadan. The interrogation/questioning lasted for about forty five minutes.

Excerpt 1

IPO:You know why you are here. Why are you here?

SUS: There is an allegation that there is an issue of money; customer's money int. To the

IPO:
tune of?

SUS: I don't know it offhand

SUS: *Don't even tell me that*; it has been read to you.

Here, the IPO was direct, making it apparently obvious he was not interested in the suspect's claim he could not remember the amount of money he was alleged to have duped his victim (the woman at the centre of their discourse) with. The statement is likened to a command born out of anger, which literally means "shut up or what rubbish are you saying!". The IPO chose to go this way to send a message to the suspect that he could not bear the "nonsense" he was saying. The IPO deliberately resorted to this use of *seek disagreement* sub-strategy of positive impoliteness to counter the suspect's claim. The motivation for the use of this strategy by the IPO is his belief that if the suspect's claim that he could not remember the actual amount he was alleged to have defrauded his customer with was not challenged from the very beginning of their interaction, he

could use that to prove his innocence all through the process of the interrogation exercise; a fact which the IPO was not ready to come to terms with. This shows that IPOs have power to control the speech of suspects during police-suspect interactions. We shall see more of this in the subsequent excerpts.

Excerpt 2

SUS: I am not hiding anything from you. Even if (mention the name of his accomplice) is here, I will say all these in his presence....., he can't deny it

IPO 1: It is you that will take us to where we can get him

IPO 2: *How do you mean he can never deny? Is there any written document that he signed?* (↗)

SUS: I don't know where he lives, but I do normally send him text messages

IPO: *Ogbéni, Ogbéni, sé ó sign sínú ìwé kànkán pé òun gbowó lówó ẹ? All these things you are saying are nothing.*

Mr (man), did he sign any document that showed he collected any money from you?

In the excerpt above, the use of “Ogbéni” is connotative. The way it is used here by the IPO to address the suspect does not portray its literal meaning as used by the Yorùbá to mean “Mr.”(to show politeness). It is a metaphoric expression used to address the suspect by the IPO to create a social distance between him and the suspect. Having succeeded in creating a social distance between him and the suspect, the IPO asserted his authority in the interaction, asserting himself as the powerful participant in the exchange. As if this was not enough, the IPO threatened the positive face of the suspect with the statement “*all these things you are saying are nothing*” which interprets as “Mr man, you are saying rubbish”. Here again, the IPO unmitigatedly **disagreed** with the suspect and his explanation. This strategy was used to mount pressure on the suspect to say what exactly (the truth) the IPO wanted to hear. This constitutes a threat to the positive face of the suspect . With the use of this positive impoliteness strategy by the IPOs in this excerpt, it is obvious that the interaction is more of an interrogation than an interview or questioning. As the powerful participant in the interaction, the IPO held the power to disagree with the suspect's statement whenever he was not pleased with it but the suspect could not, considering his powerless status.

CASE 2: Details as stated earlier

Excerpt 1:

IPO: Bàbá, sẹ ẹ mọ X?

Old man, do you know X?

SUS: Mo mọ ọn

I know him

IPO: Sẹ ẹ mọ Y?

Do you know Y

SUS: Mo mọ ọn

I know him

IPO: Bàwo lẹ sẹ mọ wọn?

How did you know them?

SUS: Èmi ni mo talẹ fún wọn

I was the one that sold a parcel of land to them

.....
IPO:Ah!ah!! (short silence). It is okay. Ìgbà tì ìjà ti wà lórí ilẹ nàà bá yí, kí lẹ fẹ sẹ?

Okay. What do you want to do now that there is a dispute over the land?

SUS: Ehn, bí wọn bá gbà mí láàyè, bí ó bá di Monday, à á kówó wọn wá fún wọn.

If I am permitted, we will return their money on Monday

IPO: (short silence) Bàbá, wọn máa gbowó wọn kí ẹ tó kúrò ní bí lónì

Old man, they will collect their money before you leave here today

SUS: Ọwọ yín ló wà (with a shaky voice)

It is in your hand

Here, the IPO came out fully to threaten the positive face of the suspect where he issued a threat as follows: IPO: *Bàbá, wọn máa gbowó wọn kí ẹ tó kúrò ní bí* 'Old man, they will be refunded before leaving here today. He succeeded in making the old man uncomfortable with his threat that his movement for the day had been restricted until he paid his victims. The message in this statement is very clear and unambiguous. The IPO had indicted the personality of the suspect, and, therefore, he would not be allowed to leave the custody of the police until he paid the

money he had *dubiously* collected from the victims. This is a serious blow on the integrity of the suspect, who so far had not been able to convince the IPO he was not guilty of the allegation levelled against him as far as the land transaction was concerned.

Hearing this, the suspect quickly resorted to the use of *positive politeness* strategies ‘*make the hearer feel good, and minimize the speaker and maximize the hearer*’ to appeal to the conscience and positive face of the IPO, whom he knew, at this instance, had enough institutional power to detain him. He appealed to the positive face of the IPO with the statement: ‘*Ọwọọ yín ló wà*’ ‘it is in your hand’ rather than argue with the IPO; what could have further aggravated his impending punishment. Even when the IPO had not fully established the fact that the old man was actually guilty of the said allegation, he was already bringing in elements of interrogation in his interaction with him. And the fact that the IPO could decide the fate of the suspect in terms of his movement and the suspect acknowledging it as displayed above is another indication of asymmetrical distribution of power between IPOs and suspects during police-suspect interaction. Instead of going this way, the IPO could have resorted to the position of the law that indicted the suspect, so that he would know why his movement had to be restricted by him(the IPO) until he(the suspect) paid the said money.

Exerpt 2

IPO: anybody tí ẹ bá fẹ pè, ẹ pè é nísinyí o, ẹ ẹ san seven hundred thousand (naira)

fún àwọn people yíí kí ẹ tó kúrò nǐbí lénìí

Call whoever you want to call now; you will pay this people seven hundred thousand (naira) before you leave this place today

SUS: Èmi ò níèni kankan tí mà á... int

I don't have anyone that I will

IPO:

Oníjìbìtì nì yín

You are a fraudster

SUS: Ẹ jẹ kì n sọ nńkan fún un yìí int

Let me tell you something

IPO:

Ní sùúrù. Oníjìbìtì nì yín; ẹ dẹ sọ pé ẹ ò ríran

SUS: Oh! ògáà mi, jẹ kí n sọ fún ọ ...

Okay my boss, let me tell you

IPO:

*Hold on. You are a fraudster; and you claimed to have
sight problem*

ínt

Tèmi ni kí ẹ gbó; èmi ò ní gbó ti yín

because ẹ tí hùwà olè

It is mine you should listen to; I won't

listen to you because you have

manifested the trait of a thief.

SUS: *Yes sir*

Here, the IPO employed the 'call the other names' (derogatory nomination) positive impoliteness sub-strategy to attack the face of the suspect. In the excerpt, the IPO practically called the suspect *Oníjìbìtì*, a 419er, a fraudster, olè, thief, because he concluded the suspect was in the know as to the controversies surrounding the land before he sold it in a dubious way: IPO: *E jẹ kí n sọ fún yín, wi pe ẹ sọpé owó lẹ fẹ dá padà tùmò sí pé ẹ gbowó yẹn lónà jìbìtì ni.* The suspect, in the estimation of the IPO, was a dubious, cunning and dishonest old man who lacked integrity in spite of his age, hence should be dressed down. Name-calling here is an impoliteness-cum interrogation strategy employed by the IPO to overwhelm and wield power over the suspect. In the middle of all these, the suspect was still appealing to the positive face of the IPO, employing the positive politeness strategy 'minimise self, maximise the hearer,' calling him 'ògá mi' my boss, because he recognised the institutional authority of the IPO, who in this context was very powerful.

Here again, there is evidence of power abuse on the part of the said IPO as he disrobed the old man of his rights to dignity, calling him all sorts of names, including thief, a fraud, etc, even when the court had not stated so. And even if the old man-suspect was guilty, it was not within the powers of the IPO to pronounce him so. Even when the IPO had got the faintest clue of the culpability of the suspect in the said offence, the law does not bestow upon the police the power to condemn him the way he had done in this excerpt. As a matter of fact, it is only the court that has such power, which had obviously been usurped in this context by the IPO.

CASE 4: Rape

Background Information: The suspect, in his early twenties, was alleged of raping a young lady in company of his friends. He actually allegedly lured the victim into his room and conspired with his alleged accomplice to rape her. The matter was brought to the attention of the police, consequent upon which the suspect was arrested and brought to the police station for questioning.

Excerpt 1

IPO1: Are you ready to say the truth now?

SUS: Mo pè é ní ojó yen, a jò sòrò pé a fẹ́ fẹ́ ara wa; ó dè ní òun ti gbọ́

I called her on that day to propose to her, and she agreed

IPO1: Ago mélòó lẹ́ wọ́lé?

What time did you both go into the room?

SUS: Ìgbà (int)

When

IPO: () Ago mélòó lẹ́ wọ́lé? (↗)

What time did you both go into the room?

SUS: Ten!ten!!ten!!!, mo n dá a yín l'óhùn *daddy*

Ten!!! I am actually answering you, daddy

In the excerpt above, the IPO demonstrated his impatience and disinterest in the long story the suspect wanted to start narrating when asked what time he and his accomplice took the victim into the room, where he allegedly forcefully slept(raped) with her. This he did by interrupting the suspect and raising his voice at him to intimidate him. The suspect, being scared and uncomfortable by this act, responded *three times*, acknowledging the IPO's superiority over him as he referred to him as "*daddy*". While the IPO employed the positive impoliteness strategy (*make the other feel uncomfortable*) to instill fear in the mind of the suspect, the suspect resorted to the use of positive politeness strategy "*make the hearer feel good*" to appeal to the positive face of the IPO where he called him "*daddy*". He did this to secure the mercy and compassion of the IPO, who had demonstrated his power in the exchange by raising his voice at him.

Excerpt 2

IPO 2: È mú tape rule wá kí á wọn okó è

Bring a tape rule for us to measure his penis

SUS: Mummy ẹ jòó!

Mummy, please!

IPO 3: Èyin ènìyàn yìí ẹ è kí n sèyàn gidi olóríburúkú ni yín.....

You people are not genuine human beings..... you are misfortune bearers

SUS: È jòó ma.

Please ma

Here, IPO2 threatened the face of the suspect by calling on her colleague to get a tape-rule to measure the length of his (suspect) penis. She did not stop there; she rained curses and abuses on the suspect and his accomplice, likening them to “animals” and bearers of misfortune “*olóríburúkú*”. In the Yoruba world, an *olóríburúkú* is a never-do-well and unfortunate human being who might not make it in life. These are positive impoliteness sub-strategies: *use profane and abusive* words employed by the IPO to relegate the suspects to the background. The IPO did not mind the weight of this word but used it to attack the face and personality of the suspects. The suspects, acknowledging the powerful status of the said IPO here, could not respond or show their grievances at this even when it did not go down well with them. The act of calling the suspects ‘*olóríburúkú*’ is evidence of power abuse on the part of the said IPOs, if this is considered within the context of Section 34 of Nigeria’s 1999 Constitution where the rights of suspects are stated. While one would not be defending ‘guilty’ suspects, it is essentially important that the police, who are saddled with the responsibility of keeping and protecting the law of the land, act within the ambit of that same law, such that the law itself is not trampled upon.

Excerpt 3

IPO 3: Šé o ní ìyá?

Do you have a mother?

SUS: Mo ní

I do have

IPO 3: *Şé o lwọn br obnn?*

Do you have younger sisters?

SUS: Mo n

I do have

IPO 3: *O l b y  sn?*

You can sleep with your mother?

IPO 3: *O l d y ?*

You can have sexual intercourse with your mother?

In this excerpt, the IPOs threatened the suspects' faces with their questions on whether they could sleep with their mother and sister. This is like a bitter pill for the suspect to swallow because in the Yoruba culture, it is actually a taboo for relatives to have sexual intercourse, and asking an individual if he could sleep with his mother or sister in such a sharp and undiluted manner, especially in public as this, could be very embarrassing and face-damaging; what the IPOs wanted to achieve with their questions. The IPOs in this excerpt intentionally resorted to the use of these taboo questions to reduce the suspects to animals among whom incest is possible. This was possible because the IPOs, by virtue of the context of the interaction, was very powerful and could dress down the 'powerless' suspects. All these are tantamount to infringing on the rights of the suspects, which ultimately culminates into trampling on the Constitution of the land.

Excerpt 4

IPO 2: *J k n wo ok  b  şe r*

Let me see how your penis looks like

IPO 1: *Wn n n k o gbk  sta! (↗)*

She ordered you to bring out your penis (for us to see!)

IPO 3: *Gb kin sta! (↗)*

Bring the thing out!

SUS: (Brought out his penis)

IPO 1: *Olrburk. Ok t  t nkan*

A Misfortune bearer! A ridiculously small penis

IPO 2: *È è lè rójú rere Olóun.....*

You people cannot see the favour of God.

In the excerpt above, one of the IPOs commanded one of the suspects to bring out his penis for public examination, a development that birthed a face-damaging taunt from one of the IPOs as follows: “*Okó tí ò tó ǹ̀kan*” A ridiculously small penis. The IPO, being a full-grown Yoruba woman, is assumed to be well aware of the popular proverb in the language that says: *A k̀̀í t’ojú oǹ̀ka m̀̀s̀̀n àn k̀̀ à á* which translates as “ We don’t usually count the fingers of a nine-fingered man in his presence”. However, she chose not to abide by the principle and ideology of this proverb when she told the suspect to his face that his penis was ridiculously small. This is tantamount to reducing the manliness of the suspect, portraying him as one that would be a “little man” before his woman. This comment by the IPO is a diminutive one deliberately employed to damage the positive face of the suspect, following the position of Culpeper (1996). In this same excerpt, another IPO raised her voice at the suspect, commanding him to bring out his penis for her perusal; a request the suspect was reluctant to respond to initially, but having been shouted upon by the IPO, he finally complied. The said IPO actually raised her voice to frighten the suspect into doing her bidding.

Compounding the pressure already mounted on the faces of the suspects, the last IPO in the excerpt above cursed them “they will never see the favour of God”. All these are positive impoliteness strategies *use taboo words - swear, or use abusive or profane language* employed by the said IPOs to overwhelm the suspects and reduce them to criminals. The last IPO to speak crowned it all with showers of curses on the suspects, saying they were misfortune bearers who can never find the favour of God. This was the greatest of the threats meted out to the positive faces of these suspects. Any human being said to be far away from God’s favour is as good as dead, as such would live a life of frustration, hardship and regret. The IPO surely realised all these but will not mince her words in addressing the suspects the way she had done here for they had “committed” an act that is forbidden to the women folk in particular, and humanity in general. In this excerpt, the said IPOs demonstrated their power through the various commands issued to them and their application of coercive measures to compel the suspects into doing their bidding, followed up with showers of curses and abuses. Again, a critical appraisal of the

practice of the said IPOs in the situation painted above reveals acts of power abuse on the part of the IPOs. Even when the IPOs could be said to have evidence against the said suspects here, it is not within the jurisdiction of the police to pass judgement or condemn suspects. Even in the court, presumption of innocence is often given its pride of place. In other words, that a suspect admits to have committed a crime does not mean he/she has actually committed the said crime (refer to our discussions on confessions and why people give false confessions). He/she could have admitted to such, given the unpalatable circumstances he/she has found him/herself. That is why there is usually a need for thorough investigations in such situations.

CASE 5

Excerpt 2

IPO 1: Kí lo wá fẹ̀ kòlọ́pa ó ẹ̀se fún ẹ̀ báyíí?

What do you now want the police to do for you?

SUS: Tí mo bá lè rí àánú gbà, tí wón fi mí síbí iṣé

If I can receive the mercy of the police and be helped to learn a skilled job

IPO 1:

int
Olóppá

ni ó fi ó síbè! (scornful laughter)

The police will be the one to put you there

IPO 2: *Is he not a mad man?*

In the excerpt above, the IPO made jest of the suspect when he said he would appreciate it if the police would be merciful enough to assist him with resources to learn a skilled work as someone who did not know what he was saying. This was a laughter of mockery that painted the suspect as a fool. This position was further reinforced by the question the next IPO asked shortly after this derisive comment and laughter of IPO1 thus: *Is he not a mad man?* Technically speaking, IPO2 called the suspect a mad man in agreement with the view of IPO1. This was a serious blow on the positive face of the suspect. This threat to the positive face of the suspect continues in the excerpt below, where an IPO referred to him as ‘Wèrè’, “mad man”. While the IPO was free to address the suspect anyhow, employing *the call the other names (derogatory nomination)*, the reverse was impossible, considering the unequal power distribution between them. And again, the said IPOs violated the rights to dignity of the suspect by calling him a mad man.

Excerpt 3

IPO 1: Níbo ni ilé ẹ?

Where is your house/where do you live?

SUS: Sángo ni mò n gbé

I live in Sango

IPO 2: Area ibo ní Sángo?

Which area in Sángo?

SUS: Ibi ẹgbẹ ilé epo, lábẹẹ búkà yẹn

Very close to that petrol station, close to the canteen

IPO 2: Wèrè, o wá nílé!

Mad man, you called that a house!

CASE 8: Fraud

Background Information: This case involved a man, a stockbroker, in his early 50's, alleged to have mismanaged the stock of a client, which was worth 3.5 million naira.

Excerpt 1

IPO: Ẹyin gan-an sẹ ẹ mò pé ẹ jẹbi ọrọ yí, tàbí ẹ ẹ jẹbi?

Even you, do you know you are guilty , or not?

SUS: Ẹ jẹ n explain sir...

int.

IPO:

Question ni mo bi yín! Tí ó bá jẹ court, báwo lẹ se má a dáhùn?

I only asked you a question! If it were in court, how would respond?

SUS: Mà á sọ pé under the law of stock exchange...

int.

IPO:

Ẹ ní sùúrù! Kì n s'ẹyin lẹ ba ra shares ni? Şèbí ẹyin lẹgba 3.5 million lówó Y?

Hold on! were you not the one who assisted him in procuring the shares? You were the that collected 3.5 million form Y?

SUS: Cheque ni mo gbà
I only collected cheque int.

IPO: Òun náà ni mo mean now.
That is what I mean now

SUS: Mi ò sọ pé mà á bá wọ̀n rà á, mo ní Y pè mí pé...
I never said I would help him buy it, I said Y
Called me that..

IPO: *Statement wà ní bí now; mi ì
like ǹnkan tí ẹ́ ń bá mi sọ. Taló
introduce ẹ́ si? (↗)*

The statement is here now. I don't
like what you are telling me.
Who introduced X to Y?

SUS: Èmi ni
I did

IPO: *Ẹ́ dẹ́ wá ní ẹ́ ẹ́ jẹ̀bi! sẹ́ tó bá jókòó ti ẹ́ jẹ́jẹ́, sẹ́ irú ǹnkan bá yẹn á sẹ̀lẹ̀?(raising his voice↗)*
And you said you are not guilty, if the business had not been introduced to him, would all that happened have happened?

In the introductory part of this excerpt, the IPO put an indicting question across to the suspect, trying to paint him as an inept stockbroker that did not perform his responsibilities . This position was further affirmed at the concluding part of the excerpt where the IPO countered the argument of the suspect in defense of himself, threatening his face without redress, with the statement “*Statement wà ní bí now; mi ì like ǹnkan tí ẹ́ ń bá mi sọ*” “The statement is here now. I don't like what you are telling me. Who introduced X to Y”, with a raised voice. This is an obvious and unmitigated *disagreement* with the explanaton of the suspect by the IPO. The IPO chose to go this way because the suspect appeared not to be following his(IPO) line of argument, what he interpreted as lack of cooperation from him (the suspect). The IPO has the liberty to disagree with the explanation of the suspect as a demonstration of his power over him, but the latter could not do so, given his less-powerful status in the conversational exchange.

Excerpt 2

IPO: *Mo ma ñ nàyan gan-an o! Mà á la orí yín mọ pákó ibí nísín! Torí ẹ ñ fún mi ní headache bí mo ẹ wàyí. Tóbá jẹ ẹ lọ sí ibẹ yẹn láti confirm ni, gbogbo ǹkan yìí ò ní ẹlẹ*

I do beat people a lot. I will hit your head against this plank here. Because you are giving me headache as I am. If you had confirmed the transaction details, all this would have been averted.

SUS: That is true

IPO: *Kò jù báyan lọ. Ẹ ti wọ inú 18 bẹ ẹ wàyí! Ẹ ti wọ 18 kò sí bóyá kiní.*

In short, you have got yourself into trouble without mincing words.

SUS: Now tí ẹ ti sàlàyé fún mi, ó ẹ ñ yé mi ni

Now that you have explained everything to me, I now understand.

Here, the IPO employed the *make the other feel uncomfortable* positive impoliteness sub-strategy to intimidate the suspect where he threatened him (the suspect) he (the IPO) specialises in inflicting injury on suspects, and that he would hit the head of the suspect against the wooden wall if he provoked him “by saying what he did not want to hear”. The IPO made this assertion to send a warning signal to the suspect that his explanations to exonerate himself were not tenable, and that he had better cooperate with him (the IPO) if he did not want to incur his wrath. He even made the matter worse when, towards the end of the excerpt, he told the suspect he was in a serious trouble, likening him to a footballer who has committed a foul in box 18; who is bound to receive a severe penalty for his action. All these intimidatory threats are indications of power inequality between the powerful IPO and the powerless suspect; the IPO being very powerful and the suspect, powerless.

CASE 8

Excerpt 3

IPO: *Tí mi ò bá ri i, mà á detain yin. Mo ti stamp ẹ nìyẹn! Tí mi ò bá ri i, I will detain you right now. Because you are the architect of this problem.*

I will have you detained if I don't see the money, because you are the cause of this problem.

SUS: (Trying to feign a smile)

IPO: *Wọn ọ̀n tí ì pàà̀yàn l'ójú yín rí lẹ̀ ẹ̀ n r'ẹ̀rìn. Ẹ̀ má à jẹ́ kí n r'ẹ̀yín yín níta. Ó wù mí kí n fún un yín ní ẹ̀jẹ̀ díẹ̀ kí ẹ̀ tó kúrò níbí.*

You are laughing because you have not witnessed a scene where people were killed before. Don't let me see your set of teeth outside. I feel like giving you a bloody injury before you leave here today.

SUS: (Silence)

In this excerpt, the IPO made it known to the suspect without mincing words that if he did not see the other suspect (his accomplice), he was going to detain him. In fact, he concluded by accusing the suspect of being the cause of all the problems investigated here. When the suspect tried to feign a smile in order to gather momentum to refute the claim of the IPO, the IPO commanded him to shut out his teeth and threatened he felt like inflicting wounds on him before he would be done with him. All these were done by the IPO to make the suspect *uncomfortable* and powerless before him. The positive impoliteness sub-strategy employed by the IPO here is “*make the other feel uncomfortable*”. In this interaction, the IPO succeeded in overwhelming the suspect, putting him on the spot and exerting his institutional authority and power over him. This goes further to show how power is unequally distributed between IPOs and suspects in police-suspect interaction. The IPO, being the powerful participant here, controlled the action of the suspect, while the suspect, who had to do the bidding of the IPO, was the less powerful one.

Excerpt 6

IPO:Kí ló dé tí ẹ̀ gba 250,000 lórí iṣẹ̀ tí ò ì tí ì work?

Why did you collect 250,000 on an uncompleted transaction?

SUS: (Trying to explain)

IPO:

Int Ẹ̀ má à padà s'ẹ̀yìn! ẹ̀ má à dà mí lórí rú! (↗)
Don't go back! Don't get me confused!

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: O lọ́ n jẹ́ commission nígbà tí s'ẹ̀ ò tí ready. *Olè gan-na lẹ̀yin náà, olè*

You collected commission when the job was not ready. You too are a thief.

In the concluding part of this excerpt, the IPO employed the *call the other names (derogatory nomination)* positive impoliteness sub-strategy to indict the suspect, calling him thief, as though confirmed by the court of law. He called him olé “thief” as though the case had been presented at the court and the suspect found guilty. All these acts of the IPO: dressing down the suspect, calling him derogatory names even when the matter had not been decided by the court are a demonstration of the ‘untamed’ power (abuse) of IPOs over suspects in police-suspect interaction.

CASE 12: Defilement

Background Information: This is a case of a 21-year old young man who was alleged to have forcefully slept with a 6-year old girl living around his neighbourhood

Excerpt 1

IPO: Wò ó, wo ojú mi dáadáa, o ti şe exam sílẹ̀, o ò need screening, admission ti dúró fún ẹ̀ ní

Agodi, direct entry ni. Šé o ti ready láti sọ̀rò?

See, look at my eyes very well, you have written an exam, you don't need any screening, you have already secured admission into Agodi, it is direct entry. Are you ready to speak now?

SUS: (Nodded his head)

IPO: Okay, sọ̀rò bá yí

Okay, speak now

SUS: Began to explain....

IPO:

int

On the 20th tí o rán ọ̀mọ̀ yẹ̀n lẹ̀wà àti bread, kí ló şẹ̀lẹ̀?

What happened on the 20th when you sent the girl to buy beans and bread for you ?

SUS...Ehm....

IPO:

int.

Okay, o bá a sùn àbí o ò ba a sùn?

Okay, you slept with her or not?

SUS: *Daddy*, mi ò baasùn

Daddy, I did not sleep with her

IPO: O şì tún ní deny

You are still denying

SUS: *Daddy, daddy, mi ò baasùn, mi ò kí n jẹ bread ati ẹwà..*

I did not sleep with her sir, in fact I don't eat bread and beans

IPO:

int.

Ẹ dá idiot yìí padà sínú cell jòó

Please take this idiot back into the cell

SUS: *Daddy, ẹ jòó, Ọloun ò ní ba tiyín jẹ*

Please sir, may the Lord not destroy what belongs to you

IPO: *Mo mò pé hardened criminal ni ẹ*

I know you are a hardened criminal

SUS: *Daddy, ẹ jòó...*

Please sir

IPO:

int.

Olòsì, da a padà sínú cell

Idiot(useless human being); return him to the cell

IPO2: *Wà á jẹrà sí Ágodi*

You will rot in Agodi

The IPO was obviously not interested in the “cock and bull story” the suspect was narrating to exonerate himself, hence his interrupting him and calling him an idiot, who should be taken back to the cell. He then concluded without mincing words that the suspect was a hardened criminal (who would not want to own up to having committed the said crime), *Olòsì*, a useless fellow who would rot in prison (*Agodi*). These are *call the other names (derogatory nomination)* positive impoliteness strategies intentionally employed by the IPO while dealing with the suspect to demonstrate his power over him, and as such coerce him into confessing to having committed the crime. While the IPO employed positive impoliteness strategies to attack the face of the suspect, the suspect, by his powerless status, resorted to the use of positive politeness strategy *make the hearer feel good* to appeal to the positive face of the IPO, emphasizing his minus power status before him. He did this by constantly referring to the IPO as “*Daddy*”. This could be said to be a reflection of the Yoruba socio-cultural belief that anyone old enough to be one’s father is usually

referred to as *bàbá* or father. With the suspect referring to the IPO as daddy, he showed his affiliation to this aforementioned socio-cultural and ideological practice of the Yoruba; he himself being Yoruba.

Excerpt 2

IPO: Ibo ni ọmọ yẹn wà nígbà tí o fi pè é?

Where was the girl when you called her?

SUS: On the 20th tí è n sọ yẹn, mi ò rántí. Ọjọ ọdún, mo lọ sí ọdò daddy mi l'Ọmí...

I can't really remember that date, on Iléyá day, I travelled to Ọmí to celebrate at my dad's place

IPO:

Listen to me (↗), mà á fọ etí ẹ o! Tí o ò bá gbọran dáadáa, mà á fọ etí ẹ o, etí ẹ máa sí.

Listen to me, I will slap you! If you have hearing impairment, I will slap you and you will start hearing well

SUS: On the 18th daddy, mi ò sí nílé walahi....

True to God, on the 18th, daddy, I was not at home

IPO:

int.

Okay, o basùn àbí o ò basùn?

Okay, you slept with her or not?

The IPO still continued with the unfriendly tempo with which he started in Excerpt 1. He raised his voice at the suspect to call him to order, for as far as he was concerned, the latter was not addressing the question put across to him with respect to what happened on the very day the complainant claimed the investigated incident took place. He did not stop at this, he further threatened to slap the suspect if he would not “cooperate” with him. The IPO actually did this to frighten the suspect so that the fellow could cooperate with him and confess to him.

CASE 14

Excerpt 2

IPO2: Bàbá, ẹ wá n ẹe bí ẹyàn dáadáa, ẹ n ẹe bí ẹyàn Ọlọrun

Old man, you are now pretending to be a good man; you are acting like a godly man

IPO: Ọmọ àlè! (☺)

Bastard!

Barr: Bóyá torí wọn ò ní stature

Perhaps because he has a small stature

IPO: *Olóriburúkú. Tí ñ bá ti máa prepare charge ẹ, màá tún fi rape si (☺)*

Misfortune bearer. When I am preparing your case, I will include rape therein

The IPO further attacked, employing the positive impoliteness strategy, the face of the suspect without redress by calling him *Ọmọ àlè* “bastard”, *Olóriburúkú* “Misfortune bearer”. These are not good names any rational human being wants to bear, but which the IPO has deemed fit to christen the suspect. He further threatened to include rape as part of the charges against the suspect by the time he finished preparing the charge papers of the case: *Tí ñ bá ti máa prepare charge ẹ, màá tún fi rape si (hissed)* “When I am preparing your case, I will include rape therein”. Here, the IPO employed the *call the other names* positive impoliteness strategy to wreck havoc on the face of the suspect. The IPO showed his power in terms of the fact that there is no limitation as to how he could dress down the suspect; disrobing him of his dignity. That was why he called him all sorts of names, and even hissed at him. The suspect on the other hand showed his powerlessness by subjecting himself to all this abusive name-calling of the IPO, without any form of protest or objection. Here again, a case of power abuse has occurred.

Excerpt 3

SUS: *Ọloun dáríjì mí o*

God, have mercy on me oo

IPO: *Bàbá, Ọloun ò ní dáríjì yín o*

Old man, God will not forgive you

IPO2: *Èwòn lẹ́ẹ lọ*

You shall go to jail/prison

In the midst of the above situation, the suspect tried to console himself with a supplication that God should forgive him. However, this attracted a negative reaction from the two IPOs above who proclaimed God would not forgive him, and that he would surely land in prison. The two IPOs obviously did not agree with the suspect’s prayer that God should forgive him, hence his

condemnation to the prison, even when the constitution of the country has not empowered the Nigeria Police to decide the fate of any suspect in terms of determining whether the suspect will be sentenced or not. But, the IPOs made this statement as a demonstration of their power over the suspect who could not threaten the faces of the IPOs back with the same measure or dose of impoliteness strategies as employed by the IPOs.

CASE 15 : Defraudation

Background Information: *The suspect was a 68-year old man alleged to have duped a client over some acres of land. He, alongside his accomplice, was alleged to have sold the same acres of land to more than one person; a development that resulted in a very serious dispute among the victims.*

Excerpt 1

IPO: Èló ni X (the accomplice) fún-un yín?

How much did X give you?

SUS: 150,000

IPO: *It is not possible. That is a pure lie*

In this excerpt, the first IPO practically called the suspect a liar as he disagreed with him saying his statement was nothing but a lie. Here again, the IPO, employed one of the principles of bald on record without redress negative impoliteness strategy, that is “*seek disagreement*”. To the IPO, the old man was a liar and there was no any element of truth in his statement. The suspect, a 68-year old man, although far older than the IPO, was apparently powerless before the IPO who called him a liar. He could not refute the statement, neither was he able to stage any obvious protest against this derogatory statement from the IPO.

CASE 19: Mismanagement Of Business (Funds)

Background Information: *The suspect here was brought to the police custody by a complainant who claimed the suspect mismanaged a poultry he set up and put in care of the suspect. The mismanagement of the said poultry led to a great loss on the part of the complainant*

IPO: What is your name?

SUS: I am XYZ

IPO: Where were you born?

SUS: XXX

IPO: When?

SUS: 1983

.....

IPO: What was the agreement between you?

SUS: Oga promised to share the profit of the business with me after four years.....

IPO: What condition did your oga give for the sharing?

SUS: That is if the business succeeds.....

IPO: *You are a fool, and did it succeed?*

SUS: (Shakes his head). Sir, God knows I tried

IPO: (Hit his baton on the suspect's head) *Answer my question, Olé (thief)*

SUS: I can explain everything sir

In the excerpt above, the IPO called the suspect all kinds of derogatory names such as *fool, olè, thief*. All the suspect was doing, in reaction to this name-calling, was to exonerate himself and explain his innocence, but could not attack the face of the IPO back, employing impoliteness strategies, considering his powerless status.

CASE 20: Armed Robbery/ Defamation Of Character

Background Information: *The suspect, an engineer, was accused by the complainant of being among the armed robbery gang that robbed her on 2nd May 2013 at the Lagos-Ibadan express way. According to what was inferred in the course of the interaction, the complainant walked up to the suspect in a church programme in Ota and held on to him, alleging him of being a member of the robbery group that had earlier robbed her.*

IPO: Okay, have you seen this woman before?

SUS: At all sir

IPO: *It is a lie*. You mean you have never seen her before?

SUS: Yes, except the day she came to arrest me

IPO: Why did she arrest you?

SUS: In fact, I am just waiting for this matter to be over so that I rearrest her too. *I would have retaliated but I did not want to break the law*

IPO: *Thank you for not breaking the law*

In the italicised part of the excerpt above, the IPO employed the seek disagreement positive impoliteness substrategy to seek clarification from the suspect, a high-profile individual. He employed this device to debunk the claim that he had not met the complainant before coming to the station, and not necessarily to indict him as the case usually is when the interaction involves a low-profile suspect. The IPO could not use this device in the humiliating and intimidating way it is often used when dealing with low-profile suspects, as the suspect here appeared well-informed. Little wonder that he (the suspect) commanded the respect of the IPO who thanked him for not breaking the law. Ordinarily, if it were a low-profile suspect that made that remark, it could have attracted severe punishment and even unsavoury treatment from the IPO, as evident in the interactions involving low-profile suspects.

4.1.3 Negative Impoliteness Strategy

According to Culpeper (1996), negative impoliteness strategies are devices used to damage the negative face of an individual. Its sub-strategies are as follows:

- *Frighten* - instill a belief that action detrimental to the other will occur.
- *Condescend, scorn or ridicule* - emphasize your relative power. Be contemptuous. Do not treat the other seriously. Belittle the other (e.g. use diminutives).
- *Invade the other's space* - literally (e.g. position yourself closer to the other than the relationship permits) or metaphorically (e.g. ask for or speak about information which is too intimate, given the relationship).
- *Explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect* - personalize, use the pronouns 'I' and 'you'.
- *Put the other's indebtedness on record*

A critical observation of our data reveals the use of some of these sub-strategies by the IPOs in police-suspect interaction. These are discussed below:

CASE 2 : (see details above)

Excerpt 3

IPO: Bàbá, sè ẹ mọ X?

Old man, do you know X ?

SUS: Mo mọ ọn

I know him

IPO: Sè ẹ mọ Y

Do you know Y

SUS: Mo mọ ọn

I know him

IPO: Bàwo lẹ sẹ mọ wọn?

How did you know them?

SUS: Èmi ni mo talẹ fún wọn

I was the one that sold a parcel of land to them (referring to the suspect and the complainant)

IPO: Bàbá, sè ẹ mọ pé ẹjọ wà lórí ilẹ yẹn kí ẹ tó talẹ yẹn fún wọn (accuses the old man ↘)

You know there was a dispute over that land before you sold it

SUS: Rára o

No, not at all.

IPO: Kí ló wá dé tí ẹjọ wá bèrẹ nígbà tí ẹ ti talẹ fún wọn?(↗)

How come that there is a dispute over it after selling it to them?

In the italicised part of the excerpt above, the IPO employed the *explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect negative impoliteness* strategy, stating the old man knew there was a dispute surrounding the controversial land before selling it, to attack the face of the suspect without redress. Going by the tune of the statement, it is an accusatory and indicting rather than an interrogative one. The IPO intentionally chose to go this way because he had already concluded that the suspect was as good as a criminal, and he felt he needed to put him on the spot so that he would confess to have committed the crime without much ado. In actual fact, the

IPO was of the opinion that the old man was a criminal or fraudster who sold the disputed parcel of land to more than two people, in spite of his knowledge of the disputes surrounding the land.

The accusatory nature of this statement makes this interaction an interrogation rather than an interview. As a way of further overwhelming the suspect, the IPO raised his voice at him to frighten him into confessing to the fact that there had been a controversy over the land, even before the old man sold it off. With his raised voice, the IPO employed the *frighten the hearer* negative impoliteness sub-strategy to overwhelm the suspect. The IPO demonstrated his power via his unchallenged authority to accuse the suspect of intentionally going ahead to sell the disputed land amidst controversies and unresolved issues. He equally raised his voice at him, while the suspect was looking “helpless” before him.

CASE 3: Threat to life

Background information: The suspect was reported to the police by a complainant who alleged the suspect had threatened to kill him over a parcel of land, which the suspect claimed his late father gave the father of the complainant on a compassionate ground.

Excerpt 1

IPO: Bàbá, is it true that you are after his life?

SUS: It is not true

IPO: Kí lè ní jà fún?

What are you fighting for?

SUS: Èmi rẹ̀ ò jà

We are not fighting/quarrelling

IPO: E pè é lórí phone tàbí ẹ̀ pè é lórí phone?

You called him on phone or you did not call him on phone?

SUS: Èmi ò pè é lórí phone o

I did not call him on phone

IPO: Bàbá, ẹ̀ pè é níjẹta.....? *A má a kọ letter sí àwọn network láti find out o; tí ẹ̀ bá paró a má a get, a dẹ ma charge yín sí court. A máa gbé yín lọ sílé ẹjọ.*

Old man, did you call him two days ago or not? We are going to contact the various network providers to find out if you are telling a lie or not

IPO: Mo pè é níjẹta

I called him two days ago

Here again, in the italicised part of the excerpt, the IPO *frightened* the suspect with the statement that the police would contact the network providers to find out if he actually called the complainant on phone or not, and if found to be lying, he would be charged to court and eventually prosecuted. Not being able to withstand this threat the IPO meted out to him via the *frighten the hearer* negative impoliteness strategy, the suspect quickly owned up to calling the complainant. The officer must have been fully aware of the disposition of a typical Nigerian to litigation or court-related issues. Arguably, an average Nigerian, especially the lower class and non elite ones who do not really understand how the judiciary system of the country operates, is not such that likes having anything to do with the court(litigation); the mention of which often sends cold water down their spine. The IPO capitalised on this knowledge to manipulate the suspect into confessing to calling the complainant; a fact which he had earlier denied. With this strategy, the IPO was able to overwhelm the suspect, thereby securing from him the information(truth) he needed. The threat was serious damage to the suspect's negative face and a demonstration of the institutional power of the IPO over him.

Excerpt 2

IPO:Kí lẹ sọ fún un lóri phone?

What did you tell him on phone?

SUS: Mo ní báwo la ẹ fẹ ríra, simple thing

I simply asked how we were going to see each other

IPO: Kí lẹ fẹ ri fún? *E fẹ pa á?*

What did you want to see him for? You wanted to kill him?

SUS: (Trying to explain the relationship that exists between him and the complainant; how

his (suspect's) father gave out the controversial parcel of land) int

IPO:

Kí ló ẹlẹ bàbá yìí tó o

kàn n rojọ, ẹ mo wá beèrè history níbí bayìí ni? Kí lo wá dórí ilẹ wọn? Kí lo fẹ lo ta ilẹ wọn fún?.....

What happened you this old man that you narrating story; am I here to ask for

history?What are you looking for on his land? Why did you want to sell his land?
SUS: Ilẹ̀ẹ̀ bàbáà mi ni

It is my father's land

IPO: Ọwọ̀ọ ta ni bàba yín ti ralẹ̀?

From whom did your father buy the land?

SUS: Bàbáà mi ò ra ilẹ̀

My father did not buy the land

IPO: L'átòrun ni wọn ti gbé'lẹ̀ lọwọ̀!

He brought the land from heaven!

SUS: Ibi tí wọn dé sí nìun

That was where he migrated to

IPO: Sẹ o ri pé òtòtò ti n yojú nísìn yíí...*tí wọn ò bá gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀, wà á pa wọn!*

You can now see that the truth is coming out... if he refuses to remove his building from the land, you will kill him!

In the italicised part of the excerpt above, the IPO employed the *explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect* negative impoliteness strategy to associate the suspect with murderous acts or tendencies, alleging the suspect he might have gone ahead to carry out his 'threat to take the life' of the complainant if the fellow did not dance to his tune to remove his building from the land. The question "*E fẹ pa á?*" *you wanted to kill him?* in the excerpt is more of an accusatory question than a fact-finding one, aimed at pressurising the suspect into explaining the brain behind his purported threat to the complainant. And as a follow-up to this accusatory question asked by the IPO, he further depicted the suspect as one who was already guilty of attempted murder where he concluded the suspect would kill the complainant if he failed to heed his warning to remove his building from the disputed piece of land. All these were statements that indicted the suspect as someone capable of taking another person's life. They are a deliberate attempt to put the suspect on the spot and pressurise him into confessing to the allegation levelled against him. The IPO freely accused the suspect of wrong-doing, while all the suspect was doing was to defend himself; a development that portrayed the IPO as the powerful participant in the exchange, and the suspect the less powerful one.

CASE 5: Attempted murder

Background information: The suspect was said to have attempted taking the life of the complainant (an Okada/motorcycle rider) whose motorcycle the suspect allegedly boarded to a particular destination(during which the incident took place)

Excerpt 1

IPO 1:Níbo lo ti rí irin yí (pointing to the metallic object the complainant claimed the suspect wanted to strike him with to claim his life)

Where did you find this iron/metalic object?

SUS: Níbi ẹ̀sẹ̀ ibi tí a ti ń jà náà ni

Very close to where we were fighting

IPO 2: *Dòbálẹ̀!* (↗)

Prostrate!

SUS: (He prostrated)

In this conversation, the second IPO raised his voice at the suspect to *frighten* him, commanding him to prostrate. The IPO, being an ‘authority’, could not stand the fact that the suspect remained standing while talking to him. This treatment already painted the suspect as a criminal who, must not stand shoulder-to-shoulder with him, hence had to remain on the floor while talking to him. As a demonstration of his powerless status, the suspect quickly lay flat on the floor to obey the powerful IPO. Again, this practice on the part of the IPO is an indication of power abuse, since it is not in consonance with the provision of the 1999 Constitution with respect to how suspects should be treated during investigations.

Excerpt 2

IPO 1:Ènìkẹ̀jì ẹ̀ dà?

Where is your accomplice?

SUS: Èmi nìkan náà ni

I am the only one

IPO 1: Àní tí ẹ̀ jọ ma ń ẹ̀rú ẹ̀sẹ̀ yẹ̀n

I mean your accomplice

SUS: Mi ò ẹ̀rú ẹ̀sẹ̀ yíí rí

I had never been involved in the act before

IPO 2: *Àbí áyé fẹ̀ ẹ̀ se ẹ̀ ni?..... mò ǹ bọ̀ jẹ́ kí n ẹ̀ ǹkan tí mò n ẹ̀ tán; mà á fún ẹ̀ ní
mark tí o má a ma fí han ọmọ ẹ...ìyẹn tó ò bá kú sẹ̀wòn*

Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world? I am coming; let me finish what I am doing, I will give you an indellible mark with which you will narrate your bitter experience to your children, if you don't eventually die in prison.

IPO 1: O jẹ́ sòótó

You had better say the truth

In the excerpt above, IPO2 raised his voice at the suspect with the rhetorical question: *Àbí áyé fẹ̀ ẹ̀ se ẹ̀ ni?* “Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world?”. Though a question in structure, the pragmatic import of the question/expression is very deep. For anyone that understands the Yoruba language very deeply, the statement is not just an ordinary question but a curse or an abuse deployed to threaten the face of the suspect. In the Yoruba world-view, the word “Ayé” is polysemous. It could mean the world in which we live as human beings, and also, it could mean the evil forces in the world, the powers that control the affairs of man, who oftentimes are responsible for the misfortune that betides any man who has incurred their wrath. As such, when an individual is jumping from one problem or misfortune to another, it is commonly believed that such an individual is under the spell of “Ayé”, hence such expressions as “ayé n ẹ̀ se ẹ̀” meaning “the evil forces of the world are working against him/her”, ayé n tẹ̀ le” meaning the evil forces of the world are pursuing him, etc.

IPO2 asked this question to signal his rejection of the suspect's claim that he had never been involved in the act of criminality he was alleged to have committed before. Following this was the threat the IPO issued out to the suspect in the latter part of the excerpt that he was going to inflict an indellible injury on him with which he would narrate his ordeal to his children for having committed a criminal act. The IPO was assertive as to his position that the suspect was going to be jailed as evident in his concluding remarks thus: “ìyẹn tó ò bá kú sẹ̀wòn” “that is if you don't eventually die in the prison”. Obviously, he had already condemned and convicted the suspect, even before presenting him in court. This ultimately constituted a threat to the negative face of the suspect, who at the hearing of this, began to shiver; a demonstration of his helplessness in the hands of the powerful IPO that had made the proclamation.

CASE 6: Rape

Background information: *The suspect is a young man in his late teens. He was alleged to have forcefully slept with the victim, whom we later got to know was the suspect's girlfriend.*

Excerpt 1

IPO: When did you finish secondary school?

SUS: 2009

IPO: And since then what have you been doing?

SUS: I went for computer training and wrote JAMB

IPO: What was your score?

SUS: 210

IPO: What are you hoping to read?

SUS: Law

IPO: You want make we finish your career. *By the time your admission letter comes, you will be in remand.*

In the concluding part of the excerpt above, the IPO threatened the negative face of the suspect with a statement that portended his freedom of movement would be restricted until otherwise stated: *“By the time your admission letter is out, you will be in remand”*. Obviously, the suspect would not be happy to hear this as no man enjoys having his freedom (of movement) snatched away from him. However, the suspect could not do anything about this than to consider himself to be at the mercy of the IPO that had “spoken” as an authority. The IPO continued as follows:

Excerpt 2

IPO: *You know the offence wey carry you come (here) na very big offence, and if you gather the whole lawyer for this town, den go remand you. Sebi your career don finish. You know the offence that brought you here is a very great one and even if you engage the services of all the lawyers in the town, you will still be remanded.*

In the above excerpt, the IPO threatened the negative face of the suspect with the information that he had committed a very gigantic offence; so big that he cannot escape being remanded (and perhaps jailed), and even if he secured the services of the whole of the legal practitioners in the

town, he would still not escape being jailed. One can feel the element of exaggeration in the IPO's statement; a negative impoliteness strategy he intentionally employed to paralyse the mind of the suspect who would now see himself as being "hopeless", "helpless" and at the mercy of the police as far as his freedom and future career are concerned.

Excerpt 3

IPO: How old are you?

SUS: I am 19 years old

IPO: *You are ripe for conviction. If I send you to Agodi now, your career is finished.*

Nobody will ever take your bail.

SUS: *Silent*

The IPO threatened the negative face of the suspect with his unmitigated threat that he would be sent to *Agodi*, a popular prison in Ibadan where criminals are "taught the lesson of their lives", having initially pronounced him (the suspect) as being ripe for conviction. To criminals/offenders, "the fear of Agodi is the beginning of wisdom". This face damage was a deliberate attempt by the IPO to instill fear in the suspect and get him overwhelmed. The IPO here exaggerated his institutional power, painting himself as one that had the power to sentence the suspect to prison, even when the constitution of the country has not empowered the police with such powers.

CASE 7: Sexual misconduct

Background information: The suspect is a secondary school teacher, who was alleged to have used his position/office as a teacher to manipulate a student of his into sleeping with him.

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Monkey don hang itself oo. Ìtìjú ni fún ẹ nísinyí pe iyàwó ẹ n gbọ pé iwọ teacher n bá ọmọléwé sùn*

The monkey has hanged itself..It is a shame to you now for your wife to be here to hear you, a teacher, are sleeping with your student

SUS: *Silent*

IPO: *You slept with your student and you are a teacher*

SUS: *Silent*

IPO: Kí ni qualification ẹ?

What is your qualification?

SUS: HND (Higher National Diploma)

IPO: In what?

SUS: Musicology

IPO: *You go go sing for Agodi*

You will go and sing in Agodi

In the excerpt above, the IPO employed the *Condescend, scorn or ridicule the other negative* impoliteness strategy to attack the face of the suspect, where he directly and visibly made a ludicrous comment on the “shameful” act of the teacher(suspect) in question. In fact, the comments of the IPO are such that questioned the morality and integrity of the suspect as a teacher where he commented: *You slept with your student and you are a teacher!*”. The message here is clear : in the estimation of the IPO, the suspect is not a responsible teacher. This was further made worse with the obvious and unmitigated threat of the IPO to the suspect’s negative face that he would go and sing in Agodi, a notorious prison. The IPO said this to threaten the face of the suspect without any effort to redress it. By the conclusion of the IPO, the suspect was already guilty of the allegation against him, even when the court had not pronounced so.

CASE 8

Excerpt 3

IPO: *Ọpolọ yín ò pé tẹ̀lẹ̀ àbí? Ó sẹ̀ n pé ni!*

You were not in full possession of your mental prowess before? You are just getting normal!

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Ẹ dá mi lóhùn. *Ọpolọ yín yẹn ò pé tẹ̀lẹ̀!*

Answer me. You were not in full possession of your mental prowess before

SUS: (Silent)

In the excerpt above, the IPO referred to the suspect as someone not in full possession of his mental prowess via an insulting question : “*Ọpolọ yín ò pé tẹ̀lẹ̀ àbí? Ó sẹ̀ n pé ni!*” *You were not*

in full possession of your mental prowess before? You are just getting normal! The suspect felt embarrassed at this provoking-cum-abusive question, looking at his countenance but could not do or say anything to register his displeasure at this, considering his “powerless” status before the “powerful” IPO. The said IPO employed this “*Condescend, scorn or ridicule - emphasize your relative power*” negative impoliteness sub-strategy to insult the suspect, who, in his conclusion, was dubious and should not be accorded any form of respect, even when he (the suspect) obviously appeared older than he (the IPO).

CASE 8

Excerpt 4

IPO: *E ti jèbi. E è sé dáada bàbá yìí, and you said you are 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?*

You are guilty. You have not done well this man, and you claimed to be 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?

The IPO pronounced the suspect guilty at the end of the conversation and even questioned his age: *E ti jèbi. E è sé dáada bàbá yìí, and you said you are 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?.* You are guilty. You have not done well this man, and you claimed to be 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?. The IPO here combined two negative impoliteness sub-strategies: *explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect and condescend, scorn or ridicule* to wreck havoc on the face of the suspect. To the IPO, it is shameful that someone who claimed to be 47 years old could be so bereft of wisdom and experience to handle the situation at hand. His ineptitude was the cause of the problem at hand as far as the IPO was concerned. This is an unmitigated threat to the negative face of the suspect.

Excerpt 5

IPO: Now do you believe you are at fault now?

SUS: Can I explain? Since the money was not paid to me ...

IPO:

int.

Correct yourself. The cheque

was given to you and you gave it to somebody. Haven't you been collecting cheque before?

SUS: Ehn, ehn...

IPO:

Int

Yes or no (●), I don't want all this.

SUS: Yes!!

IPO: So, what is your complaint now?

SUS: The complaint is that the person is supposed to do it...

IPO:

Int.

Listen now, mr man, don't provoke me! (↗)

SUS: (Began another round of explanation)

IPO: Èlò ni commission yín?

How much was your commission?

IPO2: 500,000

SUS: Èmi! Irò ni èyí o..

Me! This is not true. int

IPO:

Int

Sh!!! ẹ má a gbò mi o, ọ̀rò ti di ọ̀rò ara nísìn yí..

Sh!!! Be listening to me, the matter is now ours

SUS:

Int.

Wọ̀n ò fún mi..
lówó o
They did not give me money

IPO :

int

Listen to me (↗) Èlò ni commission yín?

How much was your commission?

Excerpt 6

IPO: O lo ní jẹ commission nígbà tí isé ò tí ì ready. Olè gan-an lèyin náà, olè. Sè ọmọ

X(mentioned a town in a southwestern state) lẹ pe ara yín?

You have already taken commission when the job is not yet completed. You too are a thief. Did you say you are from X ?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Ibo ni ní XYZ?

Where in XYZ?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Ìlú gidi wá ni iyẹn ni?

Is that a good town?

In the excerpts above (5 and 6), every attempt by the suspect to defend and exonerate himself was frustrated by the IPO, who had already concluded the suspect was guilty. In doing this, he employed both linguistic and paralinguistic tools (as indicated in the bold parts of the excerpts). In the concluding part of this excerpt, the IPO did not only demean the suspect, damaging his face without redress, but he also extended same to his race, perhaps in reference to that Biblical statement “Can anything good come out of Nazareth?”: IPO: *Ìlú gidi wá ni iyẹn ni? Is that a good town?* The IPO threatened the negative face of the suspect here without redress, by passing ridiculous comments on the home-town of the suspect, and by extension, the entire race to which the suspect belongs. This is nothing short of the violation of the fundamental rights of the suspect by the IPO; a phenomenon termed power abuse in this work. Meanwhile, earlier in the excerpt, the IPO had frightened the suspect, warning him not to provoke him; a statement that portended a serious danger for the suspect if he did not cooperate with him. Here, the IPO combined the *frighten the other* and *condescend, scorn or ridicule* the other negative impoliteness sub-strategies to relegate the suspect to the background. Even when this did not go well with the suspect, he could not make or stage any protest or reply the IPO in the same manner, considering the unequal distribution of power between them.

Excerpt 7

SUS: Mi ò dé ọ̀dọ̀ ọ̀lọ̀pàá rí láti ìgbà tí mo ti bèrè isé yíí...

*I had never been to the police station since I started
this business*

IPO:

int. *E ti wò ó lónì. E ti wò “gàù”.*

Case yín kì ò se case kékeré.

Federal High court ni, wòn

má a wòn ọ́n fún un yín neat ni.

You are in for it today. You are in great trouble. Your case is a very serious one; one that would be decided at the federal high court, and your sentence/judgement will be a stiff one.

In the excerpt above, the IPO employed the “*frighten the hearer- instill a belief that action detrimental to the other will occur*” negative impoliteness sub-strategy to put the suspect on the spot and throw him off balance. The IPO reiterated the suspect was in for it; he had caught himself in the “web” and that his case was so serious that it would have to be tried at the Federal High Court and he was very sure he (the suspect) was going to be sentenced. All these were done by the IPO to overwhelm the suspect, who now began to see himself at his (the IPO) mercy. Looking at the countenance of the suspect, it was obvious that he looked worried at the IPO’s mentioning of the Federal High Court; a pointer to the fact that the IPO had succeeded in achieving his aim of putting the suspect on the spot, mounting pressure on his negative face.

CASE 9: Being in Possession of Contraband (India Hemp)

Background Information: *This case involved two “lovers” caught with some quantity of India Hemp and arrested, following a tip-off from their neighbours. The conversation here was between an IPO and the female of the two suspects.*

Excerpt 1

IPO1: Ta làwọ́n òbí ẹ?

Who are your parents?

SUS: Ìyáa Alágbo ni

Ìyá Alágbo(my mother sells local herbal concoction)

IPO2: *O ò rí èyàn advise ẹ, orí ẹ ti burù. Wọn ò lè ẹ case yín níbí, NDLEA ni.*

You have not got anyone to advise you, you are an unfortunate person. Your case cannot be handled here, but at the NDLEA

SUS: (Trembling) Ẹ jòó

Please

IPO: Ìwọ náà wo ojú ẹ; Ò n mugbó tàbí o ò mugbó?

You too examine your eye balls, do you smoke India hemp or not?

SUS: Mo ti gbó mò n muu

I have heard; I do smoke (India hemp)

IPO: Ẹ o lọ school?

Did you attend any school?

SUS: (Responded in a low voice that the IPO could not pick)

IPO1: Má a sòrò sóke! (↗ ; ●)

Speak louder!

The IPOs in this excerpt employed the use of *frighten and condescend, scorn or ridicule the other* negative impoliteness strategies to launch an onslaught on the face of the suspect, addressing her as follows: *O ò rí èyàn advise ẹ, orí ẹ ti burù. Wọn ò lè ẹ case yín níbí, NDLEA ni* “*You have not got anyone to advise you, you are an unfortunate person. Your case cannot be handled here, but at the NDLEA.* As mentioned earlier in this work, the Yoruba people strongly believe that certain negative ways of life characterise the lifestyle of an individual who is termed unfortunate or a carrier of misfortune. One of such was what the suspect here had been accused of; being found with Indian Hemp, and especially considering the fact that the suspect was a female. The IPO, being a Yoruba woman, quickly resorted to this belief as a way of explaining what could be responsible for this unwholesome act of the suspect. She abused the suspect, telling her to her face she is an unfortunate being. The suspect on the other hand could not react back or abuse the IPO back because, considering the context of the interaction, she was powerless relative to the powerful IPO, who, by virtue of her institutional power, believed she could dress down the suspect. This is another manifestation of asymmetrical power distribution between police and suspects during police-suspect interaction, and more importantly, a typical instance of power abuse on the part of IPOs.

Similarly, the IPO threatened the face of the suspect with the mention of NDLEA (Nigeria Drug and Law Enforcement Agency) in her(the IPO) statement to the suspect, threatening her her case would be handled by the agency. The suspect, who was quite aware of how tough this agency could be on individuals caught with Indian Hemp, began to scream and cry for mercy before the IPO. IPO1 too did not help the situation when he raised his voice and banged his table at the suspect to intimidate and overwhelm her while trying to seek further information from her.

Excerpt 2

IPO3: Ìgbà wo lo kúrò ní school? (He hit the suspect with his stick)

When did you drop out of school?

SUS: (Still trembling)

IPO3: Àní ìgbà wo lo kurò ní school? (↗). *Wo irun tó o ɛ se sórí, omọ àlè!*

I demand, when did you drop out of school? Look at her hairstyle, bastard!

SUS: *E ɣàánú mi*

Have mercy on me

IPO1: Orí ẹ ò pé. Ẹ́ o lọ primary school?

You are not sane. Did you attend primary school?

SUS: Mo lọ.

I attended

As evident in the italicised parts of this excerpt, the IPOs employed the *condescend, scorn or ridicule the hearer* negative and *Call the other names - use derogatory nominations* positive *impoliteness* strategies respectively to demonstrate their institutional power over the suspect. IPO3 raised his voice at her, calling her a bastard and an insane individual. With their words, the IPOs reduced the suspect to a nonentity that was good for nothing. These are great unmitigated threats to her face. Submitting to the authority and power of the IPOs, the suspect resorted to the use of positive politeness strategy of *making the hearer feel good* to appeal to the positive face of the IPOs. She literally was begging for mercy in the hands of the IPOs, an action that could be interpreted as massaging their institutional ego and power. This further paints police officers as

the more powerful participants in police-suspect interactions. The tone of the IPOs in this excerpt depicts the exchange is an interrogation rather than an interview.

Excerpt 3

IPO4: *Mo ti rójú ẹ, ojú ẹ jọ ti ẹni tó ń fagbó*

I have seen your eyes; they look like that of someone who smokes India hemp

IPO: *O ń fagbó tàbí o ò fagbó?*

You smoke India hemp or not?

SUS: *Mo ń fà á*

I do smoke it

IPO: *Şé ó ma ń dùn?*

Is it sweet/palatable?

SUS: *Ehm, ehm....*

IPO: *Şé ó ma ń dùn?* Int. (↗ ; ●)

Is it sweet/palatable?

IPO4: *Ta ló kọ ẹ bí wón se ń fagbó? Şé ọkọ ẹ ni?*

Who taught you how to smoke India hemp? Is it your boyfriend?

SUS: *Kì ń se*

It is not

IPO: Int. *Ta ló kọ ẹ?* (↗ ; ●)

Who taught you?

SUS: *Àti Ọyọ náà ni wón ti kọ mi nígbó.*

I was taught in Ọyọ

In this excerpt, the IPOs threatened the negative face of the suspect bald on record without redress in myriads of ways. One of the IPOs (IPO 4) employed the “*explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect*” negative impoliteness strategy by associating the suspect with the act of taking or smoking Indian Hemp, saying, having carefully examined the eyeballs of the suspect, it was clear she was an ardent smoker of Indian Hemp. Another IPO banged the table at the suspect, with a raised voice aimed at frightening her into confessing to the allegation that

brought her to the custody of the police. With all these, the said IPOs demonstrated their power on the suspect, who before them was powerless, helpless and overwhelmed. When this interaction is viewed in line with the position of Inbau (2001), it can be said to manifest elements of interrogation, without any trait of an interview.

Excerpt 4

IPO1 and IPO4: Ta ló kọ ẹ?

Who taught you?

SUS: XYZ (mentioned a lady's name)

IPO4: Obìnrin ló kọ ẹ ní igbó! Dìde ná. *Şé o lómú báyiì?* (bursts into laughter)

A woman taught you how to smoke India hemp! Stand up. Do you have breasts at all?

IPO: (Burst into laughter) Wón béré ìbèèrè lówó ẹ o ò dáhùn! (↗)

They were asking you a question and you refused to respond

SUS: Mo lóyàn (*in a low voice, then coughed*)

I do have breasts

IPO5: *Má à wúkọ Tuberculosis ní bí o, ko fowó bo ẹnu ẹ o*

Don't spread tuberculosis here; cover your mouth!

IPO: Orí ẹ ò pé

You are not sane

In this excerpt, IPO4 made a spiteful comment on the masculine physique of the suspect. Nothing could be as humiliating as abusing a woman with the essential part of her body which she lacks. The said IPO asked the question below to get at the suspect : IPO4: Obìnrin ló kọ ẹ nígbó! Dìde ná. *Şé o lómú báyiì?* (bursts into laughter) “A woman taught you how to smoke India hemp! Stand up. Do you have breasts at all?”. This is not just an ordinary question, but one asked to make jest of the suspect and ridicule her; an embarrassing one for that matter. As the suspect was still trying to recover from the pain this embarrassing question must have caused her, she was further “hit” again by another IPO, who addressed her as being infected with **Tuberculosis** and as such should not infect them (the IPOs) with it when the former coughed during the interrogation exercise. These are a clear use of the *condescend, scorn or ridicule the hearer* negative impoliteness strategy by the IPOs to demonstrate their power to dress down

suspects, depicting them as criminals, even when they have not been taken to the court, where they would be pronounced guilty or otherwise. The suspect demonstrated her powerlessness before the IPOs by complying to their order to present herself for their examination; to check if she had breasts or not. If what happened in the conversation is examined critically in the eye of the law, the rights to dignity of the said suspect could be said to have been violated, hence a case of power abuse on the part of the IPOs.

CASE 10: Malicious Damage

Background Information: *This case involved two male suspects and a complainant. The suspects were alleged to have set the room of the complainant ablaze, hence their arrest. The IPOs here were reacting to the written statements of the suspects, one of whom claimed to be a graduate of Economics from a university and the other a second-year student of a polytechnic. The IPOs made spiteful and malicious comments on the “terrible write-up” of the suspect. These are presented below:*

IPO: *I was “boned”* (burst into laughter). Óyá, spell the “born” you meant.

SUS: B-O-N-E-D

IPO: “*Boned*” lò ñ sọ yẹn. A graduate of Economics, University of X. “*You were boned*”!

You have wasted these papers. I will look for another paper, but you won’t be the one to write it. *A graduate for that matter!*

IPO2: Eléyí ò graduate; irò ló ñ pa

This one did not graduate; he is only telling lies.

IPO1: Ó ní “*I lives at Bólórundúró, Awotan area, I when to, W-H-E-N. Went yẹn gan bad. Ó*

ní I when to Temitope “N-U-S-T-R-Y”. “1999 I was finished” (the IPO burst into another laughter) He said I lives at Bólórundúró, Awotan area, I when to... even that “went” is very badly written. He said I went to Temitope “N-U-S-T-R-Y”, and was finished in 1999.

IPO 3: ògá, if you see their youth corper uniform, na in dey neat pass.

Sir, if you see the NYSC uniform of people like this, it is usually very neat, even neater than that of every other corps member.

IPO: Ó ní *I attended “nustry” in 2005, and I was finished in 1999 (burst into laughter, alongside other IPOs, numbering about 5)*

He said I attended nustry in 2005, and I was finished in 1999.

IPO: *Then I gained my “hardmission” in the year 2008; I pased out, P-A-S-E-D, in the year*

2012. *About the “isident”. Kì n ̄ se incident lo kọ yìí, ah! Mo ti fẹ́ kú o.*

It is not not the spelling of “incident”. I am dying oo”

IPO4: *Owó ti jóná* (burst into laughter)

You have wasted your parents’ resources

IPO: *Ṣé suspect le léyìí? I “suput” Drugbu and Baba D. E ti waste ìwé mi. E ẹ̀ mọ̀ ǹnkan kọ.*

O ò graduate. No! You are not a graduate.

Is this the spelling of suspect? I suput (suspect) Drugbu and Baba D. You have wasted my paper. You don’t know how to write.

SUS: Silent

IPO: My first born is a 7-year old boy. Wọn ọ̀n bí i da kó kọ̀ ǹnkan tí ẹ̀ n kọ̀ yìí. He can even take your statement.

I have a 7-year old boy who dares not write the rubbish you are writing

IPO5: And if you see this people when they see police for road, den go say see these idiots, àwọn tí ò mọ̀ ǹnkan, and den no know say they are the anti-idiots, tí ò lè kọ̀ anything 😊)

And these are individuals who would refer to the police as ignoramus and idiots, whereas they are actually idiots themselves.

IPO6: (Trying to read the statement of the suspect) *Ah! o ò lọ school rárá*

Obviously, you did not attend any school at all.

IPO: Kí n ti ẹ̀ kọ̀ kọ̀ lọ dàwọ̀n sínú cell ná tí mi ò bá ti rẹ̀ni bámi attend sí wọn

Let me first of all throw them in the cell, if I cannot get anybody to help attend to them

IPO6: Ibo lo ti lọ secondary school?

Where did you attend secondary school?

SUS: Ìbàdàn

IPO6: Kí ni discipline ẹ̀?

What is your discipline?

SUS: Economics

IPO: Economics! O ò wá lè kọ̀wé.

Economics! And you cannot write well.

IPO7 : *Criminial ni bọ̀bọ̀ yìí*

This guy is a criminal

IPO6: *Sà̀ngó ni ó pa ó. O lọ fì owó jóná ni. Ọ̀mọ̀ primary 2 gan-an lè kọ̀ Ọ̀yìbó jù ẹ̀ lọ.*

May the god of thunder strike you to death. Even a primary 2 pupil can write better English than you.

Essentially, the whole of this excerpt is presented above because of its peculiarity, as it is replete with bald on record impoliteness strategy with its sub-strategies. The IPOs in the excerpt commented with scorn on the incompetence of the suspects and the complainant in their written English. In particular, the IPOs made jest of the suspect who claimed to be a university graduate, whose written statement was said to be terribly bad; being fraught with many errors. He then got such face-threatening comments such as: *A graduate for that matter!; About the "isident". Kì n' se incident lo kọ yìí. ah! Mo ti fẹ́ kú o* "This is not the spelling of "incident". I am dying oo", *E ti waste iwé mi. E ẹ̀ mọ̀ nńkan kọ* "You have wasted my paper. You don't know how to write". *O ò graduate, No! You are not a graduate, Owó ti jóná* "You have wasted your parents' resources". And to cap it all, one of the IPOs expressly called the suspect a criminal: *Criminal ni bọ̀bọ̀ yìí* "this guy is a criminal", and as if this was not enough, another one commented thus: *Sàngó ni ó pa ó. O lọ́ fí owó jóná ni. Omọ primary 2 gan-an lè kọ Òyìbó jù é lọ* "May the god of thunder strike you to death. Even a primary 2 pupil can write better English than you". The IPO here rated the suspect who claimed to be a university graduate far below a primary two (2) pupil. None of these instances of the use of bald on record impoliteness strategy was redressed by the IPOs.

The way the IPOs derided the suspects and the complainant in the excerpt above, with the latter helplessly swallowing the bitter pills from them, is a clear demonstration of unequal access to power in police-suspect interaction. The IPOs called the suspects names, laughed them to scorn and ridiculed them in public. These are against the position of the 1999 Constitution, Section 34, sub-section 1 precisely, which spells out the rights of suspects (as observed by Salman 2009). The said IPOs disrobed the suspects and the complainant of their rights to be addressed with dignity in the excerpt; a case of power abuse on their part.

CASE 12: Defilement 1

Background Information: This is a case of a 21-year old young man who was alleged to have forcefully slept with a 6-year old girl living around his neighbourhood.

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Wò ó, wojú mi dáadáa, o ti se exam sílẹ̀, o ò need screening, admission ti dúró fún ẹ ní Agodi, direct entry ni. Sẹ o ti ready láti sọrọ?*

See, look at my eyes very well, you have written an exam, you don't need any screening, you have already secured admission into Agodi, it is direct entry. Are you ready to speak now?

SUS: (Nodded his head)

IPO: Okay, sọrọ báyí

Okay, speak now

SUS: Began to explain....

IPO:

int

On the 20th to rán ọmọ yẹn lẹwà àti bread, kí ló sẹlẹ?

What happened on the 20th when the girl brought the bread and beans you sent her?

SUS: Àkókó, mi ò ran ní bread àti ẹwà, mi ò ran ní anything daddy

First of all, I did not send her on an errand to get bread and beans for me

The IPO here began his interaction with the suspect, employing the *frighten the other* negative impoliteness strategy as he indicted and convicted the suspect, saying his “offence”, even when yet to be presented in court, would land him in *Agodi*. This statement was made to frighten the suspect whom the IPO was fully convinced had committed the crime attributed to him. With the statement of the IPO, he demonstrated his power over the suspect, declaring to him he was due for prison (*Agodi*).

CASE 15 (see details above)

Excerpt 2

IPO2: *At this age, you are still lying. Ẹ ma kú sẹwọ̀n by the time you are convicted*

You are still telling lies at this stage of yours, you would die in prison when you are Jailed

IPO3: And you are still sitting down! Stand up (↗)

IPO1: *Until baàlẹ̀ comes, you are not leaving here*

OC: *That means he and X are partners in crime*

IPOs: Yes they are

Following this case from its first excerpt presented under our analysis of Positive Impoliteness strategies in police-suspect interaction, the second IPO did not salvage the situation as he commented thus: *At this age, you are still lying. E ma kú sẹwòn by the time you are convicted* “You are still telling lies at this stage of yours, you would die in prison when you are jailed”, employing the *explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect*, as he associated the old man with the act of telling lies. As far as he was concerned, the old man was a monstrous liar, in spite of his old age. This untoward statement and the ones that followed, as made by the IPO, painted the old man as an irresponsible man and criminal. The IPO further made a proclamation that the old man would die in prison by the time he would be convicted. The first IPO avowed authoritatively that the old man would not be let go until the community head (baàlẹ̀) surfaced, and the OC who was equally present at the scene of the interrogation exercise commented the old man was a partner in crime to the other suspect, whose arrest was yet to be effected. These IPOs and the OC threatened the negative face of this old man without redressing it.

As a demonstration of his power over the old-man suspect, the OC raised his voice at him, commanding him to stand up while talking to him. In his helpless situation, the old man quickly rose to his feet in obedience to the OC’s command. This portrayed the powerful status of the police and the powerless status of low-profile suspects in police-suspect interaction.

CASE 21: Conspiracy and Stealing

Background Information: *The suspect was brought to the custody of the police by his boss, a shop owner in Ibadan, who claimed the suspect was in the know as to how thieves came to burgle the shop and carted away goods worth 205,000 naira.*

IPO: Àwọn olè wá wọlé wọn jí àwọn ẹ̀rù yẹ̀n lọ?

So thieves came and carted the goods away?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir

Yes sir

IPO: Sẹ̀ o ò mò wọn rí ni?

Don’t you know them?

SUS: Rára, ògá

Not at all sir

IPO: *Wà á pé ní cell, sẹ o gbọ. Ó sure pé o máa lọ sí èwọn*

You will stay long in the cell. It is very certain you are going to be jailed.

In the interaction above, the IPO employed the frighten the other impoliteness strategy with an affirmative statement that the suspect would surely land in jail to instill fear in him. This is an intimidating statement he hoped would make the suspect confess to having committed the crime or knowing one or two things about the robbery case at hand. As far as the IPO was concerned, the suspect was guilty and surely going to be jailed, even when the fellow had not been presented in the court.

CASE 25: False Representation and Fraud

Back Information: *The suspect here is being quizzed in connection to the fraudulent activities of a sacked bank marketer who presented herself as a staff member of XYY bank and defrauded many unsuspecting customers of a huge amount of money. The principal suspect, before her sack, was directly reporting to the suspect being questioned here, being her boss. It was insinuated that there might have been an amorous affair between them and that was why, even long after the principal suspect had been sacked, she still had access to some of the facilities of the bank; which aided her nefarious activities. The exchange had started before the researcher came in.*

IPO: *Mr XXX, do you know as the coordinator of her group, your not retrieving the facilities of the bank from her after she was sacked could have aided her in perpetrating that act?*

SUS: *You are treating me like there is a personal interest here. I am not a criminal and should not be treated so. It appears you police officers are always after bankers (↗ **angrily**)*

IPO: *Mr XXX, do you know that is an allegation? I need you to explain that allegation. Do you know where you are?*

SUS: *Yes, I know I am at the SCID*

IPO: *So you expect me to take your words at the face value.*

SUS: *You have asked me questions, and I have answered you; yet you are paraphrasing the questions to indict me*

IPO: *Mr XXX, accept your fault. Yoruba ni gbogbo wa (we are all Yoruba)*

SUS: *The bank is not her primary employer. YYY employed her on behalf of the bank*

IPO: *Mr XXX, do you know the essence of investigation? We need to do proper investigation*

in order to apportion blame properly. You can never fight with your IPO. Most of the successful lawyers in the court get ideas from their IPOs.

SUS: È máà bínú sir

Don't be annoyed sir

In the italicised parts of the excerpt above, both the IPO and the suspect employed the *explicitly associate the other with a negative aspect* impoliteness strategy to achieve different purposes. Consequent upon the insinuations that the suspect might have been having amorous affairs with the principal suspect in this case, the IPO indirectly accused the suspect of dereliction of duty 'not retrieving the facilities of the bank from the principal suspects, months after she had been sacked, hence, her being able to defraud the complainants with the facilities'. The suspect too fired back by accusing the police of always being on the trail of us bankers. Interestingly and surprisingly, even when the IPO expressed his displeasure at this indicting statement of the suspect, he was not verbally nor physically assaulted as it often was in cases involving low-profile suspects. In other words, even when the IPO still demonstrated himself as the (powerful) one in charge of the interaction, he never failed to respect the relative power of the suspect in the gentle manly voice and manner he was addressing the suspect. This must have been necessitated by the status of the suspect, who portrayed himself as one who knew his rights.

4.1.4 Mock Politeness Strategy

As explained by Culpeper (1996), face-threatening acts can be performed with the use of obviously insincere politeness strategies. In other words, the speaker can make insincere statements, which superficially appear polite and pleasant but pragmatically impolite, to attack the face of the hearer. Instances of this are found in our data and are presented below:

CASE 3

Excerpt 3

IPO: *O lè lọ agbo ilé, but kí lo wá lọ ilẹ tí wọn kọ ilé sí tí o tún fẹ gbe tà?*

You can go to the family house but what are you looking for on the land

he(complainant) has built his house that you want to sell it?

SUS: *Mi ò gbe tà*

I don't intend to sell it

IPO: Meeting kí lo wá fẹ ba ẹ?.

What meeting did you want to hold with him?

SUS: Ñkan tó fa gbogbo èyí ni wípé èmi ni Mógàjí ilé wa

What actually caused all this is the fact that I am the family head

IPO:

máa n tà kiri (*sounding derisive*)

A responsible family head sells land indiscriminately

SUS: Èmi ò talè kiri

I am not involved in indiscriminate selling of land

(int)
Ilè náà ni mógàjí

In the excerpt above, the IPO intentionally flouted the social rule/norm of the language (Yoruba) on the use of honorific pronouns in addressing the elderly ones during interactions (*see details in Withhold Politeness Impoliteness*). This, he did, to be able to dress down the suspect whom he felt had done something hideous and as such did not deserve to be respected or regarded in this situation. This is really a great threat to the face of the suspect who had had his respect and honour disrobed of him by the IPO, who failed to accord him respect with the use of appropriate honorific pronouns. The IPO used "O" for him instead of "E". Furthermore, in one of his comments to the suspect's responses, the IPO taunted the suspect with a derisive and derogatory comment that portrayed him as an "irresponsible" family head who does not know his role as the "Mógàjí" "Head" of his family. To the IPO, a responsible family head will not be involved in the act of indiscriminate selling of land as the suspect had been alleged to be doing. If the IPO were seen to be sincere with this statement that superficially supports the idea of the Mógàjí suspect selling the family's land, one would classify the utterance as such employed by the IPO to save his positive face by employing what Brown and Levinson (1987) would call "give approval to the hearer" positive politeness sub-strategy. It would then mean that the IPO was supportive of this very act. However, in this very context, the IPO used this statement to mock the suspect, depicting him as an irresponsible family head. The suspect, being a full-grown Yoruba man, understood this to be an insult on him, but could not restrain the IPO nor retaliate because of his powerless status before the IPO. All he could do was to gently refute the proposition of the IPO.

CASE 14

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Şèbí o ñ mutí?*

Of course you drink (alcohol)?

SUS: *Muslim ni mí, mi ò n mutí*

I don't drink (alcohol); I am a muslim

IPO: *È káre o* (with a tone of mockery)

Well done oo

The comment of the IPO here in reaction to the response of the suspect that he does not drink (alcohol) in consonance with his religious belief, if taken at the face value without putting the context of the utterance into consideration, would be interpreted as a praise or a commendation, hence positive politeness strategy. However, both the suspect and the IPO understood this not to be so, considering the context of discourse. In fact, if this comment would be critically appraised, the IPO could be said to mean that, if the suspect was indeed a good muslim and as such would not take alcohol as he claimed, then how come he could not control his emotion, even to the point that he had to be sleeping with his daughter. In the Yoruba language, the expression *káre o* “well done or bravo” is inherently a positive politeness statement that shows commendation when an individual has done something worth commending. However, in the Yoruba culture, it could also be used to ridicule or rebuke somebody when the individual has done something that is considered unacceptable. Such is the case as observed above. The suspect understood this, being one that could be said to have communicative competence in the language, who knows when this statement could mean praise, condemnation or ridicule, to be a derisive comment on him by the IPO. However, he could not react back because he considered the IPO as being powerful than he was, given the institutional power platform upon which the IPO is operating.

CASE 13: Murder

Background Information: *This case involved a man, who, estimatedly, should be in his mid-forty's; a driver, alleged to have sent a driver colleague to his early grave.*

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Óyá, ẹ wólé*

Now, come in

SUS: (Entered with a hand-cuff in both hands)

IPO: *Ẹ jókòó*

Sit down

SUS: (Knelt down, perhaps having weighed the gravity of his “offence”)

IPO: Ah! mi ò ní kẹẹ kúnlẹ; mo ní kẹẹ jókòó ni

I did not ask you to kneel down; I asked you to sit

SUS: *Ẹ jẹ n wà báyí*

Let me remain like this

IPO: *Ẹ ẹ need láti worry, wón a yanjú gbogbo ẹ (winking at another IPO with a smile, a gesture noticed by the suspect)*

You don’t need to be worried, everything will be resolved.

SUS: (Remained on his knees) after which he was whisked away to another interrogation room, where the researcher could not access.

In this excerpt, the IPO offered the suspect a seat as soon as he was ushered in to the interrogation room; a gesture that ordinarily could be interpreted as a positive politeness strategy “*offering the other a gift*”. However, it became glaring that the IPO was not sincere about this later in the conversation where he told the suspect not to worry and that everything would be resolved, after which he winked at the IPO with him. The suspect insisted on remaining on his knees knowing the IPO did not mean what he said. In other words, he would not interpret the statement of the IPO to mean that the problem would indeed be resolved, as he saw him(the IPO) wink at the other IPO present. Whereas, if these statements were to be taken at the face value, they would be classified under positive politeness strategies: “*be optimistic, give gifts to H, and offer a promise*” as proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987). The manner in which the IPO made these seemingly polite statements revealed that he did not mean to make a promise to the suspect that everything would be resolved, neither was he optimistic that the matter would be resolved.

4.1.5 Withhold Politeness (Impoliteness Strategy)

The Withhold Politeness Impoliteness strategy operates where there is the absence of politeness work where ordinarily politeness would have been expected. For instance, not saying thank you to someone for an act of benevolence is naturally interpreted to mean deliberate impoliteness (Culpeper 1996: 8-9).

CASE 3: Threat to life

Background information: The suspect was reported to the police by a complainant who alleged the suspect had threatened to kill him over a parcel of land, which the suspect claimed his late father gave the father of the complainant on a compassionate ground.

Excerpt 1

IPO:Kí lẹ sọ fún un lórí phone?

What did you tell him on phone?

SUS: Mo ní báwo la ẹ fẹ ríra, simple thing

I simply asked how we were going to see each other, that is all

IPO: Kí lẹ fẹ rí i fún? Ẹ fẹ pa á?

What did you want to see him for ? You wanted to kill him?

SUS: (Trying to explain the relationship that exists between him and the complainant; how his (suspect) father gave out the controversial parcel of land) ^(int)

IPO:

Kí ló ẹlẹ bàbá yí tó o kàn n rojò,

ẹ mo wá bère history níbí bayí ni? Kí lo wá dé orí ilẹ wọn? Kí lo fẹ lo ta ilẹ wọn fún?.....

What is it with you old man that you are just narrating story; am I here to ask for story? What are you looking for on his land? Why did you want to sell his land?

IPO: Ọwọ ta ni bàba yín ti ralẹ?

From whom did your father buy the land?

SUS: Bàbá mi ò ra ilẹ

My father did not buy the land

IPO: Látòrun ni wọn ti gbélẹ lówó!

He brought the land from heaven!

SUS: Ibi tí wọn dé sí nìun

That was where he migrated to

IPO: *Sé o rí i pé òdòtò tí n yojú nísinyíí...tí wọn ò bá gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilè, wà á pa wọn!*

You can see that truth is coming out now... if he refuses to remove his building from the land, you will kill him!

In the italicised part of the excerpt above, the IPO who began his interaction with the suspect with the use of honorific pronoun “*e*” “*honorific you*”, used to show politeness in the Yoruba language, resorted to the use of “*o*” “*non honorific you*” in addressing him when he felt his continued showing of respect to the suspect would not allow him wield his power over him in the interaction. As soon as he saw the opportunity to withhold the use of the deference he had been showing to him, he capitalised on it to exert his power in the interaction. Perhaps the IPO could have continued relating to the suspect with the use of honorific pronouns, but for the notion he already had that the suspect was actually “guilty” of the allegation against him, and as a “criminal”, he did not deserve to be shown any form of respect or courtesy. The IPO further demonstrated his power over the suspect by accusing him he would have carried out the threat ‘to kill the complainant if he failed to heed his warning (to remove his building from the disputed land). The suspect, although obviously not happy about this statement, could not respond back nor protest, but was just looking despondent and helpless before the IPO.

Excerpt 2

IPO: *Kí ló dé tẹ̀ fì ní kí wọn gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilè?*

Why did you ask him to remove his building from the land?

SUS: *Ó ti wó lẹ̀yìn*

A part of it had collapsed(at the back)

IPO: *Kí ló kàn é nìbè? Ilé wọn wó; ǹnkan tó bá wu onílé ló lè sẹ. What is your own interest?.*

Alára ní ara ò ròdùn, ẹ̀ ní ó kú à̀sùn, ó kú à̀ìwo (●).

What is your problem with that; the landlord has the prerogative to decide what he would do about that. A burden bearer claims he is not experiencing any pains, why then are you unnecessarily sympathetic?

Excerpt 3

IPO: *O lè lọ agbo ilé, but kí lo wá lọ ilé tí wọn kó ilé sí, tí o tún fẹ̀ gbe e tà?*

*You can go to the family house but what are you looking for on the land
he(complainant) has built his house that you want to sell it?*

SUS: Mi ò gbe e tà

I don't intend to sell it

IPO: Meeting kí lo wá fẹ ba ẹ?.

What meeting did you want to hold with him?

An examination of the IPO's statement in the the bold part of the excerpt above reveals a serious "blow" on the face of the suspect. He questioned the interest of the suspect in the fact that a portion of the building on the disputed land had collapsed, using the *withhold politeness impoliteness strategy* by referring to the suspect with the use of non-honorific pronoun 'o' instead of the honorific ones such as 'ẹ'. He further made the matter worse with the Yoruba proverbial statement "Alára ní ara ò ro òun, ẹ ní ó kú àìsùn, ó kú àìwo" "One with a body ache has refused to admit to feeling pain, yet you are busy expressing unnecessary empathy", banging the table (●) at the suspect. Proverbs, according to Meider (1993:24), are a "short, generally known sentence (statement) of a folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals and traditional view in metaphorical, fixed and memorizable form which is handed down from generation to generation". Proverbs are used in the Yoruba language to admonish, explain hidden facts, give warnings, motivate, chastise or criticise unacceptable acts or behaviour. They are believed to be exclusive preserve of the elders. For any individual who understands the Yoruba language deeply, this is an insulting proverb that simply instructs whoever it is said to to mind his/her business, as such is seen as a meddlesome interloper. Apparently, the IPO resorted to the use of this proverb to criticise and condemn the action of the suspect who, by the IPO's estimation, had trespassed, prying into the complainant's affairs. Contrary to the practice in the Yoruba culture, the IPO did not show any deference to the old man before uttering the proverbial statement.

The IPO further accused the suspect of scheming to kill the complainant if the latter refused to heed his demand: *Şé o ri pé òdòtò ti ñ yojú nísinyí. tí wọn ò bá gbé ilée wọn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀, wà á pa wọn!* "If he refused to yield to your request, you will kill him". This is nothing short of an accusatory statement that portrays the suspect as a murderer. The IPO used the non-honorific pronoun to address the suspect here; a withhold politeness impoliteness strategy deliberately employed by the IPO to reduce the suspect to nothingness before him. This further attests to the

fact that IPOs maximize their power in police-suspect interactions while the power of suspects is minimized and reduced to nothingness. Also, the fact that the IPO addressed the suspect like a criminal is abuse of power, as it is not within the jurisdiction of the police to condemn or convict a suspect, who is considered innocent until the court decides otherwise.

CASE 14 Defilement 2 (incest)

Background Information: *The suspect is a 48-year old man, a surveyor by profession, who was reported by his daughter to have been sleeping with her without her consent.*

Excerpt 1

IPO: *Bàbá!! ẹ̀ mèlòó ni ẹ̀ ti bá ọmọ yî sùn?* (↗)

Baba, how many times have you slept with the girl?

SUS: *Mí ò kà á*

I did not count it

IPO: *Okay, kí ló mú ẹ̀ dé bè to ń báa sùn?*

What came over you that you are sleeping with your daughter?

.....
SUS: *SUS: Silent.. à fi bí èdì*

it was like a spell

IPO: *Èdì wo! Tó o bá sọ pé èdì, màá fọ́ kíńí mọ́ ẹ̀! Èdì ò se mú ẹ̀ lọ sílé aṣẹwó?*

What spell! If you say it was a spell, I will hit you with an object. Why didn't the spell spur you into visiting a brothel?

SUS: *Ọlórún nìkan lóyẹ́, walahi...*

Honestly, only God understands

IPO:

int

Ọlórún wo lóyẹ́? (☺)

What did you mean God understands?

At the beginning of this excerpt, the IPO showed deference to the suspect with the use of honorific pronoun 'ẹ̀' in deference to his age. However, after this introductory part of the interaction, the IPO resorted to the use of non-honorific pronouns, *withhold politeness impoliteness strategy*, to exert his authority in the exchange. The IPO combined this strategy with a raised his voice to overpower the suspect. He used 'o' and 'ẹ̀' to refer to him as against the 'ẹ̀' he started the conversation with. The IPO even threatened to hit the suspect with an object

for ascribing his hideous act to a spell, perhaps being cast on him by his enemies. It is commonplace in the Yoruba world to describe an individual as being under a spell when such does things or commits acts that are considered sacrilegious. This is because anyone in his right senses is not expected to commit such acts. The IPO went further to hiss at the suspect to condemn his ‘sacrilegious’ act. Hissing in the Yoruba language and culture is done to show displeasure, annoyance or contempt at someone or something. The IPO did this to treat the suspect with contempt. However, the suspect, being powerless in this context, could not hiss back at him. This is another clear demonstration of power and power abuse by IPOs in police-suspect interaction.

CASE 23: Assault and Malicious Damage

Background Information: The suspects were 8 in number. They had been alleged by the complainant to have assaulted him and maliciously destroyed the foundation he had done a disputed peace of land. After the general interaction the IPOs had with the suspects at their arrival, they were called upon one after the other for interrogation/questioning. We were able to capture the interactions involving five of them.

INTERACTION 2

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?

What is your name?

SUS: OOO

IPO: Ibo lẹ ñ gbé?

Where do you live?

SUS: No 333, CCC

IPO: Kí ni phone number yín?

What is your phone number?

SUS: 111111111

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni yìn?

Where are you from?

IPO: *Ṣé ẹ mọ àwọn tí ó kọ ìwé yìí?*

Do you know the people who wrote this petition?

SUS: *Mo má a n gbọ orúkọ wọn ní oko ni*

I only do hear the name in our farm

IPO: *Ẹ ẹ mọ ọ́n?*

You don't know him?

SUS: *Mi ò mọ ọ́n*

I don't know him

IPO: (has the feeling that the suspect is not saying the truth) *Tí ẹ bá fẹ sọrò, kí ẹ wà careful nńkan tí ẹ má a sọ, torí nńkan tí ẹ bá sọ lè ní implication. Ṣé kí n kọ ọ síbè pé ẹ ẹ mọ ọ́n?*

When you want to talk, you have to be careful what you say because whatever you say can have implications. Should I write it down that you do not know him?

SUS: *Mi ò mọ ọ́n*

I don't know him

IPO: *Ṣé o mọ ẹni tí ó kọ ìwé yìí tàbí o ò mọ ọ́n?*

Do you know the writer of this petition or you don't know him?

SUS: *Mi ò mọ ọ́n*

I don't know him

IPO: *O ò mọ ọ́n?*

You don't know him?

SUS: *Mi ò mọ ọ́n*

I don't know him

IPO: *Ó wá dárúkọ ẹ pé ní ojúọ Sátidé yẹn pé ẹyin àti àwọn ìyókù lọ ba ilé òun jé*

He just mentioned your name that on that Saturday, you and your colleagues destroyed his land

SUS: *Rára o*

No

IPO: *Kí ló wá ṣẹlẹ ní ojúọ Sátidé yẹn?*

What now happened on that day?

SUS: *Bí èmi ẹ wà yìí, mi ò kí n ba nńkan èyàn jé*

As I am, I don't destroy people's things

IPO: (angrily) *Sh..... gbàgbé gbogbo ìyẹn, kí ló ṣẹlẹ ní ojúọ Sátidé yẹn?*

Forget all that, what happened on that Saturday?

SUS: Èmí lọ oko ni mo bá pastor níbè

I went to the farm and met the pastor there

IPO: Ago mélòó *lo* lọ oko tí *o* fi bá pastor?

What time did you go to the farm and met the pastor

In the excerpt above, the tempo of the discourse changed the moment the IPO perceived he needed to assert his authority to get the truth from the suspect, having sensed the suspect was not saying the truth when asked if he knew the complainant. In the beginning of the excerpt, the IPO was showing deference to the suspect in respect for his age. He was interacting with him with the use of honorific pronouns, usually employed in the Yoruba language to show respect to the elderly ones. However, in the latter part, he withheld the use of this device to assert himself in the interaction. This phenomenon portrays the IPO as the powerful participant here, and whatever respect or deference he accorded the suspect was a privilege and not his right. This position became apparent in the concluding statement of the IPO in the interaction, as will be presented below:

IPO: Eh, stand up! (↗) Sit on the floor. Motor park lẹ rọ pé ẹ wà ni (Do you think you are in the motor park)? If you learnt driving, is this place a motor park?

SUS: (Stands up in obedience to the command issued by the IPO)

IPO: (Talking to one of the suspects) *Ọgbéni yẹn paró. Ko deserve to be treated with respect.*

That man lied; he does not deserve to be treated with respect

4.2 Bald on Record with Redress (Negative Politeness)

There are very few instances of the use of this strategy by the police in police-suspect discourse. This manifests in form of minimised imposition on the suspect by the Investigating Police Officers. As pointed out by Brown and Levinson (1987), minimisation of imposition is one of the strategies employed to achieve negative politeness. Instances of this found in the data are presented below:

CASE 1

Excerpt 1

IPO: So what happened to her account she has been operating with you.....?

SUS: (He) usually goes to $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{int} \\ \text{int} \end{array} \right]$

IPO: I am coming, record tí woman yèn keep shows that your signature is on the signed document

Wait, the record kept by that woman reveals your signature is on the signed document

SUS: *Silent*

IPO: *See, this is me and you. Òkú ò kì í fara pamọ́ f'èni tó má a sín in.* What did you fenefit (from that deal)?

See, this is you and I, the dead does not hide itself from whoever is going to bury it. What did you benefit (from the deal)?

In the excerpt above, the IPO decided to reduce the tension that had already been built up in the suspect in the previous lines of their discourse as an alternative method or strategy of getting the information he needed from the suspect. This he did with the statement “*See, this is me and you. Òkú ò kì í fara pamọ́ f'èni tó má a sín.* “This is between us, just as the dead does not hide itself from the person that will carry out its burial rites, tell me what you benefitted from the deal”. With this, he opined the suspect would see him as a confidant and as such further confess to him. The IPO made recourse to the use of this proverbial statement to mitigate the earlier threat to the suspect’s face, since the suspect had eventually agreed he committed the crime that brought him to the custody of the police.

Another strategy employed by the IPO to achieve negative politeness is indirectness (following Brown and Levinson’s position 1987) in form of passive construction. This is presented below:

CASE 1

Excerpt 2

IPO: You explain here, the name of that person and details of her account, *because I was made to understand you have your own personal bank outside where you are working.*

SUS: Our personal account as how?

IPO: Apart from (mention the name of the bank)

SUS: That is what I have

IPO: Listen to me; *I was told you have another bank (where you keep the money you collect from your customers)*

In the excerpt above, the IPO employed the use of the passive construction noted above to mitigate the weight of the threat an active construction would have had on the face of the suspect. In other words, the IPO would not be seen as accusing the suspect as the statement was presented like it was not coming from him “*I was told.....*” when in actual fact our observation revealed this was the proposition of the IPO. If he had wanted to threaten the face of the suspect unmitigated, he could have been direct with the active counterpart of the noted passive construction as follows: *You have a bank outside where you keep customers’ money*

Also, in some other situations, the IPOs employed the “state the FTA as a general rule” strategy proposed by Brown and Levinson as one of the strategies for achieving Negative politeness in their discourse with suspects. This is evident in the data below:

CASE 1

Excerpt 3

IPO: *You know all you people were doing then is not within the ethics of the bank, uhn!*

SUS: Yes

IPO: *It is not within the ethics of the bank for you and your manager to be exchanging (customers’) money without the authority of the bank*

SUS: Actually, ìgbà tí mo pè é, ó promise

Actually, when I called him, he promised

IPO:

(int)

Uhn!!!

In the excerpt above, rather than the IPO condemning the action of the suspect (and that of his accomplice) in unequivocal terms (directly), by which he would be threatening his face bald on record without redress, he made use of the state the FTA as a general rule to mitigate the threat to the suspect's face; by which the suspect would agree and concede to the fact that his action was wrong, as an individual who knows the *rules* and *ethics* of the banking system. This message was apparently clear to the suspect as he eventually conceded to having done something wrong.

4.3 Bald on Record with Redress (Positive Politeness)

Observation shows that this strategy is employed by the police in interactions between IPOs and elderly suspects generally, apparently in deference to their age (as is the practice in the Yoruba language and culture); while interacting with high-profile suspects, and sparingly while interacting with low-profile suspects, who “cooperate” with them. It is however perpetually employed by suspects to appeal to the face of the IPOs. This is evident in the excerpt below. In a bit to clearly pursue the claim made above, the excerpt here is divided into three: A, B and C; the first showing how the IPO was wreaking havoc on the face of the suspect, not knowing his personality and status, B showing how the suspect attempted to asset himself in the discourse and C showing how the tempo of the exchange changed when the suspect had finally asserted himself.

CASE 11: Obtaining Goods and Credit on False Pretence

Background Information: The suspect here was an Alhaji, a businessman who deals in grains for feeding livestock. He was said to have collected goods on credit on false pretence.

Excerpt A

IPO: *Şé wón ti gbòjà fún yín tẹ̀lẹ̀?*

Has he supplied you goods before?

SUS: *Kìí ẹ́ first; wón ti gbòjà fún mi tẹ̀lẹ̀, but kì n ẹ́ pé èmi ni wón gbé e fún directly, ẹni tí wón gbòjà fún ló n gbe fún mi....*

That was not the first; he has been supplying goods to me before, but not directly; it has always been through a third party..

IPO: int. Sh!!!, Alhaji (●)

SUS: Yes please

Excerpt B

IPO: Tell us how you met the three of them

SUS: *È fẹ̀ wà aggresive sí mi* (You want to be aggressive to me), and I don't deserve that. *Yes. If you know me very well, if you ask the people that know me, you will know I don't deserve this.* (His phone rang and was discussing another transaction with the caller, after which he continued with his statement)

Excerpt C

IPO: *Are you through sir? Àbí kí ñ fún un yín lómi?*

Are you through with the statement or should I offer you water?

SUS: *Olóun yòd ní fẹ́ yín. È mu wá. È ri pé mo ti ñ sweat gan, mo ní ifún pá*

God will love you too. Bring it. You see I am already sweating, because I am hypertensive

IPO: *(Offered the suspect water) Ó yẹ kẹ ma calm down ni anything tí ẹ bá ñ ẹ*

You are supposed to be calm whatever you are doing

SUS: *Mi ò experience irú eléyí rí*

I never experienced this kind before

IPO: *Kò sí wàhálà*

There is no problem

SUS: *Ó da*

Okay

IPO: *Bàbá, ẹ ẹ maa je àşáró?*

Baba, will you eat porridge?

SUS: *Yí ó da fún yín, wàláhì, ẹ yà mí lẹnu gan*

It will be well with you. True to God, you really surprise me.

A careful examination of this excerpt is very insightful. In the **A** part of the excerpt, the IPO, not knowing the status of the suspect, was somewhat aggressive to him (as voiced out by the

suspect). In the **B** part, the suspect tried to save himself from the hand of the IPO by pointing out to him he did not deserve the ridiculous treatment meted out to him by the IPO, considering his status and personality (being an accomplished businessman). This perhaps sent a signal to the IPO who had to change the tempo of the interaction to redress the threat he had done to the face of the suspect, as shown in the **C** part. To achieve this redress, the IPO employed the “offer/give a gift to the hearer”: *Àbí kí ñ fún yín lómi?* “Or should I offer you water?”, *Bàbá, sè ẹ maa jẹ àşáró?* “Baba, will you eat porridge?”; “be optimistic”: *Kò sí wàhálà* “There is no problem”; “Exaggerate interest, approval, sympathy to H” : *Ó yẹ kẹ ma calm down ni anything tí ẹ bá ñ sẹ* “You are supposed to be calm whatever you are doing”. He equally allowed the suspect pick his phone when it rang; a privilege low-profile suspects did not enjoy, as observed during the data collection. The suspect equally employed the use of positive politeness strategy to appeal to the IPO where he prayed for him(the IPO) thus: *Ọlòun yòò nífẹ yín* “God will love you” . He also referred to the IPO, whom he was apparently much older than. with the use of the honourific pronoun *ẹ* (honourific you).

Another case in point that shows status influences the way IPOs employ language during police-suspect interaction was the case of a barrister that was arrested over an undisclosed crime or offence. Having met with the IPO in charge to indicate my interest in the case, the IPO later got back to me that the OC (Officer in Charge) of the case ordered him to take the lawyer-suspect to his personal office to take his interview, “considering his personality”. What can then be deduced from this therefore is the fact that high-profile individuals enjoy some level of preferential treatment from IPOs during interrogation, while low-profile individuals are subjected to demeaning conditions.

What struck me the most was the use of the word “interview” when the said IPO was whispering the order of the OC into my ears as follows: “*Ògá mi ní kí n sẹ interview yẹn nínú office òun because of the personality of the person involved*” “My boss ordered me to conduct the interview in his office, considering the personality of the person involved”.

Similarly, we noticed a situation akin to the one presented above. There was a case that involved an engineer who was repeatedly referred to as Alhaji in an interaction that took place in the

office of the SO (Station Officer) which we were denied access to, as we were not allowed to record the interaction. However, we were able to catch a glimpse of all that transpired through the open door of the SO's office which was an extension of the interrogation hall. Apparently, the interaction revolved round some parcels of land which the Alhaji gave a surveyor as compensation for a particular job done, which later generated controversies. In the office of the SO was a set of executive chairs to which the Alhaji suspect was ushered. What transpired in the room could be best described as an interview in which the suspect, on the executive chair offered him, interacted with the SO, one IPO and the said surveyor. He chatted with the officers freely as though they were friends. This was a picture that was never witnessed in cases involving low-profile suspects, who sometimes sat on plastic chairs, wooden benches and most times on the bare floor, depending on the mood of the IPOs.

CASE 4

Excerpt 1

IPO: Ta lo fún ní number ọmọ yẹn?

Whom did you give that girl's number?

SUS: (Mumbled the name of the person but not clear to the IPO)

IPO: Tani?

Who?

SUS: (Mentioned the name again)

IPO: Now, ẹ sòrò yẹn lójú...(trying to remember the name of the second suspect) (int)

Now, say what you just said in the presence of

SUS: (Reminded the IPO)

IPO: *Very good of you; tó bá yá nísìn yí, bí iyà bá n jẹ yín ẹ ẹ ní mọ ẹ̀ẹ̀ tẹ ti sẹ tí iyà fi n jẹ yín*

Very good of you, now if you start suffering, you won't remember you are reaping the evil that you sowed.

Following Brown and Levinson's school of thought, the situation above (in italics) is seen as an instance of positive politeness, that is, "make the hearer feel good" or "praise the hearer". The IPO here employed this strategy to commend the suspect for reminding him of the information

he was trying hard to recollect. This actually points to the fact that IPOs occasionally appeal to the positive face of low-profile suspects, especially in instances where the suspect gives his/her cooperation to them, giving them adequate information that would aid their investigation activities.

CASE 20: Armed Robbery/ Defamation of Character

Background Information: The suspect, an engineer, was accused by the complainant of being among the armed robbery gang that robbed her on 2nd May 2013 at the Lagos-Ibadan express way. According to what was inferred in the course of the interaction, the complainant walked up to the suspect in a church programme in Ota and held on to him, alleging him of being a member of the robbery group that had earlier robbed her, afterwhich the matter was brought to Iyaganku

Excerpt 1

IPO: Your name sir

SUS: I am XXX

IPO: What is the name of your town?

SUS: XX

IPO: Your date of birth?

.....

IPO: Why did she arrest you?

SUS: In fact, I am just waiting for this matter to be over so that I rearrest her too. I would have retaliated but I did not want to break the law

IPO: Thank you for not breaking the law

IPO: Where did she arrest you?

SUS: At XXY

In this excerpt, the IPO had, from the very beginning, accessed the suspect and realised he was well-informed, hence the less manifestation of interrogative elements inherent in the impoliteness strategies witnessed in cases involving low-profile suspects. The suspect was very articulate and presented himself as one who knew the law, hence his resort not to do anything injurious to the complainant whom he claimed accused him wrongly. This position is apparent in

the bold part of the excerpt. The IPO here employed the positive politeness strategy of making the other feel good or honoured where he thanked him for not breaking the law. However, this is not usually the case in cases involving low-profile individuals. From our observation, what could have followed the statement made by the suspect here if it were a low-profile one would have been acts of molestation like slapping, abuse or literal beating. But this could not be done to the suspect here, considering his status.

Excerpt 2

IPO: This woman said you look like one of the robbers on that day

SUS: Is that a case, Oga?

IPO: Yes, it is

SUS: *I just feel I should kill her*

IPO: *You can't do that or else....*

int

SUS: In fact...[int.]

IPO: Madam, you see, you need to tell us your intentions about the case.

IPO: Mr Man, are you not guilty of the allegation?

SUS: Oga, I am not sir

The picture painted in the excerpt 1 is further reinforced here where the suspect reacted he felt like killing the complainant who “accused him wrongly”. The response of the IPO to this statement is devoid of the act of intimidation that usually characterised IPO’s dealings with low-profile suspects. Considering the weight of the utterance, if it were from a low-profile suspect, the IPO could have capitalised on it to conclude the suspect was a criminal, hence should be treated as such. In many of our observed cases involving low-profile suspects, statements that are not as sensitive as this would attract severe punishment and verbal assaults from the IPOs. The suspect even interrupted the speech of the IPO in the latter part of the interaction without being “punished”.

CASE 29: Allegation of Fraud and Forgery

Background Information: *The suspect is in his late 50's. He is a certified surveyor and estate management, who schooled both in Ghana and Nigeria. He speaks impeccable English. Prior to the commencement of their verbal interaction, the IPO offered his own seat to the suspect, while he (the IPO) stood up. The IPO later sat on the table next to him while the interaction was still on-going.*

IPO: (Hands over the confessional statement paper to the suspect and *offers him his own seat*)

SUS: (Reads the cautionary statements aloud). If you ask me a question and I refuse to respond, what will you do to me? Hope you are not going to force me.

IPO: *At all*

SUS: Okay (hands the paper back to the IPO)

IPO: *Thank you sir*

SUS: Let me read the petition first before I make any response (the suspect remembers he needs to call his lawyer but he is not with his phone)

IPO: *Let me give you my phone to call him*

SUS: Don't worry. I will do that later

SUS: I live in Ibadan

IPO: Where do you live?

IPO: Where in Ibadan?

SUS: XXX

IPO: *Thank you sir*. How many wives do you have?

SUS: Why did you ask for that?

IPO: Because it is part of your biography. We need to know because some people do deny their statements

SUS: Okay, 1

IPO: How many issues?

SUS: How is that related to the issue here? I don't want to get my children involved in this

IPO: Oga, do you know YYY?

SUS: Yes

IPO: How do you know him?

SUS: I know him as an agent. You know, I am not denying that he paid

IPO: *Of course, I know you. I know you very well now.*

SUS: I don't want to write my statement in reaction to his (the complainant) petition, because I don't want to be defensive. I need to first of all give the background information. Now, I will explain what I want to write.

IPO: Alright sir

SUS: (Continues with the writing of his confessional statement)

IPO: You want to tell me the documents are not forged?

SUS: Yes sir

IPO: Are you now telling me you did not connive with those vendors?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Okay, that is what I am trying to confirm before we go to madam (his boss)

SUS: (Completes writing his confessional statement)

IPO: Oyá sign

IPO: You will assist us

SUS: In what way

IPO: To call them (other suspects mentioned in the petition of the complainant)

A critical examination of this excerpt confirms the central idea accentuated in this work: class or social status plays a significant role in police-suspect interaction. The suspect here, being a well-informed high-profile individual, got a treatment that was devoid of harassment, intimidation, coercion, and humiliation, elements that characterise impoliteness, from the IPO. In fact, virtually all the phenomena that Brown and Levinson argued mark positive politeness are witnessed in this excerpt. For instance, the IPO offered the suspect his own seat to sit, while he himself was standing up for the most part of the interaction (offer H a gift), promised not to force the suspect to write anything if he chose not to (offer promise and avoid disagreement), appreciating him for his cooperation 'thank you sir' (appreciate the H), among others. All these point to the fact that IPOs do not handle high-profile suspects the way they handle low-profile suspects. High-profile suspects are accorded respect, shown deference and treated with courtesy, while low-profile suspects are subjected to interrogation, with its attendant features such as intimidation, abuse, threat and molestation; all of which culminate in power abuse on the part of IPOs.

CHAPTER FIVE
DATA ANALYSIS II

5.0 Discourse-cum-Power Markers in Police-Suspect Interaction/Discourse

As explained in chapter one, social power is defined in terms of the *control* exercised by a group or an organisation (or its members) over the *actions* and/or the *minds* of (the members of) another group, thus limiting the freedom of action of the others, or influencing their knowledge, attitudes or ideologies (Clegg, 1989; Lukes, 1974; 1986; Wrong, 1979). In social or public discourse, power distribution is determined by access to valued social resources, such as wealth, jobs, status, or indeed, a preferential access to public discourse and communication. As evident in the data collected, police power and dominance over and above suspects in police-suspect discourse has its basis in the institutional power of the institution. This institutional power is marked by the police's use of linguistic and paralinguistic tools such as questions, interruptions, abuse, threat, intonation and kinesics during interrogations. These devices are stairs the police climb to power during interrogations. The order in which these are used is represented in figure 13 later in this work.

5.1 Questions (Interrogation)

Observation of the data gathered for this work has revealed that the greatest linguistic tool or weapon the police employ in establishing their institutional authority over suspects is question; by which nature could be regarded as interrogation. Several scholars have attempted to describe the concept of question as it operates in police-suspect discourse. For instance, in the opinion of Stygall (1994: 120), "questions are a powerful tool the police interrogators use to control the flow of discourse, requesting particular information in a certain fashion, presenting the story in the order they impose, which does not necessarily follow the temporal succession of the actual events". Borrowing a leaf from Stygall (1994) as quoted above, Farinde (2011) asserts that interrogation is an asymmetrical dialogue, which denotes the fact that the goals and methods of argumentation used by the one side are quite different from those on the other side. In the course of an interrogation, the aim of the questioner or interrogator is to elicit any kind of information needed for some purpose from the respondent, while the aim of the interrogated or respondent is to pursue his own interest.

In the opinion of Walton (2002), interrogation is different from the basic type of information-seeking dialogue in that in a normal information-seeking dialogue, the parties involved are freely engaging in the dialogue and the one party is not the “prisoner” of the other; but this is not so with interrogation. Walton further posits that it is typical of a normal information-seeking dialogue for participants to be free to ask questions, put forward their arguments and opinions. No form of pressure, coercion or force is coming from either party involved in the dialogue. But in an interrogative dialogue, the respondent is seen more like the “prisoner” of the interrogator.

As revealed by the data collected, Investigating Police Officers dominate police-suspect discourse with questions. This points to the police’s domination of the interaction between them and suspects. The IPOs can ask any type of question, ranging from declarative questions to choice, and wh- questions. All these are highlighted below. Our focus here is on the italicised parts of the excerpts presented.

5.1.1 Declarative Questions

Declarative questions are such questions loaded or pregnant with the questioner’s views, positions, ideas and proposition, aimed at indicting or convincing the respondent. They are very powerful questions because they contain the proposition of the questioner (Farinde, 2011 : 11). These questions are employed by the IPOs to indict suspects, particularly, low-profile suspects. Here are some examples as found in the data collected.

CASE 1

IPO: *You know all you people were doing was not within the ethics of the bank, uhn?*

SUS: Yes

CASE 3:

IPO: Kí lẹ fẹ ri fún? E sòrò now bàbà

What did you want to see him? Talk now old man!

SUS: Báyàn bá ti jọ ríra tipé, èyàn lè pè lórí phone

Since it is quite sometime we last spoke, I deemed it fit to call him on the phone

IPO: Ehn, Kí lẹ fẹ ri fún? *E fẹ pá?*

Why did you want to see him? You wanted to kill him?

IPO: L'átòrun ni wòn ti gbé ilẹ̀ lówó!

He brought while coming from heaven!

SUS: Ibi tí wòn dé sí nìun

That was where they settled on their arrival

IPO: *Şé o ri pé òótó ti yojú nísín yí. O fẹ́ kí wòn gbé ilẹ̀ wòn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀; tí wòn ò bá gbé ilẹ̀ wòn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀, wà á pa wòn?*

You can now see that the truth has been revealed now; you want him to remove his building from the and if he fails to do that, you will kill him

SUS: Kò sí ibi tí mo kó sí pé n ó pa lágbájá, èmi ò pa anybody

I never wrote it anywhere that I wanted to kill anyone.

The bold parts of the excerpt above are some examples of declarative questions noticed in the data collected.

5.1.2 Choice Questions

Choice questions are otherwise known as polar or Yes/No questions. They are questions that require the respondent to oscillate between two options of yes and no. The police make use of this type of question in police-suspect discourse to limit the choice of response of suspects. Such questions are also used by the police to prevent suspects from deviating from the subject of discourse. Examples from the data collected are presented below:

CASE 1:

IPO: *Ògbéni, ògbéni, all these things are nothing. Şé ó sign sínú ìwé kànkán pé òun gbowó lówó ẹ?*

Mr man, Mr man, all these things are nothing. Did he sign any document that he collected any money from you?

SUS: No

IPO: Dáhùn, time n ló

Answer me I am running out of time

CASE 3

IPO: *Bàbá, is it true that you are after his life?*

SUS: It's not true

IPO: Ehn!

SUS: It is not true

IPO: *Bàbá, ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta?* A ma kọ letter sí àwọn network láti find out o, tẹ bá paró a má a get a dẹ ma charge yín sí court; a má a gbéyín lọ sílé ẹjó. ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta? (raising his voice)

Old man, did you call him two days ago or not? We are going to contact the telecommunications outfits and find out, and if it is discovered that you are lying, you will be charged to court

IPO: *Is he a blood relation?*

SUS (Not being able to continue with the discourse in English, he requested if he could switch to Yoruba. The request was granted by the IPO) Relationship kan ò sí ju pé èmi ò ta ilée wọn

The only relationship between us is that I don't intend to sell his house

CASE 5

IPO: *Olè pórířirířì, irú olè wo ni tì ẹ?*

There are different kinds of thieves, what category is yours?

SUS: (Silence)

IPO: *But irin yìí, ẹ ẹ iwọ lo dógbón fipamó síbè ni?*

But this iron, were you the one that cunningly kept it there?

SUS: *Èmi kó mo dógbón fipamó síbè*

I was not the person that kept it there

IPO: *Şé mechanic nìwọ?*

Are you a mechanic?

SUS: *Bèni sir*

Yes sir

IPO: *O ti kọşé, o dè ti şe freedom?*

You have learnt the work and you have got your freedom?

SUS: *Bèni sir*

Yes sir

CASE 18: Gang Rape

Background Information: The suspect is a twenty-nine year old young man, accused of joining his friends to forcefully sleep with his girlfriend

IPO: Condition wo lo bá ọmọ yẹn?

What condition did you meet the lady?

SUS: Skirt wà ní ìdí è

She had her skirt on

IPO: *Şé ó sùn sílè ni tàbí ó jóòkó?*

Was she lying down or sitting?

SUS: (Silent)

The italicised parts of the excerpts above are few examples of the choice questions observed in the collected data.

5.1.3 Wh- Questions

Wh- questions, restricted or non-restricted, are questions usually posed at suspects by the police for specific facts and information. They are introduced by wh- words as where, who, when, why, how, and what. This type of question is the one that is mostly employed by police officers in the course of their interaction with suspects. Some examples are presented below:

CASE 2

IPO: Şé ẹ mọ X?

Do you know X?

SUS: Mo mọ ó

I know him

IPO: *Bóo lẹ şe mọ ọn?*

How did you know him?

IPO: *Lát'ọdún wo?*

Since when?

SUS: Ó tọdún méta nísìn yí

It's about three years now

IPO: *Níbo ni ilè yẹn wà?*

Where is the land?

SUS: Arúgbó XYZ

IPO: *Kí ló wá dé tẹ́jọ́ wá bèrẹ̀ nígbà tẹ́ ti talẹ̀ fún wọn?*

Why did dispute spring up when you sold the land to them?

SUS: Ehn! Àwa kó ò, ìyẹn íń ẹ́jọ́ àwa ínt.

It's not us; that is not our fault

IPO:

Aha! ẹ́bí ẹ̀yin lẹ̀ nilẹ̀?

Aha! but you are the land owner?

CASE 3

IPO: *What actually is causing the dispute?*

SUS: I don't know the reason.

IPO: *How is this man to you?*

IPO: *Kí lo wá fẹ́ tà?*

What then did you want to sell?

SUS: Èmi ò ta ònkànkà

I am not selling anything

IPO: *Kí lẹ́ wá ń jà fún?*

What then are you fighting for?

SUS : Èmi rẹ̀ ò jà

He and I are not fighting

CASE 18

I.P.O.: *Ọmọ ọdún mélòó ní ẹ́?*

How old are you?

SUS: 29

IPO: *Işé wo lò ń ẹ?*

What job do you do?

SUS: Àwọn tó ń ẹ aluminium

Those who make a

IPO: *Ibo lò ò gbé?*

Where do you leave?

SUS: (mentioned the area)

CASE 20: Street Fight/Public Disturbance

Background Information; The suspect was said to have been involved in a street fight that led to the beating and maltreatment of a police officer

IPO: *When the problem started, where were you?*

SUS: Wọn ní jà

They were fighting

IPO: *Who were the people fighting?*

SUS: Àwọn ọmọ àdúgbò náà nì

The people living on our street

IPO: *What story did you hear?*

The italicised parts of the excerpts above are few examples of the use of wh-questions in police-suspect discourse.

These question forms and types are part of the linguistic weapons Investigating Police Officers employ to assert their institutional authority in police-suspect interaction.

5.2 Paralanguage

The concept of paralinguistics is such that has attracted the attention of scholars in language study as well as other related fields, and as such has been viewed from different perspectives. It is however worthy of note that it is a concept that derives from the term paralanguage, defined in terms of parameters like pitch, loudness, speed, pause, rhythm, etc. As maintained by Neuliep (1957), paralanguage is a means by which people communicate their emotional state, veracity and sincerity. In their own view, however, Roach et al. (1998) view paralinguistic features as those employed deliberately or intentionally by the speaker (for a particular purpose) as opposed to what they term non-linguistic features that cannot be used intentionally; such as age, sex, state

of health, etc. For clarity, below is a table on some classifications of paralinguistic information in speech in the literature.

Table 1: Scholars’ Classification of Paralinguistic Information

Scholarly Works	Paralinguistic Information
Laver (1980)	Affective information
Linblad (1992)	Emotions, attitudes, age, sex, dialect, sociolect, etc.
Marasek (1997)	Non-linguistic and non-verbal information; attitude, emotions, dialect, sociolect
Mixdorf (2002)	Speaker attitude, intention, dialect, sociolect
Quast (2001)	Momentary changes, whispering, emotions
Roach (1998)	Intentional; voice qualities (modal, falsetto, breathy voice, etc) and voice qualifications (non-linguistic vocal effects; sobbing, laughing and tremor, etc.
Traunmuller (2001,2001)	Organic; age, sex, health,and expressive; emotions, attitude, and adaptation to environment

Central to the works of scholars whose views on paralinguistics are tabulated above is the functional use of non-linguistic phenomena as voice in human interaction. Generally speaking therefore, paralanguage includes verbal and non-verbal means of communication like kinetics. This concept is one of the many “weapons” employed by the police to overwhelm suspects and as such exert their institutional power over them during interrogations. Examples of these found in our data are raised voice, table banging, hissing, and stern (angry) look. They are used to instill fear in the mind of suspects. The frequency of the use of paralanguage and all other power markers identified will be presented in a table later in this section.

5.3 Interruptions

Another device that demonstrates asymmetrical distribution of power by the police and suspects in police-suspect discourse is interruption. Interruptions are an important element in the interactive character of discourse (Grosz and Sidner, 1986). Yang (2008) opines that in discourse, the expression of cognitive state and co-occurring representation of topic hierarchy are accomplished simultaneously with the mutual and cooperative negotiating of the discourse process by

participants. To this effect, when participants encounter an asymmetry in their respective informational or expressive needs, it is often through the use of interruptions that these needs are satisfied or achieved. Yang further states that, while interruptions can be locally disruptive to discourse flow, they play a significant role in the overall flow of discourse by bringing about a mutual accommodation of interests and knowledge states of each participant. He further argues that interruptions are situations in which one person intends to continue speaking, but is forced by the other person to stop speaking, at least temporarily, or the continuity or regularity of that person's speech is disrupted. From this position of Yang, it becomes obvious that interruption has embedded in it three pertinent components viz intention of the main speaker to continue, entrance of the other person into the conversation, and disruption or stopping of the main speaker, at least temporarily.

French and Local (1986) classify interruptions into two: Cooperative and Competitive interruptions. Cooperative interruptions occur when one speaker wants to support, corroborate or reinforce the point(s) being made by the main speaker without disrupting the main speaker's continuation. This type of interruption is often in form of short commentaries or clarifying questions. This is not attested to in our data (see appendix). Competitive interruptions on the other hand occur when one speaker makes an attempt or attempts to hijack the floor of discourse by making his or her own remarks a higher priority over the main speaker's speech, even when the main speaker still intends to continue with his speech. Competitive interruptions are typically high in pitch and amplitude (Yang, 2008). Such is the situation observed in our data. IPOs are observed to be fond of interrupting the speech of suspects in the course of interrogations. In fact, this occurs several times in our data. The police make use of this device to disagree, shut down and sometimes hijack the floor of discourse from suspects. Consider the following examples from the collected data.

IPO: Kí lẹ fẹ ri fún? Ẹ fẹ pá?

What did you want to see him? You want to kill him?

SUS: (Trying to explain the relationship that exists between him and the complainant; how his (suspect) father gave out the controversial parcel of land)

IPO:

int
Kí ló ẹlẹ̀ bàbá yìí tó o

kàn n rojọ, ẹ́ mo wá bẹ̀rẹ̀ history níbí bayì ni? Kí lo wá dórí ilẹ̀ wọn? Kí lo fẹ̀ lẹ̀ ta ilẹ̀

wọn fún?.....

What happened you this old man that you narrating story; am I here to ask for history?What are you looking for on his land? Why did you want to sell his land?

SUS: Oun tó jẹ kí n sọ bẹ ẹ ni pé

The reason I said that was that

int

IPO:

Ẹ máà sòrò; ó dígbá tí n bá sòrò tán

Don't talk; until I finish talking

SUS: Ẹ máà gbọ

Hear me out

int

IPO: Ẹ gbọ tẹ̀mi (↗)

SUS: Yes sir

CASE 16: Murder

Background Information: A case of a fifty year old man who was alleged to have macheted his grandparents to death

IPO: Ṣàlàyé òkàn tó ṣẹ̀lẹ̀

Explain what happened

SUS: Wọn sọ pé kí n wá gẹrun

They asked me to come barb my hair

int.

IPO:

Taló sọ pé ko wá gẹrun?

Who asked you to come barb?

SUS: Màma

Old woman

5.4 (Verbal) Abuse

Edmonton Police Service (2015) describes verbal abuse as a form of abusive behaviour involving the use of language (criticizing, name-calling, blaming, etc). It is a pattern of behaviour that can seriously interfere with one's positive emotional development and over time, can lead to significant detriment to one's self-esteem, emotional well-being and physical state. Verbal abuse refers to the use of language as a means to control or subordinate another

person for either self-gratification or to impose one's view or will on another or to gain an unfair advantage in resolving a dispute. Verbal abuse involves one party typically causing more distress to the other party, and causing insecurities in that party, typically for the purpose of exploitation. In other words, the person wielding the verbal abuse does so to gain an advantage over the abused, typically to his or her own desire. Verbal abuse takes several forms including threats, foul or demeaning language, hostile tone or volume, intensity of delivery whether loud or quiet and sarcasm. Similarly, Bosch (2007) notes that verbal abuse is a form of domestic violence which is a condition precedent to physical violence. It manifests in form of accusing, blaming, criticising, threatening and name-calling.

From the foregoing, verbal abuse could be described as derisive use of language in addressing an individual. The police employ this device to reduce suspects to criminals during police-suspect interaction. This is evident in the examples below (the bold parts):

Example 1

IPO : Area ibo ní Sàngo?

Which area in Sàngo?

SUS: Ibi ègbẹ ilé epo, lábé búkà yẹn

Beside the filling station, under the canteen

IPO : *Wèrè, o wá nílé!*

Mad man, do you have a house!

Example 2

IPO : *Olóríburúkú. Okó tí ò tó ònkan*

Misfortune bearer! A ridiculously small penis

IPO : *È è lè rójú rere Olóun.....*

You people cannot see the favour of God.

Example 3

IPO : Ènìkejì ẹ dà?

Where is your accomplice?

SUS: Èmi nìkan náà ni

I am the only one

IPO : Àní teḡo ma n̄ ṣerú iṣé yẹn

I mean your accomplice

SUS: Mi ò ṣerú iṣé yíí rí

I had never been involved in the act before

IPO : *Àbáyé fẹ̀ ṣe é ni?. Mò n̄ bọ̀ jẹ́ kí n ṣe n̄nkan tí mò n̄ ṣe tán; mà á fún ẹ ní mark*

tí o ma ma fi han ọmọ ẹ; iyẹn tó ò bá kú sẹwọn

Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world? I am coming, let me finish what I am doing; I will give you an indellible mark which you will be showing your children that is if you don't eventually die in the prison.

Example 4

SUS: Èmi ò lẹ̀nì kankan tí mà á int

I don't have anyone that I

IPO: Onjìbìtì ni yín

You are a fraudster

SUS: Ẹ jẹ́ kí n sọ n̄nkan fùn un yìn int

Let me tell you

IPO: Ní sùúrù. Onjìbìtì ni yín; ẹ dẹ̀ sọ pé ẹ ò ríran
Be patient. You are a fraudster; and you claimed to be visually impaired. sight problem

In example 1, the IPO called the suspect “wèrè” mad man or mad person, in 2, the IPO called the suspect an “Olórìbùrùkù” a misfortune bearer and worsened the matter by pronouncing the suspect(s) will never see the favour of God “Ẹ è lè rójú rere Ọlójun”, in 3, the IPO abused the suspect with a rethorical question “Àbáyé fẹ̀ ṣe é ni?” Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world?. In 4, the IPO called the suspect a fraudster and commented abusively on the claim by the suspect that he had sight problem. These are few examples of the instances of the use of abuse by the police to ridicule suspects

The data below from Farinde (1997: 50) further buttress the points made above:

A.P : ògá, no be me do this thing now

Sir, I was not the perpetrator of this act now

IPO: Will you keep quiet! *Idiot* .Keep quiet. You are the person who stole the properties. I must make sure I torture you.

IPO: I go read am for you. ògá make you kúkú sign(his statement)

I will read it to you. ògá, you can even sign

A.P : I will sign. I don sign

I will sign. I have signed

IPO: Look at the yèyè signature of the *idiot*. And this one, he go take thief up and down.

Look at the terrible/useless signature of the idiot. And this is what he uses to steal all over the place

S.H : Go put him in the cell

IPO : I understand sir. I no say this man na *stubborn goat*. óyá, let's go to the cell

I know this man is a stubborn goat. Now, let us go into the cell

A.P : Ògá, na true I go tell you now

Ògá, I will tell you the truth now

In the excerpt above, the Investigating Police Officers abused the suspect, calling him *idiot* and as if this was not enough, he further called him a *stubborn goat*.

5.5 (Verbal) Threats

Threats are used to scare or intimidate a person into submission. It can come in form of bodily harm to a person or other family, friends or pets of the person. In fact, the legal system can be used against another and thus threats include telling another person they will unjustly use the legal system to gain an unfair advantage over them. In police-suspect discourse, threats are used by the police to intimidate, overwhelm and demonstrate their superiority over suspects. This is evident in the data collected as presented below:

CASE 2:

SUS: Ehn, bí wọn bá gbá mí láyè, mà á kówó wọn wá ní Monday

Ehn, if I they permit me, am permitted, I will bring their money on Monday

IPO (short silence) E dúró bàbá, ẹ sọ nkan ẹ sọ again (↗)

Wait old man, say what you just said

SUS: (repeated what he said earlier)

IPO: *Bàbá, wọn á gbowó wọn kẹtó kúrò níbí*

Old man, they will collect their money before you leave here

SUS: *Ọwọ́ yín ló wà*

It is in your hand

CASE 3

IPO: Okay, ó ní ẹ pe òun lórí phone

Okay, he said you called him on the phone

SUS: Mi ò pè é lórí phone

I did not call him on the phone

IPO: *Bàbá, ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta? A ma kọ letter sí àwọn network láti find out o, tẹ bá parọ́ a má a get a dẹ ma charge yín sí court; a má a gbéyín lọ sílé ẹjọ. ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta? (raising his voice)*

Old man, you called him two days ago or not? We are going to write a letter to the telecommunications outfits and find out, if you are lying, we will detect and we will charge you to court.

CASE 5

SUS: *Látọ́jọ́ tí wón ti bí mi, mi ò ẹ́rú ẹ́şé yíí rí*

Ever since I was born, I had never been involved in this kind of act before

IPO: *Mò n bọ́, jẹ́ kí n ẹ́ nkan tí mò n ẹ́ tán. Mà á fùn ẹ ní mark to mama fi han ọmọ ẹ, iyẹn tí o ò bá kú sẹ́wọ́n*

I am coming, let me finish what I am doing. I will give you a mark that you will be showing to your children, that is if you don't die in prison.

CASE 7:

IPO: Kí ni qualification ẹ?

What is your qualification?

SUS: HND (Higher National Diploma)

IPO: In what?

SUS: Musicology

IPO: *You go go sing well for Agodi*

You will go and sing very well at Agodi

Consider the following example from Farinde (1997: 52)

IPO: Kólé dey for cell now, na him say na you with am go burgle that house o. *If you no talk true now, you go meet am for cell*

Kólé is already in the cell, and he was the one that said it was you and he that burgled the house.. if you refuse to say the truth, you will go and meet him in the cell

A.P : Na dat one, na him own ògá

Sir, that is for him

IPO: Na him own?

That is for him?

A.P : Me I don travel, he don tey

I have been away for some time

IPO: *Until we hang you before you no say you go tell us true*

It is until we hang you before you will own up and tell us the truth

A.P : You just wan suffer me for the thing wey I no do

You just want to punish me for a crime/ an offence I have not committed

IPO: *Make you bring baton make we hang am. He go talk true*

Bring the baton and let us hang him. He will confess

The table below shows the frequency of the use of the observed discourse-cum-power markers in police-suspect discourse, using the first thirty cases of the total number of fifty-five collected.

Table 2: Frequency of the Identified Power Markers in Police-Suspect Discourse

	CASE 1	Question	Paralanguage	Interruptions	Abuse	Threat
IPO		9	1	9	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 2					
IPO		23	2	17	3	2
SUS		1	0	1	0	0
	CASE 3					
IPO		32	3	11	0	1
SUS		1	0	0	0	0

	CASE 4					
IPO		20	4	7	5	0
SUS		0	0	1	0	0
	CASE 5					
IPO		29	2	4	4	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 6					
IPO		13	0	0	1	2
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 7					
IPO		4	0	0	0	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 8					
IPO		25	5	20	2	4
SUS		1	0	1	0	0
	CASE 9					
IPO		23	5	3	4	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 10					
IPO		3	0	0	3	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 11					
IPO		16	0	1	0	0
SUS		2	0	0	0	0
	CASE 12					

IPO		9	1	7	3	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 13					
IPO		0	0	0	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 14					
IPO		15	3	3	2	3
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 15					
IPO		1	1	0	0	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 16					
IPO		23	4	0	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 17					
IPO		12	2	1	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 18					
IPO		19	2	2	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 19					
IPO		15	2	1	0	4

SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 20					
IPO		16	1	1	0	0
SUS		1	1	0	0	0
	CASE 21					
IPO		14	0	1	1	2
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 22					
IPO		24	0	1	0	3
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 23					
IPO		159	17	2	0	0
SUS		1	0	0	0	0
	CASE 24					
IPO		16	4	1	0	20
SUS		1	0	0	0	
	CASE 25					
IPO		4	0	0	0	0
SUS		0	0	1	0	0
	CASE 26					
IPO		4	0	0	0	0
SUS		0	0	0	0	0

	CASE 27					
IPO		36	2	1	0	2
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 28					
IPO		5	0	0	1	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0
	CASE 29					
IPO		7	0	0	0	0
SUS		3	0	0	0	0
	CASE 30					
IPO		43	6	5	0	1
SUS		0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: Summary of Table 2

Description	Question	Paralanguage	Interruption	(Verbal)Abuse	Threat
Total IPO	619	67	98	29	49
%	97%	100%	93%	100%	100%
Total SUS	11	1	4	0	0
%	3%	1%	7%	0%	0%
Grand Total	630	68	102	29	49
%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

The figures in the tables above are represented on the bar chart below:

Fig.9 : Graphical Representation of the Frequency of Power Markers in Police-Suspect Discourse

From the pictures painted in tables 4 and 5 above, it becomes clear that out of the 630 questions that were observed in thirty police-suspects interactive sessions, for instance, , 619(97%) were from the IPOs while 11(3%) were from suspects. There were 68 instances of the use of paralanguage, 67 (99%) were from IPOs while 1 (1%) was from suspects. There were 102 instances of the use of interruption, 98 (93%) were from IPOs while 4 (7) were from suspects. There were 29 instances of the use of abuse, all (100%) of which came from IPOs and none (0%) from suspects. And finally, we noticed 49 instances of the use of (verbal) threat, all (100%) of which came from IPOs and none (0%) from suspects. All these point to the fact that Investigating Police Officers dominate police-suspects interaction during investigations. How these phenomena are employed by the police to clinch to power during investigations is presented in the diagram below:

The diagram below shows how the various linguistic and paralinguistic devices identified above serve as stairs upon which the police climb to power in police-suspect discourse.

Fig. 10 : The stairs upon which the police climb to power in police-suspect discourse

CHAPTER SIX

DATA ANALYSIS III

6.0 Power and Ideologies in Police-Suspect Discourse

Several scholars have argued ideology and power go hand in hand. For instance, Fairclough (2001) and Wodak (1996) argue ideology is an implicit assumption held, largely in interaction with power relations, and this implicitness has embedded in it the capacity of ideology to give sustenance to power inequalities and thus serve “political” purposes (Fairclough, 2001 cf Odebunmi, 2010). In her words, Wodak (1996:18) opines ideologies are “particular ways of representing and constructing society, which reproduce unequal relations of power, relations of domination and exploitation”. Coward and Ellis (1977: 6) opine that ideology both constructs and is constructed by the way in which we live our role in the social totality, and by the way we represent that process in art. This, succinctly put, all our social activities and practices are informed by ideology, such that it determines the ways in which what we say and believe connects with the power-structure and power relations of the society we live in (Eagleton, 1983:14).

From the positions of these scholars, it can be deduced that ideology is the rationale behind what we do, what we say, how we say it, and the purpose we intend to achieve by what we say, etc; a position that reinforces Fairclough and Wodak’s (1997) claim that ideologies are produced and reflected in the use of discourse.

Scholars have attempted to shed light on the different types of ideologies that could manifest through discourse. For instance, scholars like Eagleton (1991) and van Dijk (2006) have identified typologies of ideologies such as class, sex, social, cultural, racial, ageist, professional and institutional ideologies. However, the one found related to this study, as evident in the police’s deployment of language during police-suspect interaction, is institutional ideology. In the institutional ideology of the Nigeria Police are the ideological beliefs that: the police’s institutional authority overrides the low-profile suspects’ constitutional rights (to dignity); a low-profile suspect is as good as a criminal, and a high-profile suspect is not a criminal until otherwise proved.

The Nigeria Police as an institution and how she employs impoliteness and politeness strategies in promoting her institutional ideologies shall be discussed here. Relevant excerpts are picked from the pool of data collected for the analysis of this section.

6.1 The Nigeria Police as an Institution with Ideologies

Institutions are not easy to define, as people always associate them with physical buildings or institutional settings, such as schools, hospitals, media organizations, prisons or courts of law (Mayr, 2008). Agar (1985: 164) opines institutions are ‘a socially legitimated expertise together with those persons authorized to implement it’. This view of Agar’s includes the ideological conception of institutions as involving asymmetrical roles between representatives of institutions or ‘experts’ and ‘non-experts’ or ‘clients’, who must comply with institutional norms and objectives (Mayr, 2008). Scholars such as Weber (1914), Althusser (1971), and Habermas (1987) have further accentuated the notion that institutions have immense power which they impose on people. The Nigeria Police, saddled with, among others, the responsibility of maintaining law and order in the country (see Chapter One for the duties of Nigeria Police) could be said to have certain institutional ideologies with which its men operate while interacting with suspects. These institutional ideologies of the Nigeria Police become obvious in the way Investigating Police Officers deploy impoliteness and politeness strategies in their interaction with suspects. The institutional ideologies of the Nigeria Police, as observed in our data, are captured in the ideological statements below:

6.1.1 Police’s institutional authority overrides the constitutional rights of civilians in general, and of low-profile suspects (to dignity) in particular

This is an ideology that is very evident in the way and manner Investigating Police Officers “handle” low-profile suspects with language, employing impoliteness strategies in dressing them down in the interrogation room. In the interrogation room, the police officers assume a high echelon by virtue of their institutional power. Even when, as custodians of the law, they are aware of the constitutional rights of suspects (see chapter one), they have been observed not to recognise these rights in their dealing with low-profile suspects. The Nigeria police believe their institutional authority overrides the constitutional rights of low-profile suspects and accused persons in particular and civilians in general. Their non recognition of these rights manifests in

the ignoble and unsavoury manner the police use all kinds of derogatory language (impoliteness strategies) on (low-profile) suspects, including abuse, name-calling, direct and unmitigated accusation and sometimes severe threat (and torture). To the average Nigerian police, a low-profile does not deserve any right to dignity. This fact is exemplified below, as found in our data:

Example 1

IPO 2: Area ibo ni Sango?

Which area in Sango?

SUS: Ibi egbe ile epo, labé búkà yèn

Beside the filling station, under the canteen

IPO 2: Wèrè, o wá nílé!

Mad man, do you have home!

IPO 3: *You are a syndicate*

Example 2

IPO 2: *Olórí ibú ni ó*

You are an unfortunate being/ You are a bearer of misfortune

SUS: Silent

IPO 2: *E è lè rójú rere Olóun.*

You cannot see the favour of God.

Example 3

IPO 3: *O lè bá òyá ẹ̀ sùn?*

You can sleep with your mother?

IPO 3: *O lè dó òyá ẹ̀?*

You can sexual intercourse with your mother?

Example 4

IPO: *E mò pé wàhàlà wà lórí ilẹ̀ yèn kẹ̀ tó talẹ̀ fún wọn*

You know there are controversies over the land before you sold it to them

SUS: *Kò sí wàhàlà lórí ilẹ̀ ọ̀gá mi*

There was no dispute over the land, my boss.

IPO: *E jẹ́ kí n sọ fún yín, wipe ẹ̀ sọpé owó lẹ̀ fẹ́ dá padà tùmò sí pé ẹ̀ gbowó yèn lònà jìbìtì ni*

Let me tell you, that you said you will return their money on Monday shows you collected their money in a fraudulent way.

IPO: . *Anybody tẹ bá fẹ̀ pè, ẹ̀ pè é nísinyí o, ẹ̀ é san seven hundred thousand (naira) f'áwọ̀n people yìí kẹ̀ tó kúrò níbí lénìí*

Call whoever you want to call now; you will pay these people seven hundred thousand (naira) before you leave this place today

SUS: Èmi ò lénì kankan tí mà á int

I don't have anyone that I

IPO: *Oníjìbìtì ní yín*

You are a fraudster

SUS: Ẹ̀ jẹ́ kì n sọ̀ nńkan fùn un yìn

Let me tell you something

IPO: *Oníjìbìtì ní yín; ẹ̀ dẹ̀ sọ̀ pé ẹ̀ ò ríran*

You are a fraudster; and you claimed to be visually impaired.have sight problem

The fact expressed above is further reinforced in the conversation below:

Example 5 (from CASE 22) Details at the appendix

IPO: Where are the other ones now?

SUS: I don't know sir

IPO: What does X do?

SUS: He is pastor

IPO: We need to arrest him after this interrogation

IPO: What about XX?

SUS: He is an agent

IPO: He was the one teaching you what to do

IPO: (Drags the suspect close to himself) when did you sell the land to Mrs XX

SUS: That was around March, 2014

IPO: How much did you sell it?

SUS: I think 700,000

IPO: How many people were there when she paid?

SUS: My friend, my family member and I

IPO: (Slaps the suspect) Don't say our family members. Mention names

Even when the said IPO here is expected to know that his action of dragging and slapping the suspect is tantamount to infringing on his human rights, he did not refrain himself, after all, he is "covered by his institutional authority" which "overrules" the constitutional rights of suspects

Example 6 (CASE 19)

IPO: What was the agreement between you?

SUS: Oga promised to share the profit of the business with me after four years.....

IPO: What condition did your oga give for the sharing?

SUS: That is if the business succeeds.....

IPO: *You are a fool, and did it succeed?*

SUS: (Shakes his head). Sir, God knows I tried

In the excerpt above, the IPO insulted the suspect, calling him a fool. Would one then say the said IPO did not know this statement was an infringement on the right of the suspect? The answer is no considering his supposed knowledge of the position of the constitution concerning the rights of suspects. However, he chose not to acknowledge this right, because he believed he was operating on the platform of his institutional power and authority, hence it did not matter if the right of the suspect was violated in the process.

Example 7 (Secondary Data, Farinde 1997: 56)

IPO: What is your tribe?

A.P: I come from XYZ

IPO: XYZ! *No wonder. Na una dey spoil this country.*

XYZ!No wonder.. You people are the ones maligning the image of this country

A.P : Ògá, make una no dey talk something ...int

Ògá, don't be saying something

IPO:

Shut up! I don tell you make una no dey

bandy words with me. I go beat you oo

Shut up! I have always told you not to exchange words with me. I will beat you ooo

In the excerpt above, the IPO did not only insult the suspect, he equally insulted his race (his people). This is not a sign of respect or dignity for the suspect and everybody that comes from his state.

Example 8

Background Information: An officer came into the large interrogation hall, and was hailed by another police officer, who asked the officer that just came in about a previous issue discussed by them. Here is the conversation that took place after exchanging pleasantries:

Officer 1: I don come back o

I am back

Officer 2: Ehn go collect am now. Go meet them say make them give you your thing. Go there, ah! ah!! *You are a corporal oo. You are not a civilian!*

Okay, go and collect it now. Go and meet them and ask them to give you your stuff.

You are a corporal and not a civilian.

Officer 1: I go follow my oga now

I will go with my boss now.

All these attest to the aforesaid that the police believe, by virtue of their institutional authority and power, they are not on the same social pedestal with the 'ordinary citizens' of the country, and as such their institutional power overrides their constitutional rights. In particular in Example 8, the statement of the second officer is an indication that the police do not see themselves as being on the same pedestal with the ordinary citizens of the country, by virtue of the institutional power with which they operate, and this institutional power, they believe, overrides the

constitutional rights of the ordinary citizen, hence they are superior to them. This is further reinforced in the excerpt below:

Example 9

Background Information: The two police officers in this excerpt were reacting to the manner a senior officer queried him over an issue in the presence of a suspect. Obviously, the two officers are not on the same rank from the tone of their interaction.

Officer 1: Good morning ògá

Officer 2: How you dey jàrè?

How are you(emphasis)?

Officer 1: I see the way you dey look your ògá the other time

I observed how you were looking at your boss the other time

Officer 2: In fact, I just dey look am oo. Imagine how he was talking to me, a senior police officer in the presence of a suspect

In fact, I was just looking at him. Imagine how he was addressing me, a senior police officer in the presence of a suspect

Officer 2: Àbí oo

Yes oo

The statement of Officer 2 in the excerpt presented above further sheds more light on the ideology with which IPOs handle suspects, and especially, the low-profile ones. What could be inferred from this statement is that, even if he was going to be scolded at all by his boss, it should not be in the presence of a suspect, who in the organogram of the society and the context of the interaction, was below him. The Officer was not complaining about the fact that his boss scolded him, as this is a normal practice in any organisation; however, he considered himself ridiculed because the scolding took place in the presence of a suspect, who obviously was a ‘bloody civilian’ as the men of the institution often refer to non officers. The justification for our position here becomes clearer in the excerpts below:

Example 10

Junior Officers: (Six in number, all on their feet. Following the gesture of these officers, every

civilian in the hall, except one woman complainant, stood up) : Morning sir!

Senior Officer: (Looked round the interrogation hall. He observed all except the said woman were on their feet): *Who is this woman sitting down?*

Woman Complainant: I am XXX. I am a daughter of a military man. I came to see the IPO handling my case

Senior Officer: *Is that why you could not stand up? I am the only officer here; every other person in this place is an attachment*

Woman Complainant : I am sorry sir; I actually get injury for leg (speaking Nigerian Pidgin)(shows the officer her leg)

Senior Officer : Okay sit down. (He later exchanged pleasantries with the junior officers and asked the woman complainant what her complaint was before leaving the hall)

Example 11 from CASE 31

IPO: *Şé o lè kòwé?*

Can you write?

SUS: *Rárá*

No

IPO: *Kí ló dé tí o paró fún mi?* (obviously from their interactions before entering the investigation hall)

Why are/were you lying to me?

SUS: *Mi ò paró fún un yín ìn*

I did not tell you lies(emphasis)

IPO: *Mà á fọ etí ẹ. Idiot ni ẹ*

I will slap you. You are an idiot

Example 12 : A report drawn from some officers' reactions and comments on an officer's misdemeanour

The said officer was said to have set out the previous day in company of some other officers to arrest a particular suspect in town, and on their way back, the vehicle conveying the officers had a minor collision with a popular big commercial bus provided by the state government for mass movement of people in the capital city. As reported by the officers who witnessed the scenario,

instead of the said officer to resolve the issue amicably, he resorted to discharging tear gas into the bus, causing the passengers great discomfort. Out of anger, the passengers rushed down of the bus, pounced on him and beat him seriously.

Example 13: A report drawn from the discussion between four officers during data collection

Generally, the officers were reacting to the way and manner issues that have to do with officers' funds are handled by civilians. During this interaction, one of the officers commented thus:

Officer: A á se n̄kan, a á ma bẹ civilian kó bá wa approve è, whereas military have trained officers who handle their financial issues.

We are in for it; we are subjected to seeking approval from civilians on our financial issues whereas it is not so in the military, where they have trained officers who handle such activities.

For the sake of clarity on the statement of the officer, we later (the researcher) interviewed him informally as follows:

Researcher: Sir, ẹ jò o, ẹ n̄ sòrò nípa financial issues lẹ̀ẹ̀kan, kò yé mi

Sir, please I need some clarifications on what you just said concerning your finances, I did not understand

Officer: Ẹhn ẹ o mò pé ní military, àwọn officers wọn ló má n̄ handle anything tí ó bá involve anything like loan, cooperative; but ní ti ọlọ̀pá, àwọn civilian ló má n̄ handle è tí kò dẹ yẹ kó rí bẹ̀

Ehn, know in the military, there are trained officers who handle their finances, but it is not so with the Nigeria Police. Civilians are the ones saddled with such responsibilities, and this is not supposed to be so

All these are pointers to how police officers perceive themselves as individuals who are superior, by virtue of their institutional authority and power, to civilians in the country.

6.1.2 A low-profile suspect is guilty until otherwise proved

Perhaps this proposition becomes apt here : *“To lawyers, no one is guilty until he is convicted by the court; but to the policeman, no suspect is innocent until he is acquitted by the court.* This is another ideology that could be observed as being behind the manner IPOs interact with low-profile suspects in the interrogation room. This is very glaring in the data collected. There are instances where the IPOs used expressions that condemned the suspects as though they had been pronounced guilty by the court. Perhaps, this ideology is anchored on the inclusion of the sensitive term “criminal” in the name of the department saddled with the responsibility of investigating suspects in the Nigeria Police. Maybe, if it had been christened Police Investigation Department (PID), the situation could have been milder. The examples below illustrate this ideology.

Exmample 14

IPO: Kí ni qualification ẹ?

What is your qualification?

SUS: HND (Higher National Diploma)

IPO: In what?

SUS: Musicology

IPO: *You go go sing for Agodi*

You will go and sing in Agodi

Agodi is a place for those who have been declared guilty of the allegations levelled against them by the court. The IPO above declared the suspect will land in Agodi, even when the court had not pronounced so. The IPO said this, because to him, the suspect was guilty already and was very certain he was going to be jailed.

Example 15

IPON 1: Níbo ni ilé ẹ?

Where is your house/where do you live?

SUS: Sánńgo ni mò ń gbé

I live in Sańńgo

IPO 2: Area ibo ni Sàngo?

Which area in Sàngo?

SUS: Ibi ègbẹ ilé epo, lábẹẹ búkà yẹn

Beside the filling station, close to a cafeteria

IPO 2: Wèrè, o wá nílé!

Mad man, do you have home!

IPO 3: *You are a syndicate*

Example 16

SUS: Mi ò ẹ irú isẹ yíí rí

I had never been involved in the act before

IPO 2: Àbáyé fẹ ẹ ẹ ní? Mò n bọ jẹ kí n ẹ nńkan tí mò n ẹ tán; mà á fún ẹ ní mark

tí o ma ma fi han ọmọ ẹ, iyẹn tó ò bá kú sẹwòn

Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world? I am coming, let me finish what I am doing; I will give you an indellible mark which you will showing to your children, that is if you do not die in prison..

In example 15 above, the IPO here referred to the suspect as being a **syndicate**, a conclusion he reached even when the suspect had not been presented before the court, and also in 16, he made a statement that already depicted the suspect as a criminal who will rot in jail. All these are predicated on the ideological belief of the police that any low-profile individual brought before them as a suspect has actually committed the very crime for which the fellow is summoned, and as such should be treated as a criminal, both in action and words of mouth.

Exmample 17

IPO: Wò ó, wójú mi dada, o ti ẹ'exam sílẹ, o ò need screening, *admission ti dúró fún ẹ ní*

Agodi, direct entry ni. ẹ ẹ o ti ready láti sòrò?

See, look at my eyes very well, you have wrtten an exam, you don't need any screening, you have already secured admission into Agodi, it is direct entry. Are you ready to speak now?

SUS: (Nodded his head)

IPO: Okay, sòrò bá yíí

Okay, speak now

The IPO, having already concluded the suspect was a criminal, declared the crime he was alleged to have committed would land him in prison, Agodi.

Example 18A culled from CASE 19 (see details in the appendix)

IPO: What condition did your oga give for the sharing?

SUS: That is if the business succeeds.

IPO: You are a fool, and did it succeed?

SUS: (Shakes his head). Sir, God knows I tried

IPO: (Hit his baton on the suspect's head) *Answer my question, Olé*

SUS: I can explain everything sir

Here, the IPO already concluded the suspect was a thief, hence his hitting him with his baton and calling him *Olé*, thief. This was further repeated in the latter part of the excerpt as follows:

Example 18B from CASE 19

IPO: (Puts a handcuff on the suspect's hands) You will go to prison. This is not aailable
case

SUS: Oga, I am ready to sell my Toyota Sienna and piece of land I have

IPO: *Olòsì, omọ olè*. You even used the money you stole well

Useless (human) being, son of a thief

SUS: No sir, I had bought all that before I got the job

IPO: Are you ready to refund the money or go to court?

SUS: I don't know sir, please help me

All these are pointers to the fact that, more often than not, IPOs treat low-profile suspects as criminals, who are already guilty of the allegation against them, even when the court has pronounced such suspects so.

Example 19 (Secondary Data: Oyebade, 2007: 150)

P.O. : Do you hear English? (Do you understand English?)

Driver: No

P.O. : Where is your driving licence?

Driver: Ó ti sọ̀nù. Mo ní (*I had but it is missing*)

P.O.: *You are lying*. You better say the truth or you will suffer.

Driver: Ó ti sọ̀nù. Mo ní..... (It is missing. I had....)

P.O: *You are lying* I will detain you

(Oyebade, 2007: 150)

In the excerpt above, the police officer had already concluded in his mind that the driver-suspect had committed the crime of driving without having a driving licence and would do anything possible to pursue this cause.

6.1.3 A high-profile suspect is not guilty until otherwise proved

This ideology becomes apparent in the way the IPO in CASE 11 changed the tempo of the interaction with the alhaji-suspect, who tried to assert himself in the course of the interaction between the two. The moment the suspect declared himself as a man who did not deserve the “harsh” treatment meted out to him during the interaction, considering his personality, the IPO started treating him with respect and courtesy; a development that presupposes the assumption of the said IPO that the suspect, being a successful businessman, could not have committed the crime or offence he was being questioned over. (see Case 11). Similarly, the lawyer suspect whose case was considered as an appendage to Case 11 was not subjected to the same ridiculous treatment low-profile suspects are usually subjected to during police-suspect interaction. His own ‘questioning’ actually took place in the OC’s office because of his status. The situation was not different in all the cases that involved high-profile suspects observed in this work. All these critically examined, inform the conclusion that low-profile suspects are actually taken through the process of interrogation (which is coercive in nature), while high-profile ones enjoy the benefit of interview (non coercive in nature).

This is further reinforced in the excerpt below:

CASE 26: Assault and Threat

Background Information: *The complainant had claimed the suspect assaulted and threatened him. The suspect is a well-educated old man who should be in his late sixties. He is the landlord of the suspect.*

IPO: È gbó sè ẹ pè é ní ghost? (while he was still writing his statement)

SUS: Èmi, a ghost? O tún n paró mó mi

I, a ghost? You are even lying on me

IPO: *Daddy*, sè ẹ ti kọ ó tán? È kọ orúkọ yín síbí sir, kí ẹ dè sign

Daddy, are you done writing it. Write your name here and sign

SUS: Okay

IPO: Sé ẹ fẹ drop èyí ni?

Do you want to drop this ?(referring to the document the suspect was handling as evidence

SUS: Bèni

Yes

IPO: Sé ẹ ní photocopy lówó?

Do you have a photocopy with you?

SUS: Rára

No

IPO: È jẹ kí n lọ báa yín sè photocopy (goes out to make the photocopy for the suspect)

Let me go and make the photocopy for you

SUS: Okay

IPO: *Daddy* ẹ jókòó

Daddy, sit down

After some minutes, the IPO surfaced with the photocopies of the said documents. She genuflected while giving the suspect a copy as a sign of courtesy. Afterwards, she announced the matter would be taken to the DC's office.

IPO: *Daddy*, èyin ẹ máà bò

SUS: Okay

The complainant was later seen prostrating to the suspect, begging him to forgive him.

6.2 Cultural Ideology and Its Manifestations in Police-Suspect Interaction

The concept of Culture has been defined differently in different ways by different scholars. This explains why conflicting perspectives exist on the subject. However, there appears to be a consensus on understanding culture “as a knowledge system that renders meaningful the world in which we live: no one among us is a perfect example of the cultural group in which we live, but rather each of us is a repository of a small part of the knowledge system of that group” (Jourdan and Tuite, 2006). Geertz (1973) opines culture is produced by social relations that are in turn, produced by it. In other words, the concept of culture manifests in the way people interact, relate, dress, eat, etc. It can then be posited that culture influences the way a people view the world. If culture is seen as the way a people do their things and ideology as what influences the way they do their things, then it will not be out of place for one to posit that culture and ideology go hand in hand, hence the concept of cultural ideology. Cultural ideology refers to values, norms, and standards that exist independently of a single person and that are shared by a group as part of its mutual culture (Narvaez et al 1999: 478). In other words, cultural ideology refers to the common orientation of a group of people or individuals, that guides their relational or social interaction. This common orientation can be attuned to via social interaction.

In police-suspect interaction, there are numerous instances of reference to the cultural ideological beliefs of the participants, that is, the IPOs and suspects. In virtually all the observed cases, which largely took place in the Yoruba language and sometimes a mixture of Yoruba and English; perhaps because the Yoruba language is the major language of the larger society in which our setting is situated. In the cases observed, preponderant reference was made to the cultural ideology of the Yoruba people and language. This cultural ideology manifests in the way IPOs and suspects employ the use of honorific pronouns and deference expressions during their interactions.

6.2.1 Use of Honorific Pronouns and Deference Terms

Honorific pronouns are parts of the linguistic devices used to show politeness in the Yoruba language (Oyetade, 1995; Ajayi and Balogun, 2014). This is usually employed by a younger interactant in a speech situation to refer to or address the older interactant. Any younger individual who addresses an older one with the use of non honorific pronoun is considered rude

and non-conformist in the Yoruba language and culture. The manifestation of this cultural ideological belief of the Yoruba in the use of honorific pronouns to mark or show politeness was observed during police-suspect interactions as captured in our data.

In CASE 2 for instance, the IPO was still found using the honorific pronouns such as *ẹ*, *yín* (honorific you) while interacting with the suspect who was an old man, far older than he was. Amazingly, even when the IPO was seriously attacking the face of the old man, calling him a fraudster or a dubious old man, he still kept relating to him with the use of honorific pronouns, although occasionally he would flout this ideological principle, especially when seriously angry. Consider the following examples:

Example 20

IPO: *Ní sùúrù, oníjíbítí ni yín. Ẹ dẹ sọ pé ẹ ò ríran*

Be patient, you are dubious and you claim to have visual impairment

SUS: *Oo! ògá mi*

All right my master/boss

The words in italics are honorific pronouns employed by the IPO to address the suspect here.

We equally have a similar situation in CASE 3 as follows:

Example 21

IPO: *Kí ẹ sọ fun lórí phone?*

What did you tell him on the phone?

SUS: *Mo ní báwo la ẹ fẹ ríra simple thing*

I asked how we were going to see each other

IPO: *Kí ẹ fẹ ri fún? Ẹ sòrò now bàbà*

What did you want to see him? Talk now old man!

SUS: *Béyàn bá ti jọ ríra tipé, èyàn lè pè lórí phone*

Since it is quite sometime we last spoke, I deemed it fit to call him on the phone

IPO: *Ehn, Kí ẹ fẹ ri fún? Ẹ fẹ pá?*

Why did you want to see him? You wanted to kill him?

In the excerpt above, the IPO would still relate to the suspect with the use of honorific pronoun *ẹ* in deference to his age, even when he put him on the spot like an offender. The suspect also kept to this cultural ideological principle in addressing the IPO, even though he was much older than he was. Perhaps this was due to the powerful status assumed by the IPO in this conversational exchange.

In addition to the use of honorific pronouns, there is the use of deference terms such as *bàbá*, *ọgá*, *mummy* and *daddy* by the IPOs and suspects respectively. This is captured in the examples below:

Example 22

IPO: *Bàbá*, *şé ẹ mọ X* (mentioned the name of the complainant)

Old man, do you know? (mentioned the name of the complainant)

SUS: *Mo mọ ọn*

I know him

IPO: *Şé ẹ mọ Y*

Do you know ẹẹẹ?

Example 23

IPO: *Bàbá*, is it true that you are after his life?

SUS: It's not true

IPO: Ehn!

SUS: It is not true

Example 24

IPO: *Ìwà tẹ*

wù yẹn, báwo lẹ şe ri?

What will you call that very act of yours?

SUS: *Daddy*, *kò da*

Daddy, it is not good

Example 25

IPO 2: È mú tape-rule wa ká wọn okó è!

Bring a tape-rule for us to measure his penis!

SUS: *Mummy*, ẹ jò ó!

Mummy, please!

Example 26

IPO: Tí mo bá bèrè òrò lówó ẹ, ko ma dáhùn, o mọ ọmọ yẹn tàbí o ò mò ó? Sẹ iwọ lò n kọ ní Kéú?

When I ask you questions, you answer me, do you know that girl or not? Are you the one teaching her Arabic?

SUS: Èmi kọ ni mò n kọ ní Kéú.

I am not the one teaching her Arabic

IPO: Ní on the 20th, o ní o rán òun ní ẹwà àti bread, sẹ iró ni tàbí òótó?

She alleged you sent her on an errand to buy bread and beans for you on the 20th, true or false?

SUS: Iró ni *daddy*

It is false daddy

In examples 22 and 23 above, the suspects called the IPOs *bàbá* as though they were their biological father. This was in consonance with the Yoruba cultural ideological belief that anyone as old as one's father is addressed as one's father. This same ideological belief explains why the suspects in examples 24, 25 and 26 addressed the IPOs as *daddy* and *mummy*.

6.3 Conclusion

So far, this work has given insights into the (im)politeness strategies found in police-suspect discourse in the State Criminal Investigation Department, Iyaganku Police Division, Ibadan, Oyo State. The first chapter gave an introduction to the motivation for the work. Chapter two reviewed existing literature on politeness, impoliteness and police language and discussed the theoretical framework adopted in the work. Chapter three delved into the research methodology

adopted. Chapters four to six focused on data analysis. The following have therefore been observed:

- The IPOs often demonstrate their power via the use of impoliteness strategies viz bald on record impoliteness strategies; positive, negative impoliteness and mock politeness strategies in police-suspect discourse to overwhelm suspects and relegate them to zero power status in order to get confessions from them; ;
- Positive and negative politeness strategies are employed by the police in police-suspect interactions, when :
 - ❖ The suspect has agreed to have committed the said crime
 - ❖ The suspect cooperates with the IPO
 - ❖ The suspect is a high-profile individual
- However, low-profile suspects employ positive politeness strategies while interacting with IPOs to appeal to the positive face of the IPOs, demonstrating their powerless status during such interactions.
- High-profile suspects employ the positive politeness and the negative impoliteness strategies to assert themselves in police-suspect interactions.
- The use of impoliteness strategies sometimes yields positive results, as it compels low-profile suspects to confess. But, this ultimately culminates in the violation of their fundamental human rights, as stated in sections 34 and 36 of Nigerian Constitution. In the light of this, one wonders why the same phenomenon is not deployed by the police in its full measure while interacting with high-profile suspects, if indeed they believe that is the only weapon they could use to seek confessions from suspects.
- Therefore, power distribution in police-suspect discourse is asymmetrical in line with the position of Sadiq (2011) and Farinde (1997), in that the police assume a powerful position and low-profile suspects a less powerful position in police-suspect discourse;
- The police employ linguistic tools such as question, verbal abuse, verbal threats, interruptions and paralinguistic weapons as table banging, raised voice and hiss in exerting their institutional power on low-profile suspects;
- The ideology behind police's use of language in police-suspect interactions reveals the ideological beliefs of the men of the institution, which are "the institutional

authority/power of the police overrides the constitutional rights and power of Nigerian citizens, especially low-profile suspects, hence their superior status in such interactions; a low-profile suspect is a guilty until otherwise proved, and a high-profile suspect is not guilty until otherwise proved”. Similarly, suspects’ deployment of language, especially low-profile ones, shows their ideological belief in the superiority of the police during police-suspect interactions;

- Culture plays a vital role in police-suspect interactions in the setting, as police and suspects demonstrate their inclination to the Yoruba culture in their deployment of positive politeness strategies in police-suspect interactions;
- Police-suspect interaction involving low-profile suspects is highly interrogative in nature, although, in principle, the police believe they question and do not interrogate suspects.
- From the above, it suffices to say that, the rights of suspects, as enshrined in Section Nigeria’s 1999 Constitution are, most times, not being regarded by the police in police-suspect interactions. This is predicated on the fact that many of these individuals do not know their rights.

6.4 Recommendations

From the findings of this work, it is obvious that many citizens of the country do not really know much about their constitutional human rights; perhaps, a development that the police has capitalised upon in their treatment of suspects. Even as a suspect, an individual is entitled to certain rights as provided in the 1999 constitution of the country, but unfortunately, many people are not aware of these. It is therefore recommended that:

- There is a need for constant orientation and re-orientation of the men (sic) of the institution, especially on the need to act professionally to ensure the protection of the rights of suspects, particularly in their deployment of language during police-suspect interactions. To achieve the above, Nigeria Police College needs to include in her curriculum language drills that focus on how confessions can be sought from suspects without necessarily violating their fundamental human rights through verbal utterances. Particularly, topics on politeness should be included in the training manual of the institution. Similarly, adequate and regular re-orientation of the men of the Nigeria Police

by language experts and psychologists on the fundamental differences between the two related but different terms ‘suspects’ and ‘criminals’ is highly pertinent, as the men of the institution are observed to treat suspects as criminals in their utterances and practices. The concept of ‘presumption of innocence’ should be reinforced in the training manual designed for the men of the institution. We recommend a review in the name of the department saddled with the responsibility of conducting investigations into crimes from Criminal Investigation Department to Police Investigation Department. This, perhaps, would change the mentality of an average Investigating Police Officer who subjects suspects to criminal treatment, drawing inspiration from the adjective ‘criminal’ in the name of the department, which produces the ideological belief that a suspect is a criminal.

- Nigerians should be well orientated on what their fundamental rights are. Although these are spelt out in the nation’s constitution, not many people have access to it considering the ‘esoteric language’ in which it is couched. One does not need to be a law expert before one can interpret the laws of the land. To achieve this, more radio and television enlightenment programmes on citizens’ fundamental rights should be sponsored by the government of the country.
- For further study, this work recommends that a detailed and exclusive research into how the Nigerian Police interact with high-profile suspects be carried out to examine if the situation is any different from the picture just painted in this work, as not much access was granted to interactions involving police officers and high profile suspects in the course of collecting the data for this study. We hope a work that concentrates on this phenomenon could help shed more light on the observations raised in this study as far as police-high profile suspect interactions are concerned.

References

- Adebowale, I. 2010. *A sociolinguistic analysis of the language of police interrogation in Nigeria: a case study of Sango police station in Ibadan*. B. A project in the department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.
- Adegbija, E. 1989. A comparative study of politeness phenomena in Nigerian English, Yoruba and Ogori. *Multilingua*, 8, 57-80.
- Adegbite, W. and Odebunmi, A. 2010. Face threats in conversational interactions in orthodox and traditional medicines among the Yoruba in Southwestern Nigeria. In Ogunsiji, A., Kehinde, A, and Odebunmi, A. (Eds) *Language, Literature and Discourse*. Lincom Europa, Muenchen
- Adejumo, A. 2010. A post-colonial analysis of the literary and cultural consequences of the abolition of the 18th century Trans-Atlantic slave trade on the Yoruba of southwestern Nigeria. *Lumia* 21. 2: 1-23
- Adesiyun, D.O. 2005. *An accused person's rights in Nigerian criminal law (revised edition)*. Heinemann Studies in Nigerian Law. Ibadan
- Afonja, S.A. 2008. *Essential laws for the Nigeria police and other law enforcement agencies*. Flocel Publishers. Akure.
- Agar, M. (1985) 'Institutional discourse'. *Text*, 5(3), 147-68.
- Ajayi, D.O. 2012. *The language of abuse in the contemporary Nigeria hip-hop music*. An unpublished M.A project in the department of English and Literary Studies, University of Ibadan.
- Ajayi, T.M and Balogun K.O 2014. Politeness in the Yoruba and French languages, *International Journal of Language Studies*, vol. 8, number 4, pp. 77-94
- Aloia, L.S. 2009. *I'm sorry about your face: a study of face, politeness, and investment in the context of apology*. A thesis submitted to the Faculty of the University of Delaware in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Arts in Communication
- Althusser, L. (1971) *Lenin and Philosophy and Other Essays*. London: New Left Books.
- Agar, M. (1985) 'Institutional discourse'. *Text*, 5(3), 147-68.
- Ambuyo, B. A., Indede, F. N., and Karanja, P. N. 2011. Face threatening acts and standing orders: politeness or politics in the question time discussions of the Kenyan

- parliament. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* Vol. 1 No. 9 210-216
- Arundale, B. R. 2009. Constituting face in conversation: face, facework, and interactional achievement. *Journal of Pragmatics* 42 (2010) 2078–2105
- Asch, S.E. 1956. Studies of independence and conformity: A minority of one against a unanimous majority. *Psychological Monographs*, 70, 416.
- Austin, J. 1962. *How to do things with words*. Oxford: Clarendon Press
- Bach, K. and Harnish, R.M. 1979. *Linguistic communication and speech acts*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press
- Bamgbose, A. 1971. The English Language in Nigeria”. In *West African* (Ed) Spencer, J. London: Longman
- Bamgbose, A. 1995. English in the Nigerian Environment. in *New English: A West African Perspective* (Eds) Bamgbose, A., Banjo, A. and Thomas, A. Ibadan: Mosuro
- Banton, M. 1964. *The policeman in the community*. New York: Basic Books.
- Bar-Hillel, Y. 1954. Indexical expressions. *Mind*, 63,359-379
- Bosch, K. 2007. When words are used as weapons: the signs of verbal abuse (part 2 of a 4 part series). NebGuide G1812, University of Nebraska, Lincoln
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. 1978. Universals of language usage: Politeness phenomena. In E. Goody (Ed.), *Questions and politeness* (pp. 56-289). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, P. 1980. How and why are women more polite: some evidence from a Mayan community. In S. McConnell-Ginet, R. Borker & N. Furman (Eds.), *Women and language* in E. Goody (Ed.), *Questions and politeness*, pp. 56-289. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. 1987. *Politeness: Some universals in language usage*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Buckner, H.T. 1967. The police: the culture of a social control agency. A Ph.d dissertation in Sociology in the Graduate Division of the University of California, Berkeley
- Burns, R.B. 1994. *Introduction to Research Methods*. Melbourne: Longman Cheshire.
- Burton, D. 1981. Analyzing Spoken Discourse. in Coulthard, M. and Montgomery, M. (Eds), *Studies in Discourse Analysis*. London: Rutledge and Kegan Paul.
- Corey , T.S.B. & Henderson, C. (Eds.) 2005. *Encyclopedia of Forensic and Legal Medicine*.

- Volume 2. London: Elsevier pp. pp. 169-174.
- Clegg, S. R. 1989 *Frameworks of power*. London: Sage.
- Coward, R. and Ellis, J. 1977 *Language and Materialism*, London
- Culpeper, J. 1996. 'Towards an anatomy of impoliteness', *Journal of Pragmatics* 25, 349-367.
- Culpeper, J., Derek, B., and Anne, W. 2003. Impoliteness revisited: with special refence to dynamic and prosodic aspects. *Journal of Pragmatics* 35: 1545-1579
- Culpeper, J. 2005. Impoliteness and entertainment in the television quiz show: the weakest link. In Christie, C., Bargiela, F., Harris, S., Mills, S. and Watts, R. (eds) *Journal of Politeness Research: Language, Behaviour and Culture*, vol. 1 number 1 pp. 35-71
- Culpeper, J. 2008. Reflections on impoliteness, relational work and power in Bousfield, D & Locher (eds.), M. *Impoliteness in Language – Studies on its Interplay with Power and Practice*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Culpeper, J. 2011. *Impoliteness – Using Language to Cause Offence*. Cambridge: University Press.
- Deng, Y, et al. 1989. *Language and Culture*. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
- Dimitrova-Galaczi, E. 2005. Issues in the definition and conceptualisation of politeness. *Teachers College, Colombia University Working Papers in TESOL & Applied Linguistics*, vol 2, Issue 1, pp. 1-20
- Drizin, S. A., & Colgan, B. 2004. Tales from the juvenile confession front: A guide to how standard police interrogation tactics can produce coerced and false confessions from juvenile suspects. In G.D. Lassiter (Ed.), *Interrogations, confessions, and entrapment* (pp. 127-162). New York: Kluwer Academic/Plenum.
- Eagleton, T. 1983. *An introduction to literary theory*. Blackwell. UK.
- Eagleton, T. 1991. *Ideology: an introduction* , Verso New York, NY 10001-2291
- Edmonton Police Service 2015. What is Abuse? Accessed from www.edmontonpolice.ca/victim-support/what-is-abuse.aspx, 27/04/2015
- Eggs, S. 1994. *An introduction to systemic functional linguistics*. London: Pinter
- Erbert, L. A., & Floyd, K. 2004. Affectionate expressions as face-threatening acts: Receiver assessments. *Communication Studies*, 55(2), 254-270.
- Fairclough, N. 1989. *Language and power*. Cambridge: Polity Press

- Fairclough, N. 1992. *Discourse and Social Change*, London: Polity Press.
- Fairclough, N. 1995. *Critical discourse analysis: the critical study of language*. London: Longman
- Fairclough, N. And Wodak, R. 1997. Critical discourse analysis: an overview, in van Dijk T.A. (ed.) *Discourse as social Interaction*. London: Sage, pp. 67-97.
- Fairclough, N. 2001. *Language and Power* (second edition). England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Farinde, R.O. 1997. *A linguistics study of police/accused discourse*. An unpublished thesis in the department of English, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Farinde, R.O. 2011. *Questioning in Nigerian police-suspect discourse*. A paper presented at the annual conference of the Linguistic Association of Nigeria at Bayero University, Kano. Federal Republic of Nigeria: *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999*
- Fox, G. 1993. *A comparison of policespeak and normalspeak: a preliminary study*. In Sinclair, J.M, Hoey, M., and Fox, G. (eds) *Techniques of Description: spoken and written discourse*. London and New York, Routledge
- Fraser, B., & Nolen, W. 1981. The association of deference with linguistic form. *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 27, 93-111.
- Fraser, B. 1990. Perspectives on politeness. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 14, 219-236.
- French, P. and J. Local. 1986. Prosodic features and the management of interruptions. In C. Johns-Lewis, (ed.) , *Intonation in Discourse*. San Diego: College-Hill Press. 157-180,1986.
- Gall, J.P. et al. 2005. *Applying Educational Research*. Boston: Pearson.
- Geertz, C. 1973. *The interpretation of cultures*. New York: Basic Books.
- Goffman, E. 1967. *Interaction ritual: Essay on face to face behavior*. Garden city, NY: Anchor.
- Grice, H. P. 1975. Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and semantics*, vol. 3: Speech acts, pp.41-58. New York: Academic Press.
- Grosz, B. and Sidner, D. 1986. Attention, Intentions, and the Structure of Discourse. *Computational Linguistics* 12(3):175-204.
- Gudjonsson, G. H., Sigurdsson, J. F., Einarsson, E., Bragason, O. O. & Newton, Milgram, S. 1974. *Obedience to authority: An experimental view*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Gudjonsson, G.H., & MacKeith, J.A.C. 1982. False confessions: Psychological effects of

- interrogation. In A. Trankell (Ed.), *Reconstructing the past: The role of psychologists in criminal trials*, pp. 253-269. Deventer, The Netherlands: Kluwer
- Gudjonsson, G. H. 2003. *The psychology of interrogations and confessions: A handbook*. Chichester, England: John Wiley & Sons.
- Gudjonsson, G. H., Sigurdsson, J. F. and Einarsson, E. 2004. The role of personality in relation to confessions and denials. *Psychology, Crime and Law*, 10, 125-135.
- Gudjonsson, G. H. 2005. Fitness to be interviewed. . In J. Payne-James, R. W. Byard, T. S. Corey, & C. Henderson (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Forensic and Legal Medicine. Volume 2*. London: Elsevier , pp. 169-174.
- Gudjonsson, G. H. 2006. Disputed Confessions and Miscarriages of Justice in Britain: Expert Psychological and Psychiatric Evidence in the Court of Appeal. *The Manitoba Law Journal*, 31, 489-521.
- Gudjonsson, G. H. 2007. Investigative interviewing. In T. Newburn, T. Williamson & A. Wright (Eds.), *Handbook of Criminal Investigation*. Devon: Willan Publishing, pp 466-492
- Haugh, M. 2007. The discursive challenge to politeness research: An interactional alternative. *Journal of Politeness Research* 3, 295–317.
- Held, G. 1992. Politeness in linguistic research. In R. J. Watts, S. Ide & K. Ehlich (Eds.), *Politeness in language* ,pp.131-153. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter
- Henry, S., and Lanier, M. 2001. *What is crime? controversies over the nature of crime and what to do about it*. New York: Rowman and Littlefield Publishers.
- Ho, D. 1976, 'On the concept of face', *American Journal of Sociology* 81(4): 867--84.
- Hu, H. 1944, 'The Chinese concepts of "face"', *American Anthropologist* 46(1): 45--64.
- Huang, Y. 2008. Politeness principle in cross-cultural communication. *English Language Teaching*, vol. 1, no 1
- Hutchby, I. 1996. Power in discourse: the case of arguments on a British talk radio show. *Discourse and society*.7, 481-497
- Hutchby, I. and Wooffitt, R. 1998. *Conversation analysis: principles, practices and applications*. Cambridge: Polity Press
- Hutcheon, L. 1991. *Power and ideology : humanism and postmodernism*. Chrysalis Books Group Plc. Chicago
- Ide, S.1989. Formal forms of discernment: Two neglected aspects of linguistic politeness.

- Multilingua*, 8, 223-248.
- Ide, S., Hill, B., Carnes, Y., Ogino, T., & Kawasaki, A. 1992. The concept of politeness: An empirical study of American English and Japanese. In R. J. Watts, S. Ide & K. Ehlich (Eds.), *Politeness in language*, pp. 281-297. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Ide, S. 1993a, 'Linguistic politeness, III: linguistic politeness and universality', *Multilingua* 12(1).
- Ide, S. 1993b. Preface: The search for integrated universals of linguistic politeness. *Multilingua*, 12, 7-11.
- Inbau, F.E., Reid, J.E., Buckley, J.P and Jayne, B.P. 2001. Criminal interrogations and confessions. Gaithersburg, MD: Aspen
- Jourdan, C and Tuite , K. 2006. *Language, culture, and society: key topics in linguistic anthropology*. New York: Cambridge University Press
- Kassin, S. M., & Wrightsman, L. S. 1985. Confession evidence. In S. Kassin & L. Wrightsman (Eds.), *The psychology of evidence and trial procedure*, pp. 67-94
Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Kassin, S. M.1997. The psychology of confession evidence. *American Psychologist*, 52, 221-233.
- Kassin, S. M., Goldstein, C. J., & Savitsky, K. 2003. Behavioral confirmation in the interrogation room: On the dangers of presuming guilt. *Law and Human Behavior*, 27, 187-203
- Kassin, M.S., Steven A. Drizin, A.S., Thomas Grisso,T., Gudjonsson, H.G., Leo .A.R., Redlich,.D.A 2010. Police-Induced Confessions: Risk Factors and Recommendations. *Law Hum Behav* (2010) 34:3–38
- Kasper, G.1990. Linguistic politeness: Current research issues. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 14, 193-218.
- Kasper, G.1994. Politeness. In R. E. Asher et al. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of language and Linguistics*, pp. 3206-3212. Edinburgh: Pergamon and University of Aberdeen press.
- Katz, J.J. 1977. *Propositional structure and illocutionary force*. New York: Crowell
- Koch, H. 1996. *Casablanca: script and legend*. Woodstock. New York: Overlook Press
- Kress, G. 1991. Critical discourse analysis. *Annual review of applied linguistics*, 11, 84-99
- Krsul, I. and Spafford, E.H. 1997. Authorship analysis: identifying the author of a program.

- Computer Security*, 16:3: 233-257
- Labov, W. 1970. The study of language in its social context. *Studium Generale*, 23, 30-87.
- Lakoff, R. 1973. The logic of politeness, or, minding your p's and q's. *Chicago Linguistic Society*, 9, 292-305.
- Lakoff, R. 1975. *Language and woman's place*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Lakoff, R. 1989. The limits of politeness: Therapeutic and courtroom discourse. *Multilingua*, 8, 101-129.
- Laver, J. 1980. *The phonetic description of voice quality*. Cambridge University Press.
- Law Commission of Canada (ed.) 2004. *What Is a Crime? Defining Criminal Conduct in Contemporary Society*. UBC Press
- Leech, G. 1983. *Principles of pragmatics*: London : Longman
- Leo, R. A. 2008. *Police interrogation and American Justice*. Harvard University Press, London
- Lim, T. 1994. Facework and interpersonal relationships. In Stella, Ting-Toomey (ed.) *The challenge of facework: cross-cultural and interpersonal issues*, pp. 209–229. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press.
- Lindblad, P. 1992. *Rösten*. Lund. Studentlitteratur.
- Locher, M.A and Watts, J.R 2005. *Politeness theory and relational work* . In Christie, C., Bargiela, F., Harris, S., Mills, S., and Watts, R. (eds) *Journal of politeness research: Language, behaviour and culture*, vol 1 number 1
- Lukes, S. 1974. *Power: a radical view*. London: Macmillan.
- Lukes, S. (ed.) 1986. *Power*, Oxford: Blackwell
- MacMartin, Clare, Wood, Linda A., Kroger, Rolf O. 2001. Facework. In: Robinson, W.P., Giles, H. (Eds.), *The New Handbook of Language and Social Psychology*. Wiley, New York, pp. 221–237.
- Mallison, C. and Brewster, Z.W. 2005. Blacks and bubbas: stereotypes, ideology, and categorisation processes in restaurant servers' discourse. *Discourse and society*, 16, 787-807
- Marasek, K. 1997. *EEG & voice quality* (Tutorial) : <http://www.ims.unistuttgart.de/phonetik/EGG/frmst1.htm> accessed 17/06/2013
- Matsumoto, Y. 1988, 'Reexamination of the universality of face: politeness phenomena in Japanese', *Journal of Pragmatics*, 12(4): 403--26.
- Mieder, W .1993. *Proverbs are never out of season: popular wisdom in the modern age*. New York, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Meier, A. J. 1995a. Defining politeness: Universality in appropriateness. *Language Sciences*, 17, 345-365.
- Meier, A. J. 1995b. Passages of politeness. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 24, 381-392.
- Meissner, C. A., Russano, M. B., & Narchet, F. M. 2010. The importance of a laboratory science for improving the diagnostic value of confession evidence. In G. D. Lassiter & C. Meissner's (Eds.) *Interrogations and confessions: Research, practice, and policy*. Washington, DC: APA.
- Meissner C. A., Redlich A., Bhatt S., and Brandon, S. 2012. *Interview and interrogation methods and their effects on true and false confessions*. UK. Campbell Systematic Reviews
- Mey, J. 2001. *Pragmatics. An introduction*. Oxford
- Milne, R., & Bull, R. 1999. *Investigative interviewing: Psychology and practice*. Wiley. New York
- Mills, S. 2003. *Gender and politeness*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mixdorff, H. 2002. Speech technology, ToBI, and making sense of prosody. In B. Bernard & M., Isabelle (Eds.) *Speech prosody*. Proceedings, Aix-en-Provence, France.
- Moradeyo, S, A. 2004. *Sociolinguistic using linguistic means to detect crime during police interrogation: a case study of Nigeria Police station, Bodija, Ibadan, Oyo State*. A B.A project, Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.
- Morris, C.W. 1938. Foundations of the theory of signs. In Neurath, O., Carnap, R. And Morris, C.(eds) *International encyclopedia of unified science*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, pp. 77-138
- Narvaez, D., Getz, I., Rest, J.R., Thoma, S.J. 1999. Individual Moral Judgment and Cultural Ideologies, *Developmental Psychology*, Vol. 35, No. 2, 478-488, American Psychological Association, Inc.
- Nurani, L. M. 2008. Critical review of ethnographic approach. *Jurnal Sosioteknologi Edisi 14 Tahun 7, Agustus 2008*, 441-446
- Nwoye, O. 1992, 'Linguistic politeness and socio-cultural variations of the notion of face', *Journal of Pragmatics* 18(4): 309--28.
- Obilade, T. 1984. Mother-tongue influence on polite communication in second language. *American Psychological Association 4.4: 295-299*
- Odebunmi, A. 2002. "The Pragmatics of Face Acts in a Nigerian University Administration". in Babatunde, S.T. and Adeyanju, D.S. (Eds), *Language, Meaning and Society: Papers in Honour of E. Adegbija At 50*. Ilorin: Haytee Press, 1791-192

- Odebunmi, A. 2009. Politeness in Print Media Political Interviews in Nigeria. *California Linguistic Notes*, Volume XXXIV, No. 1, 2-11
- Odebunmi, A. 2010. Tracking ideology in political news. *California Linguistic Notes* Volume XXXV No. 2, pp 1-23
- Odebunmi, A. 2013. Greetings and politeness in doctor-patient encounters in Southwestern Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Society, Culture & Language* (1) 1, pp 102-115
- Ofshe, R. J., & Leo, R.A. 1997a. The social psychology of police interrogation: The theory and classification of true and false confessions. *Studies in Law, Politics, and Society*, 16, 189-251.
- Ofshe, R. J., & Leo, R. A. 1997b. The decision to confess falsely: Rational choice and irrational action. *Denver University Law Review*, 74, 979-1122.
- Ogunsiji, A. 1989. *The Language of the Police in Ila Local Government Area of Oyo State: A Discourse Analysis Approach*. An MA project in the department of English and Literary Studies, University of Ibadan.
- Ojoawo, A. O. Politeness strategies among Yoruba speakers of English. An M.A project in the Department of English, University of Ibadan
- Okonkwo, C.O. 2012. *Criminal law in Nigeria (second edition)*. Spectrum Books Limited. Ibadan
- Okunola, Z. P. 2005. *Taboos in Yoruba literary discourse*. An M.A project in the department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan
- Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (7th edition). Oxford University Press. New York
- Oyebade, T.A. 2007. *The pragmatics of English usage in police communication in Ibadan metropolis*. Unpublished MA English Dissertation, University Of Ibadan
- Oyetade, S.O. 1994. Taboo expressions in Yoruba. *Africa and Ubersee Band 77*, pp.90-103
- Oyetade, S.O. 1995. A sociolinguistic analysis of address forms in Yoruba. *Language in Society*, vol 24, number 4, pp 515-535
- Page, R.E. 2003. Cherie: lawyer, wife, mum: contradictory patterns of representation in media reports of Cherie Booth/Blair. *Discourse and society*, 14, 559-579.
- Paltridge, B. 2006. *Discourse analysis*. Continuum. New York
- Quast, H. 2001. *Automatic Recognition of Nonverbal Speech: An Approach to Model the*

- Perception of Para- and Extralinguistic Vocal Communication with Neural Networks.*
Thesis. University of Göttingen
- Raine, P. 2010. An application of the Sinclair and Coulthard (1975) method of discourse analysis. http://www.cels.bham.ac.uk/resources/essays/raine_sinc-coul.pdf
Retrieved 1/5/ 2011
- Roach, Peter. 2000. Techniques for the phonetic description of emotional speech. In *Proceedings of the ISCA Workshop on Speech and Emotion*. Newcastle, Northern Ireland. September 2000, pp 53-59)
- Sadiq, M. T. 2011. *A Discourse Analysis of the Language of Interrogation In Police/Criminal Investigations In The Kano Metropolis*. An M A Thesis Submitted To The Department of English and Literary Studies, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Salman, R. K. 2009. Rights of Accused Person Under Nigerian Criminal Justice System: A Need For Improvement, *Confluence Journal of Private and Property Law*, Vol. 2 Part 1, p. 137
- Scollon, R. and Scollon, W.S. 2001. *Intercultural Communication: A Discourse Approach (Second Edition)* Blackwell Publishers Ltd. UK
- Schiller, J., Black, W. & Murphy, P.V. *Crime and criminality*
www.des.ucdavis.edu/faculty/Richerdson/Bookonline accessed 15/5/2015
- Sigurdsson, J. F., & Gudjonsson, G. H. 1996. The psychological characteristics of false confessors: A study among Icelandic prison inmates and juvenile offenders. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 20, 321-329.
- Sigurdsson, J. F. and Gudjonsson, G. H. 2001. False confessions: The relative importance of psychological, criminological and substance abuse variables. *Psychology. Crime and Law*, 7, 275-289.
- Sinclair, J. and Coulthard, R.M. 1975. *Toward an Analysis of Discourse*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Stoddart, M. C. J 2007. Ideology, Hegemony, Discourse: A Critical Review of Theories of Knowledge and Power, *Social Thought & Research*, Vol. 28. 192-222
- Stokoe, E. H. 2003. Mothers, single women and sluts: gender, morality and membership categorisation in neighbour disputes. *Feminism & Psychology*, 13, 317-344
- Stygall, G. 1994. *Trial language; differential discourse processing and discursive formation*.

- Amsterdam/ Philadelphia : John Benjamin Publishing Company.
- Sunday, A.B. 2010. Verbal assault in Fuji music: the case Sikiru Ayinde Barrister and Kollington Ayinla. *Journal of Pragmatics*. 2010: 1403-1421
- Svartvik, J. 1968. *The Evans statements: a case for forensic linguistics*. Gothenburg: University of Gothenburg: Benjamins
- Tappan, P.W. 1947. "Who Is the Criminal?" *American Sociological Review* 12: 96-102.
- Terebo, O.Y. 2012. *The role of police interpreters in interrogation exercise: a case study of Iyaganku Police station, Ibadan*. Unpublished MA project in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.
- Terkourafi, M. 2008 Toward unified theory of politeness, impoliteness and rudeness in Bousfield, D. & Locher, M. (eds.), *Impoliteness in language – Studies on its interplay with power and practice*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Thomas, J. 1995. *Meaning in interaction: An introduction to pragmatics*. London: Longman.
- Trautmüller, Hartmut. 2000. *Evidence for demodulation in speech perception*. <http://www.ling.su.se/staff/hartmut/demod.pdf> (contribution to ICSLP 2000). Accessed 17/06/2013
- Trautmüller, Hartmut. 2001. *Paralinguale Phänomene*. To appear in Ammon, A. Dittmar, N & Mattheier, K. J. (Eds.). *Soziolinguistik – Ein Internationales Handbuch zur Wissenschaft von Sprache und Gesellschaft*. 2nd ed. Berlin/New York
- Urbanova, L. A 1986. *Reader in English Stylistics*. V Prešove: *Filozoficka fakulta v Prešove*.
- van de Walle, L. 1993. *Pragmatics and classical sanscrit: a pilot study in linguistic politeness*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamin Publishing Company
- Van Dijk, T.A. 1998. *Critical discourse analysis*. <http://www.hum.uva.nl/teun/cda.htm>. (1/25/2000) accessed 10/06/2013
- van Dijk T. A. 2006. *Ideology and discourse: A Multidisciplinary Introduction*, www.discourses.org/.../Ideology/ accessed 10/6/2013
- Teo, P. 2005. Mandarinizing Singapore: a critical analysis of slogans in Singapore's "speak Mandarin" campaign. *Critical discourse studies*, 2. 121-142.
- Thomas, J. (1995). *Meaning in interaction: An introduction to pragmatics*. London: Longman.
- Walton, D. 2002. The interrogation as a type of dialogue. *Journal of pragmatics*, 35, 1771-1802
- Wardaugh, R. 1986. *An introduction to sociolinguistics*. Oxford. Basic Blackwell.

- Watts, R. J. 1989. Relevance and relational work: Linguistic politeness as politic behavior. *Multilingua*, 8, 131-166.
- Watts, R. J. 1992a. Linguistic politeness and politic verbal behavior: Reconsidering claims for universality. In R. J. Watts, S. Ide & K. Ehlich (Eds.), *Politeness in language* (pp. 43-69). Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Watts, R. J., Ide, S., & Ehlich, K. 1992b. Introduction. In R. J. Watts, S. Ide & K. Ehlich (Eds.), *Politeness in language* (pp. 1-17). Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Watts, R.J. 2003. *Politeness*. Cambridge University Press
- Weber, M. 1914. 'The Economy and the Arena of Normative and De facto Powers', in Roth, G. and Wittich, C. (eds), *Economy and Society*. New York: Bedminster Press.
- Werkhofer, K. T. 1992. Traditional and modern views: the social constitution and the power of politeness. In Richard J. Watts, Sachiko Ide & Konrad Ehlich (eds.) *Politeness in Language: Studies in its history, theory and practice*, pp. 155–199. Berlin & New York, NY: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Wiersma, W. 1986. *Research Methods in Education: An Introduction*. Newton: Allyn and Bacon
- Wilson, S. 1977. The use of ethnographic techniques in educational research. *Review of Educational Research*. 47: 245-265
- Wodak, R. 1996. *Disorders of Discourse*. London and New York: Longman.
- Wodak, R. 1997. Das Ausland and anti-semitic discourses: the discursive construction of the other, in Riggens, S. (ed.) *The language of politics and exclusion*. London: Sage, pp. 65-87
- Wodak, R. 2001. What is CDA about? A summary of its history, important concepts and its development. In *Methods of critical discourse analysis* (eds) Wodak, R. And Meyer, M. London: Sage
- Woods, P. 1986. *Inside school: ethnography in educational research*. London: Routledge.
- Wrong, D. H. 1979 *Power: its forms, bases and uses*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Yang, L. C. 1996. Interruptions and intonation. *Spoken Language, Proceedings., Fourth International Conference Vol. 3*, pp. 1872-1875.

Appendix

CASE 1

1. IPO: What is your link with the bank (mentioned the name of the bank)?
2. SUS: I got an appointment with the bank in 2008 [int.]
3. IPO: [as what?]
4. SUS: As a marketer
5. IPO: As a marketer, tell us the schedule of your work
6. SUS: My schedule of duty is to look for customers, open accounts for them and follow instructions given by my manager
7. IPO: I was made to understand that there are some customers who do not come the bank for transaction.
8. SUS: Sure
9. IPO: How?
10. SUS: The manager tells us where to go..... whenever a customer calls the bank that they want to make deposit [int.]
11. IPO: [] but mostly you are the one that usually goes to these customers, being the most senior officer
12. SUS: We are three there that are seniors [int]
13. IPO: [But] I want a clarification about
14. this (the IPO mentioned the name of the suspect)
15. SUS: We were employed the same day; I was an office assistant but by the time they want to employ us, they employed about three of us, after which I was transferred to Odogbolu, but my manager insisted I should be retained with the branch
16. IPO: (Long silence) You are aware why you are here? Why are you here?
17. SUS: There is an allegation that there is an issue of money, customer's money [int.]
18. IPO: [To] the tune of?
19. SUS: I don't know it offhand

20. IPO: Don't even tell me that. It has been read to you
21. SUS: They said that 16 point something million
22. IPO: Is it true?
23. SUS: No
24. IPO: Explain
25. SUS: Actually, there is one customer who has 14 million in her account (int.)
26. IPO: (int.)
And who is that customer?
27. SUS: (Mentioned the name of the customer) and she has collected 3 million, five zero nine
28. IPO: You, explain here how you normally collect money from the customer, because I was made to understand you have your own personal bank outside where you are working.
29. SUS: I don't have any bank outside where I work (int.)
30. IPO: (mentioned the name of the bank)
31. SUS: That is what I have
32. IPO: Listen to me, I was told you have another bank, a situation where you collect cash from those people (short silence) when those people need money, they will issue cheque.....
33. SUS: I don't have a personal bank
34. IPO: Okay, explain how you know that woman and some other customers like her
35. SUS: Narrated how he met the customers, and the woman whose name he earlier Mentioned
36. IPO: So, what happened to her own account she has been operating with you? Kì ló happen sí àwọn owó yẹn?
37. SUS: My partner usually goes to (int.)
38. IPO: (I am) coming, record tí woman yẹn keep shows that your signature is on the signed documents
39. SUS (Silence)
40. IPO: See, this is you and me, òkú ò kí n'fara pamọ́ fún ẹni tí ó má a sìn. Uhn, what did

you benefit from the transaction?

41. SUS: I am not hiding anything away from you. Even if my partner is here, I will say all these in his presence [int]
42. IPO: It is you that will take us to where we can get him
43. IPO 2: How do you mean he cannot deny? Is there any written documents that he signed?(raised her voice)
44. SUS: I don't know where he lives, but I do normally send him text messages
45. IPO: Ọgbéni, ọgbéni, all these things are nothing. ẹ́ ọ́ sign sínú ìwé kànkán pé òun gbowó lówó ẹ?
46. SUS: No
47. IPO 2: So you are doing it on a humanitarian ground
48. IPO: You know all you people were doing was not within the ethics of the bank, uhn?
49. SUS: Yes
50. IPO: It is not within the ethics of the bank for you and your manager to be exchanging money without the authority of the bank
51. SUS: Actually, ìgbà tí mo pè é, ọ́ promise [int.]
52. IPO: [Uhn] Uhn!! Uhn!!!

CASE 2

1. IPO: Bàbá, ẹ́ ẹ́ mọ X (mentioned the name of the complainant)
Old man, do you know? (mentioned the name of the complainant)
2. SUS: Mo mọ ọ́n
I know him
3. IPO: ẹ́ ẹ́ mọ Y
Do you know Y
4. SUS: Mo mọ ọ́n
I know him
5. IPO: Bóo lẹ ẹ́ mọ ọ́
How did you know him?
6. SUS: Èmi mo talẹ fún wọ́n

I was the one who sold them a piece of land

7. IPO: Lát'òdún wo?

Since when?

8. SUS: Ó tódún méta n sù

It's about three years now

9. IPO: Níbo ni ilè yẹn wà?

Where is the land?

10. SUS: Arúgbó OO

11. Ní' bàdàn n bí?

In Ibadan here?

12. SUS: Bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni

Yes

13. IPO: Èlọ̀ lẹ̀ tàá?

How much did you sell it?

14. SUS: Three hundred thousand naira

15. Èlọ̀ lẹ̀ tà á fún X?

How much did you sell it to X

16. Three hundred thousand

17. Èlọ̀ lẹ̀ tà á fún Y?

18. *How much did you sell it to Y?*

19. SUS: Three hundred thousand naira

20. IPO: Sé ẹ̀ fún wọ̀n ní receipt?

Did you give them receipt?

21. SUS: A fún wọ̀n ní rìsítì

We gave them receipts

22. IPO: Èlọ̀ lẹ̀ kọ̀ sínú receipt?

How much did you write on the receipts?

23. SUS: Three fifty (thousand)

24. IPO: Ti X n kó?

And that of X?

25. SUS: Three hundred

26. IPO: Okay, èyin àwọn mélódó lejo talè?

Okay, you and who sold the land?

27. SUS: Èmi àti (int.)

I and

28. IPO: E dúró, ta ló n jé (mention some names on the documents accompanying the sold parcel of land)

Wait,, who bears (mention some names on the documents accompanying the sold parcel of land)

29. SUS: Answered accordingly (int.)

30. IPO: It's okay. Kí ẹ tó talè fún wọn, sé ejó wà lórí ilè náà?

It's okay. Before you sold the land to them, was there a dispute over it?

31. SUS: Ejó ò sí lórí ilè nígbà ta talè fún wọn

There was no dispute over the land when we sole the land to them

32. IPO: Nísin yí n kó?

And now?

33. SUS: (Trying to digress by grumbling and was incoherent) (int.)

34. IPO: Bàbá, sé ẹ mò pé ejó wà lórí

kí ẹ tó talè (accusing the old man)

Old man, you know there was a dispute over that land before you sold it

35. SUS: Rára o

No, not at all

36. IPO: Kí ló wá dé téjò wá bèrè nígbà tẹ ti talè fún wọn?(raised his voice)

So, why did disputes start when you sold the land to them?

37. SUS: Ehn! Àwa kó ò, iyẹn ín şejo àwa (int.)

It's not us, that is not our fault

38. IPO: Aha! şebí èyin lẹ nilè?

Aha! but you were the land owner?

39. SUS: Ehn, ẹ máa gbó, àwa la nilè nítòótó (int.)

Yes, listen, we are the owners of the land truly

40. IPO: Owo tí ẹ gbà báwo lẹ şe pin in?

The money you collected, how did you share it?

41. SUS: Láàrín wa la gbé pin (int.)
*We shared it among
among ourselves*
42. IPO: Èlọ́ ló bọ́ síyíín lówọ́ nínú seven hundred and fifty thousand
got to your hand from seven hundred and fifty naira?
43. SUS: Mi ò lè sọ ba ẹ pin
I cannot say how we shared it
44. IPO: It's okay. Ní síí táwọ́n èyàn tí n dàwọ́n láàmú lórí ilẹ̀ yẹ̀n, kí lẹ̀ wá ẹ̀ si?
It's okay. Now that people are troubling them over the land, what have you done ?
45. SUS: Mo lọ ibẹ (int.)
I went there
46. IPO: Ní sùúrù, látì ìgbàwo ni ẹ̀jọ́ tí bèrẹ̀ lórí ilẹ̀ yí?
Be patient, since when has there been a dispute over the land?
47. SUS: kò tì ju ọ̀dún méjì
It's not more than two years
48. IPO: Ọ̀dún méjì?
Two years?
49. SUS:Uhn!
50. IPO: Kí ló dé tẹ̀ ẹ̀ talẹ̀ f'ọ̀dún méjì tẹ̀jọ́ dẹ̀ wà lórí ẹ̀ tẹ̀ ẹ̀ rí ǹh̀k̀àǹk̀àǹ ẹ̀ si?
*Why did you sell a land for two years and there are issues over it and you have not found
something to do about it?*
51. Ẹ̀ ẹ̀mi ni n wá kólé le ni ọ̀gàà mi?
Am I the one building on it my boss?
52. IPO: Ah! Ah!! (short silence). It's okay. Ìgbà tí ìjà tí wà lórí ilẹ̀ nàà bá yí, kí lẹ̀ fẹ̀ ẹ̀?
*Ah! Ah!! (short silence).It's okay. Now that there is a dispute on the land, what do you
want to do?*
53. SUS: Ehn, bí wọ́n bá gbá mí láyè, mà á kówó wọ́n wá ní Monday
Ehn, if I am permitted, I will return their money on Monday
54. IPO (short silence) Ẹ̀ dúró bàbá, ẹ̀ sọ nkan tẹ̀ sọ again (raises his voice)
Wait old man, repeat what you said again

55. SUS: (repeated what he said earlier)

56. IPO: Bàbá, wán gbowó wọn kí ẹ tó kúrò nǐbí

Old man, they will collect their money before you leave here

57. SUS: Ọwọ yín ló wà

It's in your hand

58. IPO: Yes!

59. SUS: It's all right oo, but eh (int.)

60. IPO: Ẹ mò pé wàhálà wà lórí ilẹ yẹn kẹ tó talẹ fún wọn

You know there are controversies over the land before you sold it

61. SUS: Kò sí wàhálà lórí ilẹ ọgá mi (int.)

There were no issues over the land my boss

62. IPO: Ẹ jẹ kí n sọ fún yín, wípe ẹ sọpé owó lẹ fẹ dá padà

túmò sí pé ẹ gbowó yẹn lònà jìbìtì ni(integrity)

Let me tell you, that you said you will return their money on Monday shows you collected their money in a dubious way.

63. SUS: On tó jẹ kí n sọ bẹ ẹ ni pé (int.)

The reason I said so is that

64. IPO: Ẹ má sọrò, tí n ba sọrò tán (int.)

Don't say anything until I am through

65. SUS:

Ẹ máa gbọ (int.)

Listen to me

66. IPO:

Ẹ gbọ tẹmi (raises

his voice to shut the suspect down)

Listen to me

67. SUS: Yes sir

68. IPO: Ẹ mò pé ilẹ yẹn kí n ẹ tiyín kẹ tó tàá

You know that land was not yours before you sold it

69. SUS: Àwa la nilẹ o bàbàà mi (int.)

The land was ours (my father)

70. IPO: Ní ọ̀nà jìbìtì ni ẹ fì talẹ yẹn(integrity)

You sold the land in a dubious way

71. SUS: Şè bí oun tí wọn wí fún yín nìyẹn

That was what you were told

72. IPO: Anybody tí ẹ bá fẹ̀ pè kẹ̀ pè é ní sín o, ẹ̀ ẹ̀ san seven hundred thousand fáwọn people
yí kẹ̀tó kúrò níbí lé nì o

You can call whoever you want to call now, you are paying that money (seven hundred and fifty thousand naira) before you leave this place today

73. SUS: Èmi ò lẹ̀nì kànkán tí mà á (int.)

I don't have anyone to call

74. IPO: ẹ̀ ẹ̀ san owó yẹn kẹ̀ tó kúrò níbí lénìí. Oníjìbítí ni yín

You will pay that money before you leave here today; you are a dubious (419) man

75. SUS: Ẹ̀ jẹ́ kí n sọ̀ nkan fún yín (int.)

Let me tell you

76. IPO: Ní sùúrù, oníjìbítí ni yín. Ẹ̀ dẹ̀ sọ̀ pé ẹ̀ ò ríran

Calm down, you are dubious and you claim to have visual impairment

77. SUS: O o! ògá mi

All right my master

78. IPO: Ẹ̀ ẹ̀ wà níbí tí tí tẹ̀ ma fi san owó olówó¹¹

You will remain in our custody till you pay that money

79. SUS: Má a gbọ̀ tẹ̀mi, jẹ́ kí n sọ̀ fún o (int.)

Listen to me, let me tell you

80. IPO: Fẹ̀ni ni kẹ̀ ẹ̀ gbọ̀ because ẹ̀ ti wùwà olẹ̀¹

You should be the one to listen to me because you have actually acted like a thief

81. SUS: Ẹ̀ şa jẹ́ n fẹ̀sì (int.)

Let me respond

82. IPO: Ẹ̀ ẹ̀ le fẹ̀sì o

You cannot respond

83. SUS: Yes sir

CASE 3

1. IPO: Bàbá, is it true that you are after his life?

2. SUS: It's not tue

3. IPO: Ehn!
4. SUS: It is not true
5. IPO: What actually is causing the dispute?
6. SUS: I don't know the reason. The reason is that (int)
7. IPO (int) How is this man to you?
8. SUS: because he is my junior brother
9. IPO: Uhn!! What is the distance your area and his area?
10. SUS: The same compound
11. IPO: Is he a blood relation?
12. SUS (Not being able to continue with the discourse in English requested if he could switch to Yoruba. The request was granted by the IPO) relationship kan ò sí ju pé èmi ò ta ilée wọn
The only relationship between us is that I don't intend to sell his house
13. IPO: Kí lo wá fẹ̀ tà?
What then did you want to sell?
14. SUS: Èmi ò ta òkànkan
I am not selling anything
15. IPO: Kí lẹ̀ wá n jà fún?
What then are you fighting for?
16. SUS : Èmi rẹ̀ ò jà
We are not fighting (int)
17. IPO (int) È pè é lórí phone tàbẹ̀ẹ̀ pè é lórí phone?
Did you call him two days ago or not?
18. SUS:Pe tani?
Called who?
19. IPO: Ọkùnrin yí
This man
20. SUS: Èmi ò pè é lórí phone oo

I did not call him on the phone

21. IPO: Okay, ó ní ẹ pe òun lórí phone

He said you called him on the phone

22. SUS: Mi ò pè é lórí phone

I did not call him on the phone

23. IPO: Bàbá, ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta? A ma kọ letter sí àwọn network láti find out o, tẹ bá paró a má a get a dẹ ma charge yín sí court; a má a gbéyín lọ sílé ejó. ẹ pè é níjẹta tàbí ẹ ẹ pè é níjẹta? (raising his voice)

Old man, did you call him two days ago or not? We are going to contact the telecommunications outfits and find out, and if it is discovered that you are lying, you will be charged to court

24. SUS: Mo pè é níjẹta mo ní

I called him two days ago; I said

int

25. IPO:

Kí lẹ pè é fún? (raised his voice and banged the table?)

Why did you call him?

26. SUS: Nígbà tó jẹ pé àbúrò mi ni

When he is my younger brother

27. IPO: Kí lẹ sọ fun lórí phone?

What did you tell him on the phone?

28. SUS: Mo ní báwo la ẹ fẹ ríra simple thing

I asked how we were going to see each other

29. IPO: Kí lẹ fẹ ri fún? Ẹ sòrò now bàbà

What did you want to see him? Talk now old man!

30. SUS: Báyàn bá ti jọ ríra tipé, èyàn lè pè lórí phone

Since it's being a while we last saw each other, I deemed it fit to call him on the phone

int

31. IPO:

lẹ fẹ ri fún? Ẹ fẹ pá?

Why did you want to see him? You wanted to kill him?

Ehn, Kí

32. SUS: *(Trying to explain the relationship that exists between him and the complainant and how his father gave out the controversial parcel of land to the complainant's father on a compassionate ground)* [int]

33. IPO: Kí ló şelè bàbá yìi to kàn n' r'ojò, şé mo wá bère history níbí bàyí ni? Kí lo wá dórí ilè wọn? Kí lo fè lọ ta ilé wọn fún? Kí lo wá lọ'bè?

What is it old man that you are just narrating story, am I here to ask you to tell me history/story? What were you looking for on his land? Why did you want to sell his house. What were you doing there?

34. SUS: Ilè ẹ̀ bàbá mi ni
It is my father's land

35. IPO: Ibo? Şé ilè tí bàbá rẹ̀ fún wọn, ibè ló n' gbé?
Where? Are you living on the land your father gave them?

36. SUS: Agbo ilé bàbá mi ni [int]
It is my father's family compound

37. IPO: O lè lọ agbo ilé but kí lo wá lọ ilè tí wọn ilé sí tí o tún fè gbe tà?
You can go to the family compound but what were you looking for on his own particular land that you even wanted to sell it?

38. SU: Mi ò gbé e tà
I am not selling it

39. IPO: O ò gbe tà! Meeting kí lo wá fè ba şe? şé ẹ̀ jọ ma n' şe meeting ọmọ ilé tẹ̀lẹ̀ ni?
You are not selling it! What form of meeting were you planning to hold with him? Have you been holding family meetings before?

40. SUS: Ìnkan tó fa gbogbo èyí ni pé èmi ni Mógàjí ilé e wa.... [int]

41. IPO: Ilẹ̀ náà ni mógàjí ma n' tà kiri (Derisively)

All family heads do is to sell land indiscriminately

42. SUS: Èmi ò ta'lẹ̀ kiri

I am not in the habit of selling land indiscriminately

43. IPO: Àní kí lẹ̀ fẹ́ fi' lẹ̀ yẹn ẹ̀?

I mean what do you want to do with the land?

44. COMP: There is even a letter from his lawyer asking me to remove my building from the land

45. IPO: Lawyer wo?

Which lawyer?

46. SUS: (Mentioned the name of the lawyer)

47. IPO: What is the problem with your lawyer?

48. SUS: Kò sí problem kan ju pé

There is no problem than that

(int)

49. IPO:

Letter wo lẹ̀ kọ̀ pé kán gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀?

What letter did you write that he should remove

his building from the land?

50. SUS: Ọmọ̀ sísítà mí ní mọ́ fún ní ìwé kó fún bàbá rẹ̀

I asked my sister's child to give it to his/her father

51. IPO: Ibo ni ilé àwọn yẹn wà?

Where is the residence of those people?

52. SUS: (Trying to respond)

53. IPO: Kí ló dé tẹ̀ fí ní kí wọn gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀?

Why did you ask him to remove his building from the land?

54. SUS: Ó ti wó léyìn

It has collapsed at the back

55. IPO: Kí ló kàn ẹ̀ ní bẹ̀? Ilé wọn wó, nkan tó bá wu onílé ló lè ẹ̀. What is your own

interest? Alára ní ara ò ro òun, ẹ̀ ní ó kú àisùn, ó kú àìwo. Ìwé kí lẹ̀ fún wọn? (Banging the table)

What is that your problem with that? His house collapsed; he has the right to decide what to do about that. What is your own interest. A burden bearer claims not to be experiencing any pain; why then are you unnecessarily sympathetic?

56. SUS: Ìwé kí wọn gbé ilé wọn kúrò lórí ilẹ̀.

The letter was meant to ask him to remove his building from the land.

57. IPO: Torí k̀ini?

Why?

58. SUS: Torí pé a f̀e lo il̀e

Because we want to use the land

59. IPO: Il̀e wo?

Which land?

60. SUS: Il̀e tí bàbá mi f̀un.....

The land my father gave...

int

61. IPO:

Ìwé wo ni bàbá yín se tó fi f̀un wòn ní'l̀e?

What document did your father give them to the fact

that he gave them the land?

62. SUS: Il̀e bàbá mi ni

It is my father's land

63. IPO: Ọwọ́ tani bàbá yín ti ra'l̀e?

From whom did your father procure the land?

64. SUS: Bàbá mi ò ra'l̀e. Ìgbà tí wòn ǹ b̀o...

*My father did not buy the land (from anyone),
when he was coming.....*

int

65. IPO:

Ì'átòrun ni wòn ti gbé il̀e l̀owó!

He brought while coming from heaven!

66. SUS: Ibi tí wòn dé sí ǹun

That was where they settled on their arrival

67. IPO: S̀e o ri pé òótó ti yojú ǹsin ỳi. O f̀e kí wòn gbé il̀e wòn kúrò il̀e; tí wòn ò bá gbé il̀e wòn kúrò l̀órí, il̀e wà á pa wòn?

You can now see that the truth has been revealed now; you want him to remove his building from the and if he fails to do that, you will kill him

68. SUS: Kò sí ibi tí mo kó sí pé ǹ ó pa l̀agbájá, èmi ò pa anybody

I never wrote it anywhere that I wanted to kill anyone.

69. IPO: S̀e ẹ́ ní copy ìwé yèn l̀owó?

Do you have a copy of the letter?

70. SUS: Ó wà l̀owó ọmò mi

It is with my child

71. IPO: È fi phone pè é

Call him on the phone

CASE 4

1. IPO: Are you ready to say the truth now?

2. SUS: Mo pè é ní ọjọ yẹn, a jọ sòrò pé a fẹ fẹ ara wa, ó dè ní òun ti gbó

I called her that day and told her that I wanted us to start a relationship and she said ok. int.

3. IPO:

à paró o, má à paró o

Don't tell lies oo!!

4. SUS: Òótó nàà ni mà á sòò. L'ọjọ yẹn mo lọ gbe sùgbón kí SS tó dé ó ti yó. Ó ní òun má a dó ọmọ yí... int

I will say the truth. That day, I went to pick her but before SS got to my place he was already drunk and he insisted on sleeping with the girl

5. IPO:

SS ti mọtí yo!

SS was drunk!

6. SUS: Bẹ̀ni. Ó ti mu ọ́tí yó. Ó ní òun má a dó ọmọ yí o

Yes. He was drunk. He said he was going to sleep with her

7. IPO:

Ìyẹn ìyàwó ẹ?

You mean your girlfriend?

8. SUS: Mo ní kò possible. Sùgbón léyìn èyí, a jọ lọ sí junction láti lọ mu jèdí int

I said that would not be possible but after then we both went to the junction to take jèdí³

9. IPO:

tilẹ̀kùn mọ nígbà tí ẹ n jáde

But you locked her inside when you were going out

10. SUS: Ìgbà tí a wọlé padà, SS ní òun lò n má a kókó do sùgbón int

When we got back, Sheriff said he was going to be the first to sleep

³ A kind of locally made alcoholic drink that aids sexual performance

- with the girl but.....*
11. IPO: Int
 Ó sá à dó ọmọ
 yẹn. Ìgbà tó do tán n kó, ìwọ náà sẹ̀sẹ̀ wá do?
In short, he slept with the girl. When he was done, you too did sleep with her?
12. SUS: Ọmọ náà jí mi; ó ní inú n run òun.....
The woke me up to tell me she was experiencing stomach pain int
13. IPO: Má à paró o, má à
 paró o. Jẹwọ fún wa. È é mélédo ni iwọ do?
Don't lies oo. Tell us the truth. How many rounds did you go with her?
14. SUS: È męta
Three times/rounds
15. IPO: Ìgbà mélédo ni SS do
How many rounds did SS go with her?
16. SUS: Ìgbà méjì
Two rounds/times
17. IPO: Lójú ẹ ló basun lẹ ẹ mejì? Ìwọ náà wá basun lẹ ẹ męta. Ago mélédo lẹ wolé?
He slept with her in your presence after which you equally slept with her. What time did you go in?
18. SUS: Ìgbà int
 when
19. IPO: Ago mélédo lẹ wolé? (raised his voice)
What time did you go in?
20. SUS: Ten, ten ,ten mo ó dayín lóhùn daddy.
Ten!!! I am answering you daddy
21. IPO: Now listen, ìgbà tẹ ẹ tán án wolé tán, ẹ wá tilẹkùn mọ sínú ilé, ẹ wá lọ mutí, nígbà tẹ mutí tán, SS ní òun fẹ do?
Now listen to me, after you had deceived her into the room, you people locked her inside and went to drink after which SS said he would sleep with her?
22. SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir.
Yes sir.
23. IPO: Ago mélédo lẹ fi lady yẹn sílẹ níjọ kejì?

What time did you people release the lady the following day?

24. SUS: Twelve

25. IPO: Ìwà tẹ wù yẹn, báwo lẹ ẹ ri?

What will you call that very act of yours?

26. SUS: Daddy, kò da

Daddy, it is not good

27. IPO: Tíjọba báwá fiyà jẹyín lórí ẹ̀sẹ tí ẹ̀ sẹ̀ yí, taló jẹ̀bi?

If the government now takes a punitive measure against you now for your act, who is at fault?

28. SUS: Àwa la jẹ̀bi

We are the ones guilty

29. IPO: Ta ló fún ẹ ní phone number ọmọ yẹn

30. SUS: (Mentioned the name of another suspect whom he claimed gave him the number)

31. IPO: Now, ẹ sòrò yẹn lójú.... (trying to remember the name of the other suspect who had not been around all along).....

Now make your claim in the presence of

32. SUS: Mentioned the name as to remind the IPO

int

33. IPO: Very good of you! Tó bá wá yá bíyà kan bá n jẹ yín ẹ ẹ ní mọ ẹ̀sẹ tẹ ti sẹ tíyà fí n jẹyín.....

Now when you start suffering the consequences of your hideous act, you won't know you are actually reaping what you have sown...

In the process, two women IPO walked in and the IPO that started interrogation session.

34. IPO 2: Ẹ mú tape-rule wa ká wọn okó ẹ!

Bring a tape-rule for us to measure his penis!

35. SUS: Mummy ẹ jò ọ!

Mummy please!

36. IPO 3: ẹyin èyàn yí ẹ ẹ n sẹyàn gidi ò. Olórfurúkú ni yín

You people are not human beings (at all). You are misfortune bearer

37. SUS: Ẹ jòọ ma

Please ma

38. IPO3: Tani SS?

Who is SS?

39. SUS: SS wà nísàlè

SS is downstairs

40. IPO 3: Nígbà tẹ ti bá ọmọ yẹn sùn tó ti rẹ é, ta ló gbe lọ ilé ìwẹ?

After you people had slept with her to the point that she became tired, who carried her to the bathroom?

41. Èmi ni mo lọ wẹ é

I was the one

42. IPO 3: Şé o ní ìyá?

Do you have a mother?

43. SUS: Mo ní

Yes I do

44. IPO 3: Şé o lówọ̀n àbúrò obìnrin?

Do you have younger sisters?

45. SUS: Mo ní

Yes I do

46. IPO 3: O lè bá ìyá ẹ̀ sùn?

You can sleep with your mother?

47. IPO 1: O lè dó ìyá ẹ̀?

You can have sex with your mother?

48. IPO 3: No, sọ́ fún mi... kí ni reason tó ò lè bá ìyá ẹ̀ sùn?

No, tell me the reason you cannot sleep with your mother?

49. IPO 2: Olórí ibú ni ọ

You are an unfortunate being/ a misfortune bearer

50. IPO 3: Kí lo fẹ̀ fi ẹ̀ tẹ̀lẹ̀ tó ò bá gbelọ́ sí'lé ọ̀rẹ̀ ẹ̀?

What do you want to do to her before if you did not take her to your friend's place (to rape her)

51. IPO 1: Tó bá jẹ́ pé o ní intention láti fẹ̀, o ò ní sọ́pé kí ọ̀rẹ̀ ẹ̀ má a do. Olóríburúkú ni yín.

If you really had the plan of getting married to her, you would not have allowed your friend sleep with her. You unfortunate human beings.

52. IPO 1: Àwọn ẹ̀rù tí ẹ̀ gbà lówó ẹ̀ dà?
Where are the valuables you collected from her?
53. SUS: Mi ò lè paró, mi ò gba ẹ̀rù kànkán lówó ẹ̀
I can't lie, I did not collect anything from her
54. IPO 2: Jẹ́ kí n wo okó ẹ̀ bó ẹ̀ rí!
Let me see how your penis looks like!
55. IPO: Wón ní o gbókó ẹ̀ síta! (raised his voice)
You are asked to bring out your penis!
56. IPO 3: Gbé kí síta! (raised his voice)
Bring out the thing!
57. IPO 1: Olóríburúkú okó tí ò tó ònkan!
Unfortunate being, what a ridiculously small penis!
58. SUS: Mummy ẹ̀ jòó
Mummy please
59. Ẹ̀ ẹ̀ lè rójú rere ọ̀lórún
You can never see the favour of God

CASE 5

1. IPO: Níbo lò n lọ?
Where were you going?
2. SUS: Ìdo
3. IPO: Kí lò n lọ ẹ̀ ní Ìdó?
What were you going to do in Ido?
4. SUS: Mò n wáyàn lọ ni
I was going to look for someone
5. IPO: Tani?
Who ?
6. SUS: Bòdá James
Brother James
7. IPO: Báwo ló ẹ̀ jẹ́ sí ẹ̀?
How is he to you?

8. SUS: A ti jọ ẹ́ṣẹ́ rí kótó dipé wọn ní kí n lọ wà owó ẹ́ṣẹ́ wá int
We worked together before we I was asked to go and look
apprentice fee
9. IPO: Irú ẹ́ṣẹ́ wo lẹ jọ ẹ
What kind of work did you
do together?
10. SUS: Mecho
11. IPO: Kí ló n jẹ mecho?
What is mecho?
12. SUS: Mecho trailer
13. IPO: Mecho tàbí mechanic?
Mecho or mechanic?
14. SUS: Mechanic
15. IPO: Irú motor wo lẹ ma n túnṣe?
What type of automobile do you repair?
16. SUS: Daf
17. IPO: O ti wa lọ ibè rí?
Have you gone there to look for him before?
18. SUS: Mi ò lọ ilé wọn rí
I have never been to his house before
19. IPO: Ẹ́ mechanic nìwọ?
Are you a mechanic?
20. SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir
Yes sir
21. IPO: O ti kọ́ṣẹ́, o dẹ ti ẹ́ freedom?
You have learnt the work and you have got your freedom?
22. SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir
Yes sir
23. IPO: O ti lò tódún mélòdó?
You have spent up to how many years?
24. SUS: Mo ti lò tósù méta

I have spent up to three months

25. IPO: So, tí wọn bá gbé motor fún ẹ báyíí o ti lè ẹ?

So, if you are given a car to repair now you can repair it?

26. SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

27. IPO: O ò wá lọ báwọn òbí ẹ pé wọn ní ko wá owó ìyànda wá?

You did not tell your parents that you are asked to bring the freedom fee

28. SUS: Àwọn òbí mi ti kú

My parents are late

29. IPO: Ta ló fi ẹ senu isẹ?

Who put you at the work?

30. SUS: Nígbà tí mo fé wọ́sẹ́, ìrírí wọn

When I wanted to enrol, their experience

int
Ta ló fi ẹ senu isẹ
Who put you at the work?

31. IPO:

Ta ló fi ẹ senu isẹ

Who put you at the work?

32. Enìkankan ò fi mí senu isẹ́, sùgbón a ẹ àdéhùn oşù méfà

Nobody put me at the work, but we had a six-month agreement

33. IPO: Oşù méfà! ẹ́ o dẹ́ ti moşẹ́ báyíí?

Six month! Have you really perfected your knowledge of the work now?

34. SUS: Mo ti moşẹ́ yẹn díẹ

I have learnt the job to some extent

35. IPO: Níbo lo tí rí irin yíí? (pointing to the metallic object the complainant claimed the suspect wanted to strike him with)

Where did you find this iron object?

36. SUS: Níbi ẹşẹ́ ibi ta ti n jà náà ni

Very close to where we were fighting

37. IPO: Ìwọ àti talẹ́ n jà?

You and who were fighting?

38. IPO 2: Dòbálẹ́ ! (raised his voice)

Prostrate/lie down!

39. SUS: Èmi àti bọ̀bọ́ ọ̀lọ̀kadà

The commercial motorcyclist and I

40. IPO: Kí ló mú yín tẹ n jà?

Why were you fighting?

41. SUS: Ìgbà tí mo sọ pé ẹni à n wá lọ, wọn dè sọ pé òun ò lọ ibi kànkán mó

I said the person we were going to look for and he said he was not going again.....

42. IPO:

lọ?

The person we were going to look for?

43. SUS: Mo ní ẹni tí à n wá lọ, mi ò ri number rẹ ò sì lọ..

I said I could not find the person we were going to see and his number was not going through

44. IPO: Kí lo wá fẹ kólópa ó ẹ fún ẹ báyií?

What do you now want the police to do for you?

45. Tí mo bá rí àánú gbà, tí wọn fi mí síbi isẹ

If I can get their favour such that I would be assisted in learning a work

46. IPO:

Olópàá ni yóò fi ọ síbẹ! (laughter)

*The police will be the one to put you at work!
(laughter)*

47. IPO 3: (Laughter) is he not mad?

48. IPO 1: Şé Olópàá ni yóò wá fi ọ senu isẹ?

Is the police that will enrol you at work?

49. SUS: (Silence)

50. IPO 1: Ìyà ẹşẹ wo lo fẹ kólópa fi jẹ ẹ àbí o ò dẹşẹ báyií?

What punishment do you now expect from the police or don't you think you have erred?

51. SUS: Ìyà tó bá tó sí mi

The punishment the police deems fit for my kind of offence

52. IPO: Kí lẹşẹ rẹ?

What is your offence?

53. SUS: Olè ni kí a pè é

We can call it theft

54. IPO: Olè?

Theft ?

55. SUS: Bèni

Yes

56. IPO: Olè pórìsirísi, irú olè wo ni tì ẹ?

There are different kinds of theft, what category is yours?

57. SUS: (Silence)

58. IPO: But irin yí, ẹ̀ ̀wọ lo dógbón fipamó síbẹ̀ ni?

But this iron, were you the one that kept it there?

59. SUS: Èmi kó mo dógbón fipamó síbẹ̀

I was not the person that kept it there

60. IPO: Àwọn méjì ló ma ń sáà ẹ̀ irú yẹ. Ènikẹ̀jì ẹ̀ dà?

Such an operation is usually carried out by two people. Where is your accomplice?

61. SUS: Èmi nìkan nàà ni

I am the only person

62. IPO: Àní tejo ma ń ẹ̀ irú isẹ̀ yẹ

I mean your accomplice on the act

63. SUS: Mi ò ẹ̀rú isẹ̀ yí rí

I have never been involved in this act before

64. IPO 2: Àbáyé fẹ̀ ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ni? (raised his voice)

Do you want to incur the wrath of the evil forces of the world?

65. SUS: Látojó tí wọ̀n tí bí mi, mi ò ẹ̀rú isẹ̀ yí rí

Ever since I was born, I had never been involved in this kind of act before

66. IPO: Mò ń bọ̀, jẹ́ kí n ẹ̀ nkan tí mò ń ẹ̀ tán. Mà á fùn ẹ̀ ní mark to mama fi han ọ̀mọ ẹ̀, ìyẹ̀n tí o ò bá kú sẹ̀wọ̀n

I am coming, let me finish what I am doing. I will give you a mark with which you will tell your children your ordeal; that is if you don't end up dying in the prison

67. IPO 1: O jẹ̀ sòótó

You better say the truth

68. IPO: Wà á sọ̀ fún wọ̀n pé irọ̀ tí o pa òun ló kó bá ẹ̀ o

You will tell them you were severely dealt with for telling lies.

69. IPO 1: Níbo ni ilé ẹ?

Where is your house?

70. SUS: Sángo mò n gbé

I live in Sango

71. IPO: Area ibo ní Sango?

Which area in Sango?

72. SUS: Ibi ẹgbẹ ilé epo, lábẹ búkà yẹn

Close to the filling station, under that buka

73. IPO 2: Wèrè, o wá nílé?

Mad man, do you have a house?

74. You are a syndicate.

CASE 6

1. IPO: How did you meet the girl?

2. SUS: We stay in the same barracks

3. IPO: How long have you been moving (dating)?

4. SUS: Four months

5. IPO: Where do you normally meet?

6. SUS: We do meet in my aunt's place.

7. IPO: Is it with her knowledge?

8. SUS: Yes sir

9. IPO: If it is with her knowledge, why did she report you?

10. SUS: (Silence)

11. IPO: Why did you take her to the chemist to buy drugs?

12. SUS: After sleeping with her, she said she was scared of getting pregnant

13. IPO: When did you finish your secondary school?

14. SUS: 2009

15. IPO: And since then , what have you been doing?

16. SUS: I went for computer training and wrote JAMB

17. IPO: You sat for JAMB?

18. SUS: Yes sir

19. IPO: What was your score?
20. SUS: My score was 210
21. IPO: What are you hoping to study?
22. SUS: Law
23. IPO: You want make we finish your career. By the time your admission comes, you will be in remand.
24. SUS: (Silence)
25. IPO: You know thw offence wey carry you come na big offence, and if you gather the whole lawyers for this town, dem do remand you. Sebi your career don finish?
You know the offence that brought you here is a very big one and if you secure the service of all the lawyers in town, you will still be reamanded.
26. SUS: Silence
27. IPO: How old are you?
28. SUS: I am nineteen years old
29. IPO: You are ripe for conviction then.if I send to Agodi now, your career is finished. Nobody will ever come to take your bail.
30. SUS: (Silence)
31. IPO: You are a small boy. You said you are nineteen, you are more than that oo

CASE 7

1. IPO: O ti ba sùn rí?
You have slept with her before?
2. SUS: Bèèni
Yes
3. IPO: You slept with your student, and you call yourself a teacher
4. SUS: (Silence)
5. IPO: What discipline or morality are you teaching if you can be having fun with your students?
6. SUS: (Silence)
7. IPO: Monkey don hang itself oo. Ìtìjú ni fúu ẹ nísín yíí pé ìyàwó ẹ ń gbó pé ìwọ teacher ń bá ọmọ iléèwé sùn

The monkey has hung itself. It is a shameful thing to you for your wife to hear that you teacher are sleeping with your student

8. SUS: (Silence)

9. IPO: You are supposed to teach discipline and morality but you are the one now encouraging immorality

10. SUS: (Silence)

11. IPO: Kí ni qualification ẹ?

What is your qualification?

12. HND (Higher National Diploma)

13. IPO: In what?

14. SUS: Musicology

15. IPO: You go go sing well for Agodi

You will go and sing very well at Agodi

CASE 8: FRAUD

Background Information: This case involved a man, a stockbroker, in his early 50's, alleged to have duped a client to the tune of 3.5 million naira.

IPO: How long have you known the man (referring to the complainant)?

SUS: Mo ti mò ọ ní over fifteen years ago

I have known for over fifteen years now

IPO: Kí ló wá ẹlẹ?

What then happened?

SUS: (Trying to recollect the date, as he had indicated in his statement) Can I refer to this(statement)?

IPO: Go on

SUS: I wan t to go through the cheque to see

IPO: Ehn ẹ wò ọ now, you go through the cheque and see the date

SUS: (Going through the statement)

IPO: Just tell me exactly when the issue started

SUS: On the 16th of April

IPO: This year or last year?

SUS: This year

IPO: Around what time?

SUS: In the afternoon

IPO: What time?

SUS: About 2 o'clock

IPO: (Guided the suspect in how to include this in his statement)

IPO: How many units ni owó yẹn rà?

How many units of share could that money buy?

SUS: 2,500 units

IPO: Uhn! Along the line ñkó?

Then along the line?

SUS: (Trying to explain this in his written statement)

A LONG PERIOD OF SILENCE

SUS: This is the draft of the amount...

IPO:

int.

Kí ni interest?

What is the interest?

SUS: Dividend la ma ñ pè é

We call it dividend

IPO: Okay, dividend

SUS: This is the draft... .

IPO:

int.

Ehn, kí ló ma ñ show evidence pé okay o, this is the evidence of the money I have paid?

What usually counts as evidence for whatever amount one pays for shares?

SUS: Òun nàà ni ñkan tí kiní yẹn deliver after payment

That was what was delivered after payment

IPO: What?

SUS: We call it Central Security Planning System

IPO: That bank draft?

SUS: Ehn, ìyẹn ló yẹ kó deliver

Yes. That was he should have delivered

IPO:

int.

Şé ẹ ti ri báyíí?

Have you found it now?

SUS: Òun náà laàrí ta n promise kó tó di pé.....

That was exactly what we were promising to provide before

IPO:

int.

for this one oo. We are talking of this
1.5 oo

SUS: No, no, no, no, kò tí sí 1.5 ñbè...

No, 1.5 is not yet included

IPO:

int.

È ní sùùù, ẹ má a gbó, mi ò fẹ jẹ ka mix up things.

We are talking of 3 million?

Hold on, listen, I don't want us to mix things up.

We are talking of 3 million naira?

SUS: Uhn(Yes)

IPO: Then what of the 1.5 million?

SUS: He is also promising to issue another cheque after this one and which the owner of the money understands

IPO:

int.

So let it show here (pointing to the written statement of the suspect)

SUS: Okay

A LONG PERIOD OF SILENCE

IPO: Ehn, şé ẹ wà aware nigbati X sọ pé owó yí wọn fún òun? Kí ni àwọn efforts tí ẹ make?

Were you aware when X said he was not given the money? What efforts did you make?

SUS: Good, I made efforts to contact the debtor, which the complainant is aware of this; the effort resulted in this cheque.

IPO: Óyá, put it down!

IPO: Ẹ ti n bá X şe láti bí 15 years, işẹ wo ni X n şe?

You have been dealing with X for the past 15 years, what exactly does he do for a living?

SUS: Professional valuer

IPO: èyin gan sè ẹ mò pé ẹ jèbi ọrò yí, tàbí ẹ è jèbi?

Even you, do you know you are equally guilty of the issue at hand, or not?

SUS: Ẹ jẹ n explain sir...

int.

IPO:

Question mo bi yín! Tí ó bá jẹ court, báwo ẹ se ma dáhùn?

I only asked you a question! If it were in court, how would respond?

SUS: Mà á sọ pé under the law of stock exchange...

int.

IPO:

Ẹ ní sùúrù! Kì n sẹyin ẹ ba ra shares ni? Sèbí èyin ẹgba 3.5 million lówó Y?
Hold on! were you not the one who assisted him in procuring the shares? You were the that collected 3.5 million form Y?

SUS: Cheque ni mo gbà

I only collected cheque

int.

IPO:

Òun náà ni mo mean now.

That is what I mean now

SUS: Mi ò sọ pé mà á báwọ̀n rà á, mo ní Y pè mí pé....

I never said I would help him buy it, I said Y

Called me that..

int

IPO:

Statement wà ní bí now; mi ì lile òkan tí ẹ n bámi sọ. Taló introduce è si? (he raised his voice)

The statement is here now. I don't like what you are telling me.

Who introduced X to Y?

SUS: Èmi ni

I did

IPO: Ẹ dẹ wá ní ẹ ẹ jẹbi! ẹ́ sẹ́ tó bá jòkó ti ẹ́ jẹ́jẹ́, ẹ́ sẹ́ irú ñkan béyẹn á ẹ́lẹ̀? (raised his voice ↗)
And you said you are not guilty, if the business had not been introduced to him, would all that happened have happened?

SUS: Tó bá jẹ́ pé ó deliver, gbogbo ñkan yìi ò ní ẹ́lẹ̀
If he had delivered, all this would not have happened.

IPO: Mo ma ñ nà ‘yàn gan o! Mà la orí yín mó pákó ibí nìsín! Torí ẹ́ ñ fún mi ní headache bí mo ẹ́ wàyí. Tóbá jẹ́ ẹ́ lọ sí ibẹ́ yẹn láti confirm ni, gbogbo ñkan yìi ò ní ẹ́lẹ̀
I do beat people a lot. I will hit your head against this plank here. Because you are giving me headache as I am. If you had confirmed the transaction details, all this would have been averted.

SUS: That is true

IPO: Kò jù béyẹn lọ. Ẹ́ ti wọ́ inú 18 bẹ́ ẹ́ wàyí! Ẹ́ ti wọ́ 18 kò sí bóyá kiní.
In short, you have got yourself into trouble without mincing words.

SUS: Now tẹ́ ti sàlàyé fún mi, ó ẹ́ ñ yé mi ni
Now that you have explained everything to me, I now understand.

IPO: Ọpọ́lọ́ yín ò pé tẹ́lẹ̀ àbí? Ó ẹ́ ñ pé ni!
You were not in full possession of your mental prowess before? It is just getting normal!

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Ẹ́ dá mi lóhùn. Ọpọ́lọ́ yín yẹn ò pé tẹ́lẹ̀!
Answer me. You were not in full possession of your mental prowess before

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Ẹ́ wá ní ẹ́ ẹ́ jẹ́bi! Ẹ́ fẹ́ jẹ́bi pani! 3.5 million! Tí mo bá ní mo fẹ́ gbà á lárò yí ñkó? (banging his table)
And you said you are not guilty! What more! What if I insist you must pay the 3.5 million naira this morning?

SUS: Now tí mo ti gbọ́ nìsìn yí...
Now that I have heard..

IPO: int. Ẹ́ ti gbọ́! ẹ́ ẹ́ ẹ́ gbọ́ tẹ́lẹ̀?
Have you not heard before?

SUS: (Trying to explain)

IPO: Tí mi ò bá ri, mà á detain yin. Mo ti stamp è nìyẹn! Tí mi ò bá ri, I will detain you right now. Because you are the architect of this problem.

I will have you detained if I don't see the money, because you are the cause of this problem.

SUS: (Trying to feign a smile)

IPO: Wọ̀n àn tí ì pà̀yàn lójú yín rí lẹ̀ ẹ̀ n rẹ̀rìn. Ẹ̀ má jẹ́ kí n réyín yín níta. Ó wùmí kí n fún yín ní èjẹ̀ díẹ̀ kí ẹ̀ tó kúrò níbí.

You are laughing because you have not witnessed a scene where people are killed before. Don't let me see your set of teeth outside. I feel like giving you a bloody injury before you leave here today.

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Ẹ̀ ti jẹ̀bi. ẹ̀ ẹ̀ sẹ́ dáda bàbá yí, and you said you are 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?....

You are guilty. You have not done well this man, and you claimed to be 47 years old! How do you know you are 47 years old?

SUS: That is my age

IPO: You can prove it? Are you not more than 47?

SUS: (Trying to do the calculation)

IPO: You are lying to me. You are over 50 years of age.

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Am I correct?

SUS: Yes, but that is my official age

IPO: Now do you believe you are at fault now?

SUS: Can I explain? Since the money was not paid to me ...

IPO:

int.

Correct yourself. The check was given to you and you gave it to somebody. Haven't you been collecting cheque before?

SUS: Ehn, ehn...

IPO: Int Yes or no (banging his table), I don't want all this.

SUS: Yes!!

IPO: So, what is your complaint now?

SUS: The complaint is that the person is supposed to do it...

IPO: Int. Listen now, mr man, don't provoke me!(raising his voice ↗)

SUS: (Began a new round of explanation to exonerate himself)

IPO: Èlò ni commission yín?

How much was your commission?

IPO2: 500,000

SUS: Èmi! Iró lèyí o.. .
Me! This is a lie.

IPO: int Sh!!! ẹ má a gbọ mi o, ọrò ti di ọrò ara nísìn yí..
Sh!!! Listen, the matter is now between us

SUS: Int. Wọn ò fún mi..
lówó o
I was not given money

IPO : int Listen to me(raising his voice ↗) Èlò ni commission yín?
How much was your commission?
If you give me headache, I will give you blood oo.

SUS: (Trying to check what he had put down in his written statement)

IPO: Kí lè n wò? Sè kí n fún yín nígò ?

What are you looking at? Should I lend you glasses?

SUS: 250,000

IPO: Tóbájù béèlò, ẹ dáràn o!

If it is more than that, you are in trouble o

SUS: Kò jùbèè sir.

IPO: Kíló dé tẹgba 250,000 lórí iṣẹ tí ò tí ì work?

Why did you collect 250,000 on an uncompleted work?

SUS: (Trying to explain)

IPO:

Int Ẹ má padà séyìn!, ẹ má dà mí lórí rú! (raised his voice ↗)
Don't go back! Don't get me confused!

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: O lọ n jẹ commission nígbà tí 'sé ò tí ready. Olè gan lèyin náà, olè. Sè ọmọ Ifè lẹ perayín?

You have already taken commission on a job that is not yet completed. You too are a thief.

Did you say you are from Ife?

SUS: ọṣun

IPO: Ibo ni l'Ọṣun?

Where in Ọṣun?

SUS: Odòlówá

IPO: Ìlú gidí wá niyẹn ni?

Is that a good town?

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: Sè ẹ mò pé ẹ ẹ wà lára àwọn tí ó gbá bàbá yìí?

Do you know you are part of those who duped this old man?

SUS: Em.... and....

IPO:

int Mi ò fẹ "and" oo, kẹ sọrò bi Yorùbá
I don't want "and", talk like a Yoruba

SUS: (Silent)

IPO: E sọ orí yín pèlú mi ò. Shèbí ẹ è tí nirun funfun lórí? Irun funfun yẹn tó bá má a jáde, kó má lọ jẹ Makurdi prison ló ti ma jáde (banging his table). E sètò bówó yẹn á ẹ jáde! Pé wọn ò ní detain yín, mà á detain yín (banging his table).

Mind yourself with me o. You have not had grey hair; I hope by the time the grey hair begins to come, you would not have been in Makurdi prison then. I will make sure I detain you.

SUS: S'eri...

You see

IPO: int. E lọ n gba commission lórí ki ní kan; commission yẹn ló kóbá yín.

It was the commission you collected that has implicated you now.

SUS: Mi ò dé òdò olópà rí látìgbà tí mo ti bèrè isẹ̀ yíi...

I had never been to the police station since I started this business

IPO:

int. E ti wò ọ léní. E ti wò “gàù”.

Case yín kí n ẹ case kékeré.

Federal High court ni, wán wòn ọ́n fún yín neat ni.

You are in for it today. You

are in a great trouble. You

case is a very serious one; one

that would be decided at the

federal high court, and your

sentence/judgement will be a

stiff one.

CASE 9: BEING IN POSSESSION OF CONTRABAND (INDIA HEMP)

Background Information: *This case involved two “lovers” caught some quantity of India Hemp and arrested, following a tip-off from their neighbours. The conversation here was between an IPO and the female of the two suspects.*

IPO1: Talàwọ̀n òbí ẹ?

Who are your parents?

SUS: Ìyá Alágbo ni

Ìyá Alágbo(my mother sells local herbal concoction)

IPO2: O ò rí ẹ̀yàn advise ẹ, orí ẹ ti burù. Wọ̀n ò lè ẹ case yín níbí, NDLEA ni.

You have not got anyone to advise you, you are an unfortunate person. Your case cannot be handled here, but at the NDLEA

SUS: (Trembling)

IPO: Èsìn wo lò n sìn?

What is your religion?

SUS: Mò n lọ mọ̀sáláṣí

I am a muslim

IPO: Ibo lò n gbé?

Where do you live?

SUS: Baṣọ̀run l’Ọ̀yọ

Baṣọ̀run in ọ̀yọ

IPO: Kí ni number ilé yín?

What is the number of your house?

SUS: Kò ní number

It does not have any number

IPO: Ìwọ náà wo ojú ẹ; Ò n mugbó tàbí o ò mugbó?

You too examine your eye balls, do you smoke India hemp or not?

SUS: Mo ti gbọ̀ mò n mu

I accept I do smoke (india hemp)

IPO: Ẹ́ o lọ school?

Did you attend any school?

SUS: (Responded in a low voice that the IPO could not pick)

IPO: Má a sòrò sóke! (he raised his voice ↗ and banged his table)

Speak up!

IPO3: Ìgbàwo lo kúrò ní school? (He hit the suspect with his stick)

When did you opt out of school?

SUS: (Still trembling)

IPO3: Àní ìgbàwo lo kurò ní school? (raising his voice ↗). Wo irun tó ẹ̀e sóri, ọmọ àlè!

I demand, when did you opt out if school? Look at her hairstyle, bastard!

SUS: Ẹ̀ ẹ̀sàánú mi

Have mercy on me

IPO: Orí ẹ̀ ò pé. Ẹ̀ o lọ primary school?

You are not sane. Did you attend primary school?

SUS: Mo lọ.

I attended

IPO: Níbo lo ti lọ primary school?

Where did you attend primary school?

SUS: Shasha

IPO4: Kí ná mú ẹ̀ fún?

What were you arrested for?

SUS: Igbó

India Hemp

IPO4: Ojú ẹ̀ jojó ẹ̀ni tó n mugbó. Ẹ̀e offence ni kẹ̀yàn f'agbó ní Nigeria ni?

You eye balls betray you as an India hemp smoker. Is it an offence to take India hemp in Nigeria?

IPO5: Kì n ẹ̀e offence; doctor ní wọ̀n ti legalise ẹ̀.

It is not an offence; doctors have legalised it.

SUS: Ẹ̀ dákun ẹ̀ ẹ̀sàánú mi; ọ̀gá mi ò tí ì rí mi látì ànà.

Please have mercy on me; my boss has not seen me since yesterday.

IPO: ọ̀gá ẹ̀ ò mò pé o lọ Jóbèlè?

Your boss did not know you travelled to Jobele?

SUS: Bèni

Yes

IPO4: Ọmọ ọdún mèlòó ni ẹ?

How old are you?

SUS: 19 years

IPO4: Iṣẹ wo lò n kọ?

What work are you learning?

SUS: Hairdressing

IPO4: O ṣẹ n kọṣẹ ni?

You are just learning work?

SUS: Bèni

Yes

IPO4: Iṣẹ wo l'òun n ṣe? (pointing at her boyfriend, the male suspect)

SUS: Ó n kọ tailor

He is learning tailoring

IPO: Ẹ jọ ma n fagbó ni?

You people smoke India hemp together?

SUS: Rára a à.....

No, we are not..

IPO:

Uhn!! O tún bèrè o

No, there you go again

IPO4: Mo ti rójú ẹ, ojú ẹ jọ teni tó n fagbó

I have seen your eyes, they look like that of someone who smokes India hemp

IPO: O n fagbó tàbí o ò fagbó?

Do you smoke India hemp or not?

SUS: Mo n fà á

I do smoke it

IPO: Ṣé ó ma n dùn?

Is it sweet?

SUS: Ehm, ehm....

IPO: *Şé ó ma n dún? Int. (banging his table)*

Is it sweet?

IPO4: *Ta ló kó ẹ bíwón ẹ n fagbó? Şé oko ẹ ni?*

Who taught you how to smoke India hemp? Is it your boyfriend?

SUS: *Ki n ẹ...*

It is not..

IPO: *Int. Taló kó ẹ? (raising his voice and banging his table)*

Who taught you?

SUS: *Àtòyó náà ni wón ti kó mi nígbó.*

I was taught in òyó

IPO1 and IPO4: *Taló kó ẹ?*

Who taught you?

SUS: *Kausarat*

IPO4: *Obinrin ló kó ẹ nígbó! Dìde ná. Şé o lómú báyií?*

A woman taught you how to smoke India hemp! Stand up. Do you have breasts now?

IPO: *(Burst into laughter) Wón béré ibéèrè lówó ẹ o ò dáhùn! (raising his voice)*

SUS: *Mo lóyàn (in a low voice, then coughed)*

I do have breasts

IPO5: *Má à wúkó Tuberculosis ní bí o, ko fowó bo enu ẹ o*

Don't spread tuberculosis here; cover your mouth!

IPO: *Orí ẹ ò pé*

You are not sane

CASE 10: MALICIOUS DAMAGE

Background Information: This case involved three male suspects. The suspects were alleged to have set the room of the complainant ablaze, their arrest. The IPOs here were reacting to the written statements of one of the suspects, who claimed to be a graduate of Economics from a university. The IPOs made spiteful and malicious comments on the "terrible write-up" of the suspect. These are presented below:

IPO: *I was "banned" (burst into laughter). Óyá, spell the "born" you meant.*

SUS: B-O-N-E-D

IPO: “*Boned*” lò n sọ yẹn. A graduate of Economics, University of X. “*You were boned*”!

You have wasted these papers. I will look for another paper, but you won’t be the one to write it. A graduate for that matter!

IPO2: Eléyíí ò graduate; irò ló n pa

This one did not graduate; he is only telling lies.

IPO: Ó ní “ I lives at Bólarundúró, Awotan area, I when to, W-H-E-N. Went yẹn gan bad. Ó ní I when to Temitope “N-U-S-T-R-Y”. “1999 I was finished” (*the IPO burst into another laughter*) *He said I lives at Bólarundúró, Awotan area, I when to... even that “went” is very badly written. He said I went to Temitope “N-U-S-T-R-Y”, and was finished in 1999.*

IPO 3: ògá, if you see their youth corper uniform, na in dey neat pass.

If you see the NYSC uniform of people like this, it is usually very neat, even neater than that of every other corps member.

IPO: Ó ní I attended “nustry” in 2005, and I was finished in 1999 (*bursting into laughter, alongside other IPOs, numbering about 5*)

He said I attended nustry in 2005, and I was finished in 1999.

IPO: Then I gained my “hardmission” in the year 2008; I pased out, P-A-S-E-D, in the year 2012. About the “isident”. Kì n sẹ incident lo kọ yíí, ah! Mo ti fẹ kú o.

..... *This is not the spelling of “incident”. I am dying oo”*

IPO4: Owó ti jóná

You have wasted your parents’ resources

IPO: Sẹ suspect le léyíí? I “suput” Drugbu and Baba D. E ti waste iwé mi. E ẹ mọ nkan kọ. O ò graduate. No! You are not a graduate.

Is this the spelling of suspect? I suput (suspect) Drugbu and Baba D. You have wasted my paper. You don’t know how to write.

SUS: Silent

IPO: My first born is a 7-year old boy. Wọn ọn bi da kó kọ nkan tẹ n kọ yíí. He can even take

your statement.

I have a 7-year old boy who dares not write the rubbish you are writing...

IPO5: And if you see this people when they see police for road, den go say see these idiots, àwọn tí ò mọ̀ òkànkán, and den no know say they are the anti-idiots, tí ò lè kọ̀ anything. (He hissed)

And these are individuals who would refer to police as ignoramus and idiots, whereas they are actually the idiots themselves.

IPO6: (Trying to read the statement of the suspect) Ah! o ò lọ school rárá

Obviously, you did not attend any school at all.

IPO: Kí n ti è kókó lọ dàwọ̀n sínú cell ná tí n bá ti rẹ̀ni bámi attend sí wọ̀n

Let me first of all throw them in the cell, after I have got somebody to help attend to them

IPO6: Ibo lo ti lọ secondary school?

Where did you attend secondary school?

SUS: Ìbàdàn

IPO6: Kí ni discipline ẹ?

What is your discipline?

SUS: Economics

IPO: Economics! O ò wá lè kòwé.

Economics! And you cannot write well.

IPO7: Criminial ni bọ̀bọ̀ yí

This guy is a criminal

IPO6: Sàngó ni ó pa ó. O lọ fi owó jóná ni. Omọ primary 2 gan lè kọ̀ Òyìbó jù ẹ̀ lọ.

May the god of thunder strike you to death. Even a primary 2 pupil can write better English than you.

CASE 11: OBTAINING GOODS AND CREDIT ON FALSE PRETENCE

Background Information: The suspect here was an Alhaji, a businessman who deals in grains for feeding livestock. He was said to have collected goods on credit on false pretence.

IPO: Ibo lẹ̀ n gbé?

Where do you live?

SUS: ọ́jọ̀

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín lẹ́ẹ́kan sí?

What is your name once again?

SUS: (Mentioned his name)

IPO: Ibo lẹ ti mọ Alhaji X?

Where did you get to know Alhaji X?

SUS: ọ̀rẹ̀ mi tí a jọ́ n̄ s̄is̄ẹ̀ ló mú mi mọ́ ọ́

I was introduced to him by my business partner

IPO: Látí ọ̀dún wo?

Since when?

SUS: Ọ̀dún yìí nàà la mọ̀ra

We met this very year

IPO: Sẹ̀ wón ti gbọ̀jà fún yín tẹ̀lẹ̀?

Has he supplied you goods before?

SUS: Kìí ẹ̀ first.... wón ti gbọ̀jà fúnmi tẹ̀lẹ̀, but kì n̄ ẹ̀ pé èmi ná gbefún directly, ẹ̀nití wón gbọ̀jà

fún ló n̄ gbe fún mi....

That was not the first, he has been supplying goods to me before, but not directly; it has always been through a third party..

IPO:

int.

Sh!!!, Alhaji (banging his table)

SUS: Yes please

IPO: Ẹ̀ ẹ̀ mọ́ ọ́ tẹ̀lẹ̀, ọ̀jà n̄ wá, ẹ̀ n̄ tajà ni?

You did not know him before, but you just kept selling the goods as they are coming?

SUS: Mò n̄ tajà ni

I am only selling the goods

IPO: Látìgbà tẹ̀ ti mọ́ ọ́, this is the first ọ̀jà tó ma gbé fún yín?

Since you met him, this is the first time he would be supplying you goods?

SUS: Ọ̀un gan kọ́ ló gbe fún mi, ọ̀rẹ̀ mi gan ló gbe fún mi

He was not even the one that supplied me, it was my partner that did

IPO: Ọ̀jà yẹn, three point kí lẹ̀ pè é?

Three point what did you call the worth of the goods?

SUS: Close to 7 million l'ọjà ọ́ún

It was close to 7 million naira

IPO: Ibo ni warehouse yín wà?

Where is your warehouse?

SUS: Mi ò ní warehouse, a ma ń supply káàkiri ni, anywhere in the federation

I don't have a warehouse, I do supply goods all over the country

IPO: Kí ni educational qualification yín?

What is your academic qualification?

SUS: Ẹ fi school cert síbẹ̀

School Certificate

IPO: Torí mo ri bí ẹ̀ se gbá biro mú

Because I could observe how well you handle the biro

IPO: Eló lẹ̀ ti san ní police station?

How much have you paid at the police station?

SUS: Three hundred, mo dẹ̀ ti gbé ọ̀kọ̀ kan sílẹ̀ láti tà

Three hundred thousand naira, and I have already placed "for sale" on a vehicle to recover the remaining.

IPO: Irú ọ̀kọ̀ wo nìyẹn?

What kind of vehicle is that?

SUS: Motor ńlà ni, truck.

A big vehicle (truck)

IPO: After your secondary school, what did you do?

SUS: I went into trading

IPO: Did you learn it?

SUS: No

SUS: Kí ni orúkọ̀ yín?

What is your name?

IPO: X

SUS: X what?

IPO: X Y

IPO: Ibo ni base business yín?

Where is your business base?

SUS: Bodija ni, though it was Orita Merin before

IPO: Tell us how you met the three of them

SUS: È fẹ̀ wà aggresive sí mi (*You are a bit aggresive to me*), and I don't deserve that. Yes. If you know me very well, if you ask the people that know me, you will know I don't deserve this. (*His phone rang and was discussing another transaction with the caller, after which he continued with his statement*)

IPO: Are you through sir? Àbí kí n fún yín lómi?

Are you through with the statement or should I offer you water?

SUS: Ọlọ̀n yòd nífẹ̀ yín. È mu wá. È ri pé mo ti n sweat gan, mo ní ifún pá

God will love you too. Bring it. I am already sweating, because I am hypertensive

IPO: Ó yẹ̀ kẹ̀ ma calm down ni anything tí ẹ̀ bá n ẹ̀

You are supposed to be calm then whatever you are doing

SUS: Mi ò experience irú eléyí rí

I never experienced this before

IPO: Kò sí wàhàlà

There is no problem

SUS: Ó da

Okay

IPO: Bàbá, ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ma jàşáró?

Baba, will you eat porridge?

SUS: Yí ó da fún yín, wallahi, ẹ̀ yà mí lẹ̀nu gan

It will be well with you. Honestly, you surprise me

CASE 12: DEFILEMENT

Background Information: This is a case of a 21-year old young man who was alleged to have forcefully slept with a 6-year old girl living around his neighbourhood.

IPO: Wò ó, wojú mi dada, o ti ş'exam silẹ̀, o ò need screening, admission ti dúró fún ẹ̀ ní Agodi, direct entry ni. Şé o ti ready láti sòrò?

See, look at my eyes very well, you have wrtten an exam, you don't need any screening,

you have already secured admission into Agodi, it is direct entry. Are you ready to speak now?

SUS: (Nodded his head)

IPO: Okay, sòrò bá yí

Okay, speak now

SUS: Began to explain....

IPO:

int

On the 20th to rán ọmọ yẹn lẹwà àti bread, kí ló şelẹ?

What happened on the 20th when the girl brought the bread and beans you sent her?

SUS: Àkókò, mi ò ran ní bread àti ẹwà, mi ò rán ní anything daddy

First of all, I did not send her on an errand to get bread and beans for me

IPO: Kí ló şelẹ kó tó di pé ẹ lọ sílẹ àwọn complainant?

What happened before you visited the complainant's place?

SUS: L'álẹ ọjọ Friday, ẹni tójókò yí àti mummy mi...

On Friday night, this person seated and my

Mother...

IPO:

int.

Kí lorúkọ ẹ?

What is the person's name?

SUS: XX,.....

IPO:

int.

Okay, má ti ẹ sòrò mọ; şé torí pé o rí ìyá ẹ àti àwọn ẹyàn níbí? ẹ jòó ẹ excuse wa. Şé o ready láti jéwó

Is it because your relatives are here? You people should please excuse us. Are you ready to say the truth now?

SUS: Silent

IPO: Jé kí i sọ fún ẹ, ş'ori moní o ti şe exam Jamb, direct entry ni, but bóyá to bá sòótó, ìgbà yẹn gan la ma slow down

Let me tell you, like I said earlier, you have secured direct admission into Agodi, but if you say the truth, we could temper justice with mercy.

SUS: Silent

IPO: Tí mo bá béré ọ̀rò lówó ẹ, ko ma dáhùn, o mọ ọmọ yẹn tàbí o ò mò ọ? Sẹ̀ iwọ̀ ló n kọ ní Kéú?

When I ask you question you answer me, do you know that girl or not? Are you the one

SUS: Èmi kọ̀ ni mò n kọ̀ ní Kéú.

I am not the one teaching her Arabic

IPO: Ní on the 20th, o ní o rán òun ní ẹ̀wà àti bread, sẹ̀ irọ̀ ni tàbí òótọ̀?

She alleged you sent her on an errand to buy bread and beans for you on the 20th, true or false?

SUS: Irọ̀ ni daddy

False sir

IPO: Ibo ni ọmọ yẹn wà nígbà to fi pè é?

Where was the girl when you called her?

SUS: On the 20th tí ẹ̀ n sọ yẹn, mi ò rántí. Ọjọ̀ ọ̀dún, mo lọ sí ọ̀dọ̀ daddy mi l'Ọ̀mí...
I can't really remember that date, on Iléyá day, I travelled to Ọ̀mí to celebrate at my dad's place

IPO:

int.

Listen to me (raising his voice ↗), mà á fọ̀ etí ẹ̀ o! Tí o ò bá gbọ̀ran dada, mà á fọ̀ etí ẹ̀ o, etí ẹ̀ ma sí.

Listen to me, I will slap you! If you have hearing impairment, I will cure it with slap

SUS: On the 18th daddy, mi ò sí nílẹ̀ wallahi....

Sir, honestly, I was not at home on the 18th

IPO:

int.

Okay, o basùn àbí o ò basùn?

Okay, you slept with her or not?

SUS: Daddy, mi ò basùn

I did not sleep with her sir

IPO: O s̄i tún deny

You are still denying

SUS: Daddy, daddy, mi ò basùn, mi ò kí n̄ je bread ati èwà...

I did not sleep with her sir, in fact I don't eat bread and beans

int.

IPO:

È dá idiot ȳi padà sínú cell
jòó
Please take this idiot back into the cell

SUS: Daddy, ẹ jòó, Ọlòun ò ní ba ti yín jé

Please sir, may the Lord not destroy what belongs to you

IPO: Mo mò pé hardened criminal ni ẹ

I know you are a hardened criminal

SUS: Daddy, ẹ jòó...

Please sir

int.

IPO:

Olòṣì, da padà sínú cell
Idiot(useless human being), return him to the cell

IPO2: Wà á jerà s'Ágodi

You will rot in Agodi

CASE 13: MURDER

Background Information: This case involved a man, who, estimatedly, should be in his mid-forty's; a driver, alleged to have sent a driver colleague to his eraly grave.

IPO: Óyá, ẹ wólé

Now come in

SUS: (Entered with a hand-cuff in both hands)

IPO: È jókò

Sit down

SUS: (Knelt down, perhaps having weighed the gravity of his “offence”)

IPO: Ah! mi ò ní kẹẹ kúnlẹ; mo ní kẹẹ jókò ni

I did not ask you to kneel down; I asked you to sit

SUS:È jẹ n wà báyi

Let me remain like this

IPO: È ẹ need láti worry, wán yanjú gbogbo ẹ (*winking at another IPO with a smile, a gesture noticed by the suspect*)

You don't need to be worried, everything will be resolved.

SUS: (Remained on his knees) after which he was whisked away to another interrogation room, where the researcher could not access.

CASE 14 DEFILEMENT

Background Information: The suspect is a 48-year old man, a surveyor by profession, who was reported by his daughter to have been sleeping with her without her consent.

IPO: Bàbá!! ẹ mélòò lẹti bá ọmọ yí sùn?

Bada, how many times have you slept with the girl?

SUS: Mi ò kà á

I have lost count

IPO: Okay, kí ló mú ẹ dé bè to ní basùn?

What took over you that you are sleeping with your daughter?

SUS: Mi ò mọ

I don't know

IPO: Şé torípé iyá ẹ ò sí lódò ẹ mọ?

Is it because her mother is no longer with you?

SUS: Rára kì í... int

Not at all..

IPO: Okay, kí ló mú ẹ tó jẹ ọmọ ẹ l'okó ẹ ní le sí?

Okay, what then in your daughter has been stimulating erection in you?

SUS: Kò yé mi gan

I don't even understand

IPO: Kíló dé to fi n threaten è?

Why have been threatening her?

SUS: Kò yé mi gan sir

I don't even understand sir

IPO: Ibo ni iyá è wà?

Where is her mother?

SUS: Abeokuta

IPO: Ìgbà tí iyá è ti kò è, kí ló dé tó ò fi lọ sílé aṣẹwó?

Since the mother has left you, why have you not been visiting a brothel?

SUS: Silent

IPO: Ilé ìwé wo lo fi sí?

What you school did you enrol her?

SUS: Mo fi sí primary school, ibi tó ti n lọ sí... int

IPO:

Ṣé primary school ló wà báyií?

Is she still in primary school now?

SUS: Ó ti jáde kúrò ní primary, ó wá n kòṣé

She has dropped out of primary school; she is an apprentice now

IPO: Iṣé wo ló n kó?

What work is she learning?

SUS: Ó n kó hairdressing

She is learning hairdressing

IPO: Kí ló wá dé tó ò jé kó kòṣé yẹn tán?

Why did you not allow her finish the work she was learning?

SUS: Òun náà ló n kó lọwó

She is still on it

IPO: Lo wà n basùn!

And you are sleeping with her!

SUS: Silent.... à fi bí èdì

Perhaps it was a spell

IPO: Èdì wo! To sọ pé èdì, màá fọ ki ní mọ ẹ! Èdì ò ẹ mú ẹ lọ sílé aṣéwó?

What spell! If you say it is a spell, I will hit you with an object. Why didn't the spell spur you into visiting a brothel?

SUS: Ọlórún nìkán lóyẹ, wallahi...

Honestly, only God understands

IPO:

int

Ọlórún wo lóyẹ? (*hissed*)

What did you mean God understands?

SUS: Silent

IPO: Ṣẹbí o n mutí?

Of course you drink (alcohol)?

SUS: Muslim ni mí, mi ò n mutí

I don't drink; I am a muslim

IPO: Ẹ káre o (with a tone of mockery)

Well done oo

IPO2: Bàbá, ẹ wá n ṣẹbí èyàn dada, ẹ n ṣẹbí èyàn Ọlórún

Old man, you are now pretending to be a godly man

IPO: Omọ àlè! (*hissed*)

Bastard!

Barr: Bóyá torí wọn ò ní stature

Perhaps because he has a small stature

IPO: Olórí burúkú. Tí n bá ti ma prepare charge ẹ, màá tún fi rape si (*hissed*)

Misfortune bearer. When I am preparing your case, I will include rape therein

SUS: Soliloquising

IPO: Bàbá yí màá pariwo o, torí màá fọ kiní mọ ẹ

This old man stop making noise, else I will hit you with an object

SUS: Still soliloquising

IPO: Bàbá yí, to bá tún sọrò, màá kó Pankéré bò ẹ nísìn

This man, if you dare talk again, I will flog you with Pankéré

SUS: Ọlórún dáríjì mí o

IPO: Bàbá, Ọlórún ò ní dáríjì yín o

Old man, God will not forgive you

IPO2: Èwòn lẹ̀ẹ̀ lọ

You shall go to jail/prison

CASE 15 : FRAUD

Background Information: *The suspect was a 68-year old man alleged to have duped a client over some acres of land. He, alongside his accomplice, was alleged to have sold the said acres of land to more than one person; a development that resulted in a very serious dispute among the victims.*

IPO: Èlọ ni X (the accomplice) fún yín?

How much did he give you?

SUS: 150,000

IPO: It is not possible. That is a pure lie

IPO2: At this age, you are still lying. E ma kú sẹ̀wòn by the time you are convicted

You are still telling lies at this stage of yours, you would die in prison when you are Jailed

IPO3: And you are still sitting down! Stand up (**raising his voice** ↗)

IPO1: Until baàlẹ̀ comes, you are not leaving here

OC: That means he and X are partners in crime

IPOs: Yes they are

CASE 16: MURDER

Background Information: *This case involved a fifty year old man who machete his grandparents to death. The suspect was brought in with a hand-cuff in his hands and his ankle-length regalia full of blood-stains.*

IPO: Ọmọ Yoruba ni ẹ

SUS: Bẹ̀ẹ̀ni

IPO: Ọmọ ọdún mélòò ni ẹ?

SUS: Fifty years

IPO: Fifty years? Fifteen àbí fifty?

SUS: Fifty years

IPO: Işé wo lo n ń se?

SUS: Àwọn tó n ta generator

IPO: Muslim ni ẹ àbí Christian?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Okay. Ibo lo n ń gbé?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni ẹ?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: S'álàyé nńkan tó şelẹ

SUS: Wọn sọ pé kí n wá gẹrun..... int.

IPO:

Taló sọ pé kí o wá gẹrun?

SUS: Màmá

IPO: Şé ọdọ wọn lo n ń gbé ni?

SUS: Bẹni

IPO: Okay, ẹyin mélódọ lẹ jọ n gbé pẹlu màámá?

SUS: Èmi pẹlu àbúrò mi XYZ

IPO: Okay, şé ọun náà wà nílẹ nígbà tí wàhálà yẹn şelẹ?

SUS: Ó wà nílẹ...

IPO: Okay.

SUS: Wọn ní kí n wá lọ gẹrun mi; mo dẹ rò pé tí wọn bá yóò àfẹ̀tì (affect) mi

IPO: Şé màámá ló ma n ń gẹrun fún ẹ ni?

SUS: Wọn ní ká lọ sílẹe barber

IPO: Şé àwọn ló fẹ́ mú ẹ lọ ni?

SUS: Wọn ní kí n wá lọ..... mo dè sọ fún wọn pé mi ò lè gẹrun; wọn wá plan láti fi blade fa a.
Wọn

fẹ̀ dè mí lókùn lówó sẹ̀yìn.....int.

IPO:

Taló n plan láti dè ẹ̀ lókùn, sẹ̀ mà má ni?

SUS: Uhn!

IPO: Okay, bàbá ò sí níbẹ̀ nígbà yẹn?

SUS: Bàbá ò ì tū dè

IPO: Okay (continue)

SUS: Mo wá yọ àdà sí wọn; mo sá mà má ní àdàint.

IPO:

Níbo lo ti rí àdà yẹn?

SUS: Inú ilé

IPO: Ta ló ni àdà yẹn?

SUS: Èmi ni mo ni í

IPO: Kí lo n fí sẹ?

SUS: A le fí gé ịṣu tàbi igi

IPO: Ẹ̀wọ̀ ni ó ni àdà yẹn?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Okay, o sá à bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí ní sá wọn?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Okay, ịgbà tí o wá sá mà má, kí ló wá kan bàbá níbẹ̀?

SUS: Bàbá nàà wá, wọn wípé..... int.

IPO:

Ta ló pe bàbá?

SUS: Bàbá wá fúnra wọn

IPO: Láti ilé kejì?

SUS: Uhn!

IPO: Wón gbó ariwo mà má àbí?

SUS: Bèni

CASE 17: STREET FIGHT

Background Information: *The suspect was accused of being among some other individuals who were involved in a street fight that led to the beating of a police officer*

IPO: On the 30th of this month, where were you?

SUS: Mo wà nílè?

IPO: You were at home; where?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Tell us what happened in your area on the 30th of this month

SUS: Mo gbó pé àwọn kan jà níbi carnival baálè sì ní kí á lọ sí station láti lọ wo àwọn tí wón arrest

IPO: How many machine (motorcycle) did you carry to the police station?

SUS: Three machines

IPO: And where are the machines now?

SUS: Wón wà ní police station

IPO: And it was at the police station that you were arrested

SUS: Ehn, a gun machine lọ pe baálè..... int.

IPO:
(raising his

You did not go to the police station on that day

voice)?

SUS: Ehn ní alé

IPO: You may be telling lies oo, by the time we get to XYZ(the place of the incident) and they tell say they arrested you in your area

SUS: Machine tí mo gùn wá ni èyí.....int

IPO:

Sé that machine; is it your own?

SUS: Bèèni, machine mi ni

IPO: So, when the problem started, where were you? You said you were at home. What happened? Tell me what happened

SUS: Wọn jà

IPO: Who were the people fighting?

SUS: Àwọn ọmọ àdúgbò náà ni

IPO: What story did you hear? Tell us.

SUS: Ilée baàlè ni èmi wà, so..... int.

IPO: You said you were sleeping

SUS: Alé ni wọn jà; a sì lọ láti report ní police station, wọn sì tìwámólé

IPO: So what happened at the police station?

SUS: Wọn ọ̀n gba statement lènu wa, wọn kàn ò lù wá ni

IPO: So, who are the people that caused that problem within your area?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Are you now saying you did not participate in the fight and the attack against the policemen?

SUS: Mi ò sí nìbè

CASE 18 : RAPE

Background Information: *This involved a 29-year old young man who was alleged to have raped a lady in his neighbourhood with some other accomplices*

IPO: Ọmọ ọdún méèlò ni é?

SUS: 29

IPO: Iṣẹ wo lo ó ẹ?

SUS: Àwọn tó ó ẹ aluminium

IPO: Ibo lo ó gbé?

SUS: XYZ

SUS: Rára sir

IPO: Condition wo lo bá ọmọ yẹn?

SUS: Skirt wà ní ìdí è

IPO: Şé ó sùn sílè ni tàbí ó jókòdò

SUS: Silent

IPO: Dámi l'óhùn time n lọ (**raised his voice**)

SUS: Ó sùn sílè

IPO: Njè nhkan tí ẹ şe, şé o mọ ijìyà è?

Do you know the weight of the offence you committed

SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir

IPO: Şé o lè gbà kí wọn şe irú è fún àbúrò ẹ?

SUS: Rára sir

IPO: Kí ló wá dé tí o fún ọmọlómọ? Àbí igbó tí o n mu ni?

SUS: Rára sir, mi ò fa igbó

CASE 19: MISMANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS (FUNDS)

Background Information: *The suspect here was brought to the police custody by a complainant who claimed the suspect mismanaged a poultry he set up and put in care of the suspect. The mismanagement of the said poultry led to a great loss on the part of the complainant*

IPO: What is your name?

SUS: I am XYZ

IPO: Where were you born?

SUS: XXX

IPO: When?

SUS: 1983

IPO: Which primary school did you attend?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Your secondary school nkó?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Did you attend higher school?

SUS: Yes, University of XXX

IPO: How did you meet Mr XY (the complainant)?
 SUS: It was my pastor that announced the vacancy in church
 IPO: Which church?
 SUS: XYY
 IPO: What does that mean? Is that a name? (raised his voice)
 SUS: XYZ XYZ (mentioned the church in full)
 IPO: Okay. And the man employed you?
 SUS: Yes
 IPO: What was the agreement between you?
 SUS: Oga promised to share the profit of the business with me after four years.....
 IPO: What condition did your oga give for the sharing?
 SUS: That is if the business succeeds.....
 IPO: **You are a fool, and did it succeed?**
 SUS: (Shakes his head). Sir, God knows I tried
 IPO: (Hit his baton on the suspect's head) **Answer my question, Olé**
 SUS: I can explain everything sir
 IPO: Was there not a written agreement between you?
 SUS: There was
 IPO: Now, your ògá said you did not pay your staff salaries and you stole some of the chickens to your own farm
 SUS: Sir.....
 IPO: You are criminal, and I will hang you now if you lie
 SUS: I won't sir
 IPO: As I speak to you now, your oga said you are to refund two million naira
 SUS: But.....
 IPO: (Puts a handcuff on the suspect's hands) You will go to prison. This is not aailable case
 SUS: Oga, I am ready to sell my Toyota Sienna and piece of land I have
 IPO: **Olosi, òmò olè.** You even used the money you stole well
 SUS: No sir, I had bought all that before I got the job
 IPO: Are you ready to refund the money or go to court?
 SUS: I don't know sir, please help me

CASE 20: ARMED ROBBERY/ DEFAMATION OF CHARACTER

The suspect, an engineer, was accused by the complainant of being among the armed robbery gang that robbed her on 2nd May 2013 at the Lagos-Ibadan express way. According to what was inferred in the course of the interaction, the complainant walked up to the suspect in a church

programme in Ota and held on to him, alleging him of being a member of the robbery group that had earlier robbed her, after which the matter was brought to Iyaganku

IPO: Your name sir

SUS: I am XXX

IPO: What is the name of your town?

SUS: XX

IPO: Your date of birth?

SUS: 2nd XXX

IPO: Which primary school did you attend?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Your secondary school?

SUS: XXX

IPO: What do you do for a living?

SUS: I am into electrical installation

IPO: Did you attend a university at all?

SUS: Yes, XXX

IPO: Okay, have you seen this woman before?

SUS: At all sir

IPO: (Moves closer to the suspect) It is a lie. You mean you have never seen her before?

SUS: Yes, except the day she came to arrest me

IPO: Why did she arrest you?

SUS: In fact, I am just waiting for this matter to be over so that I rearrest her too. I would have retaliated but I did not want to break the law

IPO: Thank you for not breaking the law

IPO: Where did she arrest you?

SUS: At XXY

IPO: What were you doing there?

SUS: I went to pray

IPO: And she said you were among..... who?

SUS: She said I was part of the boys that robbed her one time

IPO: How did you feel when she told you that?

SUS: In fact, I can't even describe it sir. I just thank God I did not lose my temper

IPO: When last did you pass through Lagos-Ibadan express?

SUS: About six months ago

IPO: This woman said you look like one of the robbers on that day

SUS: Is that a case, Oga?

IPO: Yes, it is

SUS: I just feel I should kill her

IPO: You can't do that or else....

SUS: In fact.....

IPO: Madam, you see, you need to tell us your intentions about the case.

IPO: Mr Man, are you not guilty of the allegation?

SUS: Oga, I am not sir

CASE 21: CONSPIRACY AND STEALING

The suspect was brought to the custody of the police by his boss, a shop owner in Ibadan, who claimed the suspect was in the know as to how thieves came to burgle the shop and carted away goods worth 205,000 naira.

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ rẹ?

What is your name?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni ẹ?

Where are you from?

SUS: XYZ

IPO: Ọdún wo ni wón bí ẹ?

What year were you born?

SUS: May, XXX

IPO: Ilé ìwé wo lo lọ?

What school did you attend ?

SUS: Mo lọ sí XXX

I attended

IPO: Sé o lọ sé secondary school?

Did you attend secondary school?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni, mo lọ sí XXX

Yes, I attended....

IPO: Iṣẹ wo lo kó?

What work did you learn?

SUS: Iṣẹ́ wiring ni mo kó

I learnt wiring/electrification

IPO: Sé o ̀ sí n ̀ se iṣẹ wiring ni?

Do you deal in wiring/electrification?

SUS: Rára, ọ̀gá

Not at all sir

IPO: Báwo lo ̀ se dé ibi tí o ti n ̀ ̀ sí ̀ yí?

How did you get to the place of work?

SUS: Àbúrò ìyá mi ló mú mi lọ bẹ̀rẹ́ iṣẹ́ nǐbẹ̀

My uncle actually took me there

IPO: Ọdún mélòò lo ti n ̀ ̀ sí ̀ nǐbẹ̀?

How many years have you worked there?

SUS: Qdún méta

Three years

IPO: Njé wón ti fi ẹ̀sùn kàn é rí nǐbẹ̀?

Have you been alleged of any crime before?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Kí ló ẹ̀lẹ̀ nígbà náà?

What happened then?

SUS: Wón jí nńkan lọ náà ni

They stole goods

IPO: Ojọ wo ni iṣẹ̀lẹ̀ yí ẹ̀lẹ̀?

What day did that even take place?

SUS: Ojọ Monday tó lọ

This last Monday

IPO: Ago méèlò ló ẹ̀lẹ̀?

What time did it happen?

SUS: Ago méjọ alé

8 in the evening

IPO: Njé o wà ní ẹ̀ṣòbù?

Were you at the shop?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Báwo ni wón ẹ̀ kó àwọn ojà yẹn lọ?

How did they cart the goods away?

SUS: ọ̀gá, mi ò lè sọ torí ẹ̀mi gan-an ò mọ bí gbogbo ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ẹ̀lẹ̀

Oga, I can't even explain because I don't understand how it all happened

IPO: (Sends for a handcuff) O ò sí nǐbẹ̀ ni?

Were you not there?

SUS: ọ̀gá mo wà nǐ bẹ̀ ẹ̀

Oga, I was there

IPO: Keep quiet, idiot (raised voice)

SUS:

IPO: Omọ olè. **I will take you back to cell now**

Son of a thief

SUS: Cries repeatedly... oga ẹ̀ jọ̀

Please sir

IPO: Àwọn olè wá wọlé wón jí àwọn ẹ̀rù yẹn lọ?

So the thieves came and carted the goods away?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir

Yes sir

IPO: Sè o ò mò wón rí ni?

Don't you know them?

SUS: Rárá, ògá

Not at all sir

IPO: Wà á pé ní cell, sè o gbó. Ó sure pé o má a lọ sí èwòn

You will stay long in the cell. It is very certain you are going to be jailed.

CASE 22: FELONY

The case involved one Alhaji, the complainant, who bought some plots of land somewhere in Ibadan. He fenced the said plots of land to register his presence thereon. However, after about two years, the suspect allegedly connived with another fellow to destroy the fence, claiming the land belonged to their family. They therefore allegedly sold the same land to another fellow, a woman. The Alhaji surfaced thereafter and took the matter to the police, after which one of the suspects was arrested and brought for interrogation.

IPO: What is your name?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Old are you?

SUS: I am 39 years old

IPO: Your town?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Speak louder, please

SUS: XXX

IPO: Which primary school did you attend?

SUS: XXX

IPO: What do you do?

SUS: I teach in a primary school

IPO: Are you an agent?

SUS: No sir

IPO: So, I did you get involved in this?

SUS: I don't do things like this, but this one is our family property

IPO: What do you mean by your family?

SUS: I mean my family owns it

IPO: Who is your family?

SUS: I don't understand you sir

IPO: You are a thief

SUS: No sir

IPO: Do you know Mrs XXY

SUS: Yes, we sold the plots of land to her

IPO: Which land?

SUS: My family land
IPO: What do you mean by 'we'; how many are you?
SUS: Mr X, XX and I
IPO: Are they all thieves like you?
SUS: No sir
IPO: You are only thief
SUS: No sir
IPO: Where are the other ones now?
SUS: I don't know sir
IPO: What does X do?
SUS: He is pastor
IPO: We need to arrest him after this interrogation
IPO: What about XX?
SUS: He is an agent
IPO: He was the one teaching you what to do
IPO: (Drags the suspect close to himself) when did you sell the land to Mrs XX
SUS: That was around March, 2014
IPO: How much did you sell it?
SUS: I think 700,000
IPO: How many people were there when she paid?
SUS: My friend, my family member and I
IPO: (Slaps the suspect) Don't say our family members. Mention names
SUS: Okay sir. I know of one XX and YY
IPO: How old are they?
SUS: Ah, may be around 65 or so
IPO: But Mr XXX, the original owner of the land presented the particulars of the land,
including the red copy of his survey, plan and agreement signed by a lawyer
SUS: I don't know sir
IPO: How did you prepare the agreement for her?
SUS: We did it sir
IPO: (Slaps the suspect again). You did what?
SUS: I am sorry sir
Mrs XX: You are a liar. He called about three people and said they were his family members
IPO: Madam, be patient
IPO: The evidence before me shows that you are thief
SUS: No sir
IPO: We have to get other members of your group first and interrogate them

CASE 23: ASSULT AND MALICIOUS DAMAGE

Background Information: *The suspects were 8 in number. They had been alleged by the complainant to have assaulted him and maliciously destroyed the foundation he had done a*

disputed peace of land. After the general interaction the IPOs had with the suspects at their arrival, they were called upon one after the other for interrogation/questioning. We were able to capture the interactions involving five of them, and these shall be presented here:

INTERACTION 1

IPO: *Şé ẹ̀ lè kòwé?*

Can you write?

SUS: *Rára, mi ò kòwé*

No, I can't

IPO: *Èdè wo ni ẹ̀ gbó?*

What language do you speak?

SUS: *Yoruba*

IPO: *Ọmọ ilú wo ni yín?*

Where is your home town?

SUS: *XXX*

IPO: *Which local government?*

SUS: *XXX*

IPO: *Primary school wo ni ẹ̀ lọ?*

Which primary school did you attend?

SUS: *YYY*

IPO: *Secondary school wo ni ẹ̀ lọ?*

Which secondary school did you attend?

SUS: *Mi ò lọ secondary school*

I did not attend any secondary school

IPO: *Kí lẹ̀ n ẹ̀ báyí?*

What do you do now?

SUS: *Driver ni mí*

I am a commercial driver

IPO: *Ẹ̀ mọ TTT (mentioned the name of the complainant)?*

You know TTT?

SUS: *Mo mọ ọ̀n*

I know him

IPO: *Báwo lẹ̀ ẹ̀ mọ ọ̀n?*

How do you know him?

SUS: *Ọmọ abúlẹ̀ kan nàà ni wá; ẹ̀gbọ̀n ni ó sì jẹ̀ fún mi*

We are from the same community/village

IPO: *Ẹ̀ ní village kan ni ẹ̀ ti wá?*

You said you are from the same village?

SUS: *Bẹ̀ni*

Yes

IPO: Fine, ẹ́ẹ́ bí kan náà ni yín?

Fine, are you members of the same family?

SUS: Rárá

No

IPO: Ní on the 30th of May, ibo ni ẹ̀ wà?

Where were you on the 30th of May?

SUS: Mo lọ sí oko

I went to the farm

IPO: Ibo ni oko yín wà?

Where is the location of the farm?

SUS: Èyin OOO ni ó wà

It is located behind OOO

IPO: kí ni orúkọ ibẹ̀ yẹn?

What is the name of that place?

SUS: KKK, Ibadan

IPO: Látí lọ ẹ̀ kí ni?

To do what?

SUS: Ibẹ̀ ni àwọn òbí mi n gbé

My parents live there

IPO: Kí wá ló fa èdèàiyedè láarín èyin àtí XXX?

What was the cause of the misunderstanding between you and TTT?

SUS: Mi ò bá wọn jà.....**int**

I was not fighting

IPO: Kí ló ẹ̀lẹ̀?

What happened?

SUS: Mo bá YYY lóri ariwo; mo báa tí ó n bẹ̀ TTT

I met YYY shouting, begging TTT

IPO: Ẹ́ ẹ̀ ẹ̀ wá mọ̀ ohun tí ó fa ìjà?

You did not know what caused their misunderstanding?

SUS: Mi ò mọ̀ ọ̀n sùgbọ̀n.....**int**

I did/do not but...

IPO: Mo ní ẹ̀ ẹ̀ mọ̀ ọ̀n?

I asked if you knew/know it

SUS: Mi ò mọ̀ ọ̀n

I did/do not know it

IPO: Ta ló ní kí YYY bẹ̀ TTT?

Who asked YYY to apologise to TTT?

SUS: MMM

IPO: But, ẹ̀ ẹ̀yin mọ̀ nńkan tí wọn n bẹ̀bẹ̀ lé lóri?

But did you know why he was apologising?

SUS: Rárá, mo sàà bá wọn ní ibè ni
No, I just met them there

IPO: Wọn ní èyin nàà wà lára àwọn tí ó lu TTT. Wọn ní ẹ dé togun togun ni
They said you were part of those who beat (harassed) TTT with dangerous instruments

SUS: Mi ò mò nípa ìyẹn oo
I don't know anything about that

IPO: Wọn ní èyin ni ẹ fọ ilée wọn
They said you were among those who destroyed his landed property

SUS: Èmi kọ; mi ò mò nípa rẹ o
I was not; I don't know anything about that

IPO: èyin ò tẹlé wọn nígbà tí wọn lọ wó ilé?
You did not go with them when they went to destroy the landed property

SUS: Mi ò tẹlé ẹni kankan ooo
I did not go with anybody oo

INTERACTION 2

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?
What is your name?

SUS: OOO

IPO: Ibo lẹ ñ gbé?
Where do you live?

SUS: No 333, CCC

IPO: Kí ni phone number yín?
What is your phone number?

SUS: 111111111

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni yìn?
Where are you from?

SUS: BBB

IPO: Ibo ni ní BBB?
Where in BBB?

SUS: ZZZ

IPO: Ibo ni agbo ilée yín?
Where is your family compound?

SUS: CCC

IPO: Ibo ni ìyẹn wa?
Where is that?

SUS: LLL

IPO: Sẹ ibi LLL yẹn lẹ ẹ ñ gbé ?
Do you still live at LLL?

SUS: Rárá

No

IPO: Sè wọn n ta igbó ní LLL?

Do they smoke India hemp there?

SUS: Èmi ò mò o

I do not know

IPO: Every unit ní area yẹn ni wọn ti n ta igbó

You have India hemp sold in virtually every nook and cranny of that area

SUS: Èmi ò mò bóyá wọn n tà á o

I am not aware of that

IPO: But, ẹ mò pé wọn n ta igbó ní LLL?

But, you are aware people sell India hemp there?

SUS: Èmi ò mò o

I do not know

IPO: (Goes through the statement of one other suspect, after which he receives a phone call)

IPO: Bàbá, sè torí pé ẹyin lẹ gbé wọn lọ sí ilẹ ẹjọ lẹ se ní kí wọn lọ wó block wọn ni?

Was it because you had earlier taken them to court that you destroyed his property?

SUS2: Kò sí ẹnikankan tó wó block

Nobody did that among us

IPO: Sè block wá wó ara rẹ ni, àbí ẹni tí ó ni block ni ó wó nkan ẹ?

Did the blocks destroy themselves?

SUS2: Àwa ò mò nípa rẹ, kò sí ẹnikankan nínú un wa tí ó wó block rẹ

None of us was involved in the destruction of his landed property

IPO: Ẹ máà sọ pé àwa

Don't say we

SUS2: È mi ò bá ẹnikankan wó block; mi ò sì instruct ẹnikankan láti lọ wó block

I did not destroy his block, neither did I instruct anyone to do so

SUS3: (Intrudes) Sè mo lè dá si?

Can I come in?

IPO: Go and sit down. Ẹ ẹ kàn lè intrude bẹyẹn, because if you do, we won't leave this place.

Tí ó bá ti kàn yín mà á pè yín

Go and sit down; you cannot just intrude like that

SUS3: Okay sir

IPO (Continues with the first suspect) Sè ẹ lọ ilèwé?

Did you attend any school?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Ilèwé wo lẹ lọ?

Which school did you attend?

SUS: DDD

IPO: Ibo ni ó wà?

Where is it located?

SUS: DCD

IPO: Şé DDD primary school ni?

DDD primary school?

SUS: Bèni

Yes

IPO: Ibo ni ó wà? Şé village ni?

Where is it? In the village?

SUS: Village kó o

No

IPO: Ta ni wón pè tí ẹ fi wá?

Who was summoned that made you come here?

SUS: Fòdùn tẹmi ni wón pè

My phone was the one called

IPO: Okay, ó tí yé mi.okay, óyá, ìgbà tí ẹ kúrò ní DDD ñkó, kí lẹ tún ẹ?

I now understand; after you left DDD, what did you do?

SUS: Mo lọ secondary school. Mo lo ọdún mẹta

I attended a secondary school for three years

IPO: Class wo ni ẹ ti drop out?

What class were you when you dropped out?

SUS: Ìwé kejọ

JSS 3

IPO: Ẹ ka class 1 tí tí dé class 8?

SUS: Mo kà á dé ìwé kejọ kí n ẹ ayé SS

IPO: Ọdún méléó lẹ ló ní secondary school?

How many years did you spend in secondary school?

SUS: Ọdún mẹta

Three years

IPO: Okay

SUS: Mo tún lọ sí AAA technical college school

I also attended AAA technical college

IPO: So, ìgbà tí ẹ kúrò ní AAA technical school ñkó?

And after leaving the technical college?

SUS: Mo lọ kó işé ọkọ. Mo ẹ conductor

I ventured into bus conducting

IPO: So conductor yẹ lẹ ẹ tí ẹ fi di driver?

So, you were into bus conducting till you were able to drive?

SUS: Bèni

Yes

IPO: Ọwọọ ta ni ẹ ti kọ iṣẹ ọkọ?

Who was your boss?

SUS: Mi ò lè sọ pé ẹnìkan bá yí ló kọ mi ní iṣẹ ọkọ. Nígbà tí ó pé tí mo ti n se conductor, mo kàn ní àyà, mo dẹ gbé ọkọ ní ibi tí wọn má a n kílíà (clear) ẹ sí ní ìdájí ni mo sì fí ṣiṣẹ lọ nítèmi

I cannot say precisely because I was not consciously trained by anyone. I just developed the confidence to drive after some years of conducting bus

IPO: Okay, wọn clear ọkọ sí ibìkan?

The bus is usually parked somewhere?

SUS: Èmi ni mo má a n kílíà ọkọ ní alẹ tí mo bá ti fọ ọ tán

I used to drive the bus to its garage

IPO: Kí ni kílíà yẹn?

What does it me to 'clear'?

SUS: Kí wọn park ọkọ

It means to park a car/bus

IPO(Burst into laughter) so, iṣẹẹ driver lẹ n ẹ?

So, you are a commercial bus driver?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Sẹ ẹ mọ àwọn tí ó kọ ìwé yí?

Do you know the complainant?

SUS: Mo má a n gbọ orúkọ wọn ní oko ni

I do hear about him in the village

IPO: Ẹ ẹ mọ ọn?

You don't know him?

SUS: Mi ò mọ ọn

I don't know him

IPO: (has the feeling that the suspect is not saying the truth) Tí ẹ bá fẹ sòrò, kí ẹ wà careful nńkan tí ẹ má a sọ, tori nńkan tí ẹ bá sọ lè ní implication. Sẹ kí n kọ ọ síbẹ pé ẹ ẹ mọ ọn?

You have to be very careful whatever you are going to be saying, because whatever you say has implications

SUS: Mi ò mọ ọn

I don't know him

IPO: Sẹ o mọ ẹni tí ó kọ ìwé yí tàbí o ò mọ ọn?

Do you know the complainant who wrote this petition or not?

SUS: Mi ò mọ ọn

I don't know him

IPO: O ò mọ ọn?

You don't know him?

SUS: Mi ò mọ ọn

I don't know him

IPO: Kí n kọ ọ síbè pé ẹ ẹ mò ọn?

Should I write it down that you down know him?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: So, ẹni tí ẹ ní ẹ ẹ mò yíi dárúko yín pé ẹ wà lára àwọn tí ó wá ba nńkan òun jé. Šé orúko yín wà níbí?

So the one you claimed you do not know alleged you of being among those who destroyed his landed property. Is your name here?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Ó wá dárúko ẹ pé ní ojọ Sátidé yẹn pé ẹyin àti àwọn iyókù lọ ba ilé òun jé

He mentioned your name as being among those who destroyed his property

SUS: Rára o

Not at all

IPO: Kí ló wá şelẹ ní ojọ yẹn?

What happened on that day?

SUS: Bí ẹmi şe wà yíi, mi ò kí n ba nńkan èyàn jé.....**int**

I am not in the habit of destroying other people's property....

IPO: (Raises his voice angrily) Sh..... gbàgbé gbogbo iyẹn, kí ló şelẹ ní ojọ Sátidé yẹn?

Forget all that; what happened on that very Saturday?

SUS: Èmí lọ oko ni mo bá pastor níbè

I went to the village and I met a pastor on the land

IPO: Ago mélédo lo lọ oko tí o fi bá pastor?

What time did you visit the village where you met the pastor?

SUS: Ó ti n lọ bíi nńkan bíi to 2. Èmi àti ẹgbón ọn mi la jọ lọ

It was around 2 pm, I went in company of my brother

IPO: Oko ibo ni ẹ lọ?

Which village did you visit?

SUS: VVV

IPO: Látí lọ şe kí ni?

To do what?

SUS: Látí lọ wo oko

To check our farmland

IPO: So, ẹ wá bá ta ni níbè?

And you met who there?

SUS: Mo bá pastor níbi..... **int**

I met pastor where

IPO: Pator wo?

Which pastor?

SUS: Sir

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ pastor yẹn?

What is the name of the pastor?

SUS: Mi ò mò ọ̀n

I don't know it

IPO: Kí wá ni pastor sọ?

What did the pastor say?

SUS: Ó ní YYY ló ta ilẹ̀ fún òun

He said YYY sold the land to him

IPO: Kí ni pastor yẹn n ẹ̀ lórí ilẹ̀?

What was the pastor doing on the land?

SUS: Ó dúró nǐbẹ̀, ó ó wo pillar

He was examining the pillars on the land

IPO: Ó n examime pillar?

He was examining pillars?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: So, pastor yẹn sọ pé YYY ló ta ilẹ̀ fún òun?

So, the pastor claimed YYY sold the land to him?

SUS: Ehn, mo sì kojá lọ.....**int**

Yes, and I move on to.....

IPO: Wait!!, okay

SUS: ̀Igbà tí mo fi wọ̀ abúlẹ̀ ni mo n gbọ̀ pé ẹ̀mi ni mo wá fọ̀ ilẹ̀ òun.....**int**

By the time I got into the village, I heard the rumour that I was the one that came to destroy the on-going building construction on the land

IPO: ̀Igbà tí ó sọ pé YYY ló ta ilẹ̀ fún òun, kí lẹ̀ wá ẹ̀?

When he (the pastor) said YYY sold the land to him, what then did you do?

SUS: A lọ bá wọ̀n ní abúlẹ̀

We went to meet him in the village

IPO: ̀E lọ bá ta ni?

You went to meet who?

SUS: A lọ bá YYY tí ó ta ilẹ̀, mo sọ pé bọ̀da YYY, ẹ̀ ẹ̀yin lẹ̀ ta ilẹ̀ fún àwọ̀n MMM

We went to meet YYY to find out if it was actually true

IPO: Wait!!! ẹ̀ n sọ̀rọ̀ YYY, ẹ̀ n sọ̀rọ̀ MMM

Wait!!! You are talking about YYY and MMM

SUS: ̀Èmi àti pastor la jọ̀ lọ ibẹ̀

Pastor and I went to the place

IPO: Ta ló mú un yín lọ síbẹ̀? (Attends to a woman that walks in) so, ̀Igbà tí ẹ̀yin àti pastor dé ibẹ̀ nńkọ̀? Ta lo mú un yín lọ sí ọ̀dọ̀ YYY?

Who took you there; to YYY?

SUS: Pastor ló mú mi lọ

Pastor took me there

IPO: Okay, ní abúlé?
Okay, in that village?

SUS: Bèèni
Yes

IPO: Kí lẹ ní ẹ pèlú abúlé yẹn? Ìgbà tí ẹ dé ọdò YYY, kí lẹ ẹ?
What is your connection with that village? what did you do when you got to YYY?

SUS: Mo wá bèrè pé bọdá YYY, ẹ gbọ, wọn ní ẹyin lẹ ta fún..... **int**
I asked him, YYY, if he was the one that sold the land

IPO: Kí ló dé tí ẹ pè é ní bọdá?
Why did you address him as brother?

SUS: Nígbà tí mo ri pé ó jù mí lọ
I noticed he is older than I am

IPO: Ó jù yín lọ?
He is older than you are?

SUS: Ehn, ibi tí a ti n argue, tí wọn ti sún mó mi.....**int**
Yes, as we were arguing, he moved close to me....

IPO: Kí ni àjọsepò tó wà láàrín ẹyin àti YYY?
What is the relationship between you and YYY?

SUS: Èmi ò ní àjọsepò kankan pèlú wọn
I don't have any relationship with him

IPO: Nìkankan ò pa yín pò rí?
No any form of relationship?

SUS: Rára
Not at all

IPO: Báwo ni ẹyin ẹ jẹ sí abúlé yẹn?
What is your link with that village?

SUS: Oko daddy mi ni
It is my father's village

IPO: So, báwo ni YYY ẹ jẹ sí abúlé yẹn?
And how is YYY to that village?

SUS: Mi ò lè dáhùn ìyẹn
I don't have an answer for that

IPO: Ẹ ẹ mò bí ó ẹ jẹ síbè?
You don't know ?

SUS : Bèèni
Yes

IPO: Ìgbà wo ló ti n gbé ibè tí ẹ mò?
Since when has he been staying in that village?

SUS: Ìgbà tí a n lọ oko ni wọn ni ó kó ilé síbè

He has been farming in the village for sometime now

IPO: Ta ló sọ bẹ è?
Who told you that?

SUS: Àwọn tí ó jẹ bíí daddy wa
Our elders

IPO: Ọjọ wo ni wọn sọ bẹ è?
When did they say that?

SUS: Ó ti pé
It has been long

IPO: Síwájú kí ẹ tó wá síbí lónìí ni wọn ti sọ bẹ è fún un yín?
Before you came here today?

SUS: Ehn
Yes

IPO: Kí ló wá dé tí ẹ fi sọ pé ẹ è mò ọn?
Why then did you say you do not know him?

SUS: Èmi ò ọn nínu family wa
I do not know him as part of our family

IPO: Sẹ mo bèèrè family yín ni? Kí ló kàn mí pèlu family yín? Sẹ mo jẹ ọmọ family yín ni? Ẹ lo jókòó sí ibèyẹn. You are not a serious type. Sit on the floor
Did I ask about your family?what is my business with your family?Am I part of your family? Go and sit down there. You are not serious.....

SUS: Wants to sit on the chair

IPO: Eh, stand up! (**raised voice**) Sit on the floor. Motor park lẹ rò pé ẹ wà ni? If you learnt driving, is this place a motor park

IPO: (Talking to one of the suspects) Ọgbéni yẹn paró. Ko deserve to be treated with respect
That man is telling lies. He does not deserve to be treated with respect

INTERACTION 3

IPO: kí ni orúkọ yín, bàbá?
What is your name,old man?

SUS: FFF

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni yín?
Where are you from?

SUS: TTT

IPO: Ọmọ ọdún mélódó ni yín
How old are you?

SUS: 00

IPO: Işẹ wo lẹ n şe?
What do you do?

SUS: Ọwò

Trading

IPO: Kí lẹ́ ń tà; kí lẹ́ ń rà?

What do you buy and sell?

SUS: Èlùbọ́

Yam flour

IPO: Sẹ́ ẹ́ lọ́ iléèwé rará?

Did you go to school at all?

SUS: Mì ò lọ́ iléèwé o

I did not go to school

IPO: But ẹ́ lọ́ ilé kẹ́ú?

But you went to Arabic school?

SUS: Mì ò lọ́ ilé kẹ́ú náà lọ́ tí

Not really

IPO: But ẹ́ kọ́ ọ̀wọ́?

But you learnt trading

SUS: Mo kọ́ ọ̀wọ́

Yes, I did

IPO: Ọ̀wọ́ ta ni ẹ́ ti kọ́sẹ́ ọ̀wọ́?

Who taught you?

SUS: Àwọn tí wọn ń já ọ̀jà sí ọ̀dò mi

Those who used to deposit goods with me

IPO: Inúu OOO ni ẹ́ kọ́ ilé si?

You live in OOO?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: So, ibo ni ẹ́ ti ń ta èlùbọ́?

So, where do you sell yam flour?

SUS: Mo ní ọ̀òbù sí FFF

I have my shop/warehouse at FFF

IPO: Níbo ní FFF?

Where in FFF?

SUS: RRR

IPO: Sẹ́ ẹ́ ń lọ́ èlùbọ́?

Do you grind yam flour?

SUS: Ehn

Yes

IPO: Sẹ́ wọn ń pè yín ní bàbá ẹ̀lẹ̀rọ́?

Are you called bàbá ẹ̀lẹ̀rọ́?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

Yes

IPO: Sẹ ẹ mọ ẹni tí ó kọ iwé yíí?

Do you know the complainant?

SUS: Mo mọ ọn

Yes, I do

IPO: Ní Sátidé 30, ọdún tí a wà yíí, ó ní ẹyin àti àwọn kan gbìmò pò láti ná òun ní mọşáláşí.

Kí lẹ fẹ sọ si?

He alleged that on Saturday 30, this year, you connived with others to beat him up in the mosque. What have you to say on this?

SUS: Ó pa irò mọ mi

He lied against me

IPO: Okay, ibo ni ẹ wà ní ojó yẹn?

Okay, where were you on that day?

SUS: Ó lọ rawó ẹbẹ pé kí imáàmù bá òun dé ọdò àwọn YYY láti bẹ wọn pé ilẹ tí àwọn n tà, wọn ò ní ẹtò si, pé kí wọn dáráji àwọn

He pleaded with Imam to come and plead with us on our land that he had sold. He wanted us to forgive him.

IPO: Ìgbà wo ni ìyẹn şẹlẹ?

When did that happen?

SUS: Ó ti pé díẹ

It is been long

IPO: Ehn ehn

SUS: Olóyè wà ní ọdò baálẹ ní ojó yẹn

Chief(one of the suspects) was with Baálẹ on that day

IPO: Báwo ni ó şe níşe pèlú nńkan tí ó şẹlẹ ní on the 30?

How is that related to the incident that happened on the 30th?

SUS: Láyìn ìyẹn ni wọn rán olóyè àti èmi lọ sí oko

It was after then that Chief was sent to the village/farm

IPO: Okay, kí ló dé tí community yẹn fi rán an yín?

Why did the community send you to the land?

SUS: Omọ ibẹ ni mí

I am from that village

IPO: Okay

SUS: Wọn rán èmi àti olóyè láti lọ şàlàyé fún wọn pé tí wọn bá**int**

Chief and I were sent to explain to them that.....

IPO: Ẹ dúró náá, wait, ta ni wọn lọ bẹ?

Wait, whom did they go to plead with?

SUS: Wọn lọ bẹ imáàmù

They pleaded with the Imam

IPO: Okay, imam wá bá wọn lọ sí ọdò baálẹ?

Okay, the Imam then went with them to the Baálẹ?

SUS: Ehn

IPO: Baálè wá yan èyin àti olóyè pé kí ẹ lọ?

Baale then chose you and chief to go there?

SUS: Şé ẹ ri, ìgbà tí wọn fi àbò fún family àti baálè pé ǹnkan tí family wí nì yí.....

When they brought their report to the family and baale on the position of the family

IPO: Baálè ibo?

Baale of which community?

SUS: Mentions the name of the village

IPO: Şé oko yẹn ni baálè ǹ gbé ni?

Does Baale live in that village?

SUS: Bèèni

Yes

IPO: Okay, ìgbà tí èyin dé ibè, kí lẹ bá?

Okay, when you got there, what did you meet?

SUS: Wọn ní àwọn ti rí YYY, wọn sì ti şàlàyé işé tí wọn rán wọn

They said they had seen YYY, and had given him the message they were given for him

IPO: Kí ló wá şelè after?

What then happened afterwards?

SUS: Ohun tó şelè after ni pé èmi àti olóyè wà ní ìta ni a gbó pé wọn ti ǹ jà

What happened later was that chief and I just heard the noise arising from their misunderstanding

IPO: Wọn ní wọn ti rí YYY?

They said they had met YYY?

SUS: Bèèni

Yes

IPO: Ìgbà tí wọn ní àwọn ti jíşé fún un, kí ló wá şelè?

What then happened after they claimed they had delivered the message?

SUS: Tries to explain

IPO: Kí wá ni interest yín lórí ilè yẹn?

What is your interest on the last?

SUS:Ǹnkan tí ẹ wí ò yé mi

I don't understand you

IPO: Okay, how many acres lẹ ní sí oko yẹn?

How many acres of land do you have in that village?

SUS: 9 acres

IPO: No wonder (the IPO reads the contents of the suspect's statement to him)

INTERACTION 4

IPO: Bàbá ẹ ẹ lè kòwé?

SUS: Rára

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?

SUS: PPP

IPO: Ọmọ ọdún mélòó ni yín?

SUS: SSS

IPO: Işé wo ni ẹ n ẹ?

SUS: Àgbè

IPO: ẹsìn wo lẹ n ẹ?

SUS: III

IPO: Ẹ ọmọ Nigeria ni yín?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Ta ló bí yín, ibo ni wọn bí yín sí?

SUS: VVV

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ bàbáa yín?

SUS: MMM

IPO: Ọdún wo ni wọn bí yín?

SUS: Mí ò lẹ sọ

IPO: Báwo lẹ ẹ mọ pé 56 years ni yín?

IPO2: Kí ni inagijẹ yín?

SUS: QQQ

IPO: School wo lẹ lọ?

SUS: EEE

IPO: 19 kí lẹ lọ school

SUS: Mí ò lẹ sọ

IPO: Kí ló dé tí ẹ ẹ parí ilèwé aláakóbèrè?

SUS: Kò sí agbára

IPO: Ìgbà tí ẹ kúrò ní school, ibo lẹ lọ?

SUS: Mo lọ kóşé

IPO: Işé wo lẹ kó?

SUS: Driver

IPO: Ibo ni ẹ ti kó driver?

SUS: Ní ọ̀dò ọ̀gá mi ni

IPO: Ta ni ọ̀ga yín?

SUS: TYT

IPO: Ọdún mélòó lẹ fi kóşé?

SUS: B́í ọ̀dún ḿerin

IPO: Lẹ̀yìn ìgbà ẹ̀n, kí lẹ n ẹ?

SUS: Mo n şışé ọ̀kò

IPO: Irú motor wo lẹ bẹrẹ sí ní wà?
 SUS: Bedford
 IPO: Ibo lẹ n ná?
 SUS: Abeokuta
 IPO: Lẹyìn ìgbà yẹn n kó?
 SUS: Ìgbà tí ojú fẹ máa dùn mí, mo fi isẹ okò sílẹ
 IPO: Okay, lẹyìn ìgbà yèn, kí lẹ wá n ẹ?
 SUS: Isẹ oko
 IPO: Kí lẹ n gbìn?
 SUS: oko obì
 IPO: Okay, kí lẹ tún n gbìn?
 SUS: Kòkó, ọsàn
 IPO: Ẹ mọ àwọn tí ó wá complain yẹn?
 SUS: Bẹ̀ni, mo mò wọn
 IPO: Báwo lẹ ẹ mò wọn?
 SUS: Inú abúlẹ wa ni wọn n gbé
 IPO: Báwo ni wọn ẹ wá n gbé inú abúlẹe yín?
 SUS: Ibẹ ni bàbáa wọn bí wọn sí
 IPO: Ibo ni wọn n gbé?
 SUS: Abá TMT
 IPO: Okay, ẹ gbọ̀njú bá wọn ní ibẹ ni?
 SUS: Bẹ̀ni
 IPO: Báwo ni èyin ẹ jẹ sí wọn?
 SUS: Ẹ sẹ..... begins to explain
 IPO: Ta ló mú wọn wá?
 SUS: Bàbáa wa VVV ló mú wọn wá
 IPO: Bàbá
 SUS: Sir
 IPO: Wọn ní on the 30th of May, pé ẹ lọ sóko, tí YYY ní ẹ n fàyà jẹ òun
 SUS: Ẹ jẹ n sàlàyé.....
 IPO: Ní on the 30 yẹn,
 SUS: Bẹ̀ni sir
 IPO: Èyin mélòó lẹ lọ?
 SUS: Èmi àti bùròdá mi
 IPO: Kí lẹ lọ ẹ?
 SUS: Mo kó àwọn nńkan tí wọn fẹ fi ẹ ilé mi síbẹ
 IPO: Okay
 SUS: Continues his explanation.....
 IPO: Àwọn tí ó wá ní ojó sẹ ẹ dá wọn mò?
 SUS: Kì n ẹ gbogbo wọn, sùgbọ̀n XYZ wà nńbẹ

IPO: Báwo ni mà má tó wà ní village yẹn ẹ ẹ jí sí yín

SUS: Ìyàwo àbúrò bàbá mi ni

Another IPO cut in to discuss personal issues with the IPO interrogating the suspect above without excusing the suspect

IPO: Ta lẹ sọ pé ẹ rí nígbà tí ẹ yojú ní ojú window?

SUS: YYY

IPO: Kí ni wọn n ẹ; òun àti àwọn wo?

SUS: Mi ò mò wọn

IPO: Kí ló ẹlẹ nígbà tí ẹ rí wọn?

SUS: Nnkan tó ẹlẹ..... **int**

IPO: Ẹ ti sọ iyẹn tẹlẹ, àní kí ló ẹ ẹlẹ?

SUS: Wọn n bá wọn settle òrò yẹn nígbà yẹn

IPO: Kí ní orúkọ brother yín yẹn

SUS: TMT

IPO: Wọn ní eyin lẹ lọ fọ gbogbo nnkan tí wọn kó síbè

SUS:

IPO2: Wọn ní eyin lẹ fọ gbogbo ẹ

SUS: Èmi ò dé ibi kàn kan oo.....**int**

IPO2: Ta ló wá fọ ọ?

IPO1: Ta ló fọ ọ?

SUS: Èmi kọ, mi ò lè fọ nnkan onínnnkan

IPO: Bàbá

SUS: Sir

IPO: Nnkan tí ẹ n sọ ni pé ẹgbọn ọn yín ló lọ fọ block?

SUS: ẹgbọn ọn mi ò bé ibi block.....**int**

IPO: Báwo lẹ ẹ mò?

SUS: ẹgbọn ọn kàn n bá wọn settle òrò ni kò lè fọ block.....**int**

IPO: Ah, ẹ máà predict ooo. Àwọn psychologists ti fi yé wa pé nígbà mírán, èyàn ò wà predictable

SUS: But, ilẹ yẹn kí n ẹ ilẹ ẹgbọn mi tàbá ti bàbáà mi.....**int**

IPO: No, condition tí ẹ n fún mi ni èmí ẹ n ẹlẹyè

SUS: Kí n ẹ ilẹ bàbáà wa, kí ni ó fẹ ba ibẹ jí fún?

IPO: Ẹ ẹ n sòrò ni

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ village tí wọn ti fọ block yẹn?

SUS: Èmi ò ti ẹ mọ.....**int**

IPO: Ẹbí ẹ jọ lọ ni

SUS: Mi ò fojú kan ilẹ yẹn.....**int**

IPO: Bàbá, ọmọdé ni mí

SUS: Ọmọdé ni èmi náà

IPO: Ó possible kó jí pé condition tó wáyé ló mú ẹgbọn yín ẹ béyẹn

SUS: Mi ò mọ ibè yẹn, à fi tí mo bá dé ibè..... **int**

IPO: È jẹ n fún un yín ní example.....

IPO: Ibo ni wón ní wón ti wólé? **Tap his table**

SUS: Àwọn.....**int**

IPO: Àwọn wo ni wón wólé? Kí ni orúkọ village yín?

SUS: Wón ní MOM

IPO: Bàbá, **Tap his table**, wón ní èyàn bá ju àdà sílẹ nígbà igba, ibi peḗbẹ ni yòò fi lélé. Tí ẹ ò bá ẹ nńkan tí kò dára, kò sí ẹni tí á mú un yín

INTERACTION 5

This suspect was actually arrested having been caught taking the photograph of the activities of the police officers that went to visit the disputed piece of land. **There are two IPOs** involved here

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?

SUS: YXY

IPO: Ibo ẹ ní gbé?

SUS: YMY

IPO: Kí ni phone number yín?

SUS: XXXX

IPO: Óyá sign, ko dẹ kọ date

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Kí ló dé tí ẹ fi ní ya photo? **Raised his voice**

SUS: I was just playing with my phone ni

IPO: Simple sincerity

IPO2: (Called the name of the first IPO), X, o ò tí ì fi bàbá yí sínu cell ni? You are wicked (pointing at the suspect)

IPO: Do you know the implication of what you were doing as an alfa. È fẹ fi kiní yẹn ẹ nńkan ni

LAWYER: Kò mọ implication ẹ ni

SUS: È màà bínú sir

CASE 24: DEFRAUDATION (LAND ISSUES)

Back Information: *The suspect was a 35-year old man who was alleged of duping the victim with a sum of 350,000 over a piece of land.*

IPO: Gbé chair yẹn fún mi (ordered the suspect to pick a chair for him to seat)

SUS: (Brings the chair)

IPO: ègbón ẹ XXX ñkọ?

SUS: Mi ò ì tî rí wọn

IPO: Işé wo lo ñ şe?

SUS: Trading

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni ẹ?

SUS: XYZ. Şé mo lè fi Yoruba kọ ọ? (referring to the confessional statement he was writing)

IPO: Şé o ò gbọ English ni? Má fi Yoruba kọ ọ o (**with an angry look**). Má à waste ìwé mi.

Óyá fi Yoruba kọ ọ nígbà yẹn

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Şé ìwọ lo ni ilẹ yẹn?

SUS: Ẹni tí ó ní ló ní kí n bá òun tà á

The IPO stood up to charge his phone, after which he resumed the interaction

IPO: Báwo ni ilẹ yẹn şe jé? Ta ló nilẹ?

SUS: Ilẹ yẹn, YYY ni ó**int**

IPO: Kọkọ kọ eléyí náá (pointing to the paper provided for the confessional statement)

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Kí lo kọ?

SUS: Mo ti şe tán sir

IPO: Kí lo kọ síbẹ?

SUS: (Reads it out)

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ lawyer yẹn?

SUS: DDD

IPO: Ilẹ̀ yẹn ta ló ni í?

SUS: Èmi kọ ni mo ni í

IPO: Óyá kọ ọ sílẹ̀

SUS: (Continues with the statement)

IPO: Ìgbà tí o mú customer lọ ibẹ̀, ẹ́ o fún XYZ lówó?

SUS: Rárá sir..... (**scratching his head and looking into the eyes of the IPO**) **int**

IPO: Kí ló tún dé? O tún kọ Yoruba tì ni?

SUS: Rárá, mo fẹ̀ rántí ibẹ̀yẹn ni

IPO: Kọ ibi tí a lọ lẹ̀ẹ̀kan yẹn

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Kí ló dé tó ò fun un lówó?

SUS: Nnkan tó sèlẹ̀.....**int**

IPO: Kí ló dé tó ò fun un lówó?

SUS: Mo sọ fún un.....**int**

IPO: Ìwé tí o fí fun lówó dà?

SUS: Ó wà nínú àwọn ìwé tí mo ní wọn gbà lówó mi yẹn

IPO: Má a tan arà ẹ̀ jẹ̀ nbẹ̀

SUS: (Continues writing)

IPO: O mọ̀mọ̀ lùú ní jìbìtì ni

SUS: Mi ò lùú ní jìbìtì

IPO: Ò n lọ sẹ̀wọ̀n nìyẹn oo. O jí owó yẹn ni

SUS: Mi ò jì ì

IPO: Sè o mò nńkan tí wọn ní pè ní stealing?

SUS: Mo mò ọn sir

IPO: **Notorious criminal ni ẹ**

SUS: As ọrẹ mi.....mo ní kí ó ra ilẹ yẹn kí ó develop ẹ

IPO: Ojú ẹ ni wọn má a ta ilẹ yẹn dànù. Sè o rò pé o gbón ni!

SUS: Ẹ jòò mo fẹ charge (because he needed to make a call to one of his relatives)

IPO: With whose charger? I should remove my phone for you? **You this criminal**

CASE 25: DERELICTION OF DUTY AND FRAUD

Back Information: *The suspect here is being quizzed in connection to the fraudulent activities of a sacked bank marketer who presented herself as a staff member of XYY bank and defrauded many unsuspecting customers of a huge amount of money. The principal suspect, before her sack, was under directly reporting to the suspect being questioned here, being her boss. It was insinuated that there might have been an amorous affair between them and that was why, even long after the principal suspect had been sacked, she still had access to some of the facilities of the bank which aided her nefarious activities. The exchange had started before the researcher came in.*

IPO: Mr XXX, do you know as the coordinator of her group, your not retrieving the facilities of the bank form her after she was sacked could have aided her in perpetrating that act?

SUS: You are treating me like there is a personal interest here. I am not a criminal and should not be treated so. It appears you police officers are always after bankers (**angrily and raised voice**)

IPO: Mr XXX, do you know that is an allegation? I need you to explain that allegation. Do you know where you are?

SUS: Yes, I know I am at the SCID

IPO: So you expect me to take your words at the face value.

SUS: You have asked me questions, and I have answered you; yet you are paraphrasing the Questions to indict me

IPO: Mr XXX, accept your fault. Yoruba ni gbogbo wa

SUS: The bank is not her primary employer. YYY employed her on behalf of the bank

IPO: Mr XXX, do you know the essence of investigation? We need to do proper investigation in order to apportion blame properly. You can never fight with your IPO. Most of the successful lawyers in the court get ideas from their IPOs.

SUS: E máà bínú sir

CASE 26: ASSULT AND THREAT

Background Information: *The complainant had claimed the suspect assaulted and threatened him. The suspect is a well-educated old man who should be in his late sixties. He is the landlord of the suspect.*

IPO: E gbọ sé e pè é ní ghost? (while he was still writing his statement)

SUS: Èmi, a ghost? O tún n paró mó mi

IPO: Daddy, sé e ti kọ ó tán? E kọ orúkọ yín síbí sir, kí e dè sign

SUS: Okay

IPO: Sé e fẹ drop èyí ni? (referring to the document the suspect was handling as evidence of his innocence)

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Sé e ní photocopy lówó?

SUS: Rára

IPO: E jẹ kí n lọ báa yín se photocopy.

SUS: Okay

IPO: Daddy e jókòó

After some minutes, the IPO surfaced with the photocopies of the said documents. She genuflected while giving the suspect a copy as a sign of courtesy. Afterwards, she announced the matter would be taken to the DC's office.

IPO: Daddy, èyin e máà bò

SUS: Okay

The complainant was later seen prostrating to the suspect, begging him to forgive him.

CASE 27: FRAUD (LAND ISSUE)

Background Information: The suspect is a 40-year old man who has been alleged of duping a woman (the complainant) of an amount of money close to four hundred thousand naira.

IPO: Šé o gbòyínbo?

SUS: Rárá

IPO: Báwo lo ƣe fẹ dá owóolówó pada?

SUS: Owó á jáde. Mo ti n ƣisẹ lórí ẹ

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ ẹ?

SUS: YYY

IPO: Ọmọ ọdún mèlòò ni ẹ?

SUS: 40

IPO: Işẹ wo lo n ƣe?

SUS: Block moulder

IPO: Christian àbí Muslim?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Ibo lo n gbé?

SUS: TTT

IPO: Ọmọ ilú wo ni ẹ?

SUS: III

IPO: Primary school wo lo lọ?

SUS: SSS primary school

IPO: Secondary school nńkó?

SUS: Mí ò parí

IPO: Ìgbàwo lo parí ní primary school yẹn?

SUS: UUU

IPO: Secondary school nńkó?

SUS: Mí ò jáde

IPO: Class wo lo ti stop?

SUS: JS 3

IPO: Lẹyìn iyẹn, ibo lo tún lọ?

SUS: Mo lo kóşé

IPO: Níbo lo ti kóşé?

SUS: BBB

IPO: Níbo ni

SUS: Kwara

IPO: Léyìn ìyẹn ñkó?

SUS: Mo padà sí Ibadan

IPO: Ibo lo ti wá kó block making?

SUS: Ibadan náà ni

IPO: Year wo lo padà sí Ibadan?

SUS: 1994

IPO: Léyìn ìyẹn ñkó

SUS: Mo n şişe kiri

IPO: Ìgbàwo ni eniyen ra block lówọ yín?

SUS: 2013

IPO: O ti fẹ iyàwó àbí?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Omọ mélòó le bí?

SUS: 3

IPO: Ilé ara ẹ lo n gbé àbí?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Ìgbàwo ni woman yí ra ilẹ lówó ẹ?

SUS: 2013

IPO: Ta ló mú wọn wá?

SUS: ọrẹẹ mi tó nílẹ síbè

IPO: ọrẹẹ wo? Sàlàyé nìkan tó şelè

SUS: Begns to explain

IPO: O ò wà straightforward jàre, tí o kàn n sọrò bí kíní yí

SUS: Ehn..... **int**

IPO: Wò ó jé á lo straightforward jàre, şé o lè kọ statement ni?

SUS: Okay

IPO: Èlò ni wọn kó wá

SUS: 270

IPO: Ìgbàwo ló ní òun má a wá balance?

SUS: Ending

IPO: Ta ló nilẹ yẹn?

SUS: Mumbling

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ ẹ? (**raised her voice and banged the table**)

SUS: ZZZ

IPO: Ùh hún

SUS: Continues his explanation

IPO: Sẹ̀ ìgbà tí ìwọ gbowò tán, o ò mú wọn dé orí ilẹ̀ yẹn ni?

SUS: A à jọ dé ibẹ̀

IPO: O ò mú wọn lọ sórí ilẹ̀ kan kan?

SUS: Rára

IPO: Lẹ̀yìn tí wọn ti kó iyanrìn lọ tán lo sẹ̀sẹ̀ lọ síbẹ̀?

SUS: Ìgbà tí **int**

IPO: ọ̀rọ̀ burúkú tí ò n sọ yí, mo ní sẹ̀ ìgbà tí wọn ti kó iyanrìn tán lo sẹ̀sẹ̀ lọ síbẹ̀?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Olè ni ẹ̀ o. You are really a thief

SUS: Aunty, ẹ̀ jẹ́ kí n explain

CASE 28: DEFILEMENT

Background Information: *This case involves two teenager suspects, one 13, and the other 14.*

They are alleged of defiling a seven-year old girl in their neighbourhood.

IPO: Èyìn, ẹ̀ lọ n bá ọ̀mọ̀lọ̀mọ̀ sùn. Ibo lẹ̀ ti kọ ọ? Ibo lẹ̀ ti ri kà?

SUSs: Looking pitifully

IPO: Sẹ̀ ẹ̀ è lè sọ̀rọ̀ ni? Mà á fọ̀ etí yín o. Kí ni age ẹ̀?

SUS 1: 13

IPO: Ìwọ́ n_kó?

SUS 2: 14

IPO: Èwọ̀n ló yẹ́ kí ẹ̀ lọ

IPO2: Eh! Èyin ọmọkéékèké yìí, ìkà ni yìn o

The two suspects are then taken out of the interrogation room.

CASE 29: ALLEGATION OF FRAUD AND FORGERY

Background Information: *The suspect is in his late 50's. He is a certified surveyor and estate management, who schooled both in Ghana and Nigeria. He speaks impeccable English. Prior to the commencement of their verbal interaction, the IPO offered his own seat to the suspect, while he (the IPO) stood up. The IPO later sat on the table next to him while the interaction was still on-going.*

IPO: (Hands over the confessional statement paper to the suspect)

SUS: (Reads the cautionary statements aloud). If you ask me a question and I refuse to respond, what will you do to me? Hope you are not going to force me.

IPO: At all

SUS: Okay (hands the paper back to the IPO)

IPO: Thank you sir

SUS: Let me read the petition first before I make any response. (the suspect remembers he needs to call his lawyer but he is not with his phone)

IPO: Let me give you my phone to call him

SUS: Don't worry. I will do that later

SUS: I live in Ibadan

IPO: Where in Ibadan?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Thank you sir. How many wives do you have?

SUS: Why did you ask for that?

IPO: Because it is part of your biography. We need to know because some people do deny their statements

SUS: Okay, 1

IPO: How many issues?

SUS: How is that related to the issue here. I don't want to get my children involved in this

IPO: Oga, do you know YYY

SUS: Yes

IPO: How do you know him?

SUS: I know him as an agent. You know, I am not denying that he paid

IPO: Of course, I know you. I know you very well now.

SUS: I don't want to write my statement in reaction to his (the complainant) petition, because I don't want to be defensive. I need to first of all give the background information. Now, I will explain what I want to write.

IPO: Alright sir

SUS: Continues with the writing of his confessional statement

IPO: You want to tell me the documents are not forged?

SUS: Yes sir

IPO: Are you now telling me you did not connive with those vendors

SUS: Yes

IPO: Okay, that is what I am trying to confirm before we go to madam (his boss)

SUS: (Completes writing his confessional statement)

IPO: Oyá sign

IPO: You will assist us

SUS: In what way

IPO: To call them (other suspects mentioned in the petition of the complainant)

CASE 30: FORGERY AND FALSE REPRESENTATION

Background Information: *The suspect is an HND holder who earns his living from estate and property management. He has been accused of forging certain property documents in the name of a popular pastor in Ibadan. Two IPOs are involved here*

IPO: As a an administrative agent, kí lẹ níṣe pẹ́lú property tí tà? Who owns the property?

SUS: I have been managing it

IPO: You are an agent to bàbá?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Since when?

SUS: 2004

IPO: So since 2004, you have been the agent taking the rent of the property?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Write it down that you have been agent to Mr WWW as regards his property

SUS: I am coming oo, there was one man collecting it before.....**int**

IPO: Èwo ló kàn yín? You don't have business with that. Ìgbà wo ni? That is enough to distract us; we don't want distractions

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Óyá (**bangs th table**) kí lẹ níṣe pèlú property yẹn? Ìgbà wo lẹ ti jẹ agent fún un?

SUS: Continues with the writing of his confessional statement

IPO: (Commenting on a part of the suspect's write-up) who is asking you about sales? (**bangs his table**). Let us take it one after the other

SUS: That is why I don't want to rush so that I don't make a blunder

IPO: As his agent, what and what do you do for him?

SUS: I get people for the house and I also take care of the house

IPO: Means wo lẹ fi n remit fún un wọn?

SUS: I pay to the bank

IPO: Cash or cheque?

SUS: Cash

IPO: Write it there

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Orúkọ wo lẹ fi n fún àwọn tenant ní receipt?

SUS: (Brings out a set of documents from his nylon bag)

IPO: Document wo ló fi hand over agency business yẹn before kí HHH tó travel abroad?

SUS: That bàbá and HHH were the ones handling it before HHH travelled abroad

IPO: Mi ò understand nìkan tí ẹ sọ last yẹn. Say it again!

SUS: (Repeats himself)

IPO: Şé anything wà written down on that?

SUS: It was verbal

IPO: So, ìgbà wo ni idea to sell come in?

SUS: Láti ìgbà tí bàbá àti HHH ti n handle ẹ

IPO: Ta ló sọ fún un yín pé wọn fẹ tà á?

SUS: HHH ló sọ fún mi pé wọn fẹ tà á

IPO: Ta ló mú Mr TTT wá?

SUS: DDD

IPO: But who acted as the agent during the sale?

SUS: Thank you. Mr GGG brought Mr TTT

IPO: Then what did you do?

SUS: I called bàbá

IPO: (Stands up to attend to something and later returns). Where are we?

SUS: I was saying Mr GGG brought Mr TTT to me

IPO: What did you do?

SUS: Bàbá called all of us.....**int**

IPO: Who acted as the agent? Between bàbá and Mr TTT, you acted as the agent, is that correct?

SUS: No, it is not correct

IPO: Óyá explain

SUS: Thank you.....**int**

IPO: You are distracting me oo

SUS: Mr (calls the name of the IPO), if you want to sell**int**

IPO: So what? I am not interested

SUS: (Continues to write)

IPO: What is the relevance of that? (**Bangs his table**)

SUS: I am just explaining

IPO: I am not interested in that. You know what you are saying

SUS: Okay

IPO: Who acted as agent between them

SUS: I acted as agent

IPO: See,you are trying to be too smart. You are smart. We are not concerned with affiliated agents. Who is the known agent between them (**bangs the table**)

SUS: I am the one

IPO: Write the down

SUS: Şé I should not put XXX

IPO: You can put whatever you like. It is your statement. Include everything you know about the issue. When you finish, tell me

SUS: Yes sir

IPO2: (Goes through the statement of the suspect) You are the agent for who?

SUS: Mr WWW

IPO: Who are the all of us? E sọ fún wa èlò ni wọn tà á? Báwo lẹ ẹ san owó fún Mr WWW?

SUS: Okay

IPO: Báwo lẹ ẹ remit owó fún Mr WWWẹ

SUS: Wọn fún mi ní account number wọn; mo dè sán án síbẹ

IPO: Óyá ẹ kọ ọ sílẹ, simple

SUS: (Wants to write but is interrupted)**int**

IPO2: No!!, you can't. Write the amount first

SUS: Okay

IPO2: What about the account number?

SUS: I cannot remember now

IPO2: Okay, what of the account name?

SUS: (writes)

IPO2: What document did you use to sell the property?

SUS: Cof O

IPO2: Óyá write it down

IPO: Kí ni nńkan tí ẹ kọ last?

SUS: (Reads it out)

IPO2: Affidavit for what? Loss of what?

IPO: Who went to court to facilitate that?

SUS: Let him come and tell me that

IPO: Qdún wo lẹ ta ilẹ yẹn?

SUS: 2014

IPO: So, if you work with me for three years, it is enough to know my name

SUS: Yes

IPO: You agree with me?

SUS: Yes

IPO: I now put it to you that this man is not Mr WWW as you claimed. That is not his name.

SUS: That is his name. All the landlords know him as WWW

IPO: How much was your agency percent?

IPO2: Óyá write your percentage

SUS: I am calculating something

IPOs: What are you calculating? *Şé kò ní oye tí ẹ́ n' gbà ni?*

IPO: Percentage wo ni WWW fún un yín?

SUS: 5 percent

IPO: Óyá write it down but I am not interested in what you do with the 5 percent.

IPO2: Mention how it was shared and the names of those who partook of it.

IPO3: What about the receipt den talk say you forged?

SUS: I did not forge it

IPO: Ẹ́ ẹ́ mọ́ nńkan tó blindfold gbogbo ẹ́yin tí ẹ́ wà involved in this case, I am sorry to use that statement, ni gain tí ẹ́ má a rí lórí ẹ́. You should know this man is not WWW. You should have questioned that name

SUS: I just got back from Kwara.....**int**

IPO2: What are you saying now? (**raises her voice**)

IPO: If you have been careful enough sir, you would have found out the truth

IPO2: Let him clarify the account name

SUS: This the name of the name he gave, and when I got to the bank.....

IPO2: I am not dubious

SUS: I am not dubious ooo, please

CASE 31: LAND ISSUE (FALSE OWNERSHIP AND MALICIOUS DAMAGE)

Background Information: *There are two suspects here. They are accused of claiming ownership of some acres of land, which they claimed belonged to their late father. The two suspects are interrogated at different times*

INTERACTION 1

IPO: *Şé o lè kòwé?*

SUS: Rára

IPO: *Kí ló dé tí o paró fún mi? (obviously from their interactions before entering the investigation hall)*

SUS: *Mi ò paró fún un yín ìn*

IPO: *Mà á fọ́ etí ẹ́. Idiot ni ẹ́*

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ ẹ?

SUS: XXX

IPO: XX what?

SUS: XXXX

IPO: Kí ni address ibi tí ò n gbé?

SUS: DDD

IPO: Phone number ẹ n kọ?

SUS: 11111100

IPO: Ọmọ ibi ni ẹ?

SUS: DDD

IPO: Sẹ ọmọ DDD ni ẹ?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Ibo ni ó wà?

SUS: Abúlé tí ẹ wá ní ẹ̀ẹkan yẹn

IPO: Under ibo ni ó wà?

SUS: YYY

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ bàbá ẹ?

SUS: Òhun náà ni mo sọ ní ẹ̀ẹkan yẹn

IPO: (Angrily and firmly) Nnkan tí mo bá béèrè lówó ẹ kí o máa dàmílohùn; mo lè béèrè nígbà mēwàá

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Date wo ni wón bí ẹ?

SUS: 19XX

IPO: Primary school wo lo lọ?

SUS: FF primary school

IPO: Ibo ló wà?

SUS: Tí a bá ti kojáa GGG

IPO: Ọdun wo ni yẹn?

SUS: Mi ò rántí mọ

IPO: Secondary school wo lo lọ?

SUS: Mi ò lọ secondary school

IPO: Lẹyìn iyẹn, kí lo wá n ẹ?

SUS: Mo n ẹẹ oko

IPO: Kí ló dé tí o ò fi lọ school mó?

SUS: Kò sí owó

IPO: So, oko yẹn lo n ẹ di ìsin yìí?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Ibo ni oko yẹn wà?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Ẹ́ o mọ ẹni tí ó n jẹ DDD?

SUS: Mi ò gbọ orúkọ yẹn rí

IPO: O ò mọ ọ̀n àbí?

SUS: Rára

IPO: Ilẹ yẹn, ta ni ó ni í?

SUS: RRR

IPO: Ta ni RRR? (stands up to attend to a lawyer that walks in the course of the interaction, with a warning that the suspect should not leave the place)

IPO: (Comes back) Ibo ni a dé?

SUS: Ẹ́ ní ta ni RRR

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ bàbá tí ó bí bàbá ẹ yẹn?

SUS: Orúkọ tí mo pè ní ìsin yìí

IPO: Orúkọ kejì ñkọ?

SUS: RRR náà ni

IPO: Irọ o, kò lè jẹ ǹnkankan náà. Ta ló n jẹ EEE?

SUS: Mi ò mọ ọ̀n

IPO: O ò gbọ BBB rí?

SUS: Silent

IPO: Ta ló n jẹ GGG? Kò sí nínúu family yín, àbí?

SUS: Silent

IPO: Ibo ni ọ̀mọ AAA wà?

SUS: Mo gbọ pé ọ̀mọ ẹ ẹ se aláìsì nígbà kan

IPO: Bàbá wá ñkọ?

SUS: Wọn ti kú
IPO: Bàbá yẹn ló bí QQQ, àbí?
SUS: Ègbón àti àbúrò ni wọn
IPO: Njẹ̀ èyin mò pé AAA ilẹ̀ fún bàbá yẹn?
SUS: Mi ò mò
IPO: Sẹ ẹ ní ìwé ilẹ̀ yẹn?
SUS: Rára
IPO: È kàn bèrè sí ní tà á ni?
SUS: Wọn ti ẹ̀ survey ẹ̀
IPO: Ta ló ẹ̀ survey ẹ̀?
SUS: Bàbáa wa
IPO: Qdún wo ni wọn ẹ̀ ẹ̀?
SUS: 2004
IPO: Copy ẹ̀ nkó?
SUS: Qwó alhaja náà ló wà
IPO: Sẹ ẹ ní C of O?
SUS: Rára
IPO: Kí ló dé tí ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ẹ̀?
SUS: A à mò
IPO: Sẹ ẹ ẹ̀ mò pé ẹ̀ni tí ó ní C of O ni ó nilẹ̀?
SUS: Rára
IPO: Àti ìgbà wo lẹ̀ ti n ta ilẹ̀ yẹn?
SUS: 2004
IPO: How many acres?
SUS: 21
IPO: Báwo lẹ̀ ẹ̀ mò pé 21 acres ni?
SUS: Surveyor tí ó ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ló sọ fún wa
IPO: Surveyor wo?
SUS: Surveyor JKY
IPO: Sẹ ẹ̀ gbogbo ẹ̀ ni ẹ̀ ti tà?
SUS: Ó ku acre kan

IPO: So, ẹ ti ta 20 báyí

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Kí ni àwọn n̄kan tí ẹ bá lórí ilẹ̀ yẹn kí ẹ tó bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí ní tà á?

SUS: Wọn n̄ dáko níbẹ̀

IPO: Ta ló n̄ dáko níbẹ̀?

SUS: Man Ibo kan báyí

IPO: Látí ìgbà wo?

SUS: Ó ti tó bú ọdún m̄erin

IPO: Ta ló fún man Ibo yẹn n̄lẹ̀?

SUS: Kì n̄ ẹ̀ oun gan-an ni wọn fún

IPO: Ta ni wọn fún?

SUS: Ọkọ aunty ẹ̀

IPO: Ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ri pe irọ̀ ti wà láarín ìwọ̀ àti alhaja n̄sin yíí?

SUS: Mì ọ̀ pa irọ̀

IPO: Ìgbà tí wọn gbe fún man yẹn, ẹ̀ o wà níbẹ̀?

SUS: Ìgbà tí.....**int**

IPO: Ẹ̀ o wà níbẹ̀?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: Ìgbà wo nì y?

SUS: Mo wà ní 6 years

IPO: Ẹ̀ o ti gbọ̀n nígbà tí o wà ní 6 years?

SUS: Mo.....**int**

IPO: N̄kan tí mo bá bi ẹ̀ ni kí o dáhùn. Ta ni wọn lease ilẹ̀ yẹn fún?

SUS: ZZZ ni

IPO: Ẹ̀ o mò pé FFF ni ó n̄ jẹ̀ \$\$\$?

SUS: \$\$\$ ni mo mò ọ̀n sí.....**int**

IPO: Ta ló sọ fún ẹ̀ pé wọn lease ẹ̀ ni?

SUS: Alhaja

IPO: Ọdún m̄élòó ni wọn fí lease ẹ̀ out?

SUS: 25 years

IPO: Ẹ̀ ó ti wá expire báyíí?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Báwo lo se mò?

SUS: Èmi gan-an tí mo dé ba a, mo ti lé ni 25 years báyií

IPO: Idiot ni é

SUS: Ìgbà tí**int**

IPO: (**Bangs the table**) nńkan tí mo bèrè ni kí o dáhùn. Şé ìwé wà tí wọn fi lease ilè yẹn?

SUS: Ìwé wà

IPO: Qwọọ ta ló wà?

SUS: Qwó alhaja

IPO: E n paró... e lo n jowó ilè, e e lè bèrè ibi tí ìwé wà. Ibo ló wà? Şé ìwé wà?

SUS: Ìwé yẹn á wà

IPO: (Looks at the suspect disdainfully and continues with his writing)

IPO: Àwọn mélòó lẹ ti ta ilè yẹn fún?

SUS: (Tries to recollect) Àwọn márùn ún

IPO: Èyin náà lẹ tà á fún àwọn oní church yẹn?

SUS: Bèni

IPO: Kí ni àwọn nńkan tí wọn gbìn sí orí ilè yẹn?

SUS: Ègé

IPO: Ta ló wú ègé yẹn?

SUS: (Tries to explain)

IPO: A à mọ eni tí ó n paró nínú ìwọ àti alahajan báyií. Kí ló dé tí e n threaten wọn?

SUS: Olórùn ò jé

IPO: E e threaten wọn?

SUS: Rára

IPO: Èyin mélòó ni e ta ilè yẹn?

SUS: Àwa méjì

IPO: Èlò ni gbogbo owo tí e ti tà báyií?

SUS: Ah, mi ò lè şì ò

IPO: Kí ló dé tí o ò lè şì. Fi ojú gauge è

SUS: About 7 million tàbí kí ó jù bẹ è lo

IPO: Now, èyin mélòó lẹ jọ pín owó yẹn?

SUS: (Mentions the names)
IPO: Ibo ni MMM n gbé?
SUS: Òjòò
IPO: Sxxx nkó?
SUS: Òun ni ẹ rí ní èẹkan yẹn
IPO: Sxxx kì n ẹ family yín?
SUS: Rárá, ó kàn mú èyàn wá ra ilẹ ni
IPO: Ẹ kò jẹ nínú owó yẹn ni?
SUS: Ó jẹ nínú ẹ
IPO: (Continues with his writing)
IPO: (Calls Alhaja, the second suspect)

INTERACTION 2

IPO: Alhaja, àtìgbà wo ni daddy yín ti lease ilẹ yẹn out?
SUS: Ó ti tó 25 years
IPO: Ẹ ẹ ní ìwé tí wọn kọ ọ sí?
SUS: Bẹ̀ni
IPO: Ta ló ẹ survey ilẹ yẹn?
SUS: Bàbáa wa ẹ ìkan
IPO: Ẹ èyí tí bàbáa yín ẹ lẹ n ló?
SUS: Bẹ̀ni
IPO: Àwọn méléó lẹ ta ilẹ fún?
SUS: Àwọn márùn-ún
IPO: Bí èlọ lẹ ta ilẹ yẹn?
SUS: Bí 200, 300, 100 thousand
IPO: Èlo ní gbogbo owó ilẹ tí ẹ tà?
SUS: Èmi ò sírò ẹ. Á ti sún mó 7 million

CASE 32: LAND DISPUTE

Background Information: *The suspect is said to have encroached in the complainants' parcels of land. He is even said to always brag with his connection with a former AIG of the Nigeria Police (as reported by one of the complainants)*

IPO: Do you have any land at XXX

SUS: No, I don't

IPO: Are you not Mr YYY

SUS: Yes

IPO: Were you not the one that gave somebody a card on a land issue?

SUS: Okay, I remember.

IPO: Now that you are here now, no problem

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: They even said you came with some officers to disrupt the activities going on on the land

SUS: Let them identify me first. This is very embarrassing. I actually came late because I went to see VVV on our coming church anniversary. We need him to finance one of the activities to mark the anniversary

(As soon as the complainants came in, the IPO, the suspect and the complainants all went to the OC's office)

CASE 33: LAND ISSUE

Background Information: *The suspect, from his appearance is well-educated and informed. He is clad in a suit and accompanied by a young lady. I heard the IPO address him as Engineer XYZ.*

IPO: You are engineer XYZ

SUS: Yes

IPO: Sit down sir

SUS: Okay

IPO: (Gives the suspect a confessional Statement paper to write)

IPO 2: (A senior officer walks in) My man be suspect?

IPO: Yes sir

SUS: You call me a suspect?

IPO: I off your shoe?

SUS: Éyin gan an ẹ ẹ dá o (bursts into laughter). You just gave me a suspect's form

IPO2: Please give him Voluntary

IPO: Okay sir

SUS: (Hands his statement to the IPO)

IPO: You don't finish?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Ehn, engineer, ìgbà wo ni ẹ erect ki ní yẹn?

SUS: Last year

IPO: Láti last year, nothing is done on that place?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Ẹ kó ọ síbèyẹn

SUS: Okay, mo dè n kánjú o

IPO: Wọn kì í kánjú wá sí àgò ọlópàá; wọn kì í kán jú lọ

SUS: Okay

IPO: As it is now, what do we do?

SUS: Explains

IPO: That is a statement, put it there

SUS: Scribbles down something after which he rises to leave

IPO: Ibo lẹ n lọ?

SUS: Mo n kánjú ni. Mo ní meeting ni Secretariat

IPO: Okay

CASE 33: TRESPASS

Background Information: *The suspect is accused of trespass, being among a group of people involved in the burial of a corpse on the complainant's land*

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?

SUS: VVV

IPO: Iṣẹ wo lẹ n ẹ?

SUS: Mechanic

IPO: Christian àbí Muslim?

SUS: Muslim

IPO2: (Walks in) No be that man wey dey call us fake police be this because we no carry gun and hand-cuff?

IPO1: Yes

IPO2: And you no beat am?
IPO1: He just dey enter. I still dey collect his statement
SUS: E màà bínú ma
IPO2: It is okay
IPO1: Sè ẹ lè kòwé?
SUS: Rára
IPO1: Ojò wo lẹ wá sí Ìbàdàn? Àbí ibí ni wọn bí yín sí?
SUS: 1979
IPO1: E wá kòşẹẹ mechanic?
SUS: Bèèni
IPO1: Sè ẹ mọ XXX
SUS: Bíí brother ni ó jẹ fún mi
IPO1: Brother báwo?
SUS: Òun ni ó ó tójú mi nígbà tí mo dé
IPO1: Ègbón yín tó kú yẹn, kí ni orúkọ ẹ?
SUS: TTT
IPO1: Kí ni orúkọ ọkọ ẹ?
SUS: WWW
IPO1: Ojò wo ni aunty ẹ yẹn kú?
SUS: On the 10, oşù kejì
IPO1: Phone rings and the IPO picks the call
IPO1: Ibo ni ó kú sí?
SUS: Inú ilé
IPO1: Sè ọkọ ẹ wà níbè nígbà tí ó kó?
SUS: Wọn pe ọkọ ẹ wá
IPO1: Ibo ni ẹ gbé òkú ẹ sí?
SUS: Ibi tí wọn n gbé òkú sí
IPO1: E jẹ kí á sòótó ọrò o
SUS: Mi ò lò paró
IPO1: Stands up and goes out for about 12 minutes
IPO1: Okay, ta ló pe ọkọ ẹ wá láti Èkó?

SUS: Àwọn ọmọ è ni wọn pe bàbáa wọn wá

IPO1: DDD ò sí nílẹ nígbà tí iyàwó è kú?

SUS: Bèèni, èmi gan an ò sí nílẹ

IPO1: Okay, time tí wọn kú, ta ló wá sin òkú è sí èyin window?

SUS: Ehn

IPO1: Ta ló fún wọn iwọ àti brother ẹ ní àşẹ láti sin í sí èyin window?

SUS: Oko è ni

IPO1: Àwọn DPO ti mò sí ọrò yín báyii o, àwọn tí ẹ jọ sişé yẹn ẹ sọ fún mi. Ọmọ Íbò ni mí o, èmi ò kí n şe Yoruba o. Let me open a section of the law for you (opens and reads a section of the constitution. He stands up to attend to a visitor)

IPO1: Àwọn ọlòpá yín kí ẹ má à sìnkú síbè

SUS: Èmi kọ ni mo sìnkú now. Oko è ni, aunty mi ni ẹni tí ó kú

IPO1: It is an abomination. Gbogbo yín ló commit offence. Ẹ dárúkọ gbogbo yín fún mi

SUS: Tries to explain

Complainant: (cuts in) to counter the argument of suspect

IPO2: (Shouts the suspect down) No talk oo, because of what you did to us the other time

IPO3: Şé èyin lẹ sin òkú yẹn síbè?

SUS: Oko wọn

IPO3: Èyin ò ní ilé ni?

SUS: Silent

IPO3: Ẹ tún má a san owóo damages gan an

IPO1: Burial in the house is not allowed

IPO4: They are putting laws into their hands

IPO3: Pe XXX kí ó wá bá ẹ níbí

IPO4: Kí ni ètọọ ti yín tí ẹ lọ n sin aunty yín sí ilé onílẹ?

Complainant and suspect: (begin to exchange words)

IPO1: Don't worry, there is no point to fight.

IPO5: Ẹ gbọ, ibo ni wan sin òkú yẹn sí?

SUS: Begins to explain again

IPO2: This man is very stubborn (pointing at the suspect)

CASE 34: FORCEFUL ENTRY AND WILLFUL DAMAGE

Background Information: *The suspect in Interaction 1 here is a senior pastor of a popular church in Ibadan, whose church has been accused of forcefully entering the land of the complainant and destroyed the crops planted on the land.*

INTERACTION 1

IPO: (Comes in and conducts the suspect to a seat) Sit down sir

SUS: Thank you

IPO: (Shows the suspect a signboard) Do you recognise this?

SUS: I know the land

IPO: How?

SUS: We bought the land

IPO: There is a petition on it which we received in May this year

SUS: Did you get in touch with our G.O?

IPO: Who is the G.O?

IPO: Are you the one that used the bulldozer?

SUS: Yes

IPO: As at the time they were using the bulldozer, were you there?

SUS: No, we have people assigned for the job

IPO: The owners of the land are complaining. It is a case of forceful entry

SUS: Until it is otherwise proven, I believe my G.O has all the documents

IPO: Goes out to attend to attend to something for about 5 minutes

IPO: Are you through with it (the petition he had earlier given the suspect to peruse)?

SUS: Yes, I have never been to the land before but I know it exists. I don't have any information concerning the land

IPO: But this is your number now

SUS: No, my G.O's number. I only know those in charge of the land

IPO: Where is your G.O?

SUS: He is out of town now

IPO: All I asked you sir is what you know about the land

SUS: Anything pertaining to that land, I know nothing about it. I know we used to call the place
YYY

IPO: I asked you earlier if you know the land

SUS: I have information about the land but I don't know the land

IPO: That is the information we need sir. This information might help us

SUS: Okay

IPO: Please note that whatever you write here could be used later if the matter gets to court

SUS: Accused of what now, since the information here reads 'Accused/witness' statement?
Accused in what area?

IPO: If I put questions to you, it is what you know that you will put down and not what you don't know

SUS: Okay

IPO: Sorry oh, that is the nature of our job oh. Write your qualifications up to the higher institution sir

SUS: I am through sir

IPO: Have you written it up to the higher institution sir?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Since then, what have you been doing sir?

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Are you through sir?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Where is the location of the land?

SUS: I know it is at XXX

IPO: Write it sir. Sir, anywhere you make a mistake, don't cancel. Please sir, put where the signboard is located

SUS: (Continues to write)

IPO: Which church bears this name?

SUS: Our church. I know about this land but I don't know where it is located

IPO: You don't know?

SUS: Yes sir

IPO: Do you know anything about this signboard sir?

SUS: I saw it in the church

IPO: What can you say about the signboard?

SUS: I have written everything here. No, don't put words into my mouth. You are now telling me I know about the land

IPO: You are a minister of God oh. When you came here, I asked you about the land

SUS: Yes

IPO: I asked if you were the ones that bulldozed the land

SUS: Yes

IPO: Were you there?

SUS: No

IPO: Who put the signboard there?

SUS: I don't know

IPO: Help me put it there

SUS: (Continues to write)

IPO: And you did not bother to ask?

SUS: No

IPO: Put it down

SUS: I can't do that sir

IPO: Why didn't you ask?

SUS: I have oga

IPO: Write it down

SUS: I can't write it; I have already written what I know about the land

IPO: What did you write sir?

SUS: Shows the IPO what he has written

IPO: Who bought the land?

SUS: Ògá, I told you don't put words into my mouth.

IPO: Who bought the land?

SUS: My G.O

IPO: Put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: From who?

SUS: I don't know

IPO: Write it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Is there any document that covers the land?

SUS: I don't know

IPO: But I asked you earlier and you said yes

SUS: I don't know anything about the land

IPO: Pastor (emphasis)

SUS: Officer (emphasis)

IPO: : Pastor (emphasis)

SUS: Don't call it in a ridiculous way please

IPO: Does your G.O have documents?

SUS: I don't know

IPO: Why are you denying what you said earlier

SUS: No, I didn't say that. How did you want me to put it?

IPO: So, your G.O did not tell you anything outside what you have here?

SUS: No, there is a committee in charge

IPO: You didn't know those committee?

SUS: I only know the head

IPO: What is the name sir?

SUS: Deacon XYZ

IPO: Put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Who directed you here sir?

SUS: My G.O

IPO: Write it down why he sent you here

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Do you have another branch in Ibadan?

SUS: A branch of the ministry is at FFF

IPO: But now we are talking about the signboard

SUS: I don't understand what you are saying

IPO: Now, who can we call?

SUS: It is either the G.O or the head of the committee

IPO: Put it there

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Sign here. That is all. Let's go sir

INTERACTION 2

The suspect is a member of the committee the suspect in Interaction 1 claims is in charge of the disputed land. He has shown up the day after the suspect in Interaction 1 was questioned.

IPO: Welcome my brother

SUS: Thank you sir

IPO: What do you know about the land?

SUS: We paid for the land, collected the documents and we bulldozed the land. It was actually procured to build an estate for our members

IPO: How many people went with you to bulldoze the land?

SUS: About 9 or 10 people

IPO: Were there policemen?

SUS: The family said they would bring policemen

IPO: What you will help me do now is to put all this down in your statement

SUS: How do I go about it because I have not got the full information

IPO: Explains the content of the petition written by the complainant

SUS: I am sorry, I hope I can see the petition

IPO: (Shows the suspect the petition)

SUS: (Peruses the content) Well, thank you

IPO: Wait before you write. Take note of the cautionary statements

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: State your schools till date

SUS: Okay

IPO: Explain how you manage to buy the land, the documents, and the people involved

SUS: Okay, but from the letter they wrote here, it appears there is a mix-up

IPO: Explains how the matter concerns the church

SUS: (Starts writing)

IPO: Please don't cross the magine

SUS: Okay (continues to write)

IPO: Who were the people on the site that day?

SUS: The architect, the surveyor and the other people

IPO: Okay, who involved the uniformed men?

SUS: The other family

IPO: Please put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: How many uniformed men?

SUS: They did not really put on uniform

IPO: Do you have the contact of Mr AAA?

SUS: Well, as at yesterday, my G.O said his son said he was sick

IPO: Were there crops on the land?

SUS: No, nothing on the land

IPO: What about trees?

SUS: You know, on a normal ground, there would be trees on most underdeveloped land

IPO: Shows the suspect a photograph showing things destroyed on the land

SUS: We were the ones that erected the pillars

IPO: You people have graded it off

SUS: No, no (continues to write). Our surveyor was the one that erected the pillars on the land

IPO: What is the name of the surveyor?

SUS: XXX. (Continues to write). I am through

IPO: Okay sign

SUS: How does this thing concern us because it was not addressed to us

IPO: Your signboard shows you were the ones that bulldozed the land

SUS: Ògá, by the time we are through, you will see that those people are crooks

IPO: It is like they are two families (goes out and later returns)

IPO: My oga said you should write about what you know about the land

SUS: I have written all I know about the land

IPO: What about the photo I showed you?

SUS: Ògá, that is photo. Anybody can take photo

CASE 35: FRAUD (LAND ISSUE)

Background Information: *The suspect is a woman who is accused of duping the complainant to the tune of 3.6 million naira.*

IPO: Madam, ẹ mọ nńkan tí ó n bí mi nínú ni pé ẹ fún lawyer ní chance táti dupe ni

SUS: Bòdá, mi ògba owó lówó lawyer

IPO2: Şé date wà lóri receipt yẹn?

SUS: Daddy, ògá, ẹ jẹ kí n şàlàyé fún un yín

IPO2: Alhaja, ẹ ní sùúrù

IPO1: Ẹ gbọ mi, I must tell you the truth, ẹ kọ statement

SUS: Mi ò mọ wọn rî

IPO1: ẹyin kó la n sọ

IPO3: There is no problem, just explain everything

SUS: They just gang up against me. This one is my brother oh

IPO2: Madam, tí ẹ bá parí statement, there is no problem

SUS: Mi ò fẹ kí nńkan bájẹ, şùgbón ọwó tí wọn n gbé yìí, mí o mind. Uhn, this is an experience.

Şé ó yẹ kí ọmọ bàbá mi má a bá wọn kọ statement against mi. Ó ti da o

IPO2: Ìgbà tí iyá ò mọ ìwé kọ. Ibo lẹ n gbé nísinyíí?

SUS: Mo n sùn kiri ni, ìgbà tí wọn ti ti ilé mi pa (continues to write)

CASE 36: LAND DISPUTE

Background Information: *The suspect is accused of encroaching on the complainant's land, claiming the land belonged to his late mother*

IPO: Are you staying with mama at XXX before she died?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Are you in good terms with your mother before she died?

SUS: Yes sir

IPO: Put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: (Brings out a set of documents) Are you aware of this agreement?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Where were you then?

SUS: My mother told me

IPO: This agreement was signed in 1979, and I know you are small then. You don't know anything about the land. You were just 9 years old when your mother bought the land

SUS: I heard about it

IPO: Put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Are you aware that your mother had a building on the land?

SUS: My mother took me there

IPO: Put it down

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Who demolished the building?

SUS: It is not our mother's own

IPO: Ehn ehn, is it true?

SUS2: It was not his mother that owned the structure

IPO: Are you aware?

SUS: I am aware (Continues to write)

IPO: Do you have any question to ask me?

SUS: No question

SUS: How many are the plots?

IPO: You suppose know that now

SUS: Shey I should write it?

IPO: Write it now

SUS2: (Wants to cut to further give the prime suspect some hints)

IPO: (Calls his name) I am not talking to you yet

SUS: I have written it

IPO: That is all about yourself?

SUS: Yes

IPO: Okay sign

SUS2: O ti rò ó dáadáá, wọn ò rush ẹ ò

IPO: Weitin remain wey he wan write

CASE 37: FRAUD/MISMANAGEMENT OF FUNDS

Background Information: *The suspect is accused of syphoning a huge amount of money the complainant allegedly gave him for her building construction.*

IPO: (Brings the suspect and the complainant) Ó yá jókòdò síbè yẹn

SUS: Sits down

IPO2: Olè ni é. À á pa é síbí

IPO3: Ojò gbogbo ni ti olè, ojò kan ni ti onińńkan

IPO3: È need láti handle è dáadáa

IPO2: Ehn, olè ni

The was later taken to the DC's office

The second day. The interaction had started before I arrived

IPO4: To me, it appears you want to dupe the woman

SUS: No ma

IPO4: You know that woman sells petty petty things and instead of you to help her, you are doing something else

SUS: Tries to explain

IPO4: Who bought the land?

SUS: She bought the land. If she wants the money, I will plead for some time so that I can raise the money

IPO: The woman said you have not given her the building plan

SUS: She has not paid for it

IPO5: Okùnrin yí jéwọ kí á fi é sílẹ

CASE 38: STEALING

Background Information: *The suspect is woman apparantly in her early forty's accused of stealing a sum of 24 million naira over a period of time. She puts a gown made from Ankara and she has a pair of bathroom slippers on*

IPO: (Walks in with the suspect an ordered her to the bench before him) Jókòdò

SUS: (Sits down)

IPO: Gbà kí o kọ ó (gives the confessional statement paper to the suspect)

SUS: Okay sir

IPO: Time wo ni ìyẹn şelè?

SUS: January

IPO: Èlo ni owó yẹn?

SUS: Wọn ní 9 million

IPO: Wọn ni! O ò sí nńbè ni?

SUS: Ìgbà tí wọn şeşè şe account ni wọn sọ bẹ è

IPO: Ìgbà tí Mr KKK şe é, ó ní 9 million àbí?

SUS: Tries to explain

IPO: From when to when?

SUS: January

IPO: Jẹ kí ó reflect nínú statement ẹ

SUS: Continues to write

IPO: Kọ nńkan tó correct o

SUS: Ẹ bá mi kà á sir

IPO: Points her attention to some errors in her write-up

SUS: Resumes writing

IPO: Kì n şe pé kí o kọ nńkan tí ò relevant o

SUS: Mo mò ọn

IPO: (Examines the write-up) Kí lo kọ síbí? şé ó make sense báyẹn? (**Hisses**) Àwọn wo ni thugs?

SUS: Mo ti kọ orukọ wọn síbè

IPO: Okay, èlò ni gbogbo owó tí o fẹ gbà níta

SUS: Mi ò mò ọn sórí

IPO: Óyá calculate è, but before then, mention the number of accounts you have, ilé tí o n gbé, ẹnì tí ó ni ì, shares tí o rà

SUS: (Continues to write) mo ti kọ ọ, ọkọ mi ló nilé

IPO: Kọ ìgbà àti iye tí o rà á (shares)

SUS: Resumes writing

IPO: (Shows the the suspect a transaction alert on her phone) owó yìí, ta ló send è sí ẹ?

SUS: Àbúrò mi ní South Africa

IPO: Owóo kí ni?

SUS: Ìgbà tí mo sọ fún un pé kò sí owó lówó mi

IPO: Ṣé gbogbo àwọn eléyíí ló ti sanwó?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni

IPO: JJJ ñkọ́?

SUS: Kò ì sanwó

IPO: Ṣé gbogbo ẹ̀ nìyíí?

SUS: Mo fẹ́ calculate

IPO: (Claps in annoyance) calculate ẹ̀ jòó, a ti ñ pẹ́ nń́bí

SUS: Begins to calculate

IPO: (Comes across another message on the suspect's phone) who is the DDD importer?

SUS: Orúkọ ẹ̀ wà nń́bí. Òun náà jẹ́ owó

IPO: Kí ló wá dé tí ó jẹ́ account ẹ̀ lo send sí?

SUS: Ó ní kí n bá òun send ẹ̀ sí ẹ̀gbọ̀n òun, nígbà tí ìyẹn pa phone

IPO: Kí ni ìwọ̀ àti pastor SSS jọ̀ sọ̀?

SUS: Kò sí

IPO: When was the last time you saw pastor SSS

SUS: Last month

IPO: Write it there, mention the exact date and day

SUS: Writes

IPO: Ṣé o kó owó ìyá?

SUS: Rára

IPO: Kọ́ ọ́ sílẹ̀

SUS: Mo ti kọ́ ọ́ tán

IPO: Óyá sign

CASE 39: DEBT

Background Information: *The suspect is a thirty-five year old woman who is alleged to be owing the complainant a sum of 46,000 naira.*

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ yín?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Ibo lẹ́ ñ gbé?

SUS: YYY

IPO: Ọmọ ibo ni yín?

SUS: Ọmọ III

IPO: Ọdún wo ni wọn bíi yín?

SUS: 1980

IPO: Kí ni orúkọ daddy yín?

SUS: FFF

IPO: Kí lẹ n tà?

SUS: Provision bíi burgar, sweet, wẹwẹ sá

IPO: Ìgbà wo ni èyin rà á?

SUS: February

IPO: Kí lẹ rà?

SUS: Burgar

IPO: Èlòó?

SUS: 51, 000 mo dẹ san 5,000 nínú è

IPO: Stands up to answer the call of a senior officer

SUS: Daddy, ẹ ti bá mi kọ ọ sir?

IPO: Mo n bọ

IPO: Returns to resume where he stopped

IPO: Èlòó lẹ ti san?

SUS: 5,000

IPO: Ó ku èlòó?

SUS: 46,000

IPO: Báwo lẹ ẹ fẹ san èyí tí ó kù?

SUS: Mà á má a san 5,000 ní oşooşù

IPO: Ó yá ẹ sign

CASE 40: *The details of this case could not really be ascertained. However, from the look of things, it appears it must be a rape case*

IPO: Walks in with a young lady (the complainant), a young man and another young man with a hand-cuff in his hands. Óyá jókòó sí ibè yẹn (pointing to the floor)

SUS: Sits on the floor

Officer: Calls on the IPO to come along with the suspect to the OC's office

IPO: Óyá come

ALL: Go out.

After some minutes, I traced them to get more details about the case

SUS: (On his feet) Ọlórún, mi ò lè paró

Complainant: iró ló n pa

TWO IPOS: Sitting down

CASE 41: RAPE

Background Information: *The suspect is accused of forcefully having a canal knowledge of a-15 year old secondary girl. The IPO walks in with the suspect (having a hand-cuff in his hands) accompanied by the victim and one of her relatives*

IPO1: Jókòó sí ibèyẹn (pointing to the floor)

SUS: Sits on the floor

IPO2: (Walks in to do something in the investigation room) O ti rape àbí?

SUS: Bẹ̀ni, à̀sìṣe ni

IPO2: (Hits the head of the suspect with the bunch of keys in her hand 6 times) Olóburúkú, oko ẹ tí o fi rape dà (hits the penile area of the trouser of the suspect)

IOP2: How old are you (beats the suspect with a bunch of broom)?

SUS: Ah, ẹ jòọ!!! mi ò ṣe irú ẹ rî

IPO2: Iṣẹ wo lo n ṣe?

SUS: Teaching

IPO2: School wo lo ti parí?

SUS: Mo n ṣe part-time NCE lówó

IPO2: Ìwo lo disvirgin ẹ? Ṣé o ri pé ayé ẹ ti bàjé!

IPO2 to COM: Báwo ni iyá ẹ ṣe lè máa rán ẹ níṣé ní 8 o'clock?

IPO2: (Beats the suspect again). O ò rí irú mi nílẹ kí o wá rape mi. Olòṣì, ó yẹ kí n bó ẹ sí ihòhò ni tí mo bá ráyè tì ẹ

IPO2 to COM: How old are you?

COM: 15

IPO2: Class wo lo wà?

COM: JSS 1

IPO2: Dide (raises her voice) mo n bá ẹ sòrò o jóòkó

COM: (Stands up) JSS 1

IPO2: JSS 1 ní age ẹ yíí? A fool at forty is a fool forever. Àwọn iyá òfò tó n rán ọmọ ẹ níṣẹ láago méjọ.

IPO2: Kí ni iyá ẹ n tà?

COM: Materials

IPO2 to IPO2: Ibo ni wọn ti refer yín wá?

IPO1: Ìdí Aró

IPO2 to COM: O ti ẹ é rí?

COM: Rára

IPO2: Ẹ ẹjẹ jáde?

IPO1: Ehn, ẹjẹ tó jáde náà ni ọmọ yẹn fi ké

ALL: Go out to the Dc's office

CASE 42: DEFRAUDATION

Background Information: *The suspect is accused of defrauding the company (a publishing firm) to which he acts as a marketer and distributor to the tune of 2 million naira. The suspect was already writing his confessional statement when I arrived.*

SUS: I am trying to remember the details. Mi ò fẹ parọ nípa details

IPO: Ẹ̀gbón o lè parọ nípa figure (derisively)

SUS: (Continues to write)

IPO: Making comments about the suspect to another IPO (Irú ọmọburúkú yíí tó n quote oríṣiríṣi fún wa nígbà tí a lọ mu un ní ànà. Tí n bá fẹ ẹ é fún ẹ, wà á regret ẹ for life. Wà á rí ọlọ̀pá, wà á bẹ lugbó

SUS: Tí n bá rí bẹyẹn, ẹ ẹ nílè rí mi mú (continues to write)

SUS: Òhun ni yíí sir (hands his statement to the IPO)

IPO: (Peruses the write-up) O ò mention the total amount

IPO: Ọkùnrin yìí, the case is not new to you. Don't drag things for me. Òhun tí mo ẹ̀ mú statement ẹ̀ wá síbì (bangs the table angrily)

SUS: Okay sir (continues to write)

IPO: How much is the balance now?

SUS: Mo ti kọ ọ síbè

IPO: Sign, kọ date

SUS: (Signs and writes the date)

IPO: (Goes through the write-up again) O ò indicate your nationality and name. Kí ló n ẹ̀ ẹ̀? Can't you read?

CASE 43: BEING A SUSPECT'S SURETY

Background Information: *The case involved a suspect by proxy. He stood as a surety for a suspect who as at the time of this interaction had not shown up to fulfil his promise to refund the amount of money he was said to have falsely collected from the victim*

IPO: Kí ni orukọ ẹ̀?

SUS: XXX

IPO: Bọ bàtà ẹ̀ (raised voice)

IPO 2: Bọ bàtà ẹ̀ (raised voice)

OTHER INTERACTIONS CONSIDERED

INTERACTION1

Background Information: *An officer came into the large interrogation hall, and was hailed by another police officer, who asked the officer that just came in about a previous issue discussed by them. Here is the conversation that took place after exchanging pleasantries:*

Officer 1: I don come back o

I am back

Officer 2: Ehn go collect am now. Go meet them say make them give you your thing. Go there, ah! ah!! **You are a corporal oo. You are not a civilian!**

Okay, go and collect it now. Go and meet them and ask them to give you your stuff.

You are a corporal and not a civilian.

Officer 1: I go follow my oga now

I will go with my boss now.

INTERACTION 2

Background Information: The two police officers in this excerpt were reacting to the manner a senior officer queried him over an issue in the presence of a suspect. Obviously, the two officers are not on the same rank from the tone of their interaction.

Officer 1: Good morning ògá

Officer 2: How you dey jàre?

How are you(emphasis)?

Officer 1: I see the way you dey look your ògá the other time

I observed how you were looking at your boss the other time

Officer 2: In fact, I just dey look am oo. Imagine how he was talking to me, a senior police officer in the presence of a suspect

In fact, I was just looking at him. Imagine how he was addressing me, a senior police officer in the presence of a suspect

Officer 2: Àbí oo

I agree with you

INTERACTION 3

POLICE-POLICE INTERACTION

Junior Officers: *(Six in number, all on their feet. Following the gesture of these officers, every civilian in the hall, except one woman complainant, stood up)* : Morning sir!

Senior Officer: *(Looked round the interrogation hall. He observed all except the said woman were on their feet)*: Who is this woman sitting down?

Woman complainant: I am XXX. I am a daughter of a military man. I came to see the IPO handling my case

Senior Officer: Is that why you could not stand up? I am the only officer here; every other person in this place is an attachment

Woman complainant : I am sorry sir; I actually get injury for leg (shows the officer her leg)

Senior Officer : Okay sit down. (He later exchanged pleasantries with the junior officers before leaving the hall)

INTERACTION 4

A report drawn from some officers' reactions and comments on an officer's misdemeanour.

The said officer was said to have set out the previous day in company of some other officers to arrest a particular suspect in town, and on their way back, the vehicle conveying the officers had a minor collision with a popular big commercial bus provided by the state government for mass movement of people in the capital city. As reported by the officers who witnessed the scenario, instead of the said officer to resolve the issue amicably, he resorted to discharging tear gas into the bus, causing the passengers great discomfort. Out of anger, the passengers rushed down of the bus, pounced on him and beat him seriously.

INTERACTION 5

A report drawn from the discussion between four officers during data collection.

Generally, the officers were reacting to the way and manner issues that have to do with officers' funds are handled by civilians. During this interaction, one of the officers commented thus:

Officer: A á ̣e n̄kan, a á ma b̄ civilian kó bá wa approve è, whereas military have trained officers who handle their financial issues.

We are in for it; we are subjected to seeking approval from civilians on our financial issues whereas it is not so in the military, where they have trained officers who handle such activities.

For the sake of clarity on the statement of the officer, we later (the researcher) interviewed him informally as follows:

Researcher: Sir, ̣ jò o, ̣ n̄ sòrò nípa financial issues l̄èkan, kò yé mi

Sir, please any some clarification on what you just said concerning your finances

Officer: Èhn ̣e o mò pé ní military, àwọn officers wọn ló má n̄ handle anything tí ó bá involve anything like loan, cooperative; but ní ti ọlòpá, àwọn civilian ló má n̄ handle è tí kò d̄e ȳe kó rí b̄e

Yes, know in the military, there are trained officers who handle their finances, but it is not so with the Nigeria Police. Civilians are the ones saddled with such responsibilities, and this is not supposed to be so

INTERCATION 6

A Senior officer's interaction with a suspect's relative (SR)

Officer: (Comes into an OC's office) Who are you?

SR: My younger brother is has just been arrested

Officer: That criminal who committed forgery is your brother!

SR: Well sir, he is not guilty until convicted

Officer: (Furiously) what do you mean not convicted? Don't worry then, we will help you convict him

SR: I am sorry sir; I don't mean that. He is a small boy who does not know what he is doing

Officer: It is because we too don't know what we are doing that we too will keep him here (goes out)

Another officer brings SR to the interrogation room for a tete-a-tete in company of another officer

IPO1: ọgá, ẹ gbọ nńkan tí wọn sọ fún ọgá. Wọn ní àbúrò wọn ò guilty until convicted

Oga, hear what this man told our boss. He said his brother is not guilty until convicted

IPO2: Ahhh! Báwo lẹ ẹe máa sọ bẹẹ?

How will you say that?

SR: Ráráá, mo kàn ń try láti şàlàyé nì

No, I was only just trying to explain...

IPO2: Ẹ ẹ mọ meaning nńkan tí ẹ sọ yẹn ní? Ẹ ní kí wọn convict ẹ nìyẹn

Don't you know the meaning of your statement? You are implying he should be convicted

